

TESIS DOCTORAL

**PROGRAMA DE DOCTORADO EN TECNOLOGÍAS
INDUSTRIALES**

Director: Dr. Antonio Rovira de Antonio

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ABSTRACT

This thesis introduces a Pumped Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) that can be integrated into the power blocks of medium- and high-temperature Concentrated Solar Power plants (CSP) with the aim of improving the economic performance of the original plant. An economic analysis is also carried out to evaluate its feasibility. The proposed PTES is integrated synergistically into recompression power cycles, reducing the number of power block components compared to conventional PTES systems based on Brayton or Rankine cycles.

For medium-temperature CSP (< 400 °C), the PTES is coupled with a Hybrid Rankine-Brayton (HRB) cycle using propane. For high-temperature CSP (> 400 °C), it is integrated into a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB). The PTES system viability is assessed by comparing the economic performance of a CSP with integrated PTES against a reference CSP plant without it, based on annual operation simulations. The study includes a methodology for component sizing and annual off-design simulations. Additionally, an optimization algorithm is developed to schedule the operation of both the CSP plant and the PTES system, with the objective of maximizing annual revenue using hourly electricity prices from the 2022 Spanish market and solar data from a typical meteorological year in Seville.

The analysis has been divided in three parts:

In the first part, the PTES is not yet considered. A standalone configuration evaluation is performed on a 100 MW parabolic trough CSP plant using the HRB-propane power cycle, in order to assess its technical and economic feasibility compared to other power cycles. The analysis includes detailed component sizing, cost estimation, and annual off-design simulations to evaluate performance over a representative solar year. This recompression-based cycle shares characteristics with both recuperated transcritical Organic Rankine cycles (RT-ORC) and supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycles (sCO₂-RB), achieving thermal efficiencies similar to steam Rankine cycles with superheating and reheating. The simulated CSP plant includes 12 hours of molten salt storage, a solar multiple of 2, dry cooling, and a parabolic trough solar field. Additionally, CSP systems with other power cycles (steam Rankine with reheat and superheat, sCO₂-RB, HRB-isobutane, and ORC-toluene) are also simulated to assess the viability of HRB-propane as a potential alternative to the steam Rankine cycle in medium-temperature CSP. Of all the cycles studied, ORC-toluene and HRB-propane showed the highest annual revenues. However, toluene poses safety risks because it is flammable and toxic, and the cycle operates under vacuum on the low-pressure side. This results in air entering the system, which must be removed, and toluene being released into the atmosphere. In contrast, HRB-propane operates above atmospheric pressure, eliminating these risks. When comparing HRB-propane to the steam Rankine power block, the results indicate that HRB-propane generates approximately 1.5 % higher revenue, and its power block cost could be between 9.8 % and 28.6 % lower. The resulting LCOE reduction ranges from 1.2 % to 4.1 %. The overall improvement in profit-income and cost-income ratios are between 0.9 % and 2.3 %.

Second, the analysis and simulation of the PTES integrated into the HRB-propane power block of the CSP, which was sized in the previous section, is performed. The addition of the PTES introduces some new components to the HRB-propane, including a water/propane heat exchanger, pressurized water storage tanks, incremental cooler area, and an extra pump and compressor, each one driven by their respective electric motors. The charging process requires additional compression work compared to the reference configuration, which is stored as thermal energy. During discharging, the compressors are turned off, and the added pump circulates the propane bypass fraction, which is heated using the previously stored thermal energy, resulting in an increased power output. The feasibility of the PTES is evaluated by comparing the annual incremental revenues and costs between the PTES-CSP system and the reference configuration.

Additionally, the Levelized Cost of Storage (LCOS) of the PTES is compared to those from other studies. The results show an operational and economic improvement of the PTES-CSP over the reference CSP (without PTES). The annual net energy produced in the CSP-PTES is slightly higher than in the reference CSP, mainly due to the improved efficiency achieved during charging and discharging. This is primarily because charging occurs at higher ambient temperatures (coinciding with the photovoltaics production peak), while discharging takes place at lower temperatures (usually just after sunset). The cost-income ratio obtained is small (0.99), but considering other works, this is the first one to achieve positive profitability. The LCOS obtained is half of the LCOS of Rankine and Brayton PTES and even lower than the LCOS of a pumped hydro energy storage with the same number of storage hours.

Finally, an analysis of the PTES integration into the power block of a high-temperature CSP plant using a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB) is carried out. The solar field consists of a heliostat array and a central receiver, with molten salt as the heat transfer fluid, heated up to 565 °C. Other CSP parameters remain the same as in the previous analysis. Although the incremental revenue obtained with the CSP-PTES system is higher in the sCO₂ case than in the HRB case, the integration is not profitable due to its significantly higher cost. This is mainly due the incremental investment, that is near the double than in the HRB case.

RESUMEN

El objetivo de este trabajo es presentar un sistema de Almacenamiento de Energía Térmica Bombeada (PTES, por sus siglas en inglés) que pueda integrarse en los bloques de potencia de centrales termosolares de concentración (CSP) de media y alta temperatura, así como realizar un análisis económico para evaluar su viabilidad. El PTES propuesto se acopla de forma sinérgica a ciclos de recompresión, reduciendo el número de componentes respecto a los PTES convencionales basados en ciclos Brayton o Rankine. Para CSP de media temperatura (< 400 °C), el PTES se acopla a un ciclo Rankine-Brayton Híbrido (HRB) con propano; para CSP de alta temperatura (> 400 °C), se integra en un ciclo Brayton de recompresión con CO_2 supercrítico (sCO_2 -RB). El estudio incluye una metodología para el dimensionamiento de componentes, simulaciones anuales fuera de condiciones de diseño, y el desarrollo de un algoritmo de optimización para programar la operación conjunta de la CSP y del PTES con el objetivo de maximizar los ingresos anuales, utilizando los precios horarios del mercado eléctrico español de 2022 y datos solares de un año meteorológico típico de Sevilla.

El análisis se divide en tres partes:

En la primera parte, el PTES aún no se considera. Se lleva a cabo una evaluación de una planta CSP de 100 MW con colectores cilindro-parabólicos utilizando el ciclo HRB-propano, con el fin de evaluar su viabilidad técnica y económica en comparación con otros ciclos de potencia. El análisis incluye un dimensionamiento detallado de componentes, estimación de costes y simulaciones anuales fuera de condiciones de diseño para evaluar el rendimiento a lo largo de un año solar representativo. Este ciclo de recompresión comparte características con los ciclos Rankine orgánicos transcíticos recuperativos (RT-ORC) y con los ciclos Brayton de recompresión con CO_2 supercrítico (sCO_2 -RB), alcanzando eficiencias térmicas similares a los ciclos Rankine de vapor con sobrecalentamiento y recalentamiento. La planta CSP considerada tiene una potencia de 100 MW, 12 horas de almacenamiento en sales fundidas, un múltiplo solar de 2, un campo solar con colectores cilindro-parabólicos y un sistema de refrigeración de aire. Asimismo, se simulan CSP con otros ciclos de potencia (Rankine de vapor con recalentamiento y sobrecalentamiento, sCO_2 -RB, HRB-isobutano y ORC-tolueno) para evaluar la viabilidad del HRB-propano como alternativa al ciclo Rankine convencional en aplicaciones de media temperatura. De entre todos los ciclos analizados, el ORC-tolueno y el HRB-propano presentan los mayores ingresos anuales. Sin embargo, el uso de tolueno conlleva riesgos de seguridad, al tratarse de una sustancia inflamable y tóxica y operar el ciclo bajo vacío en el lado de baja presión. Esto facilita la entrada de aire en el sistema, que debe ser extraído, con la consiguiente emisión de tolueno a la atmósfera. En contraste, el ciclo HRB-propano opera por encima de la presión atmosférica, eliminando dichos riesgos. Al comparar el HRB-propano con el ciclo Rankine de vapor, se observa que genera aproximadamente un 1.5 % más de ingresos, y que su bloque de potencia puede tener un coste entre un 9.8 % y un 28.6 % menor. Esta diferencia se traduce en una reducción del LCOE (coste nivelado de la electricidad) de entre un 1.2 % y un 4.1 %, y una mejora en los ratios beneficio/ingresos y coste/ingresos de entre un 0.9 % y un 2.3 %.

En segundo lugar, se analiza y simula la integración del sistema PTES en el bloque de potencia HRB-propano previamente dimensionado. La incorporación del PTES añade nuevos componentes al ciclo HRB-propano: un intercambiador de calor agua/propano, tanques de almacenamiento de agua a presión, una mayor superficie de refrigeración, así como una bomba y un compresor adicionales, cada uno accionado por su motor eléctrico correspondiente. Durante la fase de carga, se requiere trabajo de compresión adicional respecto a la configuración de

referencia, el cual se almacena como energía térmica. En la fase de descarga, los compresores se apagan y la bomba añadida hace circular la fracción de propano del bypass, que se calienta con la energía almacenada previamente, incrementando la potencia entregada por la turbina. La viabilidad del sistema se evalúa comparando los ingresos y costes incrementales anuales entre la configuración con PTES y la configuración de referencia. Además, se calcula el coste nivelado del almacenamiento (LCOS) del PTES y se compara con el de otros estudios. Los resultados muestran una mejora tanto operativa como económica del sistema CSP-PTES frente a la CSP de referencia. La energía neta anual generada es ligeramente superior, gracias a la mayor eficiencia térmica durante las fases de carga y descarga, facilitada por las condiciones favorables de temperatura ambiente (alta en carga, baja en descarga). Aunque la mejora en la ratio beneficio/ingresos es reducida (~1 %), este es el primer caso que logra rentabilidad positiva teniendo en cuenta otros trabajos estudiados. Además, el LCOS del sistema PTES propuesto es la mitad que el de configuraciones PTES basadas en ciclos Rankine o Brayton, e incluso inferior al de un sistema de almacenamiento hidroeléctrico por bombeo con el mismo número de horas de almacenamiento.

Finalmente, se analiza la integración del PTES en el bloque de potencia de una planta CSP de alta temperatura basada en un ciclo $s\text{CO}_2$ -RB. El campo solar tiene una configuración basada en un campo heliostatos situados alrededor de un receptor central, utilizando sales fundidas como fluido caloportador, que se calientan hasta 565 °C. El resto de los parámetros de la planta se mantienen en los mismos valores que en los análisis anteriores. Aunque los ingresos incrementales anuales obtenidos con la integración del PTES son mayores en el caso $s\text{CO}_2$ -RB que en el HRB, la integración no resulta rentable, debido a que el coste de inversión adicional es significativamente más elevado (aproximadamente el doble que en el caso HRB).

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context and state-of-the-art

The goal of reaching net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 is driving the introduction of renewable energies. The need for further integration of renewable energies became evident following the events in Europe in 2022, when electricity prices arose because of the increase in gas prices. The high increase in electricity prices during peak hours caused coal-fired power plants to raise their production compared to previous years, failing to meet decarbonization goals [1]. In the Spanish electricity system, the production of coal-fired power stations in 2022 increased by 55.8 % compared to the previous year [2]. Additionally, in Spain and Portugal, a cap was set on the price of electricity generated using natural gas in order to reduce electricity peak prices [3].

In 2023, the global increase in renewable electricity capacity additions amounted to approximately 507 GW, nearly 50 % higher than the previous year [4]. This increase was primarily led by photovoltaic energy (PV), which grew from a total accumulated capacity of 1177 GW in 2022 to 1552 GW in 2023. Wind energy, in second place, grew from 900 GW to 1000 GW. This growth is expected to be sustained in next years due to supportive policies being implemented in most countries, which result in lower generation costs compared to fossil fuels. In terms of energy generation, it is estimated that by 2025, renewable energies will surpass coal-fired power plants and that by 2028, they will account for 42 % of global electricity generation. Of this, wind and solar PV will contribute 25 %.

The penetration of wind and solar PV technologies in the global mix constitutes a challenge to electrical power distribution systems because they are not dispatchable. This results in difficulties adjusting production to meet demand, which can create significant price disparities and grid stability issues when production exceeds demand and vice versa.

From a price perspective, during the summer of 2024 in Spain, it is common to observe very low electricity prices, even close to 0 €/MWh, between 2:00 PM and 6:00 PM [5]. This situation is a result of the high supply of electricity generated by PV. With the decrease in prices during these hours, PV projects are becoming less attractive from a profitability point of view, if it were not for policy support. In contrast, during other periods, the prices can rise to over 100 €/MWh and even may increase if fossil powerplants (which have greater dispatchability) keep shutting down.

Regarding grid stability, several reports and scientific studies warn of the risk of frequency instability as PV and wind power increase their share in the electricity mix [6–9]. The 2013 report published by CAISO (California Independent System Operator) analyzes the effects of high PV penetration during sunny spring days, noting that around 60 % of electricity demand can be met by PV at midday. This situation leads to challenges such as overgeneration, the need to keep synchronous plants running at low load to quickly ramp up production when solar output drops abruptly at sunset, increased requirements for grid flexibility and reserves, and reduced system inertia due to the declining presence of synchronous generators. CAISO proposes solutions including energy storage to absorb midday overgeneration, flexible operation of synchronous plants, controlled curtailment of solar generation, and enhanced regional grid integration. A more recent report [9] analyzes similar frequency stability challenges in the European grids under future low-inertia scenarios with high penetration of renewables like PV and wind. It recommends solutions such as virtual inertia using grid-forming inverters, synchronous condensers, and improved grid management strategies. These risks materialized in

Spain on 28 April 2025 at 12:33 PM, when a blackout occurred due to frequency instability linked to low system inertia. The event led to the shutdown of the entire electrical system across the Iberian Peninsula. Moments earlier, non-synchronous generation accounted for 67 % of total electricity supply, with 54.5 % coming from solar PV [10,11].

Given the geographical limitations of hydropower storage, the use of grid-forming inverters is proposed as an alternative to traditional grid-following inverters to provide virtual inertia and stabilize the grid in systems with high shares of non-synchronous renewables like solar and wind. Additionally, large-scale battery storage systems are recommended to help balance supply and demand. However, this solution has several drawbacks. On one hand, grid-forming inverters have only been used in small grids and isolated systems, but not yet in large-scale grids. Moreover, operating multiple inverters simultaneously in this mode can lead to frequency signal conflicts [12]. Regarding battery storage, they still have high-capacity costs and relatively short lifespans.

In this context, Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants are attractive because it produces renewable energy with synchronous generators, providing inherent inertia, and includes thermal energy storage with large capacity. Although CSP without storage is generally less cost-effective than PV for pure electricity generation, its competitiveness increases significantly when storage is included. Moreover, the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) for CSP is comparable to, or even lower than, that of utility-scale PV paired with battery storage, primarily because thermal energy storage is significantly cheaper than batteries [13,14]. Large-scale battery storage systems typically provide 3 to 4 hours of capacity and have an average lifespan of 10 to 15 years. In contrast, thermal energy storage in CSP plants allows for longer discharge durations of more than 10 hours and operational lifespans often exceeding 30 years.

Beyond costs, another important advantage of CSP with storage is its higher annual utilization compared to PV. In Spain, utility-scale PV usually achieves capacity factors of 15–20 % [15]. This value can rise to about 25–30 % when PV is combined with batteries of 4–5 hours, as shown by recent projects in Hawaii, where solar resources are similar to Southern Spain (for example, Mānā Solar with 35 MW PV and 4 h of storage delivers around 102 GWh per year) [16]. In contrast, CSP plants with molten salt storage typically reach 35–45 %, and tower plants with large storage can perform even better. For example, Gemasolar in Seville, equipped with 15 hours of molten salt storage, was designed for a capacity factor close to 55 % [17]. These figures show that CSP with TES can deliver renewable electricity in a more constant and reliable way, highlighting the importance of storage technologies in the transition to a low-carbon power system.

Regarding energy storage systems, Carnot batteries are also attracting attention. These systems convert electricity into heat, store it, and later reconvert it into electricity when needed—typically during high-price periods.

1.1.1 Energy storage systems

Regarding the energy storage systems, the pumped hydro storage is the more mature and cost-effectiveness technology nowadays, representing around 96 % of the global power storage capacity and 99 % of global storage energy volume [18–20]. However, this system is geographically limited and only suitable for large-scale applications. Another system considered for large-scale use is compressed air energy storage, but only two commercial plants have been built [21]. On the other hand, despite the increasing implementation of commercial lithium-ion battery systems, the low battery life and the high costs per capacity unit mean that they are mainly deployed for applications with low power capacity ratios. Finally, the so-called Carnot batteries

have drawn considerable attention in recent years due to their non-geographic limitation, their application to existing power plants, and their scalability from small to medium systems.

Carnot batteries convert electricity into thermal energy storing it. The electricity is restored when the prices are high using a heat engine. In the scientific literature, various classifications of the different technologies belonging to Carnot battery systems can be found [22-25]. The most studied ones are liquid energy storage system and pumped thermal energy storage (PTES). Most of the cited authors agree that PTES is the technology that can achieve the highest efficiency and probably the lowest cost compared with the other Carnot batteries technologies.

PTES use a heat pump to convert the electricity into thermal power. Among the different choices, Rankine, Brayton and transcritical PTES are the most studied. Several studies seem to indicate that PTES need subsidies to recover the investment cost before the end life of the plant: Ref. [26] conducts a mixed-integer linear programming to set operation schedules that optimize the profitability of different storage technologies considering the 2019 electricity prices of the Italian market. The authors concludes that no one storage technology was profitable in the open market and that the subsidy required to operate at zero cost should be equal to the cost of storage itself, as revenues cover at best only about 1/10 of the capital cost. They also established that pumped hydro storage is the most profitable technology with a levelized cost of storage (LCOS) around 160 €/MWh if an average electricity purchase price of 30 €/MWh were considered. In comparison, Rankine and Brayton PTES LCOS are more than double considering the same charging electricity price, that results in an average price difference that has not been reached in any European market in any year [27]. Another interesting conclusion is that the best capacity range is between 4-6 hours as the average price difference is reduced when the capacity is increased. Similar results are shown in Ref. [28] where the authors established that a Brayton PTES working in a day-ahead market for Germany and Austria in the year 2016 has a LCOS five times higher than the electricity average selling price. On the other hand, lower LCOS values are obtained in [29,30]. Both works evaluate Brayton PTES without considering real market scenarios. In the first, a LCOS between 70-110 €/MWh is achieved with an electricity purchase price of 25 €/MWh. In the second, an LCOS between 100-160 €/MWh is achieved for a purchase price between 25-75 €/MWh. However, the main problem is that daily cycles of 10 hours of charging and 8-10 hours of discharging are considered, making it difficult to find a similar average price difference for the number of hours considered in a real market.

To overcome the problem of the high LCOS of PTES, some technological alternatives have been proposed. These alternatives seek for coupling PTES systems with existing conventional plants to achieve advantages due to system synergies. For example, in [31], a PTES that uses a subcritical ORC cycle for both charging and discharging is presented. The innovation lies in using the heat discharged by the condenser of a coal-fired power plant to evaporate the working fluid of the heat pump. In [32] the Rankine cycle of a coal-fired power plant is reused for the PTES discharging process. To achieve this, the conventional boiler is replaced by a steam generator fed by the thermal energy storage coupled with the pumped heat. The heat evacuated through the heat engine condenser is used to evaporate the working fluid of the heat pump as in [31]. In [33,34] electric heaters are used instead of the heat pump of the PTES, this way, the investment is reduced, although the round-trip performance decreases. Both works also reused coal-fired power plants by replacing the conventional boiler by a steam generator that is fed by the thermal energy storage. Although real markets are not considered in either of the previous works, the obtained LCOS are lower than in conventional PTES systems. Besides, in some of

them, the LCOS of the proposed installation is compared to the LCOS of different energy storage systems under the same financial scenario, resulting in a similar LCOS to that of the pumped hydro storage and in some cases even lower. However, in all these studies, the retrofitted coal plant is not considered as an investment, and if it is, it is considered a residual investment. Additionally, the improvement in profitability of the retrofit plant over the original one seems to only be studied in [32], where the authors conclude that only considering very low charging prices (0-10 \$/MWh) and very high discharging number hours (higher than 9 h), the retrofit plant achieve a lower LCOS compared with the original coal powerplant.

In [35] the feasibility of a PTES integrated into a coal power plant, a combined cycle plant, and a concentrated solar thermal power plant (CSP) is studied. Unlike previous works, the plants retain their original functionality, so the purpose of the PTES is to improve the performance of the original plant either by reducing fuel consumption or by increasing the number of operating hours when the selling price is higher in the CSP. To achieve this, the authors conduct a mixed-integer linear programming to set operation schedules that optimize the profitability of the projects considering the 2016 electricity prices of the German market for the coal and combined plant and the Spanish market for the CSP. The charging PTES is a heat pump or an electric heater. The authors concludes that all the studied cases are not profitable.

Ref. [36–38] consider PTES integration into CSP in different ways, although no economic analysis is done. In [36] an electric heater is used to supply thermal energy to the molten salts of the Thermal Energy Storage (TES) when no solar resource is available and electricity prices are low, allowing the stored heat to be converted into electricity during high-price periods. This approach increases plant utilization during months with low incident solar radiation. In [37] a Brayton PTES using argon with thermocline packed-bed tanks is coupled with a solar field, where the argon is directly heated when solar radiation is available, allowing the installation to also operate as a power plant. In [38], a PTES system with a supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle is proposed. During the discharging process, the hot storage supplies heat to a split fraction of the CO₂ flow in parallel to the main stream through the low-temperature recuperator, so that the cycle operates in a similar way to a recompression configuration. In addition, solar heat is also provided during discharge. However, since both fractions are driven by the same compressor, the control of the mass flow split is not clearly addressed. In this thesis, two independent compressors are considered instead, which allows direct control of the split ratio and represents a more realistic implementation.

1.1.2 Renewable power generation systems with dispatchability: CSP

Regarding renewable electricity production technologies enabling dispatchability, there are fundamentally two: hydropower and concentrated solar thermal power (CSP) plants. Although the total accumulated capacity of hydropower in 2023 is somewhat lower than PV (1411 GW), it generated the same amount of electricity as the sum of PV and wind energy that year. The geographical importance of hydropower limits new projects, so the yearly added capacity is low (between 20-30 GW) and it is decreasing.

CSP technology has an LCOE average of 120 \$/MWh for 2020-2023 period [39]. However, this value may not be representative for two reasons: First because only four plants (around 300 MW) have been installed between 2020 and 2023 and second because most of them (three) have been installed in China by national companies which also seem to have the lowest

LCOE, something that according to [40],[41] could be influenced because of government policy support to CSP technology. If we consider the period of 2017-2018, during which around 1500 MW were installed, the average LCOE was around 180 €/MWh, although with significant variations: from 80-130 \$/MWh for projects in China, between 150-160 \$/MWh in Morocco, 160-200 \$/MWh in South Africa, and 210-230 \$/MWh in Israel [42]. Although these variations are also due to design and environmental factors (annual solar direct radiation energy of the location, choice of concentration technology, type of cooling, etc.), a large part of these costs is also due to the market environment (policy support, supplier market at the location ...) since CSP are generally large projects with significant participation from companies of different sectors.

Low LCOE values in new CSP projects are expected in the coming years, as most of them will be located in China: 6 new CSP projects (around 1200 MW) have been announced to be completed by 2024. On this path, it seems that China could take an important position in the CSP market since, unlike other international past projects, most new projects in China are developed entirely by national firms and with the lowest LCOE [43]. Additionally, Chinese companies are also participating as developers in upcoming international projects, such as the DEWA project in Saudi Arabia (900 MW), in which the electricity will be delivered at 73 \$/MWh, one of the lowest bids in a CSP PPA contract ever [44].

In order to increase the feasibility of CSP, various methods are being studied to reduce the cost of new projects. One such method is integrating CSP with PV in the same plant (Hybrid CSP-PV). This integration can be done with both technologies connected to the same grid point but without energy exchange between the two systems. Some commercial plants have been constructed following this scheme [45,46], and some studies state that this configuration can achieve the same LCOE as a stand-alone CSP but with higher capacity factors, potentially even functioning as a base-load plant [47,48]. Another way of integration adds an electric heater to the previous scheme, whereby the excess electrical production from the PV is used to heat the molten salts. Currently, there are no plants of this type, and it is unclear if the new hybrid CSP projects under construction will follow this model. However, studies indicate that this scheme can achieve a level of dispatchability similar to or better than stand-alone CSP or PV plus battery systems, with a significant reduction in LCOE [49,50]. Additionally, [49] suggests that battery costs would need to be reduced by 60-90 % to be integrated into a hybrid plant, corroborating that, to date, TES (Thermal Energy Storage) remains a more cost-effective storage method than batteries despite the conversion efficiency losses from heat to electricity.

Another complementary approach to increasing the feasibility of CSP is the improvement of its components. In 2017, NREL published a report [51] proposing a national program to develop a new generation of CSP systems that could achieve efficiencies greater than 50 %, based on the state of the art of central receiver CSP, as they have a greater potential to reach higher temperatures due to their higher concentration factor (the current efficiency is around 41.2 %). Regarding the receiver, the report considered the study of three new designs to achieve temperatures above 700 °C in the heat transfer fluid (the reference state is around 565 °C). The three designs considered were gas, solid particles, and alternative molten salts as the ones currently used in commercial plants cannot reach temperatures higher than 600 °C. As a result of the program, a particle receiver pilot plant is going to be built [52,53]. At the same time, a particle receiver pilot plant is also going to be built in Saudi Arabia [54]. Considering other central receiver schemes, a sodium liquid pilot CSP of 1 MW is operational since 2017 [55,56].

Regarding the power block of central receiver CSP, the supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle with recompression (sCO₂-RB) is proposed widely, as numerous studies indicate that for temperatures around 700 °C this cycle can achieve significantly higher efficiency than the superheated steam Rankine cycle (current technology) and other advanced cycles like the supercritical steam Rankine cycle, which has not yet been used in CSP but has been used in commercial coal plants, especially in Japan [57,58]. According to [59] and considering the same inlet turbine temperature for the cycles analysed, the sCO₂-RB exceeds the efficiency of the superheated steam Rankine cycle at temperatures starting from 450 °C and that of the supercritical Rankine at temperatures around 550 °C, for a low-temperature of 32 °C and a high-pressure level of 200 bar. Ref. [60] states that the sCO₂-RB exceeds the efficiency of the supercritical Rankine for temperatures around 600 °C for the same low temperature and high-pressure level as in [59]. This temperature value is reduced if the pressure is increased to 300 bar, although it remains above 550 °C. Considering a low-temperature of 53 °C (an achievable value in CSP with air cooling), the temperature at which the sCO₂-RB cycle exceeds the efficiency of the steam Rankine cycle is increased to around 700 °C. However, the current achievable temperature in steam Rankine cycles is around 630 °C, a value that sCO₂-RB could more easily surpass because it is an inert substance, although impurities percentages in the system should be controlled to avoid unexpected high corrosion rates in materials [61,62]. Besides, the sCO₂-RB cycle is more compact and simpler than the steam Rankine cycle, making it a system with less inertia, which could result in shorter startup times and quicker adaptation to changes in energy demand. Currently, there are already two sCO₂-RB demonstration loops in China and US respectively [63,64].

Regarding CSP with parabolic trough collectors there have not been many innovations in the past decade compared to central receiver CSP. Nevertheless, it remains the most mature technology, with the highest installed capacity, and it also appears to be more reliable than central receiver technology, considering the serious failures experienced by a considerable number of modern central receiver CSP plants related to molten salt tank leaks [65–68]. Regarding the solar heat transfer fluid, there has been research into using molten salts instead of thermal oils to increase the maximum temperature from the current 400 °C to 565 °C. However, some references indicate that despite the increased efficiency of the plant, the need to use heat trace to prevent the salts from freezing (around 220 °C) results in a lower annual net energy production compared to using thermal oil [69,70]. Nevertheless, a commercial plant is being constructed [71].

Regarding the power block of CSP with parabolic trough collectors, neither the sCO₂-RB nor the supercritical Rankine cycle achieve higher efficiencies than the current superheated steam Rankine cycle, considering the temperature limitation of the thermal oils used in the solar field. The use of subcritical and transcritical organic Rankine cycles (ORC) for low-power installations has been studied [72–75]. Additionally, there is a hybrid CSP plant with biomass that uses an organic Rankine cycle [76]. However, the main problem is that the thermal efficiencies are usually low since most organic fluids have a low degradation temperature. An alternative is the hybrid Rankine Brayton cycle (HRB) that was formerly introduced in [77] and whose application to CSP plants was proposed in [78]. It can achieve higher efficiencies than ORC and superheated steam Rankine cycles if the proper fluid is selected [79]. This novel cycle incorporates certain aspects from both a recuperative transcritical ORC and sCO₂-RB. Like in sCO₂-RB, a fraction of the vapour that goes out the recuperator is bypassed through a recompressor while the main flow, is condensed and then driven by a pump like in an ORC.

1.2 Research justification and main objectives

The main objective of the thesis is the sizing, simulation, and study of a PTES system to improve the economic results of CSP plants with recompression cycle power blocks. In both cases, the original purpose of the power plant—solar electricity generation—is maintained. Indeed, unlike in standalone PTES that consume electricity that it is later restored, the PTES embedded in the proposed configuration allows shifting part of the output from low-price hours to high-price hours, improving the economic performance without changing the main function of the plant. First, the PTES is studied for a CSP with parabolic trough collectors and a hybrid Brayton-Rankine cycle that operates with propane. After that, the same PTES concept is extended to higher temperatures CSP, so it is studied for a central receiver CSP that works with a sCO₂-RB power block. To demonstrate the increased profitability of CSP with PTES compared to the original CSP configuration without PTES, the levelized cost and incomes are calculated and compared. Annual simulations are considered.

As mentioned in the state-of-the-art section, PTES usually have a high LCOS that make it unfeasible, and in the cases where LCOS values are low, it is often assumed a large number of charging/discharging hours per day, which results in charge/discharge prices that are unattainable in current electricity markets. Additionally, PTES integrated into power plants are mostly aimed at achieving net zero CO₂ emissions for fossil fuel plants, with only marginal investments compared to the original plant. Few cases have evaluated the economic results of a new plant with an integrated PTES versus the original design without it.

The novelty of the PTES proposed in this thesis is its integration into the CSP power cycle, which reduces components and costs compared to PTES proposed in cited works. The components added to the original power block include an extra compressor, two pressurized water tanks, a water/power fluid heat exchanger, a second compressor or pump (depending on whether the cycle is HRB or sCO₂-RB) and incremental area for the cooler. An additional turbine is not needed since the same as the original CSP power block is used. Furthermore, the design eliminates the need for a heat pump during the charging cycle, thus avoiding the inclusion of an evaporator and a low-temperature heat source. During the charging phase, the PTES reduces the nominal electrical production of the plant, as part of the electrical energy consumed by the added compressor is stored as thermal energy. During discharge, electrical production is increased above the nominal value. In summary, the PTES integrated within the existing power plant allows increased flexibility with increased production at peak hours and decreased production at periods of low electricity demand. Another advantage of this PTES is that it also enables the storage of thermal energy that would otherwise be rejected through the condenser if the PTES were turned off, leading to efficiency improvements in some cases. Finally, from the CSP perspective, the integrated PTES improves the economic results compared to the original CSP.

For the case of CSP with the HRB cycle power block, several additional steps have been taken before integrating the PTES, as this power cycle is not as established and researched as the sCO₂-RB. Although previous works have demonstrated that the HRB cycle can achieve a nominal efficiency higher than that of ORC and the steam Rankine cycle used in current commercial plants, an economic assessment based on costs and production results from an annual simulation has not yet been conducted. Therefore, another original contribution of this thesis includes the sizing of the power block components, their cost evaluation, and calculating the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of the full CSP system without PTES. This result is then compared to equivalent

CSP configurations using other power cycles. The reference fluid used in the Hybrid Rankine Brayton is propane as it achieves the highest efficiency without requiring excessively high pressure (below 200 bar) [79]. Additionally, at common ambient temperatures, the low pressure is significantly higher than 1 bar, eliminating the need for a deaerator and reducing the risk of having air mixed with the working fluid (that is a hydrocarbon). The auto-ignition temperature of propane (around 450 °C) is also well above the maximum temperature achievable in the cycle (377 °C). This value corresponds to the maximum temperature considered in current thermodynamical correlations; however, it is a common value for the turbine inlet temperature in state-of-the-art power blocks of CSP with parabolic trough collectors [80,81].

This thesis has been developed based on the results obtained in [82,83], as well as two other works that have not yet been published.

Beyond the technical and economic scope, this research also contributes to global sustainability targets, in particular the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Specifically, it supports SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) by enhancing the reliability and competitiveness of renewable electricity, SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) by advancing innovative PTES integration into CSP power blocks, SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) by improving efficiency and reducing resource consumption, and SDG 13 (Climate Action) by facilitating greater renewable penetration and decreasing reliance on fossil fuels.

1.3 Contents summary

The work is organized into five sections. The first one corresponds with the introduction section. The next three sections address each of the main objectives previously outlined, while the final section presents the overall conclusions and future lines of work. Particularly, Section 3 to 5 are self-contained, each including their own state-of-the-art review, methodology, results and conclusions sub-sections.

In [Section 2](#), the sizing, simulation, and economic study of a parabolic trough CSP plant using an HRB-propane power cycle is conducted. Alternative power cycles that are common in the technical literature are also considered for comparison purposes (HRB-isobutane, ORC-toluene, sCO₂-RB, superheated steam Rankine). First, a parametric analysis of the power cycles is done to compare efficiencies without considering components sizing. Then, the CSP is sized using the HRB-propane based power block. A novel comparative analysis is performed, using the solar field area and the total area of the heat exchangers from the HRB-propane CSP as reference values. Annual simulations are carried out to compare the annual energy produced using a mixed—integer linear programming to set the TES and power block dispatch schedules. Finally, the components of the HRB-propane power block are sized and the LCOE of the CSP is calculated and compared with the LCOE obtained for the alternative cycles that achieve the best annual simulation results.

In [Section 3](#), the novel PTES is proposed for the HRB-propane power block from the previous section. The additional necessary components are sized. Since the LCOE is not representative for assessing the feasibility of PTES integration, different figures of merit are considered. The cost-income ratio and the profit-income ratio are calculated, considering the incremental incomes and costs between the CSP with the integrated PTES and the CSP without

it. The LCOS is also calculated to compare the proposed PTES with those from other studies. The energy consumed and produced solely due to the PTES system is calculated at each time step of the simulation by subtracting the energy dispatched by the HRB-PTES-propane plant from that produced by the CSP when the PTES is off. To ensure validity, the same TES and power block dispatch schedule has been used for both CSP configurations.

In [Section 4](#), the PTES is proposed for a central receiver CSP considering a sCO₂-RB based power block. The CSP with the integrated PTES is compared to the CSP without it using a similar methodology as in the previous section. A parametric analysis of the pressure at the main compressor inlet is conducted to achieve the best annual simulation results without significantly increasing the temperature of the PTES pressurized water tanks.

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2 ANALYSIS AND SIMULATION OF MEDIUM-TEMPERATURE CSP WITH HRB-PROPANE POWER BLOCK

2.1 Introduction

At the end of 2023, the total installed capacity of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) was 8.1 gigawatts (GW), of which approximately 70 % uses Parabolic Trough Collector (PTC) technology [1]. As mentioned in the introduction, although central receiver CSPs are undergoing more growth in both commercial projects and research due to their potential to achieve high temperatures and efficiency [1-3], the serious issues in recent projects caused by molten salt tank leakages suggest that they have not yet reached the level of maturity and reliability of PTC technology [4-7].

Few innovations have been made in CSP technology with PTC since the last decade, when the largest capacity corresponding to this technology was installed [8]. The main research efforts have focused on using heat transfer fluids that can overcome the temperature limitation in current thermal oils, which is around 400 °C. Molten solar salts seem to be one alternative since one pilot plant was commissioned in 2010 [9] and another commercial one is under construction, achieving a temperature of 550 °C [10]. Despite the potential for achieving higher thermal efficiency in the power block, the main concern of using molten salts as Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) focuses on annual production, which can be significantly reduced due to the consumption heat trace to prevent the salts from freezing (around 220 °C) [11]. Ref [12] compares the CSP annual production considering different HTF, concluding that using current thermal oil as HTF allows a lower Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) than using molten salts. On the other hand, there are ongoing developments for a new thermal oil that has a higher degradation temperature and a lower freezing temperature than the currently used commercial options [13,14].

Regarding the power block technology, the current state-of-the-art is based on steam Rankine cycles with superheating, regeneration, and reheating. The inlet turbine temperature is between 370 °C and 380 °C with a high pressure of around 100 bar [15]. The intermediate reheating of the steam leads to a steam quality at the turbine outlet between 80-90 %, without the need to decrease the high-pressure value, which would decrease the efficiency of the cycle. The maximum nominal efficiencies are around 39 % [16]. Common power rates are in a range between (50 MW- 200 MW) [17].

In the scientific literature, no alternative power cycles have been proposed that achieve a performance similar to that of the steam Rankine cycle for the specified range of temperature and power. According to [18,19] and considering the same inlet turbine temperature for the cycles analysed, the sCO₂-RB exceeds the efficiency of the superheated steam Rankine cycle at temperatures starting from 450 °C with a low cycle temperature of 32 °C until 700 °C for a low cycle temperature of 53 °C. Considering that CSP are usually located in arid places that reach high ambient temperatures, sCO₂-RB power blocks for CSP with PTC technology do not seem to be competitive compared to steam Rankine cycles. Other works focus on Organic Rankine Cycles (ORC), which are a competitive alternative compared to steam Rankine cycles for low-power applications (<1 MW) and for hot reservoir temperatures below 370 °C, such as in low-grade waste heat recovery [20], biomass [21] and geothermal applications [22]. However, the application of ORC for CSP with PTC technology is not as suitable for various reasons. First, steam Rankine cycles tend to improve their performance as the system size increases [23]. This is due to the enhanced efficiency of turbomachines and the fact that the increased complexity of the installation justifies the profitability of the system. On the other hand, a higher turbine inlet temperature allows for higher pressures, and therefore a greater expansion ratio, which improves specific work and efficiency while maintaining a high vapor fraction at the turbine outlet.

Regarding ORCs, the increase in power is a drawback because they require high mass flow rates, which demand significant pumping power and result in using turbines, a technology that for ORCs is not as established as expanders [24]. Additionally, the increase in the maximum temperature of the cycle can cause problems of flammability and stability for the organic fluid, as most have degradation temperatures significantly below 400 °C [25]. Safety issues are greater in cycles with the low pressure value below the atmospheric one, as the air can enter the circuit. Some works studied ORC for CSP applications although not for high power and temperature [26,27]. Only two commercial CSP-PTC with an ORC power block based have been developed [28,29]. Both have low power rate and low maximum temperature.

An alternative power cycle for CSP with PTC technology for high power rates is the Hybrid Rankine Brayton cycle (HRB). HRB incorporates features from both a transcritical recuperative ORC (RT-ORC) and a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB). The main flow is condensed, driven by pump, preheated in a recuperator, heated by the main heat exchanger and expanded in a turbine. The hybridization with the Brayton cycle is done bypassing a fraction of the main flow that goes out the recuperator in the low-pressure side through a compressor. As a result, the cycle takes advantage from both mentioned cycles: The recuperator is balanced in a similar way that is done in a sCO₂-RB and the heat rejection takes place at constant temperature and pressure like in an ORC. This cycle was formerly introduced in [30]. Its application to CSP with PTC technology was studied in [31], where for a maximum HTF temperature of 400 °C. The HRB working with propane exhibits a high efficiency, even higher than steam Rankine cycles and ORC that works with toluene. An off-design analysis of the HRB was done in [32] where the suitability of propane over other fluids is verified. It is important to note that the mentioned studies do not include an economic analysis of the HRB. This is the main objective of this section: the sizing, simulation, component design, and economic analysis of the cycle. To validate the results obtained, other cycles are also simulated, and their results are compared. These cycles are the HRB-isobutane, ORC-toluene, a sCO₂-RB, and a superheated steam Rankine cycle with reheat.

The maximum temperature for the propane is set to 377 °C, which is the maximum value given by the thermodynamical correlations [33]. The solar field consists of parabolic trough collectors, where the HTF fluid (Therminol VP-1) reaches a maximum temperature of 396 °C. The calculation methodology follows the next steps: first different parametric analyses are performed to determine the optimal nominal conditions for each power cycle, while also establishing a reference framework to validate the comparisons. Then each power block is sized, and a simulation of the annual operation of each CSP is conducted. A mixed-integer linear program is developed to schedule the CSP operation that maximize the incomes. Finally, the components of the HRB-propane power block are sized, and an economic study is done, comparing its LCOE with that of a CSP with a steam Rankine cycle power block.

In [Section 2.2](#) the different cycles are detailed and the justification for their selection is done. It should be noted that the thermodynamic conditions in each representative point of the cycle are only defined beforehand in the case of the steam Rankine cycle. This is because it is the most currently power cycle used in commercial CSP plants, so it is very well established. The thermodynamic states in the points of the other cycles are selected by means of parametric analyses in the following sections.

In [Section 2.3](#) the methodology for the comparison of the efficiency of the cycles is defined. This comparison allows determining which cycle achieves higher efficiency under a set of fixed and variable data. No sizing is performed, so neither power outputs nor heat exchanger areas are considered. The worth of this analysis is that it provides an initial evaluation of the efficiency of the cycles primarily based on the thermal levels of the hot and cold reservoirs, allowing for the determination of which cycles are suitable for a specific application.

In [Section 2.4](#) the different assumptions and methodologies used to size the HRB-propane power block, along with the rest of the CSP systems (solar field, TES) are defined. The input data for the power cycle are those that lead to the highest efficiency and were obtained from the previous section.

In [Section 2.5](#), the methodology of a new analysis is presented. In this analysis, the power block of each cycle is sized using the sum of the UA factors from the heat exchangers of the propane power block as reference. The other CSP components (solar field and TES) have the same size as in the CSP-HRB-propane case that is calculated in the previous section. Consequently, the thermal power absorbed by each cycle is the same, but not the efficiency. A genetic algorithm is used to maximize the net power for each cycle by optimizing the UA factors of each heat exchanger.

In [Section 2.6](#) the methodology, operations and algorithms used for the off-design model and simulation are shown. First, the general considerations and constraints of the CSP operation are explained. Then the off-design models for each system are detailed including the startup models. After that, it is explained how the different models are coupled in order to perform the simulation. Finally, the mixed-integer linear program developed to schedule the CSP operations is detailed.

In [Section 2.7](#) the methodology used for sizing the power block components of the HRB-propane is defined.

In [Section 2.8](#) the correlations used to assess the costs of the HRB-propane, and the steam Rankine power blocks are shown. The economic and financial framework for the calculation of the LCOE is also defined.

Finally, [Section 2.9](#) shows the results and [Section 2.10](#) the conclusions and future work.

2.2 Power cycles description

This section presents the reference power cycle configuration (HRB-propane) and the alternative cycles considered for comparative purposes (HRB-isobutane, sCO₂-RB, ORC-toluene, and steam Rankine). A brief technical overview of each configuration is provided in the context of CSP-PTC integration, together with the justification for their selection. This serves as the basis for the comparative performance analyses developed in [Sections 2.3–2.4](#). The thermodynamic diagrams are provided solely for illustrative purposes; in all cases (except for the steam Rankine cycle) the specific thermodynamic state points vary according to the constraints defined in those sections.

2.2.1 HRB

In the HRB cycle, a Brayton and a supercritical Rankine cycle take place jointly. Hybridization is achieved by bypassing part of the low-pressure flow that leaves the recuperator through a compressor, as it is shown in [Figure 2.1](#). Most of the main flow follows a supercritical Rankine cycle, while the bypass fraction follows a Brayton cycle. The HRB cycle incorporates specific aspects from both a recuperative RT-ORC and a sCO₂-RB. Like in sCO₂-RB, a fraction of the vapour that goes out the recuperator is bypassed through a recompressor. The other part, the main flow, is condensed and then driven by a pump like in an ORC. Similar to the sCO₂-RB, the purpose of the bypass fraction is to reduce irreversibility in the recuperator, with an optimal value that maximizes efficiency.

Figure 2.1 HRB layout

To understand how the cycle contributes to improve the efficiency, a set of factors are defined [34]. Equation 2.1 shows the derivation of these factors from the development of the expression for Carnot cycle efficiency.

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{\dot{Q}_c}{\dot{Q}_h} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{T}_c \cdot \Delta s_c}{\tilde{T}_h \cdot \Delta s_h} = 1 - \frac{T_{min}}{T_{max}} \cdot \frac{T_{max}}{\tilde{T}_h} \cdot \frac{\tilde{T}_c}{T_{min}} \cdot \frac{\Delta s_c}{\Delta s_h} = 1 - \frac{1}{CN} \cdot \frac{1}{F_{h,add} \cdot F_{c,rej} \cdot F_{s,gen}} \quad (2.1)$$

\tilde{T}_h is the mean temperature of the heat supply, \tilde{T}_c the mean temperature of the heat rejection, Δs_h the entropy increase of the heat supply and Δs_c the entropy decrease of the heat rejection. CN is the Carnot factor, which accounts for the effect of ratio of the maximum and minimum temperatures of the cycle. $F_{h,add}$ and $F_{c,rej}$ are factors qualifying the heat supply and rejection. These factors take the unit value when the temperature in the heat supply or rejection is constant. This happens when processes take place, for example, through a latent heat exchange. Sensible heat exchanges take values lower than one. On the other side $F_{s,gen}$ is the entropy generation factor. This parameter considers the irreversibilities in all the processes of the cycle.

Analysing the value of these factors in the case of the HRB cycle, $F_{c,rej}$ is high since the cooling process of the Rankine cycle is a condensing process. $F_{h,add}$ is also high because the cycle includes a recuperator, and it is well balanced. The penalisation of $F_{s,gen}$ in the efficiency can be reduced selecting a good design: The selection of an optimal compression ratio can move the heat supply process away from the critical point (in pressure), so the specific heat of the fluid remains constant during all the process. On the other hand, the irreversibility of mixing the bypassing flow and the flow that is heated in the recuperator could be reduced if the thermal state of both streams is similar. Finally, an adequate bypass factor could balance the heat capacity of the vapor and liquid state flows that exchanges energy in the recuperator.

It is important to choose a suitable working fluid. As explained in [34], a high c_p/R at ideal gas condition implies a lower difference between the specific heat of the vapor and the liquid state, so a low recompression fraction to balance the recuperator is needed. This leads to a low compression work. However, it should be noted that a very high c_p/R value could lead to wet compression, since the slope of the saturated vapor curve could be positive [35,36].

According to [32,37], propane and isobutane are the most suitable working fluids since they achieved the highest efficiency with a high critical temperature, relatively low critical pressure and a high c_p/R ratio. A high critical temperature ensures that the fluid condenses across

the entire range of ambient temperatures in which the power block operates, which is wide when using dry cooling. A relatively low critical pressure allows not excessively high maximum pressures while being well above the critical pressure. In this way, the specific heat of the working fluid remains practically constant in the main heater not only in nominal conditions but also under off-design operating conditions. This is important because the power block is considered to operate with sliding pressure under off-design conditions.

Isobutane has two main disadvantages compared to propane. The first one is that the degradation temperature is around 330 °C so the maximum temperature given by the correlations is lower which limits the inlet turbine temperature and therefore its efficiency. The second one is that isobutane can enter the wet region in the compressor when the power block operates at low ambient temperatures. This happens because butane has a positive vapour slope in the T-s diagram. This can be observed in Figure 2.2, which shows the T-s diagrams for propane and isobutane at a condensation temperature of 35 °C. This latter disadvantage does not affect the HRB operating with propane, as the slope of the saturated vapor curve is negative. So, propane will be considered the reference fluid, while isobutane will be used solely for comparative purposes.

Figure 2.2 T-s diagram of HRB layout working with propane (left) and isobutane (right)

2.2.2 sCO₂-RB

The sCO₂-RB scheme for high-temperature applications has commonly two recuperators, which is proposed in Section 4 for the central receiver CSP. However, in this section the sCO₂-RB layout proposed has only one recuperator since the maximum temperature is not very high (under 400 °C). Figure 2.3 shows the layout and Figure 2.4 the T-s diagram of sCO₂-RB cycle.

Figure 2.3 sCO₂-RB layout

Figure 2.4 T-s diagram of sCO₂-RB

As one can observe from Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.3, sCO₂-RB and HRB power cycles have similar layouts, as they have a bypass to balance the recuperative heat exchanger, and a compression stage associated to this bypass. Indeed, the only differences (besides the working fluid) are that the HRB uses a pump instead of the main compressor and a condenser instead of a cooler at supercritical pressure. In the sCO₂-RB, the inlet compressor temperature and pressure are slightly above the critical point. The high specific heat capacity and low compressibility factor near this region lead to a low compressor work and a low heat rejection mean temperature that increases the $F_{s,gen}$ factor. It should be noted that the inlet pressure to the main compressor must be optimized based on the chosen inlet temperature to maximize the cycle efficiency [18].

2.2.3 ORC

ORCs have different layouts depending on whether they are subcritical or transcritical. In the transcritical ones, the conventional boiling process is replaced by a sensible heating one that could lead to lower irreversibility. As the recuperator is not balanced (there is not a bypass fraction that enables similar heat capacities), fluids with high heat capacity of the vapor are interesting. According to [32,37] toluene is the best candidate since its high c_p/R ratio allows to achieve a high efficiency. Considering its application in a CSP with parabolic collectors, the high maximum temperature given by the correlations is very interesting, as it is even higher than the degradation temperature of the HTF (around 427 °C vs 400 °C). Figure 2.5 shows the layout and Figure 2.6 the T-s diagram of a subcritical and transcritical ORC-toluene, respectively. Toluene cannot be used in an HRB cycle because (i) the pressure ratio at the compressor would be excessive; and (ii) because, as it can be seen from Figure 2.6, the compression would be wet. This is due to its high critical temperature and because of the high slope of its saturated vapor curve.

Figure 2.5 ORC layout

Figure 2.6 ORC-toluene transcritical (left) and subcritical (right)

2.2.4 Steam Rankine

The superheated steam Rankine cycle with reheat is the technology currently used in CSP power blocks. Therefore, it serves as a reference framework for comparing the HRB-propane.

The power cycle considered includes 4 regenerative heat exchangers, three of them are close feed-water heat exchangers and the other one is a deaerator. Figure 2.7 shows the main layout and Table 2.1 the main thermodynamic properties in each state for the design point. The inlet turbine temperature is 391 °C, the steam pressure 80 bar and the thermal efficiency achieved 39.66 %, which are common values for actual commercial CSP plants with parabolic through collectors [15,16]. The condensation temperature is 35 °C, that is the same temperature considered for the HRB-propane.

It should be noted that the thermodynamic states for the other cycles are not defined yet. This is because, for them, different parametric analyses are conducted in the following sections to define the best values. On the other hand, since the Steam Rankine cycle is a power cycle currently used in commercial CSP plants, the thermodynamic design is well studied and defined. Because of that, this power cycle is not included as part of these analyses, and it is directly simulated based on the conventional design point.

A	Condenser
B	Condensate Pump
C	Feedwater heat exchanger 1
D	Feedwater heat exchanger 2
E	Deaerator
F	Feed water pump
G	Feedwater heat exchanger 3
H	Preheater
I	Boiler
J	Reheater
K	Superheater
L	High pressure turbine
M	Medium-low pressure turbine

Figure 2.7 Steam Rankine cycle

Table 2.1 Steam Rankine thermal properties

Point	Pressure (kPa)	Enthalpy (kJ/kg)	Temperature (°C)	Entropy (J/kgK)	Mass flow rate (kg/s)
1	5.63	2248.7	35	7326.6	71.2
2	5.63	146.63	35	505.13	80.65
3	350	147.10	35.05	505.51	80.65
4	350	276.97	66.1	907.01	80.65
5	350	416.37	99.29	1299.01	80.65
6	350	584.26	138.86	1727.37	99.22
7	8000	595.24	140.26	1734.02	99.22
8	8000	879.09	205.4	2371.22	99.22
9	8000	1236.06	280.01	3063.16	99.22
10	8000	2758.68	295.01	5744.99	99.22
11	8000	3113.86	391	6327.64	99.22
12	2000	2824.88	221.11	6393.29	99.22
13	2000	3162.15	361	6997.25	84.67
1e	2000	2824.88	221.11	6393.29	14.56
1e'	1847.42	2824.88	217.93	6426.33	14.56
1d	1847.42	890.34	208.4	2409.56	14.56
2e	460	2844.44	193.69	7074.23	4.02
2e'	350	2844.44	190.88	7197.46	4.02
3e	160	2671.64	113.3	7138.28	5.01
3e'	110	2671.64	102.29	7306.79	5.01
3d	110	428.84	102.29	1333.03	5.01
4e	45	2492.98	78.81	7208.56	4.44
4e'	30	2492.98	69.1	7383.04	4.44
4d	30	289.27	69.1	944.07	9.45

2.3 Non-standardized parametric analysis methodology

The non-standardized parametric analysis (NSPA) allows for the comparison of the nominal efficiency of the different cycles based on a set of fixed and variable data, without the need for sizing the components of the power block or any other system of the CSP. For each cycle, a map of efficiency values is obtained by varying the pressure ratio and the bypass fraction. The maximum pressure ratio value is limited by two constraints: A maximum absolute pressure value of 300 bar in the high side pressure and a pressure ratio limit value of 20:1 for the turbocompressor. Besides, the inlet turbine temperature is limited by one of the two following conditions: The maximum temperature given by the correlations for each power fluid (Table 2.2) and a minimum pinch point of 5 °C in the main heater. Since the HTF inlet temperature in the main heater is considered equal to the solar field outlet temperature (396 °C), this constraint limits the turbine inlet temperature to 391 °C unless a lower value is imposed by the limits in Table 2.2. The pinch point considered within the recuperator is also 5 °C.

The dry bulb temperature at nominal conditions is 25 °C and the temperature difference between the inlet air and the outlet power fluid is set to 10 °C, so the low temperature of the cycles is 35 °C. In the sCO₂-RB cycle, the value of the pressure at the inlet of the main compressor has been optimized to maximize its efficiency. The main pressure drop in the heater takes place at the high-pressure side and, in recuperator, at the low-pressure side. The pressure is assumed to decrease linearly within the heat exchanger. All these input data are shown in Table 2.3.

The polytropic efficiency is used to calculate outlet states related to the turbomachinery. Polytropic efficiency applies to small parts of the compression/expansion process, while isentropic efficiency applies only to the overall process between the inlet and outlet of the machine. To apply the polytropic efficiency, the total pressure change in each turbomachinery is discretized into 25 parts. This number is a compromise between calculation time and result

precision. It has been found that values higher than this result in minimal changes to the precision of the results. Since the inlet and outlet pressures of each machine are known, along with the inlet temperatures, the definition of polytropic efficiency can be applied to each of the 25 parts into which the total pressure change has been divided, in order to determine the outlet temperature. Equation 2.2 allows for calculating the exit enthalpy of part (i+1) from the previous one (i) for a turbine while Equation 2.3 is applied to compressors and pumps.

$$h_{i+1} = h_i - (h_i - h_{is,i+1}) \cdot \eta_t \quad (2.2)$$

$$h_{i+1} = h_i + (h_{is,i+1} - h_i) / \eta_{comp} \quad (2.3)$$

Table 2.2 Maximum temperature limit of each fluid

	HRB-propane	HRB-isobutane	sCO ₂ -RB	ORC-toluene
Maximum temperature limit (°C)	377	308.85	-	426.85

Table 2.3 Main input data for each power cycle

	HRB-propane	HRB-isobutane	sCO ₂ -RB	ORC-toluene
Fix data				
Low-temperature (°C)		35		
Low-pressure (bar)	12.17	4.64	85	0.06
Turbine inlet temperature (°C)	377	308.85	391	391
Main heater pressure drop (%)			2	
Recuperator pressure drop (%)			5	
Recuperator pinch point (°C)			5	
Turbomachinery polytropic efficiency (%)		90		
Variable data				
Bypass fraction	0-0.3	0-0.3	0-0.3	-
Pressure ratio	6-20	6-20	2.35-3.53	200-900

The outlet temperatures of the recuperator, on both the high-pressure and low-pressure sides, are calculated based on the inlet temperatures, the heat balance and the definition of the pinch point. It should be noted that the inlet recuperator temperatures correspond with the turbine and main compressor/pump outlet temperatures, which are calculated beforehand with the polytropic efficiency. The specific heat of the power fluids varies significantly around the critical point, so the pinch point in the recuperator can be achieved either the ends or inside. To determine its position, the enthalpy change has been divided into 25 parts. To calculate the recuperator outlet temperatures, the Newton-Rhapson method is used. The method is described below:

1°) The objective function, $F(T_3)$, is defined as the value of the pinch point for an estimated outlet temperature on the high-pressure side $PP(T_3)$ minus the desired value of pinch point (5 °C) (Equation 2.4).

$$F(T_3) = PP(T_3) - 5 \quad (2.4)$$

2°) An initial value of the outlet temperature on the high-pressure side is estimated (T_{3_0}). The inlet and outlet properties in each part are calculated and the outlet the objective function is evaluated $F(T_{3_0})$.

3°) The step two is repeated with another value very close to the previously estimated outlet temperature, $T_{3_0} + \Delta T$.

4°) The derivative of the function objective is then calculated as in Equation 2.5:

$$F'(T_{3_0}) = \frac{F(T_{3_0} + \Delta T) - F(T_{3_0})}{\Delta T} \quad (2.5)$$

5°) The desired value for the function objective is 0 so the Taylor first order approximation is used to find a new value of the temperature (Equation 2.6).

$$F(T_{3_1}) = T_{3_0} - \frac{F(T_{3_0})}{F'(T_{3_0})} \quad (2.6)$$

6°) The process is repeated until achieve the convergence between T_{3_1} and T_{3_0} .

Finally, the efficiency can be calculated from the specific work and the specific heat absorbed from the main heater. Equation 2.7 is used to calculate the efficiency for cycles with bypass fraction, while Equation 2.8 is used only for the ORC cycle. The nomenclature used corresponds to the diagrams shown in Figures 2.2, 2.4 and 2.6.

$$\eta_{cycle} = \frac{(h_4 - h_5) - (h_7 - h_6) \cdot x - (h_2 - h_1) \cdot (1 - x)}{(h_4 - h_{3p})} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\eta_{cycle} = \frac{(h_4 - h_5) - (h_2 - h_1)}{(h_4 - h_3)} \quad (2.8)$$

In Figure 2.8 a process diagram summarizes the calculations to obtain the thermodynamic parameters for each power cycle point. The diagram refers to HRB and sCO₂-RB power cycles. For ORC-toluene the scheme is simplified since there is no recompressor. Should be considered that the turbine, compressor and pump polytropic efficiencies take the same value.

Figure 2.8 HRB calculation process diagram at nominal conditions

2.4 CSP-HRB-propane sizing model

In this section, the methodology for sizing the power block and the other CSP systems is shown considering a gross output power of 100 MW. The HRB-propane is taken as the reference. The selected values for the pressure ratio and bypass fraction are those that maximize efficiency, based on the non-standardized parametric analysis results. These values are shown in the [Section 2.9](#).

2.4.1 HRB-propane power block and cooling system

The power gross generated by the power block is assumed to be 100 MW. Pressure ratio and bypass fraction values are calculated in the non-standardized parametric analysis and leads to the maximum PB efficiency. The nominal inlet and outlet temperature of the solar field are respectively 290 °C and 396 °C. The other fix input values are the same that were shown in [Table 2.3](#).

The recuperator UA factor is calculated as the sum of the UA of each one of the 25 parts in which it has been divided. This number is enough for them to be small and to use the arithmetic mean temperature difference instead the logarithmic one without making significant errors. The UA of each small part is then calculated from the heat exchanged (\dot{Q}_i) and the arithmetic mean temperature difference ($AMTD_i$) ([Equation 2.9](#)). The main heater enthalpy change has also been divided in 25 parts, and its UA factor is similarly calculated. The correction factor value is one since the heat exchangers considered are in counter-flow with one tube-pass.

$$UA_{rec/mh} = \sum_{i=1}^{25} UA_i = \sum_{i=1}^{25} \frac{\dot{Q}_i}{AMTD_i} \quad (2.9)$$

The cooling UA factor is calculated as the sum of the UA factors associated to the rejection of sensible and latent heat of the cycle ([Equation 2.10](#)). The correction factor value is approximated to one since most of the heat exchanged is latent one. On the other hand, the specific heat of the propane remains nearly constant during the de-superheating of the vapor since it is quite far from the critical point, and the temperature is constant during the condensation process.

Therefore, it is not necessary to divide the enthalpy change into smaller parts, and the logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) between the inlet and outlet of each cooler body cooler is used, i.e. one body for the sensible heat exchange and other for the latent one. The outlet air temperature can be calculated considering the cooler initial temperature difference whose value is shown in [Table 2.4](#).

$$UA_{cooler} = UA_{sens} + UA_{lat} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{sens}}{LMTD_{sens}} + \frac{\dot{Q}_{lat}}{LMTD_{lat}} \quad (2.10)$$

The cooling system uses air from horizontal forced drafts. The air mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{air}) can be calculated through the heat rejected (\dot{Q}), the specific heat capacity (cp_{air}), the cooler initial temperature difference (ΔT_{ITD}) and the cooler approach temperature (AP_{cooler}) ([Equation 2.11](#)). The fan power is calculated as in [38]. The outlet fan temperature ($T_{fan,out,is}$) is calculated considering an isentropic compression ([Equation 2.12](#)) using the ideal gas model. Finally, the fan power is calculated from the total efficiency (includes isentropic and mechanical fan efficiency and speed reducer efficiency), the air mass flow rate, and the enthalpy increase ([Equation 2.13](#)).

Table 2.4 Cooling system input data

Fan total efficiency (%)	60
Cooler initial temperature difference* (%)	10
Cooler approach temperature** (°C)	3
Fan pressure ratio	1.0012
*It is the difference between the outlet temperature of the cycle and the air inlet temperature	
**It is the difference between the condensing temperature and the air outlet temperature	

$$\dot{m}_{air} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{cp_{air} \cdot (\Delta T_{ITD} - AP_{cooler})} \quad (2.11)$$

$$T_{outlet, fan, is} = T_{inlet, fan} \cdot pr_{fan}^{\frac{R}{cp_{air}}} \quad (2.12)$$

$$\dot{P}_{cooler} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} \cdot (h_{fan, out, is} - h_{fan, in})}{\eta_{fan}} \quad (2.13)$$

2.4.2 Solar field: Thermal and piping model

Thermal model

The design point conditions and the main parameters of the components of the solar field are shown in [Table 2.5](#).

Table 2.5 Solar field input data

Design point conditions	
Location (latitude, longitude)	Seville, (37.41 N, -5.9 W)
Day and hour	June 21 at solar noon
Dry bulb temperature (°C)	25
Direct Normal Irradiation (Wm ⁻²)	850
Geometrical and optical parameters of collectors (ET-150)	
Reflective aperture area of collector assembly (m ²)	817.5
Length of collector assembly (m)	150
Aperture width (m)	5.75
Mirror reflectance	0.92
Intercept factor	0.92
Geometrical parameters of receivers (Schott PTR70)	
Absorber tube inner diameter (mm)	66
Envelope transmittance	0.963
Absorber absorptance	0.96
Design operating conditions	
Mass flow rate per loop (kg/s)	7.725
Solar field outlet temperature (°C)	396
Inlet field outlet temperature (°C)	290
Solar multiple	2

The incidence angle (φ) is calculated using the expressions given in [39,40] considering that the collectors rotation axis coincides with the North-South axis ([Equation 2.14](#)). The incidence angle depends on the solar declination (δ), the latitude (λ), and the solar angle (ω). The latter could be calculated using [Equation 2.15](#) (in this case its value is 0 because the design point is at solar noon). The solar declination (δ) can be account using [Equation 2.16](#). In this equation n is the day number within the annual count (for June 21, $n = 172$). The angles are expressed in decimal degrees.

$$\varphi = \arccos(\cos\delta \cdot \sqrt{(\cos\lambda \cdot \cos\omega + \tan\delta \cdot \sin\lambda)^2 + \sin^2\omega}) \quad (2.14)$$

$$\omega = 15 \cdot (\text{SolarTime} - 12) \quad (2.15)$$

$$\delta = 23.45 \cdot \sin\left(360 \cdot \frac{284 + n}{365}\right) \quad (2.16)$$

The peak optical efficiency is calculated using Equation 2.17. The mirror reflectance (β), the intercept factor (γ), the envelope transmittance (τ) and the absorber absorptance (α) corresponds to geometrical and optical parameters of the collectors (Eurotrough-150) and the receivers (Schott PTR70) that were shown in Table 2.5.

$$\eta_{opt|_{peak}} = \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \tau \cdot \alpha|_{\varphi=0^\circ} \quad (2.17)$$

Equation 2.18 allows for the calculation of the incidence angle modifier for an ET-150. This expression includes the cosine effect [41].

$$K = \cos(\varphi) - 2.859621 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot (\varphi)^2 - 5.25097 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \varphi \quad (2.18)$$

Equation 2.19 is used to calculate the heat losses per meter of absorber tube [41] and is referred to Schott PTR70 receivers. ΔT is the difference between the average temperature of a collector loop and the ambient temperature, and DNI is the direct normal irradiation.

$$\dot{q}_{loss} = 0.00154 \cdot \Delta T^2 + 0.2021 \cdot \Delta T - 24.899 + \left[(0.00036 \cdot \Delta T^2 + 0.2029 \cdot \Delta T + 24.899) \cdot \left(\frac{DNI}{900}\right) \cdot \cos(\varphi) \right] \quad (2.19)$$

The number of required solar collector assemblies (N_{SCA}) per loop is calculated using an energy balance (Equation 2.20). This value must be an even number since a collector loop is divided into two halves. Then, the HTF mass flow rate per loop (\dot{m}_{loop}) is recalculated. $h_{outlet,sf}$ and $h_{inlet,sf}$ are the nominal outlet and inlet solar field enthalpies, and A_{SCA} and L_{SCA} are the area and length of each solar collector assembly.

$$N_{SCA} = \dot{m}_{loop} \cdot \frac{h_{outlet,sf} - h_{inlet,sf}}{DNI \cdot A_{SCA} \cdot \eta_{opt|_{peak}} \cdot K - \dot{q}_{loss} \cdot L_{SCA}} \quad (2.20)$$

The number of loops should be the upper integer number resulting from dividing the required thermal power by the thermal power of the unitary loop. As the solar multiple value is 2, the required thermal power is twice the nominal thermal power demanded by the power block.

Piping model

The piping model involves sizing the piping system of the solar field and calculating the associated pressure drop. These calculations are supported by two facts: First, the power consumed by the pump to overcome the HTF pressure drop is the highest parasitic consume along with the cooling system and can represent about 3 % of the generated gross power [42]. Second, the HTF contained in all the piping systems that is heated-up in each startup time can lead a reduction between the 10 % and 20 % of the annual electricity production [43].

The model developed is based on that described in [38]. In addition to the loops, the model sizes the hot and cold headers (the pipes that distribute the flow to the loops and collect it) and the runner pipes that connect the headers with the PB and TES. To calculate the pressure drop, the model considers friction losses in all pipes and singular losses in elbows, expansions and contractions, valves, and ball joints. The diameter of the pipes are chosen based on standardized values that ensure the flow velocity remains within a specified maximum and minimum range values. The length of the pipes (runners and headers) is calculated considering that the solar field is divided into a total of 6 subfields. This number has been chosen to ensure a similar number of loops per subfield as in Andasol III [44]. This approach helps avoid excessively long headers and too large diameters. The model is detailed in Appendix A.0.

2.4.3 TES

Two-tanks system with a storage capacity for 12 hours of nominal power block thermal power requirement have been considered. The storage fluid is molten salts (60 % NaNO₃, 40 % KNO₃) [45]. The nominal temperatures of the hot and cold molten salts tanks are respectively 391 °C and 285 °C. The HTF/molten salts heat exchanger UA factor is calculated by the NTU method (Equation 2.21):

$$UA_{TES} = \frac{\epsilon}{1-\epsilon} \cdot \frac{\dot{Q}}{T_{h,salt} - T_{c,salt}}; \quad \epsilon = \frac{T_{h,HTF} - T_{c,HTF}}{T_{h,HTF} - T_{c,salt}} \quad (2.21)$$

The tanks have the same diameter-to-height ratio as in ANDASOL I. The minimum and maximum tanks salt level has been calculated using geometric similarity from the reference data [46].

2.5 Standardized analysis methodology

The non-standardized parametric analysis does not allow an adequate comparison between the cycles, since it neither standardizes the area of the heat exchangers (recuperator, main heater and cooler) nor solar field area. Conversely, the standardized analysis compares the power block efficiency and the net power of the different cycles considering the same total area (through the UA factors) of their heat exchangers as in the pre-sized HRB-propane one, and also the same solar field.

The analysis was conducted with the help of a genetic algorithm. The objective is to maximize the net power of each power block. The constraints, the variables to be optimized, and the fixed data are shown in the Table 2.6 and Table 2.7. The variables to optimize are the low-cycle temperature (cooler outlet temperature at the power fluid side), the maximum temperature (inlet turbine temperature), the recuperator outlet temperature on the high-pressure side, the pressure ratio, and the bypass fraction. In the sCO₂-RB, the low pressure is also optimized since it has to be coupled with the low temperature of the cycle in order to achieve a high efficiency. The fixed data is similar to that used in the non-standardized parametric analysis however, in this case, the pinch points are unknowns since an optimization process is performed.

The maximum temperature of each power cycle is limited by the maximum temperature given for the correlations for each fluid and the maximum temperature of the HTF (HTF main heater inlet). The sum of the UA factors of each power block (cooler, main heater and recuperator) must not exceed the total reference UA factor. However, should be noted that in the sCO₂-RB case, the cooling process must be divided in smaller parts since the fluid is next to the critical point in this process (Equation 2.22). Additionally, the correction factor is set to one although the crossflow cooler exchanges only sensible heat. This approximation is valid if the curves that relate the correction factor to the inlet and outlet temperatures of crossflow air-cooled heat exchanger with multiple tube passes are considered, which is a common arrangement in this type of exchanger.

$$UA_{cooler,co2} = \sum_{j=1}^{25} UA_j = \sum_{j=1}^{25} \frac{\dot{Q}_j}{AMTD_j} \quad (2.22)$$

Additionally, it is assumed that the refrigerant is heated 7 °C during the cooling process, so the minimum cycle temperature cannot be lower than 32 °C (the nominal ambient temperature is 25 °C). The maximum pressure of each cycle cannot exceed 300 bar, and compression ratio of the turbocompressors cannot exceed 20:1. On the other hand, as the solar field is the same for all

the analyzed power blocks, the inlet and outlet temperatures of the main heater, as well as the thermal power transmitted to each power block are the same and match those of the reference solar field.

Table 2.6 Fixed data and constraints for the standardized analysis

	HRB-propane	HRB-isobutane	sCO ₂ -RB	ORC-toluene
Fix data				
Main heater pressure drop (%)			2	
Recuperator pressure drop (%)			5	
Turbomachinery polytropic efficiency (%)			90	
Main heater HTF inlet temperature (°C)			396	
Main heater HTF outlet temperature (°C)			290	
Thermal power required by power block		Calculated considering Section 2.4.2		
Air temperature increment			7	
Ambient temperature			25	
Fan total efficiency (%)			60	
Fan pressure ratio			1.0012	
Constraints				
Total UA factor	≤ than Reference UA factor (Calculated considering Section 2.4.1)			
Maximum pressure (bar)	≤300			
Compressor pressure ratio	≤20			
Turbine inlet temperature (°C)	≤377	≤308.85	≤396	≤396
Minimum low-temperature (°C)	≥32			

Table 2.7 Variables and objective for the standardized analysis

Variables	
Low- cycle temperature, turbine inlet temperature, recuperator outlet temperature on the high-pressure side, pressure ratio, bypass fraction	
Objective	
Maximize net power (Gross power minus parasitics)	

2.6 Annual simulations methodology

2.6.1 General considerations. Operation criteria

Meteorological hourly data corresponding to the typical meteorological year for Sevilla [47] has been considered, including the DNI and the dry bulb ambient temperature. However, the simulation time-step considered is half an hour. This is because some processes like the start-up process of the power block, take such a time. In this way, the simulation is simplified by considering a single operation per time step. These operations can be:

- 1) Electricity production and charging/discharging TES. Night production is considered.
- 2) TES charging without production.
- 3) Solar field and power block startup.

Each of these operations (except for the solar field startup) is scheduled using a mixed-integer linear optimization model to maximize revenue. The market hourly price data corresponds to the year 2022, and it has been obtained from [48].

The following criteria is considered in all cases:

- 1) The HTF mass flow rate through the main heater and the outlet temperature of the solar field takes the design value.

2) The maximum molten salts mass flow rate is its design value. This limits the maximum power that can be stored.

3) During the TES discharging process, the HTF reaches a temperature 5 °C below the temperature of the hot salt tank. The same temperature difference is considered for the salts in the TES charging process.

4) The temperature difference between the turbine inlet and the HTF main heater inlet always takes the design value. That means that if the HTF temperature at the main heater inlet decrease 1 °C below the design value, the turbine inlet temperature also does. This criterion maximizes the annual production although the power cycle efficiency is reduced. The cause of that is that the salts are discharged to the cold tank with a lower temperature, so higher energy can be stored in the charging process. This has been validated in [49].

5) In ORC-toluene, HRB-propane and HRB-isobutane, the temperature difference between the condensing one and the ambient temperature has the same value as in the design case. In the sCO₂-RB case, the air mass flow rate takes the design value when the ambient temperature is higher than the nominal. In this way, the low temperature of the cycle is the lowest possible, and the decrease in efficiency is lower.

2.6.2 Off-design models

Power block and cooling system

The following criteria are assumed:

1) The Stodola-Frügel Law is used to describe the behaviour of the turbine at partial load [50] (Equation 2.23). No minimum-load constraint is imposed, since the power cycle working fluid mass flow rate varies only due to changes in HTF inlet temperature (TES operation) and ambient temperature, while the HTF mass flow rate is kept at the design value.

2) Constant volumetric flow in the recompressor is considered (Equation 2.24).

3) The turbomachinery efficiency at off-design conditions is reduced from the nominal value as the capacity moves away from the design value [51]. Equation 2.25 relates the turbomachinery efficiency to its capacity. Equation 2.26 describes the turbomachinery capacity from the mass flow rate, the pressure, and the inlet temperature.

4) The value of the UA factors at off-design conditions decrease as the mass flow rate of the fluid with the highest thermal resistance also does (Equation 2.27). The hypothesis of constant thermal properties (Prandtl number) of the fluid in the heat transfer correlations is introduced [51, 52]. For the main heater, the mass flow rate corresponds to the HTF while for the condenser it corresponds to the air. The q exponent value is 0.8 for the main heater and the recuperator while for the cooler is 0.625. In the first case, the exponent coincides with the Reynolds number of the Dittus & Boelter correlation. In the second case, the exponent coincides with the Reynolds number of Weir correlation for the external heat transfer coefficient for finned tubes.

5) Pressure drops values (%) coincides with the nominal ones.

$$\dot{m} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{T_{inlet}}{p_{inlet}^2 - p_{outlet}^2}} = constant \quad (2.23)$$

$$\left[\frac{\dot{m} \cdot x_{rc}}{d_{inlet}} \right]_{des} = \left[\frac{\dot{m} \cdot x_{rc}}{d_{inlet}} \right]_{off} \quad (2.24)$$

$$\eta_{t_{bm}} = \eta_{t_{bm_{des}}} - \left| 1 - \frac{\phi_{t_{bm}}}{\phi_{t_{bm_{des}}}} \right| / 3 \quad (2.25)$$

$$\phi = \dot{m} \frac{\sqrt{T}}{P} \quad (2.26)$$

$$UA_{off} = UA_{des} \cdot \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\dot{m}_{des}} \right)^q \quad (2.27)$$

The off-design power cycle calculation process for the HRB is shown in [Figure 2.9](#). The input data comprises parameters obtained under nominal conditions, as well as variable parameters. The parameters obtained under nominal conditions are used in [Equations 2.23-2.27](#) to obtain the corresponding off-design parameters. The variable parameters include ambient temperature and the HTF temperature at the main heater inlet. The inlet turbine temperature and the condensing temperature are determined based on the considerations explained in [Section 2.6.1](#). Initial values for the pressure at the turbine inlet, the bypass fraction, and the propane/isobutane temperature at the main heater inlet are estimated and iteratively recalculated until convergence is achieved in two consecutive calculation loops.

The off-design power cycle calculation process for the ORC-toluene and the sCO₂-RB is similar to that shown in [Figure 2.9](#). although respective particularities should be considered: For the ORC-toluene, there is no recompressor and therefore no bypass fraction. For the sCO₂-RB, the temperature at the inlet of the main compressor is equal to the nominal value if the ambient temperature is equal or below 25 °C. However, if it is higher, it becomes an unknown variable since the air mass flow rate in the cooler is set at the nominal value. In this last case, the off-design power cycle calculation process is conducted considering a guess value of the temperature at the inlet of the main compressor. Then, this temperature is recalculated through the off-design cooler calculation process, considering the nominal air mass flow rate. Off-design power cycle and cooler calculation processes are repeated until the temperature at the main compressor inlet converges.

The off-design cooler calculation process for the sCO₂-RB is shown [Figure 2.10](#). For other power cycles, the low temperature of the cycle is a known parameter, while the unknown one is the air mass flow rate. In these cases, the LMTD is used since the power fluids thermodynamic properties are far from the critical point. In [Figure 2.11](#) are represented these last cases.

Section 2: Analysis and simulation of medium-temperature CSP with HRB-Propane power block

Figure 2.9 Off design HRB model process diagram

** The recalculated temperature is used as input for the sCO₂-RB power cycle model

Figure 2.10 Off design sCO₂-RB cooler model process diagram

Figure 2.11 Off design HRB and ORC cooler model process diagram

Solar field

For each time-step of the simulation, the incidence angle must be calculated in order to assess the incidence angle modifier (Equation 2.18), which affects the thermal power absorbed.

So first, the solar time is calculated considering Equation 2.28. The UTC time is the Local Time minus the Time Zone (Equation 2.29). The time zone for Spain is +1. The longitude corresponds to that of the location and was defined in Table 2.5. The longitude sign criterion is defined considering positive values to the east of the Greenwich Meridian and negative values to the west. The correction factor is calculated considering Equation 2.30. B is calculated using Equation 2.31 where n is the day number within the annual count.

$$\text{Solar time} = \text{UTC time} + \frac{\text{length}}{15} + \frac{\text{correc}}{60} \quad (2.28)$$

$$\text{UTC time} = \text{Local Time} - \text{Time Zone} \quad (2.29)$$

$$\text{correc} = 229.2 \cdot (0.000075 + 0.001868 \cdot \cos(B) - 0.032077 \cdot \text{sen}(B) - 0.014615 \cdot \cos(2B) - 0.04089 \cdot \text{sen}(2B)) \quad (2.30)$$

$$B = (n - 1) \cdot \frac{360}{365} \quad (2.31)$$

After calculating solar time, Equations 2.14-2.19 are applied to calculate the incidence angle, the collector peak efficiency and the thermal losses. Finally, since the inlet and outlet solar field temperatures are input data, the mass flow rate through each collector and the thermal power absorbed is calculated considering Equation 2.32 and Equation 2.33. This equation is similar to that of Equation 2.20 but contains one more variable, η_{shad} . This term assesses the row shadowing losses. This effect happens when the solar angle is so low that collectors shade each other. The shadow factor is calculated using Equation 2.34 from the distance between collector rows (Di_{brow}), effective parabola width ($Width_{loop}$), elevation angle (θ) and incidence angle (φ). It is assumed that the distance between collector rows is equal to three times the effective parabola width (a recommendation in [53]). The factor is introduced in the energy balance of the absorbed power by the solar field, reducing it.

$$\dot{m}_{loop} = N_{SCA} \cdot \frac{DNI \cdot A_{SCA} \cdot \eta_{opt|peak} \cdot K \cdot \eta_{shad} - \dot{q}_{lss} \cdot L_{SCA}}{h_{out,sf} - h_{in,sf}} \quad (2.32)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{sf} = N_{loops} \cdot N_{SCA} \cdot (DNI \cdot A_{SCA} \cdot \eta_{opt|peak} \cdot K \cdot \eta_{shad} - \dot{q}_{lss} \cdot L_{SCA}) \quad (2.33)$$

$$\eta_{shad} = \frac{Di_{brow}}{Width_{loop}} \cdot \frac{\text{sen}(\theta)}{\cos(\varphi)} ; \eta_{shad} \in (0.5, 1) \quad (2.34)$$

TES

Off-design HTF/molten salts heat exchanger UA factor value is calculated using Equation 2.27 considering the salts mass flow rate and an exponent of 0.8. To calculate the mass flow rate and the thermodynamic properties related to the heat exchanger Equation 2.35 is used.

$$UA_{TES} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{\text{LMTD}} \quad (2.35)$$

Thermal losses of the storage tanks are calculated each time step using Equation 2.36. This equation is explained in [46] and is based on a dimensionless analysis performed on tanks that have the same diameter-to-height ratio as ANDASOL I tanks [54]. TL stands for the tank level, $\dot{Q}_{losses,full}$ and $\dot{Q}_{losses,empty}$ are respectively the thermal losses when the reference tank is full, and it is at its minimum level. The heat losses are scaled by considering the ratio between the tank diameter and that of the reference one.

$$\dot{Q}_{losses} = [TL \cdot \dot{Q}_{losses,full} + (1 - TL) \cdot \dot{Q}_{losses,empty}] \cdot \frac{D}{D_{ref}} \quad (2.36)$$

2.6.3 Startup models

Solar field startup thermal energy

When solar radiation does not reach the collectors, the HTF temperature decreases due to the heat losses. The main temperature drop takes place at night. Thus, a considerable amount of energy absorbed by the solar field should be used daily to increase the HTF temperature before starting to produce electrical power. This energy is calculated as the difference between maximum daily thermal energy of the HTF contained in the powerplant and the minimum daily thermal energy of the HTF. Additionally, it is necessary to heat not only the HTF but also the pipes and other elements that have a certain thermal inertia. The energy state of the solar field in each time step could be expressed through [Equation 2.37](#) considering the two terms explained.

$$E_{th,sf} = \frac{1}{3600} \cdot E_{th,HTF} + E_{th,pipes} \quad (2.37)$$

[Equation 2.38](#) is used to calculate the thermal energy contained in the HTF. This energy is calculated considering the HTF volumes (V) of each system: loops, cold pipe headers and runners ($c, h\&r$), hot pipe headers and runners ($h, h\&r$) and main heater (mh). The thermal energy depends on HTF density (ρ) and HTF enthalpy (h). These volumes have been calculated with the piping model.

$$E_{th,HTF} = \rho_{loops} \cdot V_{loops} \cdot h_{loops} + \rho_{c,h\&r} \cdot V_{c,h\&r} \cdot h_{c,h\&r} + \rho_{h,h\&r} \cdot V_{h,h\&r} \cdot h_{h,h\&r} + \rho_{mh} \cdot V_{mh} \cdot h_{mh} \quad (2.38)$$

For each hour that the plant produces power, [Equation 2.38](#) becomes into [Equation 2.39](#). Steady state is considered.

$$E_{th,HTF} = [\rho(T) \cdot V_{loops} \cdot h(T)]_{T=\frac{T_{sf,out}+T_{sf,in}}{2}} + [\rho(T) \cdot V_{h,h\&r} \cdot h(T)]_{T=T_{sf,out}} + [\rho(T) \cdot V_{c,h\&r} \cdot h(T)]_{T=T_{sf,in}} + [\rho(T) \cdot V_{mh} \cdot h(T)]_{T=\frac{T_{sf,out}+T_{sf,in}}{2}} \quad (2.39)$$

For each hour that radiation does not reach the solar field, [Equation 2.38](#) becomes into [Equation 2.40](#) considering an average temperature in all the volumes.

$$E_{th,HTF} = [\rho \cdot h]_{T_{mean}} \cdot (V_{sf} + V_{h,hd} + V_{c,hd} + V_{mh}) \quad (2.40)$$

The energy state of pipes is calculated with [Equation 2.41](#). It considers the cold and hot headers thermal inertia ($mc_{c,hd}, mc_{h,hd}$) as well as loop thermal inertia (mc_{loop}). These experimental terms are proposed in [55]. The standard values proposed by System Advisor Model (v 2021.12.2) have been considered, which are shown in [Table 2.8](#). On the other hand, $mc_{c,hd}$ and $mc_{h,hd}$ are multiplied by the nominal power generated (\dot{P}_{des}) and the HTF temperature contained in cold and hot headers; mc_{loop} is multiplied by the length of each SCA (L_{SCA}), the total number of total loops (N_{loops}), the number of SCAs per loop (N_{SCA}), and the average temperature of each loop (\tilde{T}_{loop}).

$$E_{th,pipes} = \dot{P}_{dis} \cdot (mc_{c,hd} \cdot T_{c,hd} + mc_{h,hd} \cdot T_{h,hd}) + mc_{loop} \cdot N_{SCA} \cdot N_{loops} \cdot L_{SCA} \cdot \tilde{T}_{loop} \quad (2.41)$$

Table 2.8 Standard values of headers thermal inertia

$mc_{h,hd} \left(\frac{Whr}{We \cdot K} \right)$	$mc_{c,hd} \left(\frac{Whr}{We \cdot K} \right)$	$mc_{loop} \left(\frac{Whr}{m \cdot K} \right)$
$0.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	4.5

The thermal losses of the system are also considered every time-step that the collectors are not receiving solar irradiation. It is assumed that the loops are the only elements where the system can lose thermal energy. These thermal losses are calculated using Equation 2.19. Equation 2.42 is used to calculate the energy contained in the solar field at the beginning of an hour, considering the energy contained at the beginning of the previous hour and the energy loss. This method also allows for the calculation of the solar field energy that must be recovered after cloudy intervals before produce power.

$$E_{th,sf}(i) = E_{th,sf}(i-1) - L_{SCA} \cdot N_{SCA} \cdot N_{loops} \cdot \dot{q}_{lss} \cdot \Delta t \quad (2.42)$$

Power startup thermal energy

The time duration constraint is 30 minutes and the thermal energy that must be supplied from the solar field, or the TES, or by a combination of both, is a 20 % of the thermal energy demanded by the PB during 1 h at nominal conditions. If the available energy is not sufficient to start the cycle within half an hour, the power cycle will remain off during that time-step.

2.6.4 Systems coupling

To reduce the computing time during the simulation, a matrix with the off-design behaviour of the power cycles has been obtained. Since there are only two possible independent variables (ambient temperature and HTF inlet temperature in the main heater), a matrix of points is calculated for each one of the main results (power produced, thermal power required and outlet temperature of the HTF in the main heater). The output power cycle data is calculated by interpolation, and it is used to couple the power block with the solar field and the TES models.

At the beginning of each time step, an initial guess of the thermal power absorbed by the solar field is calculated. For the heat losses in the collectors, it is initially assumed that the inlet and outlet temperatures of the solar field take the design values. Ambient temperature and DNI values for each time step are taken from the meteorological hourly data. Since each time step is half an hour, the DNI and ambient temperature values correspond to those of that hour. Values of modified DNI (with the modifier factor, $DNI \cdot K$) below $100 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ are not considered to avoid excessive low HTF mass flow rates in the solar field.

To calculate the time required to perform the solar field start-up, next steps are followed:

- 1) The energy contained in the solar field (HTF + pipes) if the power block operates at the design HTF main heater inlet temperature is calculated for each time-step using Equation 2.37, Equation 2.39 and Equation 2.41. To calculate it, only the solar field inlet temperature must be defined since the outlet one always takes the design value. The solar field inlet temperature is calculated from the off-design points matrices of the power cycle, considering that it corresponds with the HTF outlet temperature of the main heater.

2) Once the energy contained in the solar field is calculated for each time step, the highest value is selected. This energy value represents the threshold the solar field must reach to be considered as having completed the start-up process.

3) Each day, from dawn, the energy state of the solar field is increased by adding the energy absorbed during each time step. This energy absorbed is calculated considering the value of the thermal power absorbed previously calculated. Until the energy state of the solar field reaches the threshold value, the solar field is in the startup process, and no other operations can be performed. At the same time, every time-step with no solar radiation, the energy state of the solar field decreases due to heat losses through the collectors.

After calculating the time at which the startup processes of the solar field finishes for the complete year, a mixed-integer linear algorithm is performed to set the operation schedule that maximizes the income for each time step. The algorithm considers a simplified model with a 48-hour time horizon. The simplified model used in the optimization algorithm assumes that the temperature of the tanks at any time-step is equal to the temperature value at the beginning of the time horizon. In this way, the linearization of the system is easier. Once the operations have been scheduled, a detailed model that considers the temperature variations for each time step following the previously calculated schedule is performed. Using a detailed model allows for more accurate results once the simplified model of the algorithm has defined the scheduling of operations. This model runs only during the first 24 hours scheduled. After this, the algorithm is performed again, scheduling the next 48 hours, considering the value obtained from the detailed model as the initial value. It should be noted that if a 24-hour time horizon with a 24-hour recalculation interval had been considered, the hot tank would always empty at the end of the day regardless of the hourly price. On the other hand, considering a 76-hour time horizon with a 24-hour recalculation interval would result in excessively high computation time for the algorithm without achieving significantly better results.

Three possible operations are considered: Power production, only storage and power block startup process.

For the power production case, three possible variants are considered depending on whether the solar field thermal power is higher than the power required from the power block or not: Power production and charging TES ($SF \rightarrow PB + TES$), power production and discharging TES ($TES + SF \rightarrow PB$), power production without solar radiation ($TES \rightarrow PB$).

For the only storage case, the PB is off, and the solar field thermal power is stored ($SF \rightarrow TES$).

The start-up case varies depending on the incident solar thermal power. The power block startup can consume energy from either the TES, the solar field, or a combination of both.

Process diagrams for each operation are shown below.

Power production and charging TES ($SF \rightarrow PB + TES$):

Two loops are introduced in the code. The first ensures the convergence of the inlet temperature of the solar field, which is the parameter initially estimated. The second avoids the salts mass flow rate exceeds the design value. In that case, the outlet temperature of the molten salts is recalculated while the mass flow rate is fixed at its design value. If the outlet temperature of the molten salts matches the outlet temperature of the solar field, then the solar field is defocused, and some solar energy is lost. It is shown in [Figure 2.12](#).

Figure 2.12 (SF→TES+PB)

Power production and discharging TES: (TES+SF→PB):

In this case the HTF inlet temperature to the main heater is the unknown parameter since it is calculated as the mix between the flow that comes from the solar field and that comes from the TES. It is shown in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13 (SF+TES→PB)

Power production without solar radiation (TES→PB)

The HTF inlet temperature to the main heater is the unknown parameter which is initially estimated and is recalculated through Equation 2.35. It is shown in Figure 2.14.

Figure 2.14 (TES→PB)

Only storage (SF→TES)

In this case, the power block is off, and the solar energy is only used to heat the TES.

Since the maximum value of salts mass flow rate is the nominal one, the maximum thermal power that the TES can absorb is approximately half of the solar field nominal power. To avoid large thermal losses, the same consideration from Power production and charging TES (SF→PB+TES) case have been assumed: The outlet temperature of the salts can reach the same value as the outlet temperature of the solar field. It is shown in Figure 2.15.

The diagrams for the power block startup cases are not shown because they are very similar to the previous ones. The main difference is that the thermal power required by the power block corresponds to the start-up power value, and for simplification purposes, the HTF outlet temperature of the power block is considered to have the same value than the HTF outlet temperature of the TES. In case that the solar power exceeds the PB startup thermal power required, the excess is derived to TES. Alternatively, if the solar power is not enough, the TES complements the required energy. Finally, if it is no solar radiation, the TES supplies the energy.

Figure 2.15 (SF→TES)

2.6.5 Schedule optimization algorithm

The objective of the optimization algorithm is to set the schedule of operations for each time-step in order to maximize the incomes. For this purpose, a mixed-integer linear program is used. It is considered a 48-hour time horizon that is recalculated every 24 hours. Each time-step of the algorithm coincides with the simulation time-step (half an hour).

Four optimization integer variables are considered $\hat{\alpha}(j)$, $\hat{\beta}(j)$, $\hat{\gamma}(j)$, $\hat{\eta}(j)$. Each one is defined in each time step j :

$\hat{\alpha}(j)$ is 1 when the PB is producing energy and 0 when it is not. Three processes can occur depending on whether the solar field absorbs more power than required by the PB, less power, or if there is no solar radiation: SF→TES+PB, SF+TES→PB, TES→PB.

$\hat{\beta}(j)$ is 1 when the PB is in the startup process and 0 when it is not. Like in the previous case, three processes can occur depending on whether the solar field absorbs more power than required for the PB startup, less power, or if there is no solar radiation.

$\hat{\gamma}(j)$ is 1 if the TES is storing energy and the PB is off (SF→TES) or if the power plant is off. If there is solar radiation, the power is stored, if not the CSP is off.

$\hat{\eta}(j)$ is 1 if the PB is shutting down and 0 when it is not. When active, the remaining salts from the TES are fully discharged during the considered time step. This process can only occur when there is no solar radiation.

Two additional variables are considered to determine the mass flow rate of salts lost due to defocusing in each of the two main processes: $\dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j)$, $\dot{m}_{df,WPr}(j)$. The first variable assesses the mass flow rate of molten salts that are not stored due defocusing when the power block is operating and producing electricity. The second variable refers to the salts that are not stored due defocusing when the power block is off, and the TES is storing energy from the solar field. The defocusing assessed by the algorithm avoids emptying the tanks below their minimum level.

At the beginning of the time horizon, before running the algorithm, power and molten salt mass flow rate for discharge/charge are calculated for the four possible operations at each time step. These input data are $\dot{P}_{Pr}(j)$, $\dot{P}_{WPr}(j)$, $\dot{P}_{stPb}(j)$, $\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)$, $\dot{m}_{WPr}(j)$, $\dot{m}_{stPb}(j)$. The first array indicates the net power produced (gross power minus the cooler power and minus the HTF pump consumption). The second and third arrays are negative since there is only power consumed by the HTF pump. The fourth indicates the molten salts mass flow rate stored/discharged during electricity production. The fifth indicate the molten salts mass flow rate stored when the power block is off, and the TES is storing energy from the solar field, and the sixth is the molten salts mass flow rate that is stored/discharged during the power block startup. The molten salts mass flow rate is positive when it is stored and negative when it is discharged. No economic losses are considering for charging or discharging the TES.

When the algorithm is performed, it is assumed that the temperature of the tanks at any time step matches the temperature of the tanks at the initial time step. Although this introduces some error, it is not significant because the large capacity of the tanks leads to relatively stable temperatures for the considered time horizon.

The restrictions considered in the algorithm are shown below:

Equation 2.43 sets that only one of the four main operations can take place in each time step, and only if an HTF startup is not occurring during that time step, $\hat{\tau}(j) = 0$.

Equation 2.44 and Equation 2.45 set the upper and lower bounds of the mass flow rate of molten salts that are not stored due defocusing when the power block is operating. $\dot{m}_{Ub,df,Pr}(j) = \dot{m}_{Pr}(j)$ if $\dot{m}_{Pr}(j) > 0$ and $\dot{m}_{Ub,df,Pr}(j) = 0$ in any other case.

Equation 2.46 and Equation 2.47 establish the upper and lower bounds of the mass flow rate of molten salts that are not stored due defocusing when the power block is off.

Equation 2.48, Equation 2.49, Equation 2.50 and Equation 2.51 set the relation between $\hat{\alpha}(j)$ and $\hat{\beta}(j)$. It states that if switching from not producing to producing electricity, the power block must startup in the previous time step. $\hat{\theta}(j)$ is an auxiliary variable.

Equation 2.52 and Equation 2.53 set the molten salts mass balance in the tanks. Equation 2.54 and Equation 2.55 set the maximum and minimum level of the tanks.

Equation 2.56 and Equation 2.57 set the relation between $\hat{\eta}(j)$ and $\hat{\alpha}(j)$. The shutdown can only occur if the plant was producing electricity in the previous time step. Equation 2.58 set

the upper limit of the molten salts mass flow rate that is discharged during the shutdown process. $\dot{m}_{Ub,sdPB}(j) = |\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)|$ if $Q_{sf}(j) = 0$ and $\dot{m}_{Ub,sdPB}(j) = 0$ in any other case.

Equation 2.59 to Equation 2.63 is the linearization of the non-linear constraint: $\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) = E(j-1) \cdot \hat{\eta}(j)$

Equation 2.64 is the function to be maximized. All the terms are multiplied by 0.5 since the time step is half an hour. The first term, $\dot{P}_{Pr}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}(j)$, represents the net power produced by the PB when it is producing electricity during all the time step. The second term, $\frac{\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j)}{-\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)} \cdot \dot{P}_{Pr}(j)$, is the net power produced during the shutdown, where $\frac{\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j)}{-\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)}$ is the time fraction that is producing energy. The third term, $\dot{P}_{StPB}(j) \cdot \beta(j)$, is the power consumed by the HTF pump when the PB is in the startup. The fourth term, $\dot{P}_{wPr}(j) \cdot \hat{\gamma}(j)$, is the power consumed by the HTF pump when the power block is off, and the TES is storing energy. Finally, the fifth term, $0.4 \cdot \beta(j) \cdot \dot{Q}_{StPB}$ gives an experimental value to avoid excessive PB startups number.

$$\hat{\alpha}(j) + \hat{\beta}(j) + \hat{\gamma}(j) + \hat{\eta}(j) = 1 - \hat{\tau}(j) \quad (2.43)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{Ub,df,Pr}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}(j) \quad (2.44)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) \geq 0 \quad (2.45)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{wPr}(j) \cdot \hat{\gamma}(j) \quad (2.46)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) \geq 0 \quad (2.47)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 \geq \hat{\alpha}(1) \quad (2.48)$$

$$-\hat{\alpha}(j) + \hat{\alpha}(j+1) = \hat{\beta}(j) - \hat{\theta}(j) \quad (2.49)$$

$$\hat{\beta}(j) + \hat{\theta}(j) \leq 1 \quad (2.50)$$

$$-\hat{\alpha}(96) = \hat{\beta}(96) - \hat{\theta}(96) \quad (2.51)$$

$$E(1) = \hat{\alpha}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr}(1) + \hat{\beta}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{stPb}(1) + \hat{\gamma}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{wPr}(1) - \dot{m}_{df,Pr}(1) - \dot{m}_{df,wPr}(1) - \dot{m}_{sdPB}(1) + E_o \quad (2.52)$$

$$E(j) = \hat{\alpha}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr}(j) + \hat{\beta}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{stPb}(j) + \hat{\gamma}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{wPr}(j) - \dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) - \dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) - \dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) + E(j-1) \quad (2.53)$$

$$E(j) \geq E_{max} \quad (2.54)$$

$$E(j) \leq E_{min} \quad (2.55)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}(1) \geq \hat{\eta}(1) \quad (2.56)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}(j) \geq \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (2.57)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{Ub,sdPB}(j) \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (2.58)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E_{max} \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (2.59)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \geq E_{min} \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (2.60)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E(j-1) - E_{min} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(j)] \quad (2.61)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \geq E(j-1) - E_{max} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(j)] \quad (2.62)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E_o - E_{min} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(1)] \quad (2.63)$$

$$\text{Incomes}(j) = \text{Price}(j) \cdot 0.5 \cdot \left[\dot{P}_{Pr}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}(j) + \frac{\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j)}{-\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)} \cdot \dot{P}_{Pr}(j) + \dot{P}_{stPb}(j) \cdot \hat{\beta}(j) + \dot{P}_{wPr}(j) \cdot \hat{\gamma}(j) - 0.4 \cdot \hat{\beta}(j) \cdot \dot{Q}_{stPb} \right] \quad (2.64)$$

2.7 HRB-propane components design methodology

2.7.1 Main heater

The main heater is selected as shell and tube with single segmental and one pass per tube and shell. The heat exchanger material is stainless steel. The heat exchanger meets TEMA “DEN” standard as it has a special high-pressure closure and a fixed tube sheet. The tube thickness is selected considering the ASME code [56,57].

The heat exchanger has been designed using a genetic algorithm in which the objective is to minimize the heat exchanger area. The optimization variables include the number of heat exchangers in parallel, the maximum velocity inside the tubes, the tube diameter, the pitch and the baffle cut percentage. The tube pitch and tube diameters standardized values considered in the optimization process are shown in Table 2.9. The restrictions include both those imposed by the power cycle pressure drop constraints (described in Section 2.5) and by the manufacturing of the heat exchanger [58]. Pressure limitations are considered on both the tube side and the shell side. The Reynolds number must be greater than 3000 to ensure turbulent flow. The tube length-to-shell diameter ratio must be between 4 and 15, and the tube length must be less than 20 meters. The constraints are summarized in Table 2.10.

Table 2.9 Standard tube data considered

D_{tube} (mm)	Pitch(mm)
9.525 ; 12.7 ; 15.875 ; 19.05	{1.25 ; 1.33 ; 1.5} · D_t

Table 2.10 Main heater design constraints

L_{tube}/D_{shell}	L_{tube} (m)	ΔP_{shell} (bar)	ΔP_{tube} (bar)	Re_{tube}
9.0	<20	<1.25	<1.1	>3000

It should be noted that the heat exchanger has been divided into 25 sections, with the UA factor calculated for each one. In this way, once optimization variables values have been established for the entire heat exchanger, the overall heat transfer coefficient for each section is calculated based on the thermodynamic properties of the flow at the inlet and outlet of each section. Knowing the UA factor, the required tube length for each segment is then determined and the constraints are checked.

The sizing methodology for each part is summarized below:

The heat transfer coefficient inside the tubes has been calculated using the Jackson correlation, as it provides greater accuracy than the Dittus-Boelter correlation under conditions close to the critical point [59]. This correlation is shown in Appendix A.1. The friction factor is calculated using Colebrook-White correlation [60].

The Delaware method is used to calculate the shell heat transfer coefficient and pressure drop. This method is comprehensive and involves the computation of numerous geometric

variables of the heat exchanger. There are various versions of this method, and the one used here can be found in [61]. The complete correlation is shown in [Appendix A.2](#).

The heat exchanger model considers the following steps: 1°) The Jackson correlation is used to calculate the heat transfer coefficient inside the tubes estimating an initial wall temperature. 2°) The shell diameter is determined assuming a specific pitch, tube diameter and inlet tube velocity. One tube pass and square tube pattern is considered. 3°) Delaware method is used to calculate the external heat transfer coefficient while a conduction heat transfer equation is used to calculate the external wall temperature. 4°) The overall heat transfer coefficient is calculated. 5°) The length of each heat exchanger segment is determined considering the UA factor from the power cycle design process and the U factor calculated in step 4. 6°) The internal wall temperature is recalculated, and all the steps are repeated until convergence is achieved.

2.7.2 Recuperator

The pressure drop restriction on the shell side imposed by the power cycle conditions (0.64 bar) makes it challenging to find an exchanger that satisfies it. Conventional shell and tubes with segmental baffles (simple or double) are not suitable. PCHE with same channels design for both flows like the used in [62,63] are not suitable as the density ratio between flows is too high. The design selected is a RODbaffle heat exchanger.

A RODbaffle exchanger is a shell and tube heat exchanger with longitudinal flow in the shell. Its main advantage in this application is that, having a larger hydraulic diameter of the shell compared to a tube or channel, it allows high Reynolds number with a lower fluid velocity. This leads to a relatively high heat transfer coefficient in the shell with reduced pressure losses. The purpose of the baffles is essentially to reduce the unsupported length of the tubes, thereby avoiding vibrations. Baffles are made by a grid of rods welded to a ring whose inner diameter matches with the outer tube limit diameter. Rods have the same diameter as the value of the gap between tubes and are placed between alternate tubes, so a square pattern of the tubes is needed. The rods are placed only in one direction although some perpendicular cross-support strips welded to the rods can be needed when the shell diameter is high, to increase their rigidity. A complete description of this type of exchanger is shown in [64].

The heat exchanger has a fixed tubesheet, like the main heater, and the material used is carbon steel. The sizing is performed for each of the 25 parts as in the main heater case. The heat calculation process is similarly to the main heater case. The heat transfer coefficient inside the shell and the pressure drop are calculated considering the correlations in [65]. Alternative correlations with similar results have been proposed in [66,67].

2.7.3 Air cooler

The condenser has been designed as an A-frame air cooler to reduce the total floor area and to improve condensate drainage. The tubes are made of carbon steel with aluminium fins. A standardized high fin tube array has been selected. [Table 2.11](#) shows the tube outlet tube diameter (D_{tube}), the pitch between tubes ($Pitch$), the number of fins per meter length, ($N_{fin,L}$), the fin diameter (D_{fin}), the fin height (he_{fin}), and the fin thickness (th_{fin}). The tube bundles have 4 rows to avoid excessive pressure drop. The power consumption of the fans and the pressure drop values should match to those calculated through methodology presented in [Section 2.4.1](#).

Table 2.11 Standard high-fin tube for air cooler [69]

D_{tube} (mm)	Pitch (mm)	$N_{fin,L}$ (/m)	D_{fin} (mm)	he_{fin} (mm)	th_{fin} (mm)
25.4	$2.5 \cdot D_{tube}$	393.7	57.15	15.87	0.32

The heat transfer coefficient inside the tubes is calculated considering a superheated vapor condensation process with stratified flow [69]. The correlation is shown in [Appendix A.1](#). The heat transfer outside the tubes is evaluated using the method explain in [68]. The complete methodology is shown in [Appendix A.3](#). The model considers the following steps: First, the heat transfer inside the tubes is calculated by considering an estimated internal tube wall temperature. Then, the tube length is calculated considering only the internal heat transfer coefficient. This length is required to calculate the velocity of the air crossing the bundle, which is also needed to determine the external heat transfer coefficient. Finally, the overall heat transfer coefficient is evaluated, and the internal tube wall temperature is recalculated.

After the bundles sizing, the length and width of the A-frame tube bundle is calculated considering that the tubes are at a 60° angle to the horizontal. Velocity and fan diameters can be calculated, as well as the pressure load and the total power consume.

2.7.4 Compressor

The compressor is modelled as an axial flow turbomachine. The material considered is stainless steel. The thermophysical parameters related to the inlet and outlet of the machines are known data. The degree of reaction is fixed to 0.5 (Rd), the equivalent diffusion ratio is set to 1.95 (DR_e), the β_m angle is 45° and the axial chord-pitch ratio is set to 0.9 (ch/s). These are common design values for air compressors since as lead to high efficiency and stability operation around the design point [70,71]. The number of stages, the mean diameter-first rotor height ratio, the aspect ratio of the last rotor stage (height/axial chord ratio) and the chord variation between the inlet and outlet stages are the optimizing values. These two last parameters allow to obtain the aspect ratio of each stage establishing a linear variation between the chord values at the inlet and the outlet of the compressor. In this way, the calculation is speed up since less optimizing variables are needed. The objective is to achieve an adequate isentropic efficiency (similar to that assumed in the cycle calculation). The main constrains are the Mach number, which should be lower than 0.7 and the aspect ratio minimum value (H/ch), that should be higher than 1 [72]. Additionally, the limit of 100 blades per stage set in Ref. [73] is considered an indicative design value. [Table 2.12](#) summarizes the input data and [Table 2.13](#) the constraints.

Mechanical stress is not considered due to two reasons: 1^o) The mass flow is considerably lower than in the turbine, so the mean height is much lower (that means reduced centrifugal stress); 2^o) In compressors, more stages are needed, so the specific work and the force applied in each blade is considerably lower, both reducing the bending stress. The equations and methodology used in the compressor design is shown in [Appendix A.4](#). The correlations were originally developed for air turbomachinery, but since they are expressed in terms of non-dimensional parameters, they can be applied to other fluids for preliminary sizing (blade geometry, stage count, main dimensions). In this work, the isentropic efficiency of the propane cycle is used as input to calculate the required work, while the correlations provide an approximate machine size for cost estimation, as commonly done in other studies with organic fluids and CO_2 [74–78].

Table 2.12 Propane compressor design input data

Rd	DR_e	β_m	ch/s
0.5	1.95	45	0.9

Table 2.13 Propane compressor design constraints

Mach	H/ch	$\max(n_{blades})$
<0.7	>1	Around 100

2.7.5 Turbine

The turbine is modelled as an axial flow turbomachine. The material selected is stainless steel (GTD-450) since the inlet temperature is not high (377 °C), although high mechanical strength is required. Centrifugal and bending stresses are considered in the pre-design to account its effect in the structural design, which may be significant. As the detailed structural design is out of the scope of this work, the effort due to vibrations, with a lower impact, is not considered. A constant mean diameter is assumed across all stages. The use of these assumptions is supported by the fact that the sizing objective is to estimate a cost.

The degree of the reaction is fixed to 0.5 (Rd) to achieve a high efficiency and to have a similar blade design between the rotor and the stator, the interstitial gap is 0.4 mm (ig), and the thickness-axial chord ratio is 0.3, (t/ch). The rotational speed is also considered an input data (rpm), and its value matches that obtained from the compressor. The reference axial chord-pitch ratio (ch/s), is derived from the Zweifel criteria. The number of stages, flow and load coefficients, aspect ratio of the first stage and chord variation between the inlet and outlet stages are the optimizing variables. Linear variation between the chord values at the inlet and the outlet of the turbine is considered. As with the compressor, the objective is to match a similar efficiency to that assumed in the cycle calculation. The main constraints are that mechanical stress should not exceed 550 MPa in any stage, the Mach number should be lower than 1 and, as with the compressor, the maximum aspect ratio should be greater than 1. Additionally, the limit of 100 blades per stage, as set in Ref. [73], is considered an indicative design value. Table 2.14 summarizes the input data and Table 2.15 the constraints.

The Soderberg's correlation is used to calculate the profile losses. Ref. [72] has been considered to calculate the bending stress and Ref. [79] for the centrifugal stress. The equations and methodology used in the turbine pre-design are shown in Appendix A.5. The same considerations described for the compressor apply here.

Table 2.14 Propane turbine design input data

R	ig (mm)	t/ch	(ch/s)	rpm
0.5	4	0.3	Obtained by Zweifel correlation	Obtained from the compressor

Table 2.15 Propane turbine design constraints

Mach	H/ch	$\max(n_{blades})$	stress (MPa)
<1	>1	Around 100	<550

2.8 Cost correlations and comparison with Steam Rankine cycle

The LCOE for the CSP with the HRB-propane power block is calculated and compared with that of the steam Rankine cycle case. To carry out this comparison, it is necessary first to calculate the costs of their respective components. Since the TES and the solar field are the same for both cases, the cost difference is due to the power blocks. Some studies, such as [74], have determined the cost of the steam Rankine power block for a parabolic CSP; however, they neither specify the methodology used to estimate it nor the costs of the individual components.

The HRB-propane is a novel cycle, so to estimate the cost of the power block, first the cost of each of its components must be evaluated. Thus, cost correlations generally involve a significant degree of uncertainty, thus, comparing both cycles using different cost methodologies can introduce even more uncertainty. The cost comparison is performed by estimating the costs of the components for both cycles. For the steam Rankine cycle case, the obtained value will be lower than the actual cost, as there are other components that are not sized but significantly impact the cost, such as water treatment systems, ejectors, etc. Consequently, the total cost of the steam Rankine power block given by [80] will serve as an upper bound, while the lumped sum of the costs calculated for the components will serve as a lower bound. Should be considered that Ref. [80] is cited only to support cost assumptions and not as the source of the technical design of the steam cycle itself. For the HRB-propane case, the upper cost considered is set 33 % higher than the cost obtained from correlations, corresponding to the maximum uncertainty value among the references considered.

No additional costs associated with the innovation and low TRL of HRB-propane components have been considered. In the author's opinion, such costs should only be included once more detailed designs of the components are available. At this first stage, it is more consistent to apply the same cost correlations to both cycles in order to determine whether a more in-depth study is justified.

Table 2.16 shows the references for the cost correlations of each HRB component, while Table 2.17 shows the references for the cost correlations of the steam Rankine cycle components. The design of the cooler is assumed to be the same as in the HRB-propane case. Feedwater heat exchangers, preheater, superheater and reheater have been sized as single-segmental heat exchangers with one tube pass following the Delaware's method. However, the preheater, superheater, and reheater do not have tubes in the windows, which reduces the HTF pressure drop. The boiler is designed as a kettle reboiler, with the HTF flowing through the tubes and the water/steam flowing through the shell. The Gnielinsky's correlation is used to evaluate the heat transfer coefficient inside the tubes (Appendix A.1). The condensation on the shell side of the feedwater heat exchangers is evaluated using the McNaught's correlation in conjunction with the Delaware's method (Appendix A.2). The shell side heat transfer correlation for the kettle reboiler has been evaluated considering [81]. The method is shown in Appendix A.2.

These heat exchangers have been designed using a genetic algorithm. For the single-segmental heat exchangers, the optimization variables include the number of heat exchangers in parallel, the outer tube limit diameter, the tube diameter, the pitch and the baffle cut percentage. Constraints considered are shown in Table 2.18. For all cases, the tube length-to-diameter ratio must be between 4 and 15, the tube length must be less 20 meters, and the Reynolds number inside the tubes must be greater than 3000 to ensure turbulent flow. These constraints are the same as those considered for the HRB case. For feedwater heat exchangers, both the shell and tube pressure drop must be under 15 kPa. For the entire steam generation system (preheater, reheater,

superheater and boiler), the HTF pressure drop must be lower than 1.25 bar (0.25 bar per each heat exchanger except for the boiler, whose limit is 0.5 bar). Finally, the boiler shell diameter must be under 2 m to avoid excessive thicknesses.

Table 2.16 Cost correlation references for HRB-propane

	Main heater	Recuperator	Cooler	Turbine	Compressor	Pump	Generator and gear box
Reference	[82]	[83]	[83]	[22]	[84]	[85]	[83]

Table 2.17 Cost correlation references for Steam Rankine

	Feedwater heat exchangers, preheater, evaporator, superheater, reheater	Deaerator	Cooler	Turbine	Pumps	Generator and gear box
Reference	[82]	[86]	[83]	[87]	[87]	[83]

Table 2.18 Constraints for Steam Rankine heat exchangers sizing

	L/D	L(m)	ΔP_{shell} (bar)	ΔP_{tube} (bar)	D_{shell} (m)	Re_{tube}
Feedwater heat exchangers	4 < L/D < 15	< 20	< 0.15	< 0.15	-	> 3000
Preheater/Reheater/Superheater	4 < L/D < 15	< 20	< 0.25	< 0.25	-	> 3000
Boiler	4 < L/D < 15	< 20	< 0.5	-	< 2	> 3000

Ref. [82] is used to estimate the costs of the heat exchangers except for the condenser. First, the purchased cost is calculated using Equation 2.65 where C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{13} are equipment specific coefficients and X is the characteristic equipment factor. In the case of heat exchangers, the characteristic equipment factor is the Area.

$$\log_{10} Cost_{equip,HX} = C_{11} + C_{12} \log_{10}(X) + C_{13} [\log_{10}(X)]^2 \quad (2.65)$$

According to this reference, Equation 2.65 is applicable only within a certain range of size. If the characteristic dimension of the equipment exceeds the maximum value of this range, the acquisition cost is first calculated using the maximum value of the range, and then the *six-tenth rule* is applied (expressed in Equation 2.66). Here, $Cost_{equip,mv}$ is the purchase cost considering the maximum characteristic factor value of the interval specified in the reference and X is the characteristic factor value calculated of the equipment.

$$Cost_{equip} = Cost_{equip,mv} \cdot \left(\frac{X}{X_{mv}} \right)^{0.6} \quad (2.66)$$

The total cost of the equipment is calculated using Equation 2.67. B_{c1} and B_{c2} are coefficients that represent the installation costs, F_M is the material factor and F_p is the pressure correction factor. F_p is calculated using Equation 2.68, where P is the pressure (bar) inside the heat exchanger tubes or in the shell.

$$Cost_{BM,HX} = Cost_{equip,HX} \cdot (B_{c1} + B_{c2} F_M F_p) \quad (2.67)$$

$$\log_{10} F_p = C_{21} + C_{22} \log_{10}(P) + C_{23} [\log_{10}(P)]^2 \quad (2.68)$$

The coefficients for each equipment for which Ref. [82] has been used are shown in Table 2.19. The first two components correspond to the HRB cycle, while the rest correspond to the

Rankine steam cycle. As commented, all of them except for the evaporator have been calculated considering a fixed tube sheet design. The evaporator is designed as a kettle reboiler. All heat exchangers whose temperature is higher than 370 °C are made of stainless steel (main heater of the HRB-propane power block and evaporator, superheater and reheater of the steam-Rankine power block).

Table 2.19 Coefficients for cost correlation of [82]

	Type heat exchanger	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{13}	C_{21}	C_{22}	C_{23}	B_1	B_2	F_M	Range (m^2)
Recuperator	Rod-baffle	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	1	<1000
Main heater	Single segmental	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	2.9	<1000
Feedwaters	Single segmental	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	1	<1000
Preheater	NTIW single segmental	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	1	<1000
Evaporator	Kettle	4.4646	-0.5277	0.3955	0.03881	-0.11272	0.08183	1.63	1.66	2.9	<100
Superheater	NTIW single segmental	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	2.9	<1000
Reheater	NTIW single segmental	4.3247	-0.3030	0.1634	-0.00164	-0.00627	0.0123	1.63	1.66	2.9	<1000

For all the other equipment a percentage installation cost of 20 % has been considered.

Ref. [83] is used to estimate the dry cooler cost. (Equation 2.69). The correlation is based on UA factors. Although the correlation is for CO₂ cooling, it is valid for this case because the high thermal resistance of air dominates the heat transfer.

$$Cost_{cooler} = 32.88 \cdot UA^{0.75} \quad (2.69)$$

$$where 8.6 \cdot 10^5 < UA(W/K) < 7.5 \cdot 10^5$$

Reference [22] is used to estimate the propane turbine cost (Equation 2.70). The correlation is based on the number of stages and the size parameter. This parameter depends on the volumetric flow rate (m^3/s) at the outlet and the isentropic expansion of each stage (J/kg) (Equation 2.73).

$$Cost_{turb,HRB} = 1230000 \cdot \left(\frac{N_{stages}}{2}\right)^{0.5} \cdot \left(\frac{SP}{0.18}\right)^{1.1} \quad (2.70)$$

$$SP = \frac{\sqrt{\dot{V}}}{\Delta h_{is,stage}^{1/4}} \quad (2.71)$$

Ref. [84] shows the cost of an air compressor working with air instead of propane. Thus, to apply it, we have previously designed an equivalent air compressor with the same size and number of stages as the propane one. The correlation used is shown below (Equation 2.72). It depends on the air mass flow rate (kg/s), the isentropic efficiency and the pressure ratio. In case the isentropic efficiency or the pressure ratio of the air equivalent compressor are lower than those of the propane compressor, the values of these parameters from the propane compressor will be considered to avoid underestimating the costs.

$$Cost_{comp} = 71.1 \cdot \frac{\dot{m}_{air}}{0.9 - \eta_{is}} \cdot pr \cdot \ln pr \quad (2.72)$$

Ref. [85] is used to calculate the propane pump. It depends on the power consume (kW). Equation 2.73 is used:

$$Cost_{pump,HRB} = \log(\dot{P}) - 0.03195 \cdot (\dot{P})^2 + 467.2 \cdot \dot{P} + 2.048 \cdot 10^4 \quad (2.73)$$

$$20 < \dot{P}(kW) < 3500$$

Ref.[86] shows the correlation cost for a deaerator (Equation 2.74), where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate (kg/s).

$$Cost_{deaerator} = 67114 \cdot \dot{m}_{water}^{0.64} \quad (2.74)$$

Ref.[87] is used to calculate the steam Rankine turbine cost (Equation 2.75). It depends on the turbine power (kW), efficiency and inlet temperature (K).

$$Cost_{steam\ turbine} = 3880.5 \cdot \dot{P}^{0.7} \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{0.05}{1 - \eta_{is}}\right)^3\right) \cdot \left(1 + 5 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{T_{in} - 866}{10.42}\right)\right) \quad (2.75)$$

Ref.[87] is also used to calculate the water pumps cost (Equation 2.76). It depends on the pump power (kW) and the isentropic efficiency.

$$Cost_{pump,water} = 705.48 \cdot \dot{P}^{0.71} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{0.2}{1 - \eta_{is}}\right) \quad (2.76)$$

Ref.[83] has been used to calculate the generator and gear box costs. (Equation 2.77 and Equation 2.78). Power values are in MW.

$$Cost_{generator} = 108900 \cdot \dot{P}^{0.5463} \quad (2.77)$$

$$Cost_{gearbox} = 177200 \cdot \dot{P}^{0.2434} \quad (2.78)$$

All costs have been expressed in €, so a conversion rate of 1€ = 1.05 USD representative of the 2022–2023 period is used. To update the costs obtained from each correlation, Equation 2.79 is used. The CEPCI values for each reference are summarized in Table 2.20.

$$Cost_{BM_{2022}} = Cost_{BM_{ref}} \cdot \frac{CEPCI_{2022}}{CEPCI_{ref}} \quad (2.79)$$

Table 2.20 CEPCI coefficients for each reference

Year 2022	[82]	[83]	[22]	[84]	[85]	[86]	[87]
798.7	398.7	567.5	567.3	368.1	596.2	584.6	397

Figures of merit and economic scenario

The LCOE is assessed with Equation 2.80, where LC_{INV} is the levelized costs of investment, $LC_{O\&M}$ is the levelized cost of operation and maintenance and $E_{net,year}$ is the yearly net energy production.

$$LCOE = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M}}{E_{net,year}} \quad (2.80)$$

Since the CSP has been optimized to maximize the revenues and not the net energy production, other figures of merits are also considered.

The cost-income ratio (r_{CI}) is the sum of the levelized cost of investment (LC_{INV}) and operation and maintenance ($LC_{O\&M}$) divided by the levelized incomes (LI) (Equation 2.81). It provides a figure to quantify whether or not a system is feasible. Specifically, if $r_{CI} = 1$, only the initial value of the investment is recovered at the end of the economic life of the plant, so no profit

is obtained. On the contrary, when r_{CI} is higher or lower than 1, it means the project is non-profitable or profitable, respectively.

$$r_{CI} = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M}}{LI} \quad (2.81)$$

The profits over incomes ratio (r_{PI}) is assessed using Equation 2.82 and, when it is positive, it represents the fraction of the incomes that is recovered as profits.

$$r_{PI} = \frac{LI - (LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M})}{LI} \quad (2.82)$$

In Table 2.21 the economic scenario to estimate the costs of the other systems and to perform the financial calculations are shown below.

Table 2.21 Economic scenario

Land cost [50]	2 €/m ²
Solar field cost [50]	200 €/m ²
TES cost [88]	60.5 €/kWh
Solar field O&M cost [50]	9 €/year · m ²
Yearly O&M equipment cost percentage of Inv. [50]	1 % Inv
Interest rate	4 %
Inflation	3.6 %
Amortization years	35

2.9 Results

2.9.1 Non-standardized parametric analysis

Figure 2.16 shows the values of the efficiency of each cycle depending on the bypass factor (x) and the pressure ratio (pr). The highest efficiency is achieved by the ORC-toluene cycle and HRB-propane, and it is shown in Table 2.22. The ORC-toluene pressure ratio leads to a subcritical Rankine cycle, although very close to the critical point (around 4 bar of difference), which can lead to operation problems at off-design conditions, as the high pressure will vary depending on the condensation temperature. $F_{s,gen}$ of ORC-toluene is high despite the recuperator is not balanced. This is due to various reasons: First, because of the high c_p/R factor of toluene, so the vapor has a high specific heat. Second, because there is neither a compressor nor a bypass fraction that is mixed with the main flow. However, $F_{h,add}$ is the lowest compared with the values obtained from the other cycles. This is because the recuperator is not balanced, so the pinch point is in the cold-end of the recuperator, while in the hot-end there is a high temperature difference, which leads to a lower $F_{h,add}$ value. The temperature difference in each zone can be seen in Table 2.23.

The HRB-isobutane has a higher value of $F_{s,gen}$, $F_{c,rej}$ and $F_{h,add}$ than HRB-propane. However, the HRB-propane reaches a considerably higher efficiency. This is because the maximum temperature for the isobutane is lower, which penalizes the CN factor.

The sCO₂-RB cycle has the lowest efficiency. This is because $F_{c,rej}$ and $F_{s,gen}$ are considerably lower than in the other cycles. The first term is lower due the cooling process is a sensible heat exchange process. The second term is lower because the main flow is driven by a

compressor instead that by a pump. This term could be even lower if the main inlet compressor were further from the critical point conditions.

Table 2.23 shows the UA factors in case of sizing the cycles with the solar field standardised. The thermal power supplied to each cycle coincides with those demanded by the selected HRB-propane one. The temperature difference at the cold- and hot-ends of each heat exchanger are also shown. The HRB cycles need the highest total UA values while the ORC the lowest. This is due to the high UA required by the recuperator, since it is quite well balanced. Besides, UA of the recuperator in HRB-propane is considerably higher than in the sCO_2 -RB one although the temperature difference at both ends in the latter is the same. This is because the heat capacity varies a lot inside the recuperator, so the temperature difference inside the recuperator varies considerably too. This behaviour supports the discretization of the heat exchanger in small parts. Besides, HRB and ORC cycles needs a larger cooler than the sCO_2 -RB one although, in the latter, the efficiency of the cycle is the lowest. This is because HRB and ORC reject mostly latent heat while the sCO_2 -RB rejects only sensible heat.

Figure 2.16 NSPA results

Table 2.22 Maximum efficiency NSPA results

	HRB-propane	HRB-isobutane	sCO ₂ -RB	ORC-toluene
Efficiency(%)	40	35.1	33.6	40
F _{h,add}	0.8904	0.8956	0.8806	0.8446
F _{c,rej}	0.9968	0.9989	0.9411	0.9998
F _{s,gen}	0.8899	0.9123	0.8434	0.9163
CN	2.109	1.889	2.155	2.155
x	0.25	0.25	0.29	-
rp	14	20	3.15	700

Table 2.23 Non-standardized UA factors

	HRB-propane			HRB-isobutane			sCO ₂ -RB			ORC-toluene		
	UA(MW/K)	ΔT_h (°C)	ΔT_c (°C)	UA	ΔT_h	ΔT_c	UA	ΔT_h	ΔT_c	UA	ΔT_h	ΔT_c
Main heater	7.9	19	46	2.7	87	93	14.3	5	36	7.1	5	113
Recuperator	45.8	5.2	6.5	37.2	12	6	28.1	5	5	4.5	46	5
Cooler	22.3	20	3	38.2	21	3	6.5	73	10	25	16	3
Total	75.9	-	-	78.1	-	-	48.9	-	-	36.6	-	-

2.9.2 Standardized analysis

Table 2.24 shows the results of this second analysis, which standardizes or homogenises the total UA factor and the solar field area. The designs that maximize the net power of each cycle are shown. The HRB-propane design is the same as in the previous analysis since it is the basis for the standardization. All the other cycles increase their gross efficiency over the non-standardized parametric analysis since the UA factors are increased.

The ORC-toluene cycle produces a higher nominal gross power than the HRB-propane. This difference increases in terms of net power, reaching about 2.7 % more than HRB-propane, because the ORC-toluene efficiency is slightly higher. That means a lower thermal power rejected and a lower cooler consumption. In the ORC, the UA of the cooler significantly increases, so the condensing temperature is lower than in the non-standardized analysis. The same happens with the inlet turbine temperature, which reaches the same temperature as the HTF temperature at the inlet of the main heater. Both effects lead to raise the gross efficiency over the HRB-propane around 1 %.

The sCO_2 -RB is the power cycle that improves efficiency the most, surpassing the HRB-isobutane efficiency. This is mainly because the low temperature of the cycle has been reduced to near the critical point, with the low pressure also being optimized accordingly. That leads to a high density in the main compressor inlet, reducing its consumption.

The difference in the cooler consumption between the cycles is due the different values of gross efficiency since all the power blocks receive the same thermal power. The HTF pump consumption is the same in all cases since the solar field area, HTF mass flow rate and inlet and outlet solar field temperatures have the same value.

Table 2.24 Standardized analysis results

	HRB-propane	HRB-isobutane	sCO_2-RB	ORC-toluene
Gross efficiency (%)	40	35.3	36.8	40.9
Gross power (MW)	100	88.4	92.04	102.44
Cooler consumption (MW)	3.65	3.93	3.84	3.59
HTF pump consumption (MW)	3.45	3.45	3.45	3.45
Net power produced (MW)	92.9	80.98	84.74	95.4
Low temperature (°C)	35	34.34	32	32.51
Low pressure (bar)	12.18	4.56	78.98	0.055
Inlet turbine temperature (°C)	377	308.85	395.15	396
Recuperator Pinch point (°C)	5	4.55	2.78	0.32
Pressure ratio	14	20	3.66	700.7
Maximum pressure (bar)	170.5	91.3	289.5	38.8
UA_{mh} (MW/K)	7.95	2.7	17.1	9.44
UA_{rec} (MW/K)	42.55	40.71	40.74	7.4
UA_{cooler} (MW/K)	22.54	29.61	15.19	56.2

2.9.3 Annual simulations

Table 2.25 shows the main results of the annual simulation for each cycle. The thermal energy supplied to the PB is the solar energy absorbed minus the solar field and PB startup requirements, and minus the heat losses in the molten salts tanks. Around 12 % of the absorbed solar energy is used for startup operations. The differences in absorbed solar energy are mainly related to the off-design behaviour of each cycle. Additionally, variations in return temperature and mass flow rate may influence the TES operation and the amount of solar energy that must be dumped.

The yearly efficiency is the gross energy production divided by the thermal energy supplied to the PB. The HRB-propane PB efficiency is lower than the ORC-toluene although the difference between both is lower than at nominal conditions (Table 2.24). This is because the PBs are operating more frequently during the hours with lower ambient temperatures that corresponds with the smallest PB efficiency difference between the HRB-propane and ORC-toluene. This can be seen in the row that corresponds to the PB efficiency range, where the maximum efficiency of the HRB-propane is 42 % and for ORC-Toluene is 42.4 %. On the other hand, the yearly efficiency of the steam Rankine cycle is slightly higher than that of HRB-propane, even though under nominal conditions, the efficiency of HRB-propane is higher (40 % vs 39.7 %). This is due to the high efficiency of the steam Rankine cycle under low ambient temperatures, which is even greater than that of ORC-toluene. On the other hand, the sCO₂-RB yearly efficiency is the lowest. This is due to the low efficiency achieved by the sCO₂-RB when there are higher ambient temperatures than the nominal value. Despite the special operation that has been considered for the sCO₂-RB cooler to reduce the low PB temperature, the efficiency is significantly reduced as the inlet main compressor temperature moves further from the critical point. This can be seen in the PB efficiency range where, for a low PB temperature of 43.2 °C, the efficiency achieved is 24.3 %, which is considerably lower than the efficiency obtained by other cycles. Besides, the solar energy absorbed by cycle is also the lowest. This happens because the power that can be sent to the TES is limited by the salts mass flow rate, so the collectors are defocused to prevent the HTF temperature from exceeding the design value. As the sCO₂-RB PB demands less thermal power at high ambient temperature, more power is lost due to defocusing.

The net energy production is the gross energy production minus the cooling consumption and minus the HTF pump consumption. The cooling consumption is around 4 % of the gross energy production while the HTF pump consumption is around 1.5 %. HRB-isobutane and sCO₂-RB have the lowest cooling consumption although they reach the lowest efficiency. This is because there is a limitation in the minimum temperature that the cycles can take. In the sCO₂-RB case, lower temperature values than the design one are not allowed, as they could lead to the saturation zone at the inlet of the main compressor. For HRB-isobutane, a minimum PB low temperature of around 29 °C is considered. Lower values are not allowed because they can cause the bypass fraction to enter in the saturation zone during the compression.

It should be noted that the HRB-propane power block operates the fewest hours, although its net energy production is similar to that of the steam Rankine cycle and higher than that of the sCO₂-RB and HRB-isobutane. This agrees with the values of average power and average net power produced of the HRB-propane which are similar to those of ORC-toluene despite the lower efficiency and lower total net energy production of the former. This is because the maximum power value achieved by the HRB-propane is higher than that of the other cycles. This maximum power occurs during hours with low ambient temperature, which are also the hours when the PB operates most frequently. Since the production schedule is optimized for revenue, achieving higher power in these periods is advantageous. Consequently, the revenue from HRB-propane is very similar to that of ORC-toluene (with less than a 0.5 % difference) despite the latter having higher net power production.

Table 2.25 Annual simulation results

	HRB- propane	HRB- isobutane	sCO ₂ - RB	ORC- toluene	Steam Rankine
Revenues (M€)	61.5	53.4	53.1	61.7	60.7
Solar energy absorbed (GWh)	1027.7	1028.5	1018.6	1026.1	1024.2
Solar field startup thermal energy (GWh)	101.9	101.4	102.4	101.6	101.3
PB startup thermal energy (GWh)	18.6	18.19	18.9	19	19
Heat losses in molten salts tanks (GWh)	8.5	8.8	8.5	8.7	8.5
Thermal energy delivered to the PB (GWh)	898.7	900.1	888.4	896.7	895.4
Gross energy production (GWh)	353.8	311.4	304.5	356.8	353.6
Yearly efficiency (%)	39.4	34.6	34.3	39.8	39.5
Cooling consumption (GWh)	13.1	14.2	11.4	12.9	13.1
HTF pump consumption (GWh)	5.3	5.3	5.6	5.4	5.5
Net energy production (GWh)	335.4	291.2	287.4	338.6	335.1
N° hours PB	3604	3634	3703	3641	3689
Average power produced (MW)	98.2	85.7	82.2	98	95.9
Average net power produced (MW)	93	80.3	77.6	93	90.8
Net power range (MW)	71.5/116.3	66/87.3	39.8/90.6	81/107.7	83.8/100.4
Cooling system power range (MW)	3.1/4.1	3.8/3.9	0.8/4.1	3.3/3.7	2.9/4.1
PB efficiency range (%)	34.4/42	31.2/36.8	24.4/36.8	37.6/42.4	36.9/42.7
Lower PB temperature range (°C)	11.4/53.2	29.3/52.5	32/43.2	10/50.7	11.4/53.2
Ambient temperature range (°C)	1.4/43.2	1.4/43.2	1.4/43.2	1.4/43.2	1.4/43.2

2.9.4 HRB components

The main heater has been divided into 4 heat exchangers arranged in parallel to meet the pressure drop constraint on the shell side. The highest pitch has been chosen for the same reason. Table 2.26 shows the main results

Table 2.26 Main heater results

Total exchange Area (m ²)	6012
Number of HX	4
Layout	4 in paralell
Summary results per Hx	
Area (m ²)	1503
Overall heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	1690
Tube heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	4444
Shell heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	3448
Tube pressure drop (kPa)	18
Shell pressure drop (kPa)	125
Length (m)	5.46
Shell diameter (m)	0.92
Distance between baffles (mm)	546
Outlet tube diameter (mm)	12.7
Tube pitch (mm)	25.4
Tube thickness (mm)	0.72
Baffle cut (%)	28.4
Number of tubes	1726

The recuperator has been divided into 4 lines with 4 heat exchangers in series to avoid excessive tube lengths. They are numbered from the cold side to the hot side. Each exchanger has a UA similar to the others; however, it can be observed that the lengths differ considerably each other. This is because U increases as the temperature of the fluids does, leading to lower density flows, higher velocity and higher Reynolds number. Similarly, pressure losses also increase. The maximum shell diameter had to be chosen to reduce pressure drop. The pitch has been chosen according to the tube diameter to obtain a similar internal and external heat transfer coefficient. A small tube diameter has been chosen to increase the tube number and the exchange area. This allows for a more compact exchanger design with lower pressure losses. [Table 2.27](#) shows the main results.

Table 2.27 Recuperator main results

Total exchange Area (m ²)	115164			
Number of Hx	16			
Layout	4 lines in parallel with 4 Hx in series			
Summary results per line				
Heat exchanger numeration (cold to hot)	HX 1	HX 2	HX 3	HX 4
Area (m ²)	7876	7356	6252	5594
Overall heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	338	374	420	467
Tube heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	809	892	1000	1096
Shell heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	709	788	889	1007
Tube pressure drop (kPa)	1	1	1	1
Shell pressure drop (kPa)	13.8	15.4	15.5	16
Length (m)	14.2	13.3	11.3	10.1
Shell diameter (m)	2			
Distance between baffles (mm)	150			
Outlet tube diameter (mm)	9.5			
Tube pitch (mm)	12.7			
Tube thickness (mm)	0.9			
Number of tubes	18496			

The air cooler has been divided in 5 units in parallel. Each unit is formed by a A-frame tube bundle. Since the angle of the tube bundle with the ground is 60°, the length of the tubes matches the total width of the A-frame structure. Nine fans are arranged along each unit. The heat transfer is dominated by the thermal resistance of the air, so a low global heat transfer coefficient is obtained. The calculated face velocity (air velocity when it crosses the first tube row bundle) is in the range of the recommended values given by [68]. [Table 2.28](#) shows the main results.

In [Table 2.29](#) the main results of the propane compressor are shown, alongside those for an equivalent air compressor with the same dimensions and stages as the propane compressor. This comparison is made because a correlation for air compressors was used for cost estimation purposes. The table includes parameters for both the first and last rotor inlets of each compressor. The total-to-total efficiency of the propane compressor corresponds to the isentropic efficiency calculated through the thermodynamic states at the inlet and outlet of the compressor. The maximum Mach is achieved at the inlet of the first rotor stage.

Table 2.28 Air cooler main results

Total exchange Area (m^2)	803288
Power consumption (MW)	3.647
Number of units	5
Layout	5 units in parallel
Summary results per unit	
Area (m^2)	160658
Overall heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)	28
Tube heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)	1803
Shell heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)	46
Air cooler pressure drop (Pa)	120
Number of fans	9
Tube length (m)	9.4
Fan diameter (m)	7
Width of the unit (m)	9.4
Length of the unit (m)	79.3
Number of tubes per unit	10000
Number of rows	4
Face velocity	2.46

For sizing the propane compressor, the aspect ratio of the last rotor stage has been set to the minimum allowed value, in order to keep the number of blades of the stage near the limitation given by [73] while the mean diameter–first rotor height ratio is increased to reduce the rotational speed needed without increasing excessively the number of blades. It is interesting to reduce the rotational speed since it is an input value for the preliminary design of the turbine, and it is related to the centrifugal stress. The chord variation between the inlet and outlet stages leads to adequate aspect ratio values for each stage [72]. The number of stages considered allows obtaining a Mach value lower than the imposed limit.

For sizing the equivalent air compressor, it has been assumed that the flow coefficient, loading coefficient, degree of reaction, number of stages, Mach number at the inlet of the first rotor stage, solidity, and the aspect ratio of each stage match those of the designed propane compressor. Ambient pressure has been selected for the inlet, as it is the standard for air compressors. Adjustments to the inlet air temperature and mass flow rate have been made to achieve the same mean diameter and blade height in the first rotor stage as those found in the propane compressor. However, the height of the last stage differs between the two compressors due to the distinct characteristics of each fluid, which lead to different compression processes. Additionally, there is a noticeable difference in flow rates between the compressors, mainly due to variations in inlet density. Consequently, the propane compressor requires significantly more power than an equivalent air compressor of the same size.

For the compressor cost estimation, the calculated mass flow rate of the equivalent air compressor is considered, as it is related to the size of the machine. However, the values of pressure ratio and efficiency of the propane compressor are considered to avoid underestimating the costs.

Table 2.29 Compressor main results

	Propane compressor		Air compressor	
	1st rotor stage	last rotor stage	1st rotor stage	last rotor stage
Inlet pressure (bar)	12.2	139.6	1	8.8
Inlet temperature (°C)	53.6	190.1	28.5	318.2
Mean height (mm)	77.5	6.6	77.5	16.3
Aspect ratio	3.67	1	3.67	1
Number of blades	39	123	39	49
Pressure ratio		14		10.1
Shaft speed (rpm)		11947		17892
Mass flow (kg/s)		140.45		10.35
Total-total efficiency (%)		88.25		86.96
Flow coefficient			0.5	
Load coefficient			0.41	
Degree of reaction			0.5	
Number of stages			11	
Mean diameter (mm)			286	
Axial chord-pitch ratio			0.9	
Maximum Mach			0.68	

In [Table 2.30](#), the turbine sizing is presented. A low load and flow coefficient have been chosen to reduce the centrifugal and bending stress. Compared to air turbines, higher bending stress is obtained due to the high pressures involved. Although the profile section modulus of a blade increases with the cube of the chord, the last rotor stage has the highest bending stress due to its high aspect ratio. However reducing the aspect ratio would result in lower efficiency. The last rotor stage has also the highest centrifugal stress since it has the greatest blade height. The total stress has been calculated as the sum of bending and centrifugal stress, however for future studies, it would be advisable to perform a combined stress analysis.

Table 2.30 Turbine main results

	1st stage (stator)	last stage (stator)	last stage (rotor)
Mean height (mm)	21.2	133.8	182.2
Aspect ratio	1.33	4	5.2
Chord (mm)	23.6	47.9	52
Number of blades	79	39	36
Centrifugal stress (MPa)	0	0	328.2
Bending stress (MPa)	121.8	191.1	221.4
Total stress (MPa)	121.8	191.1	549.7
Rotational speed (rpm)		11947	
Number of stages		4	
Load coefficient		0.5	
Flow coefficient		0.4	
Mean diameter (mm)		555.5	
Axial chord-pitch ratio		0.69	
Maximum Mach		0.92	
Total-total efficiency		90.85 %	

2.9.5 Economic analysis

Table 2.31 and Table 2.32 show the breakdown of the costs per each component of the HRB-propane and steam Rankine power blocks respectively.

The HRB-propane PB cost is in the range of 675-898 (€/kW). The upper cost has been calculated considering a cost 33 % higher than the total base cost. The steam Rankine cost is in the range of 741.1-1154 (€/kW). The upper cost is based in Ref. [80]. According to this reference, the PB cost for a CSP using parabolic trough collectors in 2017 was 910 \$/kW with a CEPCI of 600. Updating the CEPCI and applying the exchange rate, the cost is 1154 €/kW, that is the value shown in the table. Comparing the base costs, the HRB propane power block cost is 9.8 % cheaper than the steam Rankine power block. If the upper cost is considered, the HRB propane block is approximately 28.6 % cheaper.

The recuperator is the most expensive component in the HRB, accounting for up to 38.2 % of the total cost. This agrees with the breakdown costs of sCO₂-RB [89]. On the other hand, in the steam Rankine cycle the cost of the heat exchangers is lower even though the number of heat exchangers is higher. The most expensive ones are the evaporators, first because the required area accounts for nearly 40 % of the total area needed for all the heat exchangers, and second because the steam flows through the shell, which requires a greater thickness because of the high pressure. The low HRB main heater cost is due to the high Pinch Point value (19 °C).

In the HRB, the pump cost is more than 10 times the cost of the steam Rankine pumps although the pressure ratio is lower in the first. This is mainly due the higher volume flow rate of the propane (near 14 times more than in the water case).

In the HRB, the compressor and the turbine represent only a 5.2 % and 11.1 % of the total cost respectively. However, in the steam Rankine cycle the turbine is the most expensive component. This is mainly due to the difference in size: The lower pressure ratio in the HRB-propane leads to a higher average density throughout the turbomachines, which reduces the required flow area and, consequently, the size of the machines. It should be noted that the outlet pressure of the steam Rankine cycle turbine is in a vacuum, which means that the specific volume of the steam is very high, leading to larger blade heights at the exit. This limits the shaft speed in the turbomachine to avoid high centrifugal stresses. Therefore, the specific power is reduced. Additionally, the steam exiting the turbine is wet, producing more erosion in the last stages. This negative effect does not occur in the HRB-propane.

Table 2.31 Costs for the HRB-propane power block

HRB propane power block	
Components	Cost
Main heater (M€)	5.26
Recuperator (M€)	25.76
Cooler (M€)	18.64
Turbine (M€)	7.43
Compressor (M€)	3.48
Pump (M€)	3.88
Generator+gearbox (M€)	3.04
Total base cost (M€)	67.49
Upper cost (M€)	89.76

Table 2.32 Costs for the steam Rankine power block

Steam Rankine power block	
Components	Cost
Feedwater 1 (M€)	0.45
Feedwater 2 (M€)	0.49
Deaerator (M€)	2.28
Feedwater 3 (M€)	0.33
Preheater (M€)	0.64
Boiler (M€)	11.13
Superheater (M€)	5.42
Reheater (M€)	3.32
Turbine (M€)	26.53
Pumps (M€)	0.38
Cooler (M€)	20.74
Generator (M€)	2.39
Total base cost (M€)	74.11
Upper cost (M€)	115.4

Table 2.33 shows the main results of the figures of merit for both cycles. Although the PB cost difference between both cycles is considerable, the importance of this on the total cost of the CSP is relative since the PB cost represents only around a 15 % of the total investment.

The LCOE decrease of the HRB-propane compared to the steam Rankine ranges from 1.2 % and 4.1 %, depending on the case considered. However, since the CSP operation has been optimized to maximize the incomes and not the energy production, profits-incomes ratio and cost-income ratio give more accurate results. Profits-incomes ratio increment is about 0.9-2.3 % depending on the case. Cost-income ratio decrement takes roughly the same value.

Table 2.33 Figures of merits values

	HRB-propane CSP		Steam Rankine CSP	
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 1	Case 2
	Total base cost	Upper cost	Total base cost	Upper cost
INV _{SF} (M€)			177.15	
INV _{PB} (M€)	67.49	89.76	74.11	115.4
INV _{TES} (M€)			181.73	
INV (M€)	426.38	448.65	433.32	474.28
LC _{INV} (M€)	22.84	24.08	23.2	25.41
LC _{O&M} (M€)	21.07	21.46	21.18	21.91
LI (M€)	108.01	108.01	106.96	106.96
LCOE (€/MWh)	130.92	135.65	132.45	141.21
r _{pi}	0.5934	0.5788	0.584	0.556
r _{ci}	0.4066	0.4212	0.416	0.444

2.10 Conclusions

In this section, the HRB-propane power cycle is studied as an alternative to the current technology used in parabolic trough CSPs. To achieve this, a CSP with a power block based on this cycle has been designed and simulated for an annual operation, and an economic study has been conducted. To validate the study, other CSPs with alternative power cycles were also simulated, and the results have been subsequently compared. The chosen cycles were HRB-isobutane, ORC-toluene, sCO₂-RB, and a Steam Rankine cycle. The first was selected because

isobutane is another fluid that has been studied in previous works with good results. The second is a benchmark due to its high efficiency for the thermal level considered. The third was chosen for having a technological scheme similar to that of HRB-propane, and the last one represents the current technology.

Two analyses have been conducted to compare the cycles. In the first one, neither the power block nor the other CSP systems are sized. The bypass fraction and pressure ratio values for each cycle have been optimized to maximize the efficiency while other parameters referred to the power cycle have been fixed to similar values to validate the comparison. The utility of this analysis is that it allows to make a preliminary comparison based only in the thermal level of the application. After sizing the CSP with the HRB-propane power block that achieves the highest efficiency, a new analysis that takes as reference the sum of the heat exchangers UA factors of the propane power block and the size of the TES and the solar field is done. A genetic algorithm is considered for the analysis, optimizing the power block UA factors to maximize the net power. In that way, a comparison between the power blocks can be done without estimating the costs of the heat exchangers nor the other systems of the CSP.

Annual simulations for each CSP power block based have been performed considering hourly data. The model considers the startup processes of the PB and the SF and also the cooler and the HTF pump consumptions, which represent the highest parasitic losses of the plant. Different operations depending in the interaction between the systems are considered: Solar field delivering energy to PB and TES, TES to PB and SF; TES to PB; SF to PB. These operations along with the PB startup process have been scheduled using a mixed-integer linear program that maximizes the incomes. The results have been calculated through a detailed model.

Results obtained of the $s\text{CO}_2$ -RB and HRB-isobutane are considerably worse than that of the HRB-propane: Net power production in the standardized analysis is lower than a 10 % and the revenues obtained in the annual simulation are around a 16 % lower. The low maximum temperature that isobutane can reach without degradation (308.85 °C) significantly limits its maximum efficiency, which limits its application to lower temperature levels. In the case of the $s\text{CO}_2$ -RB, the rejection of sensible heat and the use of a main compressor instead of a pump significantly reduces its nominal performance, despite the optimization done of the temperature and pressure at the inlet of the main compressor around the critical point. In the annual simulation, the results are even worse since the increase in ambient temperature causes the inlet temperature to the compressor to move away from the critical point. As the pressure was optimized for nominal conditions, the density at the inlet of the main compressor at off-design conditions significantly decreases, increasing the specific work consumed. As a result, this cycle is suitable for higher temperature applications, where the absence of a maximum temperature limitation for CO_2 compared to propane is a considerable advantage.

On the other hand, although the standardized analysis shows that the power block efficiency and the net power production of the ORC-toluene are higher than that of the HRB-propane in nominal conditions (1 % and 2.5 % higher respectively), the revenues obtained in the annual simulation are very similar (only a difference of about 0.3 %). This is due two factors: The first one is that the HRB-propane achieves a high efficiency during low ambient temperatures, which also coincides with the hours of higher production frequency, and the second one is that it can develop a very high specific power at low temperatures, which is advantageous considering the dispatch schedule. Besides, ORC-toluene have some implicit risks that may limit its application. Since the low-pressure side is under vacuum, some air can enter the cycle, which poses a risk given that toluene is a flammable substance. Besides, this air must be evacuated from

the cycle, which inevitably leads to a small leakage of toluene. This is an important risk since the toluene is very toxic. On the contrary, the low pressure of the HRB-propane is above ambient pressure, thereby avoiding this risk.

In the comparison between the HRB-propane and the steam Rankine power block, the results show a higher revenue of the HRB-propane than that of the steam Rankine power block, around 1.5 %. However, the total net energy production is very similar. The HRB-propane PB cost has been calculated based on the cost of the sizing of their components. The steam Rankine PB cost has been calculated in the same way to minimize uncertainty in the comparison. However, since some components cannot be sized, a total cost for the complete power block obtained from the scientific literature has also been considered. The results show that the HRB-propane PB cost could be between 9.8 % and 28.6 % cheaper. The LCOE decrease achieved is between 1.2 % and 4.1 %. However, since the algorithm maximizes the revenues and not the energy production, profits over incomes and cost over incomes ratios are preferable. The improvement achieved is between 0.9 %-2.3 % depending on the case.

In conclusion, according to the opinion of the author, the results of the study encourage future research to assess whether this novel cycle can serve as an alternative to current technology. The installation is simpler than in a steam Rankine cycle, and some of the components use the same technology, like the heat exchangers. The turbine is simpler and smaller; however, there are no propane turbines available, so a complete development of this technology is required. On the other hand, studies on flammability and thermal stability should be conducted to estimate the safety costs of the installation. In addition, it is necessary to verify whether propane can reach temperatures up to 400 °C in the thermal cycle, which would enable the development of new correlations. Consequently, the efficiency of the cycle could be significantly increased, considering the decomposition of factors that was carried out to analyse the efficiency of a thermodynamic cycle (Section 2.2.1).

For future works, a compressor installed in an independent shaft will be study to select the bypass fraction that maximizes the efficiency in the off-design conditions. This will improve the efficiency in the off-design conditions, especially with high ambient temperatures where the power block efficiency is considerably reduced.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
HRB	Hybrid Rankine Brayton
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HX	Heat Exchanger
NR	Newton Rhapsod method
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PB	Power block
sCO ₂ – RB	supercritical CO ₂ recompression Brayton cycle
SF	Solar Field
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated

Symbols

A	Area (m ²)
AMTD	Arithmetic Mean Temperature Difference (K)
AP	Approach Point (K)

Section 2: Analysis and simulation of medium-temperature CSP with HRB-Propane power block

B	Correction factor for solar calculation
Bc	Constant for installation costs
C	Constant for equipment costs
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index
CN	Carnot Factor
c_p	Specific heat ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
ch/s	Axial chord-Pitch ratio
D	Diameter (m)
DR_E	Lieblein diffusion ratio
d	Density ($kg \cdot m^{-3}$)
Di	Distance (m)
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation ($W \cdot m^{-2}$)
E	Energy ($W \cdot hr$)
F	Factor
h	Enthalpy ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)
$h_{e_{fin}}$	Fin height (mm)
hr	Hour
H/ch	Mean blade height – axial chord ratio of a stage
j	Temporal horizon index
K	Incidence angle modifier
L	Length (m)
LC	Levelized Cost (M€)
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy ($€ \cdot MWh^{-1}$)
LI	Levelized Incomes (M€)
LMTD	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate ($kg \cdot s^{-1}$)
mc	Thermal Inertia
n	Day number
N	Number
$N_{fin,L}$	Number of fins per meter length of tube
NSPA	Non Standardized Parameter Analysis
P	Pressure
\dot{P}	Power (W)
PP	Pinch point (K)
pr	Pressure ratio
\dot{Q}	Thermal power (W)
\dot{q}	Thermal power per unit length ($W \cdot m^{-1}$)
rpm	Revolutions per minute
R	Gas constant ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
Rd	Degree of reaction
Re	Reynolds number
s	Entropy ($J \cdot Kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
SF	Solar field
SP	Size parameter
SPA	Standardized parameter analysis
T	Temperature (K)
\bar{T}	Average temperature (K)
t	Time (hour)
t/ch	Thickness-chord ratio
th_{fin}	Fine thickness (m)
TL	Tank Level
UA	Global heat transfer coefficient x Area ($W \cdot K^{-1}$)
V	Volume (m^3)
\dot{V}	Volume flow rate ($m^3 \cdot s^{-1}$)
X	Characteristic factor
x	Bypass fraction

Subscripts	
add	Addition

Section 2: Analysis and simulation of medium-temperature CSP with HRB-Propane power block

BM	Bare module
Brow	Between rows
CI	Cost over incomes
comp	Compressor
df	Defocus
des	Design
gen	Generation
h	Hot
hd	Headers
h&r	Pipe headers and runners
ITD	Initial temperature difference
i	Part index
int	Referred to the intermediate point in the condenser
INC	Incomes
INV	Inverstment
is	Isentropic
lat	Latent
lss	Losses
m	Material
max	Maximum
mh	Main heater
min	Minimum
mv	Maximum characteristic factor value
off	Off – design
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
opt	Optical
PB	Power block
p	Pressure
po	Polytropic
pf	Power fluid
Pr	Production
pi	Profit over incomes
rec	Recuperator
rej	Rejection
rc	Recompressor
s	Entropy
SCA	Solar Collector Assembly
Sha	Shadow
sens	Sensible
SF	Solar field
stPB	Startup power block
stod	Stodola
SP	Size Parameter
TES	Thermal Energy storage
tbm	Turbomachinery
t	Turbine
th	Thermal
Ub	Upper bound
wPr	Without production
<hr/>	
Greek letters	
η	efficiency
Δ	Increment
φ	Incidence angle ($^{\circ}$)
δ	Solar declination ($^{\circ}$)
λ	Latitude ($^{\circ}$)
ω	Solar angle ($^{\circ}$)
β	Mirror reflectance
γ	Intercept factor
τ	Envelope transmittance

α	Absorber absorptance
ϕ	Capacity
θ	Elevation angle(^o)
$\tilde{\alpha}$	Binary variable (PB producing)
$\tilde{\beta}$	Binary variable (PB startup)
$\hat{\gamma}$	Binary variable (Storing energy in TES)
$\hat{\eta}$	Binary variable (Shutting down PB)
$\hat{\tau}$	Binary input data (SF startup process)
$\hat{\theta}$	Binary auxiliary variable

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3 PROPOSAL OF A PUMPED THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE FOR A MEDIUM-TEMPERATURE CSP WITH HRB-PROPANE POWER BLOCK.

3.1 Introduction

As established in the introduction section, energy storage systems are increasingly necessary due to the growing presence of non-dispatchable renewable energies in the electricity mix. This increase is primarily led by photovoltaic energy, followed by wind energy, neither of which have storage capacity.

Pumped hydro-storage is considered the more mature and feasible storage technology nowadays and represents around 96 % of the global power storage capacity and 99 % of global storage energy volume [1-3]. However, this system is limited to certain geographic locations and for large-scale use. According to [4], energy storage systems need to increase by about six times by 2030 to achieve the NZE (Net Zero emissions) Scenario by 2050. So, new storage technologies should be developed. Although electric battery storage costs have decreased by a 90 % in the last 10 years, they still have high costs per capacity unit and the battery lifetime is relatively low [5-7]. Carnot batteries are a technology under research that, although less efficient than other storage systems, offers certain advantages over them: they are not geographically limited, can be integrated into existing power plants, and are scalable from small to medium-sized systems. Additionally, the lifetime of this technology is considerably higher than electric batteries [8].

Carnot batteries convert electricity into thermal energy, generating and storing this thermal energy when the prices are low. When the prices are high, the electricity is restored using a heat engine. As it was stated in the introduction section, although there are different classifications for the technologies that belong to the Carnot battery systems, most references agree that PTES is the technology that can achieve the highest efficiency, and the most affordable cost compared with the other Carnot batteries technologies. PTES systems use a heat pump for charging the store and a heat engine to restore the electricity, in both cases based on Brayton or Rankine-like cycles.

In Brayton PTES, a compressor and an expander are required for both the heat engine and the heat pump. If turbomachinery is used, a total of 4 machines are necessary, two for the heat pump and another two for the heat engine [9]. If volumetric machines are used, reversible machines can be considered and only 2 of them are required [10]. In this last case, although the efficiencies obtained are lower than in the previous commented case, the costs are also reduced. In order to obtain high efficiency values, the temperature difference between the hot and cold heat reservoirs is usually high. The hot reservoir can reach temperatures above 500 °C, while the cold one is commonly below -70 °C [11]. The most common technology for heat storage is the sensible packed-bed system, with one bed for the hot reservoir and another for the cold one. Liquid two-tank storage systems have been also considered in the scientific literature [12], although in this case, four tanks are needed (2 for the hot reservoir and 2 for the cold one), along with their respective heat exchangers, making the required investment usually higher than when using packed beds. Additionally, for the case of liquid two-tank storage systems, the fluids used for each heat source are different due to their different thermal levels: molten salts are used for the hot reservoir, while alcohols and hydrocarbons are used for the cold one. Regarding the working fluid employed in the Brayton cycle, they are typically fluids with a high heat capacity ratio, such as argon or helium [13]. This helps avoid excessively high-pressure ratios.

Based on the material studied, only one reversible experimental Brayton-PTES plant has been found [14]. This installation has an output/input power ratio of 120/150 kW, compressing argon to a temperature of 500 °C and cooling it during expansion to -160 °C. Reversible volumetric machines are used. The storage consists of two packed beds filled with rocks, one for the hot heat source and another for the cold one, with a nominal capacity of 600 kWh. Round-trip efficiency is around 72-74 %. Some studies are being done to scale up this installation to another one with a 1.6/2 MW output/input power ratio and a nominal storage capacity of 16 MWh [15].

Ref. [16] resumes different Brayton PTES projects in experimental phase, although they have not the conventional configuration: Enolcon-PTES [17] is a PTES system operating a closed Brayton cycle (working fluid N₂ or Ar) in both charging (heat-pump) and discharging (heat-engine) modes. Heat is stored in packed-bed reservoirs, typically reaching about 700–1000 °C in the hot bed and around -70 °C in the cold bed. An electric heater downstream of the charging compressor is considered to reach the target hot-bed temperature. The expected round-trip efficiency is between 40-43 % with a pressure ratio 6:1. The reference layouts has 7.6 MW charging power and 80 MWh of stored thermal energy. Another project is 1414 Degrees-SiBox [18], an electro-thermal storage system using silicon as the storage medium. Electrical energy is converted to heat by resistive heaters, melting silicon at up to 1414 °C. During discharge, the heat is transferred to air in an open-loop Brayton cycle, delivering high-temperature air flows (650–900 °C) for industrial processes or, if coupled to a turbine, for power generation.

Rankine cycles can achieve a similar efficiency than Brayton cycles but with considerably lower maximum temperatures (usually below 200 °C). However, reversible machines cannot be used since a pump is employed during discharge and a compressor during charging. They can be divided in two types: subcritical and transcritical. The most common are transcritical PTES cycles that use CO₂ [19,20]. Transcritical cycles have certain advantages over subcritical ones: On one hand, during the charging process, entropy generation is lower when transferring heat from the working fluid to the hot reservoir, as the temperature profiles are more similar. Additionally, a liquid expander can be used instead of a isenthalpic expansion valve to recover a certain amount of electricity when the heat pump is operating. One of the greatest advantages of using CO₂ for transcritical cycles is that its low critical temperature and high critical pressure (around 30 °C and 74 bar respectively) allows achieving supercritical conditions with low compression ratios. However, the cold reservoir cannot always be the ambient since sometimes the ambient temperature may be higher than the critical temperature. Consequently, it is common to use a cold storage with a phase change material. This cold storage is used to evaporate the working fluid during the charging process and to condense it during the discharging process. Slurry ice is generally used since other materials have a higher specific cost and lower latent heat of fusion [21]. The discrepancy between the amount of ice generated during charging and melted during the discharging process makes necessary the generation of ice by an additional chiller. Ref. [22] suggests that the electricity required by the additional chiller could be obtained from the turbine during the charging process.

Subcritical Rankine PTES systems, typically consist of ORC (Organic Rankine Cycle) systems [23-25] and other ones that use ammonia [21] as refrigerant. In subcritical Rankine PTES systems is common to use a low-temperature heat source to evaporate the working fluid (solar, waste heat) during the charging process and to utilize the ambient environment as the cold sink for the discharging process [24]. Most of the subcritical and transcritical Rankine PTES systems analyzed have hot sink temperatures below 200 °C and they use pressurized water systems for sensible heat storage. Frate [24] justifies this by indicating that for temperatures

between 100-180 °C, latent heat storage is still an immature technology that would not improve costs compared to sensible heat storage solutions. Considering the analyzed works, only in [26] there is a phase change material (PCM) storage instead of a sensible heat storage system. This is justified by the high temperature of the hot reservoir (400 °C). Additionally, the working fluid absorbs and releases heat mostly at a constant temperature, which eliminates the need for a PCM cascade. Therefore, in this thesis pressurized water tanks exchanging sensible heat are considered not only because they are economically cheaper, but also because they represent a commercially implemented and mature technology with lower cost uncertainty compared to other alternatives. Moreover, the considerable variations in charging and discharging temperatures (see [Section 3.6.2](#)) would complicate the design of an effective PCM system, even in cascade, which typically requires narrow and fixed operating temperature ranges.

Ref. [16] summarizes different Rankine PTES projects currently in the experimental or pilot phase. MAN-ETES [27] is a transcritical Rankine-PTES installation that uses CO₂ as working fluid in the heat-pump mode. During the charging process, heat is absorbed from seawater and stored as hot water in insulated tanks, while ice is formed in the cold storage. The reported round-trip efficiency is 50–55 %, with a heat-pump COP above 3 under favourable conditions. Siemens Gamesa ETES [28] considers resistive heating of volcanic rock up to 750 °C during charging. In the discharging phase, the stored heat generates steam for a Rankine power cycle. The Hamburg demonstration (2019) achieved 1.5 MWe output with a storage capacity of 130 MWh, with a target RTE of 45–50 %. Energie Campus Nürnberg [29] has developed a HP–ORC PTES pilot that couples an electrically driven heat pump for charging with a water-based sensible storage (120 °C) and an organic Rankine cycle (ORC) for discharging. The heat pump has a rated capacity of 20 kW, while the ORC delivers 6–7 kW, with a COP of 5 and an overall round-trip efficiency of 50 % at pilot scale. Finally, Malta Inc. [30] has developed a hybrid PTES concept where the charging cycle is modelled as a Brayton-type heat pump (air or CO₂ as working fluid) coupled with a steam Rankine cycle for discharging. The hot reservoir (molten salts at about 565 °C) supplies the steam generator, while the cold reservoir (antifreeze coolant at about –40 °C) acts as the condensation sink. Reported COP values are in the range of 1.2–1.6, and the expected round-trip efficiency is 50–60 %, with storage capacities designed in the 10–100 MWh_e range. A 14 MWh_e demonstration plant has been announced in Puertollano (Spain) [31], representing the first commercial-scale deployment of this technology.

Regarding financial assessment, Brayton and Rankine PTES systems are not profitable in open markets nowadays, as it was stated in the introduction section. Ref. [32] analyzes various studies, compiling the economic results obtained. The average LCOS (Levelized Cost of Storage) values obtained are 230 €/MWh for Rankine PTES and 369 €/MWh for Brayton PTES. However, it should be noted that since the LCOS depends on the number of hours of storage and on the electricity price during charging, very different values of LCOS can be obtained. Some studies establish the same electricity purchase price value to validate the comparison. For example, [33] and [34] set an electricity purchase price of 25 €/MWh obtaining LCOS around 100 €/MWh. In relation to storage capacity, daily cycles of 10 hours of charging and between 8-10 hours of discharging are considered in these works. Although the variation in costs due to storage capacity is included in the LCOS calculation, it is challenging to find a comparable average selling price in the open market, given the high number of hours of charging and discharging considered. Due to this, some other works consider schedule optimizations in real markets. As it was stated in the introduction section, reference [8] conducts an optimization of the profitability of different storage technologies in the Italian open electricity market for the year 2019, using mixed integer linear programming to establish the schedule operations. Technologies considered are pumped hydro

energy storage, compressed air energy storage, liquid air energy storage, sodium sulphur battery energy storage, flow battery energy storage and pumped thermal energy storage (Rankine and Brayton). This work considers different values of power and capacity for each technology. Also, a range of efficiencies values, number of operating years and specific costs are considered in order to establish different scenarios (pessimistic, average and optimistic). The authors conclude that, considering the storage system lifetime, subsidies are required, since all the technologies analyzed are not profitable in the open market electricity. The value needed is equal to the storage cost itself, as the revenues cover, in the best case, only around 1/10 of the capital cost. After obtaining the economic results for the proposed year, they are standardized considering different purchase prices. The most profitable technology is the pumped hydro storage with a LCOS around 160 €/MWh if an average electricity purchase price of 30 €/MWh is considered. For Brayton and Rankine PTES systems, the LCOS is more than double, in the best case, if the same electricity purchase price is considered. These values result in an average price difference that has not been reached in any European market in any year [35]. On the other hand, the results obtained by considering standardized purchase prices enable comparison with other studies. In this way, the economic results obtained from the PTES proposed in this section are standardized similarly and will be compared with the results obtained from this work.

In order to try to increase the feasibility of PTES, some technological variants that couple PTES systems with existing plants have been studied. In the introduction section some references have been detailed, which are summarized here. Most of the works that couple PTES with existing coal-fired power plants aim to try to reduce the investment costs. In some of them, the conventional powerplant maintains its purpose. This is the case of Ref. [36], where the heat rejected through the condenser of the conventional power plant is used to evaporate the power fluid of the PTES heat pump. In other cases, the conventional power plant is re-purposed, operating as the discharge cycle of the PTES, like in [37-39]. In the first case, the power plant is coupled with the heat pump of the PTES, replacing the conventional boiler by a steam generator fed by the thermal storage. In the other two cases, the heat pump is replaced by electric heaters reducing the investment costs but also the round-trip efficiency. In all cases, the feasibility is increased compared to conventional PTES; however, this is because the conventional power plant is not considered an investment and, if it is, it is only considered as an incremental one. Only in [37], the feasibility of the re-purposed plant is compared to that of the original one. The study demonstrates that the feasibility for the repurposed plant can exceed that of the original only if low purchase prices and a very high number of discharge hours are considered.

Finally, in [40] an optimization of the operation schedule of a PTES is proposed to improve the economic results of different plants: a combined power plant, a coal-fired power plant and a CSP. In all of them the power plant still maintains its original function, while the purpose of the PTES is to improve the economic results by either reducing fuel consumption or increasing the number of operating hours. However, for 2016 electricity prices in the German market (for coal and combined-cycle plants) and in the Spanish market (for CSP), the proposed configurations are not economically feasible.

In this section, a PTES is proposed to improve the economic results of the CSP analyzed in the previous section, whose power block is based on the HRB-propane. Although the purpose of the PTES is similar to that of the Ref. [40], the novelty of the proposed PTES lies in its integration within the power block of the CSP, which helps reduce the investment since the PTES shares some components with the original CSP.

As a reminder, the HRB-propane (further described in [Section 2](#)) takes some aspects from both a recuperative transcritical organic Rankine cycle (RT-ORC) and a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB). Similarly to the sCO₂-RB, a fraction of the vapour that goes out the recuperator is bypassed through the recompressor in order to balance the heat capacities of the flows that goes through the recuperator. The main flow is condensed and then driven by a pump until it reaches supercritical conditions similar to a RT-ORC. The integration of the PTES introduces some components to the HRB-propane, like an additional compressor, a water/propane heat exchanger, two storage tanks with pressurized water an additional pump, and incremental cooler area. No additional turbine is needed, as the PTES uses the same ones as those that are part of the CSP. The mass flow rate passing through the turbine during the charging and discharging processes is similar to that of the reference CSP, so the variation of the power rate during these processes does not considerably change the performance of the turbomachine. This is further explained in [Section 3.6](#). Unlike conventional PTES, no heat pump is needed in the charging cycle, eliminating the need for an evaporator and low-temperature heat sources, which simplifies the installation and reduces costs.

As detailed later, the charging process requires additional compression work compared to the reference configuration, which is used to be stored as thermal energy. During discharging, the compressors are off, and the additional pump drives the propane bypass fraction, which is then heated using the previously stored energy. This results in an increased power output. Additionally, using a pump instead of a compressor for the discharging process may improve performance at high temperatures. The main purpose of this section is to evaluate if this synergetic PTES integration is profitable, and to compare it with the economic results of the storage systems from [8]. So first, the PTES is sized, and the CSP-PTES system is simulated for a typical meteorological year in Sevilla considering the 2022 electricity hourly prices market of Spain (same as in previous section). PTES storage capacities of 3, 4 and 5 hours are considered. Then, the feasibility is assessed through the incremental costs and incomes of the CSP-PTES over the reference configuration. This method is valid since both CSP have the same size and identical input and output parameters for the nominal condition. Finally, the PTES LCOS is calculated and compared with that of the storage systems presented in [8].

[Section 3.2](#) describes both configurations: the reference one and the one that includes the PTES system. It presents the layout diagrams as well as the main input and output data for nominal conditions.

[Section 3.3](#) describes the added components proposed for the PTES along with the equations used for their design. It should be noted that the compressor is not include in this section since its design coincides with that of the previous one.

[Section 3.4](#) explains the main considerations for the annual simulations along with the mixed-integer linear program used to establish the operation schedule for the PTES integration. It should be also noted that off-design models for the different systems (parabolic through, thermal energy storage, power block) are not included since they are the same that were considered in [Section 2.5](#).

[Section 3.5](#) shows the correlations used for estimating the PTES components cost, the figures of merit to assess the profitability of the PTES along with the financial framework.

[Section 3.6](#) shows the results: First, the components sizing results are shown along with their respective calculated costs. Then, some operational points at different ambient temperatures

are calculated for the reference case and for a CSP-PTES charging/discharging processes. In this way, the variation of the efficiency between the two cases can be compared. Then, the economic annual results are shown, indicating the most feasible option for the PTES storage capacity. A sensitive analysis is carried out to compare the feasibility of the CSP-PTES under different parameter values: costs, electricity prices and financial factors. Finally, the LCOS is calculated and compared with that of the storage systems shown in [8].

Section 3.7 shows the conclusions.

3.2 Description of the configurations

3.2.1 Reference configuration

The reference plant corresponds with the HRB-propane CSP analysed in Section 2. Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2 show the power block layout and T-s diagram, respectively.

Figure 3.1 Reference HRB-propane layout

Figure 3.2 T-s diagram of the reference HRB-propane layout

The compression ratio and bypass fraction values are set to achieve the maximum thermal efficiency considering that the low temperature of the cycle is 35 °C. The net power is calculated as the power gross minus the air cooler consumption and minus the HTF pump consumption. A 12 hour storage capacity is considered for the TES, which uses a two-tank molten salts system. The nominal turbine inlet temperature is set at 377 °C, as it is the maximum value allowed by the thermodynamic properties correlations [41]. A difference of 10 °C is considered between the ambient air and the condensing temperature of the cycle, while the difference between the outlet

air and the condensing temperature is 3 °C. The main heater pressure drop value corresponds to the high-pressure side. The recuperator pressure drop corresponds to the low-pressure side. The pressure is assumed to decrease linearly. [Table 3.1](#) and [Table 3.2](#) summarize the CSP main data and the main power block thermodynamic states at nominal conditions. Specific data regarding the TES and the parabolic trough collectors were shown in [Section 2.4](#).

Table 3.1 CSP main data

Gross power (MW)	100	Turbomachinery efficiency	0.9
Compression ratio	14:1	Fan pressure ratio	1.0012
Bypass fraction	0.25	Fan total efficiency (%)	60
Thermal efficiency	39.98 %	Cooler approach temperature (°C)	3
Air cooler consumption (MW)	3.65	Solar multiple	2
HTF pump consumption (MW)	3.45	TES capacity (hours)	12
Net power (MW)	92.9	Solar field inlet temperature (°C)	290
Recuperator pinch point (°C)	5	Solar field outlet temperature (°C)	396
Recuperator pressure drop (%)	5	Hot salts tank temperature (°C)	391
Main heater pressure drop (%)	2	Cold salts tank temperature (°C)	285

Table 3.2 Main power block thermodynamic states at nominal conditions

Point	\dot{m}/\dot{m}_{total}	T (°C)	P (bar)	h(kJ/kg)	s(kJ/kgK)
1	0.75	35	12.2	292.8	1.31
2	0.75	47.3	170.5	328.7	1.32
3	0.75	259.5	170.5	998.2	2.91
3'	1	244.3	170.5	947.3	2.81
4	1	377	167.1	1392.9	3.58
5	1	266.2	12.8	1151.5	3.63
6	0.25/0.75	53.5	12.2	649.4	2.47
7	0.25	199.4	170.5	794.7	2.50

3.2.2 PTES integration into CSP

The charging process layout of the HRB-PTES-propane power block is shown in [Figure 3.3](#). Some new components are added to the system including a water-propane heat exchanger, a pressurized two water tanks system (hot and cold), a water pump to drive the flow between the tanks and the heat exchanger, a compressor for the heat upgrade to charge the PTES, and incremental cooler area. Three, four and five hours of storage are considered. The water pump operates always at a constant flow rate equal to the nominal value. The PTES compressor is identical to the recompressor, but it is placed on a different shaft. Under nominal conditions both rotate at the same speed. Consequently, under these conditions, the propane mass flow rate and the thermodynamic properties values at the outlet of each machine coincide, as they also do the thermodynamic properties of the propane at the outlet of the PTES storage system compared to that of the main stream after the main pump. The rest of the thermodynamic properties in each point take the same values as in the reference plant. A nominal pinch point value of 5 °C is considered in the water/propane heat exchanger. [Table 3.3](#) summarizes these data.

In [Figure 3.4](#), the T-s diagram for the charging configuration under nominal conditions is shown, where the equivalence between the properties of the referred thermodynamic points can be observed.

Table 3.3 HRB-PTES-propane summarized data input

T_{2c} (°C)	47.3
Propane compressor fraction	0.25
Water/propane HX Pinch Point (°C)	5
Cold water tank temperature (°C)	42.3
Storage capacity (hr)	3,4,5

Figure 3.3 Charging process layout

Figure 3.4 Charging process under nominal conditions T-s diagram

Under off-design conditions, the PTES compressor is adjusted to maintain the nominal bypass mass flow rate. This helps to keep the water/propane heat exchanger balanced, since a propane mass flow rate through the PTES system similar to the nominal value is achieved. If the PTES compressor were placed in the same shaft as the turbine, several issues would arise: first, the propane mass flow rate driven by the PTES compressor would vary significantly with ambient temperature, as the inlet pressure depends on the condensing pressure of the cycle. This could lead to an excessive propane mass flow rate at high ambient temperatures due to the density increment. Coupled with this, the rise in the outlet temperature from the PTES compressor when the ambient temperature is high would lead to high temperatures in the hot tank, since the pump drives always the same water mass flow rate. This would result in a design challenge due to the high pressure required to keep the water pressurized.

The discharging layout is shown in Figure 3.5. In this case, both compressors are off and a fraction of the main flow that goes out the condenser is directed to a pump that is located in parallel to the main one. This fraction is heated up in the water/propane heat exchanger with the energy that was previously stored in the hot water tank. The energy that was consumed by the

PTES compressor during the charging process is recovered resulting in an increase in the gross power rate compared to the reference configuration. This improvement occurs because using a pump instead of a compressor reduces the overall energy consumption. Additionally, at off-design conditions, a pump drives a mass flow rate value more similar to the nominal one than using a compressor, so the recuperator is better balanced. On the other hand, the propane mass flow rate that goes through the condenser is higher than in the reference configuration. To keep a similar pressure drop in the cooler, the cooler UA factor is increased. Additionally, this leads to an increase in the power consumption.

The implementation of the PTES can improve the off-design performance of the system compared to the reference configuration for both, charging and discharging cases, and particularly at high ambient temperatures. This is achieved by maintaining a more stable PTES bypass flow rate despite variations in condensation pressure, leading to a better-balanced recuperator and improved overall efficiency than in the original configuration. This is shown in [Section 3.6.2](#).

Finally, when the PTES is off, the CSP-PTES behaves like the reference CSP case since all the other components maintain the same size.

Figure 3.5 Discharging process layout

3.3 PTES components design and sizing

3.3.1 Water/propane heat exchanger

The specific heat of propane shows significant variations near the critical point, which can lead to considerable errors in the calculation of UA factors if the total enthalpy change is not divided into small segments. Therefore, the enthalpy change has been divided into 25 parts like in the heat exchangers from the reference configuration. This approach results in temperature variations that are small enough to allow the use of the arithmetic mean temperature difference instead of the logarithmic mean temperature difference for each segment without introducing significant errors. The total UA factor is determined using [Equation 3.1](#), which sums the UA values for each of the 25 segments. The UA of each small part is calculated from the heat exchanged (\dot{Q}_j) and the arithmetic mean temperature difference ($AMTD_j$).

$$UA = \sum_{j=1}^{25} UA_j = \sum_{i=1}^{25} \frac{\dot{Q}_j}{AMTD_j} \quad (3.1)$$

The heat exchanger has been designed as a single segmental shell and tube configuration with one pass for both, the tube and shell sides. It includes a specialized high-pressure closure and a fixed tubesheet, according to a TEMA “DEN” standard. The tube thickness is calculated according to the ASME code [42,43]. The material considered is carbon steel SA-516 GR.70.

Input data, optimization variables and constraints are the same that were considered in the main heater calculation of [Section 2.6.1](#).

The sizing methodology is applied for each part. The heat transfer coefficient inside the tubes is calculated using the Jackson's correlation. This correlation is shown in [Appendix A.1](#). The friction factor is calculated using Colebrook-White's correlation. The Delaware method is used to calculate the shell heat transfer coefficient and pressure drop. The complete correlation is shown in [Appendix A.2](#).

3.3.2 Pressurized water tanks

Cylindrical tanks are used for the heat storage and are pressurized to prevent the water from boiling. Since there are both filled and empty tanks (water and air), all the system is pressurized being all the tanks interconnected at the top. Due the pressure of the system, the tanks have a high length-to-diameter ratio. Therefore, they are arranged horizontally which avoids excessive hydrostatic pressures.

Each tank has a storage capacity of one hour, so the total number of tanks needed is equal to the number of hours of storage required plus one additional tank. For example, if four hours of storage are considered, five tanks would be needed: Four of them will be filled while the other one remains empty. In this way, during a charging/discharging process, a full tank is discharged, and the water will flow through the heat exchanger before entering the empty tank. This configuration reduces the number of tanks required compared to a scenario where an equal number of cold and hot tanks are considered. The material considered is carbon steel SA-516 GR.70.

The thickness considered is 50.8 mm what is the maximum common commercially available value for steel plates. [Equation 3.2](#) is used to calculate the diameter based in the thickness (t), the internal pressure (P) and the allowable stress value (S). This relation is taken from [42]. The internal pressure that the tanks must withstand is the vapor pressure of the maximum water temperature expected during the simulation plus the hydrostatic pressure. An additional fraction volume of a 5 % is considered in each tank to assure a minimum level of water.

$$D = \frac{2 \cdot t}{\exp(P/S) - 1} \quad (3.2)$$

To calculate the heat losses, external and internal film coefficients are evaluated through different correlations. These correlations depend on the type of surface. The curved internal surfaces of the cylinder have been modelled as horizontal plates and are divided into two halves. The corresponding to the lower half is considered as an "upper surface of a cold plate" while the upper half as a "lower surface of a cold plate". This assignment is made considering the flow movement in natural convection. The internal surfaces corresponding to the lateral closures have been considered as "vertical plates". The external surface is considered as a horizontal cylinder under natural convection. The correlations used are shown in [Appendix A.6](#). To reduce the heat losses, fiberglass wool is considered as insulation material. The amount of insulation needed is calculated considering that the thermal losses should be under 25 W/m².

3.4 Annual simulations methodology

3.4.1 General considerations. Operation criteria

As in the previous section, the meteorological hourly data corresponds to that of Seville [45] and the hourly market price data refers to the spot prices of the Spanish electricity market in year 2022 [46]. The optimization model and the operation criteria considered for the reference configuration coincides with that was explained in [Section 2.6](#).

For the CSP-PTES case two different optimization models are considered: The first model optimizes the scheduling of the main operations of the plant (start-up of the power block, charging/discharging of the TES with energy production from the PB, charging the TES with the PB off and shut down of the CSP), along with the operations of the PTES (charging and discharging). The second model constraints the CSP-PTES schedule dispatch to that of the reference configuration. While the first model enables the assessment of the profitability of the CSP-PTES configuration compared to the reference one, the second model allows for the calculation of the LCOS, as the additional energy produced or consumed solely by the PTES system can be calculated. This enables the comparison of the LCOS of the proposed system against that of other references.

The PTES off-design operation criteria, as mentioned earlier, considers a constant propane mass flow rate through the PTES compressor equal to the nominal value, along with a constant water mass flow rate provided by the pump. For the off-design model of the power block with the integrated PTES, there is one additional variable input compared to the reference configuration: the water temperature of the cold tank for the charging process and the water temperature of the hot tank for the discharging process. Consequently, for the off-design calculation of the PB with the integrated PTES, there are three input variables, in contrast to just two variables (ambient temperature and HTF inlet temperature at the main heater) for the reference configuration.

The off-design calculation process of the power cycle during the charging and discharging operations are summarized in [Figure 3.6](#). and [Figure 3.7](#). Unlike the off-design calculation of the reference power cycle ([Figure 2.9](#)), the parameters considered for iteration are the mass flow rate of propane, the outlet temperature on the low-pressure side of the recuperator, and the turbine inlet pressure. Equations are referred to those shown in [Section 2](#).

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Figure 3.6 Off design HRB model process diagram for charging operation

Figure 3.7 Off design HRB model process diagram for discharging operation

The off-design models of the other components of the power block (compressors, heat exchangers, turbine, condenser) and of the other systems (parabolic through and TES) were described in Section 2.6.2.

3.4.2 Schedule optimization algorithms

The MILP code used to schedule the production of the CSP-PTES is shown from Equation 3.3-3.32. Since the operation of the CSP with the PTES off is jointly optimized along with the operation of the PTES when it is on, two binary variables—one for charging and one for

discharging ($\hat{\alpha}_c, \hat{\alpha}_d$) – are added to those already considered for the reference case. That means that the variables and constraints corresponding to the reference case (Section 2.6.5) are also used in this code, although with the modifications corresponding to the operation variables of the PTES. It should be noted that although all the code is shown, only the constraints and variables related with the PTES are explained. The other cases corresponding only to the CSP operation when the PTES is off are not explained here, but they can be found in Section 2.6.5. As in that section, the optimization is performed with half an hour time-step. Electricity market prices, provided on an hourly basis, are assumed constant within the two sub-steps of each hour.

Equation 3.3 is similar to Equation 2.43 but adding the charging and discharging binary variables. It established that only one of the six main operations can occur at each time step and only if an HTF startup is not taking place during the same time step.

Equations 3.8-3.11 establish that, when switching from not producing to producing electricity (whether with the PTES off or on), the power block must be started up in the previous time step. They are similar to Equations 2.48-2.51.

Equations 3.12-3.13 set the molten salts mass balance in the tanks. Compared to Equation 2.52-2.53 the terms related to the charging/discharging are added. $\dot{m}_{Pr,c}(j)$ and $\dot{m}_{Pr,d}(j)$ are, respectively, the molten salts that are stored or discharged when the PTES is charging or discharging. It should be noted that molten salts and PTES storage dispatch are independent. On the other hand, no variables related to the defocus are considered for the charging/discharging. In this way, the optimization is simpler and, if defocusing is needed, it is applied only when the PTES is off.

Equations 3.16-3.17 set the mass balance in the PTES storage system. It should be noted that this balance is standardized, considering that the total capacity of the storage system is equal to the number of time steps required for the system to charge from being empty. This is valid since the water pump drives a constant mass flow rate. Equations 3.18-3.19 set the maximum and minimum capacity levels of the storage.

Equations 3.20-3.21 established that the shutdown can only occur if the plant was producing electricity in the previous time step whether the PTES is off or on. Equations 3.22-3.25 establish that the PTES must operate for at least two consecutive time steps.

Finally, in Equation 3.32, the terms related with power production during charging and discharging are added (compared to Equation 2.64) to define the incomes of the operation. $\dot{P}_{Pr,d}(j)$ and $\dot{P}_{Pr,c}(j)$ are, respectively, the power produced during the PTES charging and discharging.

$$\hat{\alpha}(j) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j) + \hat{\beta}(j) + \hat{\gamma}(j) + \hat{\eta}(j) = 1 - \hat{\tau}(j) \quad (3.3)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{Ub,df,Pr}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}(j) \quad (3.4)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) \geq 0 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{wPr}(j) \cdot \hat{\gamma}(j) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) \geq 0 \quad (3.7)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}_{c,0} + \hat{\alpha}_{d,0} - \hat{\alpha}(1) - \hat{\alpha}_c(1) - \hat{\alpha}_d(1) \geq 0 \quad (3.8)$$

$$-\hat{\alpha}(j) + \hat{\alpha}(j+1) - \hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j+1) - \hat{\alpha}_d(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j+1) = \hat{\beta}(j) - \hat{\theta}(j) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\hat{\beta}(j) + \hat{\theta}(j) \leq 1 \quad (3.10)$$

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$$-\hat{\alpha}(96) - \hat{\alpha}_c(96) - \hat{\alpha}_d(96) = \hat{\beta}(96) - \hat{\theta}(96) \quad (3.11)$$

$$E(1) = \hat{\alpha}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr}(1) + \hat{\alpha}_c(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr,c}(1) + \hat{\alpha}_d(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr,d}(1) + \hat{\beta}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{stPb}(1) + \hat{\gamma}(1) \cdot \dot{m}_{wPr}(1) - \dot{m}_{df,Pr}(1) - \dot{m}_{df,wPr}(1) - \dot{m}_{sdPB}(1) + E_o \quad (3.12)$$

$$E(j) = \hat{\alpha}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr}(j) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr,c}(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{Pr,d}(j) + \hat{\beta}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{stPb}(j) + \hat{\gamma}(j) \cdot \dot{m}_{wPr}(j) - \dot{m}_{df,Pr}(j) - \dot{m}_{df,wPr}(j) - \dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) + E(j-1) \quad (3.13)$$

$$E(j) \leq E_{max} \quad (3.14)$$

$$E(j) \geq E_{min} \quad (3.15)$$

$$E_{sec}(1) = \hat{\alpha}_c(1) - \hat{\alpha}_d(1) + E_{sec_o} \quad (3.16)$$

$$E_{sec}(j) = \hat{\alpha}_c(j) - \hat{\alpha}_d(j) + E_{sec}(j-1) \quad (3.17)$$

$$E_{sec}(j) \geq 0 \quad (3.18)$$

$$E_{sec}(j) \leq E_{sec,max} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}(1) + \hat{\alpha}_{c,0} + \hat{\alpha}_c(1) + \hat{\alpha}_{d,0} + \hat{\alpha}_d(1) \geq \hat{\eta}(1) \quad (3.20)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}(j) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j) \geq \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (3.21)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_c(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \hat{\alpha}_c(j+1) \geq 2 \cdot \delta_c(j) \quad (3.22)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_c(j) = \delta_c(j) \quad (3.23)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_d(j-1) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j+1) \geq 2 \cdot \delta_d(j) \quad (3.24)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_d(j) = \delta_d(j) \quad (3.25)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq \dot{m}_{Ub,sdPB}(j) \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (3.26)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E_{max} \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (3.27)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \geq E_{min} \cdot \hat{\eta}(j) \quad (3.28)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E(j-1) - E_{min} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(j)] \quad (3.29)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \geq E(j-1) - E_{max} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(j)] \quad (3.30)$$

$$\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j) \leq E_o - E_{min} \cdot [1 - \hat{\eta}(1)] \quad (3.31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Incomes}(j) = & \text{Price}(j) \cdot 0.5 \cdot (\dot{P}_{Pr}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}(j) + \dot{P}_{Pr,c}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \dot{P}_{Pr,d}(j) \cdot \hat{\alpha}_d(j) + \frac{\dot{m}_{sdPB}(j)}{-\dot{m}_{Pr}(j)} \cdot \dot{P}_{Pr}(j) + \\ & + \dot{P}_{stPb}(j) \cdot \hat{\beta}(j) + \dot{P}_{wPr}(j) \cdot \hat{\gamma}(j) - 0.4 \cdot \hat{\beta}(j) \cdot \dot{Q}_{stPb}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

A second model is proposed to enable the calculation of the energy produced/consumed solely by the PTES. For that, the production time intervals of the CSP-PTES are constrained to the dispatch schedule of the reference CSP. To achieve these, two new equations (Equation 3.33-3.34) are added to the previous code. $\hat{\alpha}_{ref}(j)$ and $\hat{\eta}_{ref}(j)$ represent, respectively, the values of $\hat{\alpha}(j)$ and $\hat{\eta}(j)$ for the reference case. So, they are an input data. Equation 3.33 established that the PTES charging and discharging operations can be only set in the same time intervals than the production dispatch of the reference CSP. Equation 3.34 is similar to the previous one but refers to the production of the CSP-PTES when the PTES is off. It should be noted that this equation considers also that the production of the CSP-PTES can also take place during a shutdown operation of the reference CSP. This is to compensate the molten salts storage variations due the operation of the PTES. It should be considered that the calculation of the energy produced/consumed by the PTES as the difference of the hourly production between by the CSP-PTES and the reference CSP is valid since the discharging/charging salts value does not change significantly if production with the PTES on is switched to production with the PTES off. This is

supported by the similar values obtained for the thermal power absorbed and molten salts charged/discharged that are shown in [Table 3.11](#), [Table 3.13](#) and [Table 3.15](#), and by the similar total annual production obtained by the CSP-PTES and the reference CSP ([Table 3.17](#)). It should be noted that if these values were significantly different, the method used to calculate the production due only the PTES operation would not be valid since the operation of the PTES would also affects the operation when the PTES is off.

$$\hat{\alpha}_c(j) + \hat{\alpha}_d(j) \leq \hat{\alpha}_{ref}(j) \quad (3.33)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}(j) \leq \hat{\alpha}_{ref}(j) + \hat{\eta}_{ref}(j) \quad (3.34)$$

3.5 Economic analysis

3.5.1 Estimation of the capital expenditure of the components

The additional equipment includes the water/propane heat exchanger, storage tanks, compressor, water and propane pumps and their respective motors. The cost correlations of the PTES heat exchanger, air cooler UA factor increment, compressor and water and propane pumps coincide with that were shown in [Section 2.8](#). Additionally, the PTES compressor cost coincides with the recompressor cost since they have the same size.

Ref. [47] is used to calculate the cost of the motors. First, the purchased cost is calculated using [Equation 3.35](#). The total cost of the equipment is calculated using [Equation 3.36](#). The coefficients are shown in [Table 3.4](#).

$$\log_{10} Cost_{equip} = C_{11} + C_{12} \log_{10}(X) + C_{13} [\log_{10}(X)]^2 \quad (3.35)$$

$$Cost_{BM} = Cost_{equip} \cdot (B_1 + B_2) \quad (3.36)$$

Table 3.4 Motor cost coefficients

	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{13}	C_{21}	C_{22}	C_{23}	B_1	B_2	F_M
Motor	2.9508	1.0688	-0.1315	0	0	0	0.75	0.75	1

Ref. [48] is used to calculate the tanks cost. The purchased cost is calculated using [Equation 3.37](#) where w is the weight of the emptied tank considering a carbon steel density of 7840 kg/m³. The total cost is calculated using [Equation 3.38](#).

$$Cost_{equip} = -2500 + 200 \cdot w^{0.6} \quad (3.37)$$

$$C_{BM} = Cost_{equip} \cdot 4 \quad (3.38)$$

The validity range of the main characteristic that is used to estimate the costs for both components is:

Electric motor/drip-proof:

$$75 < \dot{W} (kW) < 2600$$

Tank:

$$250 < w (kg) < 69200$$

If the characteristic dimension of the equipment exceeds the maximum value of the specified range, the purchased cost is first calculated using the maximum value of the range, and then the six-tenth rule is applied. The six-tenth rule is expressed in [Equation 3.39](#). Here, $Cost_{equip.mv}$ is the purchase cost considering the maximum characteristic factor value of the interval specified in the reference and X is the characteristic factor value of the equipment.

$$Cost_{equip} = Cost_{equip.mv} \left(\frac{X}{X_{mv}} \right)^{0.6} \quad (3.39)$$

Since each correlation has a different time reference, the prices have been updated using the ratio between the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI) value from the current year of study and that of each reference. The costs obtained from the correlations are in dollars, so a conversion rate of $1\text{€} = 1.05\text{ USD}$ representative of the 2022–2023 period, is used.

Table 3.5 CEPCI coefficients for each reference

Year 2022	[47]	[48]
798.7	398.7	478.6

3.5.2 Figures of merit and economic scenarios

The cost-incomes ratio and profits over incomes ratio are used to assess the profitability of the CSP with the integrated PTES considering Equation 3.40 and Equation 3.41. These figures of merit were also used and explained in Section 2.8. The economic scenario used is shown in Table 3.6 and it has been considered that costs and prices raise yearly with according to the inflation rate.

It should be noted that, in this case, the costs, incomes, and profits considered are the incremental values obtained with the CSP integrated with the PTES over the values obtained with the reference configuration without PTES. This approach allows for an assessment of the profitability of the CSP-PTES relative to the reference configuration considering only the costs of the added components and the new electricity dispatch. As in Section 2, annual incomes are obtained from a MILP optimization that maximizes revenues based on hourly electricity prices; in this case, the MILP is adapted to include the CSP-PTES configuration and the additional charging/discharging constraints.

$$r_{CI} = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M}}{LI} \quad (3.40)$$

$$r_{PI} = \frac{LI - (LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M})}{LI} \quad (3.41)$$

Table 3.6 Economic scenario

Yearly O&M equipment cost percentage of Investment	$1\% \cdot Inv$
Interest rate	4 %
Inflation	3.6 %
Amortization years	35

Finally, the levelized cost of storage is defined in Equation 3.42. E_{in} is the value of the annual energy production decrease resulting from the PTES charging process. It is calculated hourly, and it is equal to the energy produced by the CSP when the PTES is off minus the energy dispatched by the CSP-PTES during the charging process. E_{out} is similarly calculated but considering the energy surplus of the CSP-PTES when the PTES is discharging. c_{el} is the average charging hourly price. This expression has been obtained from references such as [8,49] but considering also the inflation, like [50] does with the LCOE.

$$LCOS = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M} + E_{in} \cdot c_{el}}{E_{out}} \quad (3.42)$$

In addition to calculating the LCOS for the reference market scenario based on the Spanish day-ahead electricity prices of 2022 [46], and for the economic scenario shown in Table

3.7, the LCOS is compared with that calculated by [8] for various storage systems. As mentioned in the introduction, Ref. [8] focuses on the dispatch optimization of different storage technologies over a specific year of market prices and considers standardized electricity purchase prices. To enable a consistent comparison, the same economic assumptions and a standardized charging price of 30 €/MWh, as adopted in [8], are applied here. Besides, it should be verified that the LCOS does not largely vary (over the previously calculated) in this new framework with different market prices. To confirm this, the dispatch schedule is recalculated considering the hourly market prices from 2019, and the LCOS is compared to that of the reference year (2022) considering the same purchase price. If the LCOS does not change significantly, then the variation resulting from select different dispatch strategies is minor, making the comparison with the LCOS of reference [8] valid.

A sensitivity analysis is also conducted based on the cost, electricity price and financing scenario. These analyses are performed independently to identify the most influential parameter. Since the cost correlations involve inherent uncertainty, a wide range (from -30 % to +30 % relative to the calculated reference cost) is considered. In all cases, the 2022 market is taken as the base scenario, except for the electricity price sensitivity analysis, where a new dispatch is calculated using the 2019 hourly market prices. For the financing sensitivity analysis, the same average scenario used in reference [8] is applied which is shown in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7 Average economic scenario of [8]

Yearly O&M equipment cost percentage of Investment	$3 \% \cdot Inv$
Interest rate	7 %
Inflation	0
Amortization years	30

3.6 Results

3.6.1 Sizing and cost results of the components

The sizing results of the propane-water heat exchanger and the water storage tanks are shown in Table 3.8 and Table 3.9. A configuration of two propane-water heat exchangers in series has been considered to avoid excessive tube length. Regarding the tanks, six tanks are needed for the five-hours case, five tanks are needed for the four-hours case and four tanks for the three-hours case. The dimensions of the tanks are the same for the three scenarios. In Table 3.10, the nominal temperature drop per hour refers to a full hot tank. Generally, full hot tanks are emptied within 24 hours. In cases where the full hot tank remains filled for 24 hours, the approximate temperature loss is only 1 °C.

Table 3.10 shows the incremental costs for equipment, including installation, for the 3-hour, 4-hour and 5-hour CSP-PTES. The calculations for the pump and compressor motor costs are based on an assumed electric motor efficiency of 99 %. The consumption of the water pump and its respective motor is minimal since the low water mass flow rate and the slight pressure drop in the propane-water heat exchanger. The incremental air cooler cost is calculated based on the difference in UA cooler factors between the reference case and the PTES discharging case, considering the nominal ambient temperature. The estimated additional volume of propane required for the integration of the PTES is about twice the propane volume contained in the water/propane heat exchanger. With those values, the cost of the additional propane needed is under 0.1 % of the total additional investment, so it has been excluded from the cost analysis.

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Table 3.8 Water/propane heat exchangers summary data

Total exchange Area (m ²)	5382	
Number of Hx	2	
Layout	2 in series	
Summary results per HX		
	HX1	HX2
Area (m ²)	3026	2356
Overall heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	1376	1868
Tube heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	2178	2821
Shell heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	6120	8529
Tube pressure drop (kPa)	13	19
Shell pressure drop (kPa)	60	63
Length (m)	18.4	17.76
Shell diameter (m)	1.23	1.17
Distance between baffles (mm)	438	438
Outlet tube diameter (mm)	9.5	9.5
Tube pitch (mm)	14.3	14.3
Tube thickness (mm)	0.6	0.6
Baffle cut (%)	35.9	32.7
Number of tubes	5498	4994

Table 3.9 Water tanks summary data

	3 hr case	4 hr case	5 hr case
Total weight (ton)	465.96	582.45	737.77
Number of tanks	4	5	6
Summary results per tank			
Mass (ton)	116.49		
Length (m)	15		
Diameter (m)	6.21		
Thickness (mm)	50.8		
Insulating thickness (mm)	236		
Pressure (bar)	23.8		
Hot tank nominal temperature (°C)	194.5		
Nominal temperature drop per hour (°C)	0.038		
Nominal thermal losses (kW)	8.5		

Table 3.10 Added components summary data

	Cost per unit (M€/unit)	Units			Total cost (M€)		
Condenser	2.1	1			2.1		
Compressor motor	1.153	1			1.153		
Propane pump motor	0.496	1			0.496		
Water pump motor	0.004	1			0.004		
Compressor	3.48	1			3.48		
Propane pump	1.995	1			1.995		
Water pump	0.027	1			0.027		
Heat exchanger	-	2 in series			1.404		
Tank	1.369	4	5	6	5.476	6.8645	8.22
					16.135	17.304	18.87

3.6.2 Operation of HRB-PTES-Propane

Table 3.11 presents the main operational results under nominal conditions for both the reference configuration (PTES off) and when the PTES is charging. The propane mass flow fractions circulating through each component for each case are shown in Table 3.12.

As it can be seen from both tables, the thermal power evacuated through the condenser during the charging process is lower than in the reference case. This is because a smaller fraction of propane circulates through the condenser as a result of the additional extraction directed to the PTES compressor. The power gross reduction in the charging case compared to the reference case can be calculated as the PTES compressor consumption minus the difference between the main pump consumption for the two cases. The main pump consumption difference is due the different flow fractions that the machine drives for each case.

On the other hand, it can be observed that the thermal power absorbed by the PTES storage is higher than the consumption of the compressor. This is because, in addition to storing the thermal energy provided by the compressor to the propane, a portion of the energy that would have been rejected through the cooler is also stored (equivalent to the heat source of a stand-alone heat pump). This energy includes both sensible and latent energy and it is proportional to the difference in enthalpy between the compressor inlet and the propane outlet from the water/propane heat exchanger. This is shown in Equation 3.43-3.45, where the nomenclature used coincides with that in Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4. \dot{Q}_{PTES} is the thermal power absorbed by the PTES storage, \dot{m}_{pf} is the propane mass flow rate that goes through the PTES, $(h_{7c} - h_{2c})$ is the specific enthalpy difference between the PTES compressor outlet and the water/propane heat exchanger outlet, $(h_{7c} - h_6)$ is the specific enthalpy gained by the fluid as it passes through the compressor and $(h_6 - h_{2c})$ is the specific enthalpy stored by the PTES that would be rejected by the condenser if the PTES were turned off. The latter term can be assessed considering sensible and latent energy contributions through Equation 3.45. $(h_6 - h_{1v})$ and $(h_{1v} - h_{1l})$ are the equivalent sensible and latent energies, respectively.

If the energy stored related to the term $(h_6 - h_{2c})$ is not entirely removed through the cooler during discharge, the overall efficiency of a PTES charging and discharging cycle will be higher than that of the CSP when the PTES is turned off. This occurs when the equivalent thermal energy that would have been rejected through the cooler in the reference scenario is instead stored during the charging process and later used to generate power during the discharge.

Table 3.11 Main HRB-PTES operation results at nominal conditions (reference and charging)

	Reference	Charging
Condensing temperature (°C)	35	35
Cold storage temperature (°C)	-	42.3
Hot storage temperature (°C)	-	194.5
PB thermal power inlet (MW)	250.3	250.3
Thermal power evacuated through the condenser (MW)	150.2	100.1
Thermal power absorbed by PTES storage (MW)	-	65.4
Gross power produced (MW)	100	84.7
Net power produced (MW)	93.3	80.1
Total propane mass flow (kg/s)	561.8	561.8
Recompressor consumption (MW)	20.4	20.4
PTES compressor consumption (MW)	-	20.4
Main pump consumption (MW)	15.1	10.1
Coefficient of Performance (COP)		3.21

Table 3.12 Propane mass flow fraction through each component (reference and charging)

	Reference	Charging
Main pump	0.75	0.5
Recuperator high-pressure path	0.75	0.75
Main heater	1	1
Turbine	1	1
Recuperator low-pressure path	1	1
Recompressor	0.25	0.25
PTES compressor	-	0.25
Condenser	0.75	0.5

$$\dot{Q}_{PTES} = \dot{m}_{pf} \cdot (h_{7c} - h_{2c}) \quad (3.43)$$

$$h_{7c} - h_{2c} = (h_{7c} - h_6) + (h_6 - h_{2c}) \quad (3.44)$$

$$(h_6 - h_{2c}) = (h_6 - h_{1v}) + (h_{1v} - h_{1l}) - (h_{2c} - h_{1l}) \quad (3.45)$$

Table 3.13 shows a comparison of the main results for the CSP when the PTES is turned off versus when it is in the charging and discharging processes, using a condensation temperature set 10 °C above the nominal value. Table 3.14 shows the mass flow fractions circulating through each component for each case. The selected cold-water temperature for the charging case is the one that allows obtaining the same value once the discharging is done. This validates the comparison between the gross efficiency obtained in the reference case and that of an operational PTES cycle (charging plus discharging), as the heat absorbed and released by the PTES reaches the same value. It should be noted that in all cases, gross efficiency is defined as the ratio of gross electric power output to the thermal power absorbed by the power block. On the other hand, the bypassed propane maximum temperature corresponds with the temperature at the outlet of the PTES compressor for the charging process and with the temperature at the outlet of the water/propane heat exchanger during the discharging. For the reference case, it corresponds with the outlet temperature of the recompressor.

It can be noted that the gross efficiency of the PTES operational cycle is higher than that of the reference case, even though the bypassed propane temperature is lower during discharge. One reason is that the sensible thermal power removed through the condenser is proportionally greater in the reference case than during discharge. This is reflected by the significantly lower temperature at the outlet of the low-pressure side of the recuperator during discharge compared to the reference case. This occurs because the recuperator is better balanced

during discharge, as the heat capacity ratio between the low- and high-pressure flows is closer to unity. In the reference case, an excessive propane fraction is bypassed because the recompressor is placed in the same shaft that the turbine. As a result, the thermal capacity on the low-pressure side of the recuperator is higher than on the high-pressure side, leading to a higher outlet temperature. By contrast, during PTES discharge the bypass fraction is close to its nominal value, since it is driven by a pump. Consequently, the thermal capacities on both sides of the recuperator are more balanced, resulting in a lower outlet temperature.

Finally, [Table 3.13](#) also shows an apparent roundtrip efficiency above 100 %. This does not mean that the PTES itself exceeds physical efficiency limits but rather reflects the synergies between the PTES and CSP systems. In fact, RTE is not the most appropriate indicator in this integrated configuration: values above 100 % appear because the power block operates more efficiently during discharge, and also because the thermal energy absorbed by the power block in charging and discharging does not exactly match the reference cycle. RTE and COP are also reported in the following tables for completeness, but no further discussion is provided since their interpretation was already addressed in this section.

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{low} \cdot c_{p-low}}{\dot{m}_{high} \cdot c_{p-high}} = \frac{\Delta T_{high}}{\Delta T_{low}} \quad (3.46)$$

Table 3.13 Main HRB-PTES operation results for a condensation temperature of 45 °C

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Condensing temperature (°C)	45	45	45
Cold storage temperature (°C)	0	70	70
Hot storage temperature (°C)	0	210.5	210.5
Bypassed propane maximum temperature (°C)	210.6	214.8	202.9
Outlet recuperator low pressure side temperature (°C)	75	79	65.3
Inlet recuperator high pressure side temperature (°C)	58.8	65.3	58.7
Recuperator heat capacity ratio (low pressure/high pressure)	1.08	1.06	0.99
PB thermal power inlet (MW)	236.7	235	240.3
Thermal power evacuated through the condenser (MW)	148.3	101.5	195.5
Thermal power absorbed by PTES storage (MW)	-	61.0	-61
Gross power produced (MW)	88.4	72.5	105.7
Net power produced (MW)	82	67.8	96.4
Total propane mass flow (kg/s)	574.6	576.3	571.1
Recompressor consumption (MW)	24.2	24.6	-
PTES compressor consumption (MW)	-	21.1	-
Main pump consumption (MW)	15.2	10.2	16.1
PTES pump consumption (MW)	-	-	5
Coefficient of Performance (COP)	-	2.89	-
Roundtrip efficiency (RTE) (%)	-		108.8
Power gross efficiency (%)	37.35		37.49
Efficiency difference (%)			0.14

Table 3.14 Propane mass flow fraction through each component

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main pump	0.71	0.46	0.76
PTES pump	-	-	0.24
Recuperator high-pressure path	0.71	0.71	0.76
Main heater	1	1	1
Turbine	1	1	1
Recuperator low pressure path	1	1	1
Recompressor	0.29	0.29	-
PTES compressor	-	0.24	-
Condenser	0.71	0.46	1

Table 3.15 compares the main results of the CSP when the PTES is off with those when the PTES is charging and discharging, using a condensation temperature that is 10 °C below the nominal value. Table 3.16 presents the mass flow fractions circulating through each component for both scenarios.

In this new analysis, the efficiency of the plant with the integrated PTES is lower than that of the reference plant. In this case unlike in the previous one, the temperature at the outlet of the low-pressure side recuperator is higher during discharge than when the PTES is off. In contrast to the previous scenario, the heat capacity ratio of the reference case is less than unity. This occurs because the inlet pressure in the recompressor is lower than the nominal value, leading to a smaller fraction than necessary to balance the thermal capacities of both fluids. However, unlike the previous case, the work done by the recompressor is also reduced, resulting in a smaller decrease in efficiency for the reference case.

Table 3.15 Main HRB-PTES operation results for a condensation temperature of 25 °C

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Condensing temperature (°C)	25	25	25
Cold storage temperature (°C)	-	47	46.9
Hot storage temperature (°C)	-	194.8	195.0
Propane bypass high temperature (°C)	194.4	199.2	184.1
Outlet recuperator high pressure side temperature (°C)	37.9	42.9	42.1
Inlet recuperator high pressure side temperature (°C)	36.0	41.5	36.1
Recuperator heat capacity ratio (low pressure/high pressure)	0.9	0.92	1
PB thermal power inlet (MW)	267.6	267	264.4
Thermal power evacuated through the condenser (MW)	157	110.4	203.4
Thermal power absorbed by PTES storage (MW)	-	63.6	-63.7
Gross power produced (MW)	110.6	92.9	124.7
Net power produced (MW)	103.5	88	115.3
Total propane mass flow (kg/s)	547.4	547.9	549.9
Recompressor consumption (MW)	17.3	17.5	-
PTES compressor consumption (MW)	-	22.4	-
Main pump consumption (MW)	15	10.3	14.1
PTES pump consumption (MW)	-	-	5
Coefficient of Performance (COP)	-	2.84	
Roundtrip efficiency (RTE) (%)	-		80
Power gross efficiency (%)	41.33		40.95
Efficiency difference (%)		-0.38	

Table 3.16 Propane mass flow fraction through each component

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main pump	0.79	0.54	0.74
PTES pump	-	-	0.26
Recuperator high-pressure path	0.79	0.8	0.74
Main heater	1	1	1
Turbine	1	1	1
Recuperator low-pressure path	1	1	1
Recompressor	0.21	0.26	-
PTES compressor	-	0.29	-
Condenser	0.79	0.54	1

During the annual simulation, charging and discharging do not happen at the same temperature. Charging typically occurs during the central hour of the days, that usually corresponds with the highest temperatures and the lowest electricity prices, while discharging usually occurs at the evening, that corresponds with the lowest temperatures and the highest electricity prices. The global efficiency is improved by two reasons: First because the power production at lower condensing temperatures enhances the efficiency. The second reason is that by charging at a higher condensation temperature than during discharge, the hot tank reaches higher temperatures compared to if the charging had been done at a lower condensation temperature. In [Figure 3.8](#) the monthly ambient temperature evolution for the charging and discharging PTES for the 4 hours case is shown. It can be observed that charging temperatures are generally higher than discharging temperatures. The average annual ambient temperatures for charging and discharging are respectively 29.7 °C and 26.6 °C. As consequence, global performance of the CSP-PTES is improved respect the reference CSP as it is shown in following sections.

In [Appendix A.7](#) tables are presented showing the number of operating hours of the PTES distributed by month and hour. They correspond with the PTES case with 4 hours.

Figure 3.8 Monthly average ambient temperature for PTES case with 4 hours

3.6.3 Annual results and sensitivity analysis

[Table 3.17](#) presents the annual economic outcomes for the reference case, along with the CSP-PTES cases considering 3, 4 and 5 hours of storage respectively. [Figure 3.9](#) shows the values for the levelized costs of investment, operation and maintenance and incomes (LC_{INV} , $LC_{O\&M}$, and LI) for the three scenarios presented in [Table 3.17](#).

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A project is considered profitable if LI surpasses the sum of LC_{INV} and $LC_{O\&M}$. This agrees with the values of the figures of merit shown in Table 3.17. Additionally, the net energy output in the CSP-PTES cases is slightly greater than that of the reference one, partly due to the synergies discussed earlier regarding potential enhancements in PTES integration.

The utilization factor for the CSP is determined by dividing the number of hours that the system operates to the total number of hours in a year. On the other hand, the utilization factor for the PTES considers the total operating hours for both charging and discharging.

The incremental incomes are calculated as the CSP-PTES incomes minus the incomes of the reference case. The incremental investment refers to the total PTES equipment costs that were shown in Table 3.10. Only the case considering the 4 hours of storage is profitable under the proposed economic framework. The 3-hour and 5-hour cases are not feasible as the cost-income ratio exceeds 1. The charging and discharging prices are the weighted averages of the market electricity prices during the respective charging and discharging periods

Table 3.17 Annual economic results for the reference case and the 3,4 and 5 hr CSP-PTES cases

	Reference case	CSP-PTES		
		3 hr	4 hr	5 hr
Net energy (GWh)	335.36	335.66	335.73	335.66
CSP utilization factor (%)	41.1	41.26	41.29	41.29
PTES utilization factor (%)	-	16.75	19.20	21.34
Incomes (M€)	61.44	62.024	62.122	62.176
Incremental incomes (M€)	-	0.584	0.682	0.746
Incremental investment (M€)	-	16.135	17.304	18.87
Cost-incomes ratio	-	1.03	0.99	1.01
Profits-incomes ratio (%)	-	-3.46	0.92	-0.93
Charging price (€/MWh)	-	144.19	142.69	142.41
Discharging price (€/MWh)	-	204.52	204.1	203.23

Figure 3.9 LC_{INV} , $LC_{O\&M}$ and LI for 3 hr, 4 hr and 5 hr HRB-PTES case

Regarding the average market electricity charging prices, as the storage capacity increase, the charging price decreases. This is because the peak and valley price intervals are wide, so with a low number of storage hours, charging also occurs during some hours of the peak price intervals. On the other hand, if the number of storage hours is high, charging will take place entirely during the valley price interval. An example of this is shown in the Figure 3.10 which displays the management of PTES storage during a production day in August along with hourly prices. It can be observed that, in the case of 4 hours, charging takes place between 13:00 and 16:00, while

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discharging occurs between 19:00 and 21:00 and at 23:00. In the case of 3 hours, a charging take place during 22:00 to allow for discharging at 23:00 since the storage is full at 15:00.

Figure 3.10 PTES storage operation during one day of CSP production

The economic results for the sensitivity analysis are shown in Table 3.18. Only the CSP-PTES case with 4 hours of storage has been analysed since it is the most profitable case. Figure 3.11 shows the levelized costs of investment, operation and maintenance, and incomes for the sensitivity analysis cases that were presented in Table 3.18. The “base case” is the same as that shown in Table 3.17. The “+30 % equipment cost” and “-30 % equipment cost” scenarios increase and reduce the investment cost by 30 %, respectively. Maintenance cost varies proportionally with the investment cost. In the “2019 market scenario”, the simulation is done considering the year 2019 instead of 2022. The costs have been updated considering the CEPCI ratio between 2019 and 2022. Finally, the last case considers the financial scenario of [8], which was defined in Table 3.7.

Table 3.18 Sensitivity analysis results

Case	Investment(M€)	Co&M (M€)	Inc. Incomes (M€)	r_{CI}	$r_{PI}(\%)$
Base (Case 1)	17.304	0.173	0.682	0.99	0.92
+30 % equipment cost (Case 2)	22.495	0.225	0.682	1.35	-34.54
-30 % equipment cost (Case 3)	12.112	0.121	0.682	0.72	27.82
2019 market scenario (Case 4)	13.199	0.124	0.063	8.53	-752.7
Economic scenario of [8] (Case 5)	17.304	0.52	0.682	2.7	-169.8

Figure 3.11 LC_{INV} , $LC_{O\&M}$ and LI for the sensitivity analysis cases

Figure 3.12 shows the monthly average hourly prices for CSP, electricity market, PTES discharge, and PTES charge for the year 2022. Figure 3.13 shows the monthly incremental

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revenues and the total operational hours for the PTES. Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16 present the same information as Figures 3.12 and 3.13, but for the year 2019. During months with low radiation, CSP generates energy for few hours, focusing on the peak market price hours. In contrast, during months with high radiation, the average price of CSP becomes similar to the market average, as the number of production hours increases.

The number of operating PTES hours follows a similar trend, regardless of the difference between the average discharge and charging prices. The difference between the average charging and discharging prices seems to be more influenced by the variations in market hourly prices than by the number of PTES operation hours. To support this, Figure 3.14 shows the hourly average electricity prices for each month for the year 2022. From these figures, it can be seen that in the months with a great difference between average hourly peak and valley prices, the difference between charging and discharging prices tends to be higher.

Monthly incomes do not display a clear trend, as months with few operating hours (like September) can generate higher incomes than months with high number of operating hours (such as July or June). This demonstrates the significant dependence of incomes on the market hourly prices.

Figure 3.12 Average monthly prices in 2022

Figure 3.13 Monthly incomes and PTES working hours in 2022

Figure 3.14 Hourly average electricity prices for each month for the year 2022 (left). First six months of 2022. (right) Last six months of 2022

The average electricity prices in Figure 3.15 follow a trend similar to that of Figure 3.12, but they are considerably lower. There is also a significant reduction in the price difference between charging and discharging, which leads to considerably lower monthly revenues, even though the PTES operating hours are comparable to those in the previous case. March revenues are negative because not all the energy charged into the PTES storage during the month is discharged within the same month, but rather also in the following one. In Figure 3.17 the monthly

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revenues for the year 2022 and 2019 are compared graphically. Finally, Table 3.19 summarizes the main annual results of the comparison between the two years.

Figure 3.15 Average monthly prices in 2019

Figure 3.16 Monthly incomes and PTES working hours in 2019

Figure 3.17 Monthly incomes comparison between 2022 and 2019

Table 3.19 Main annual results for 2022 and 2019

	2022 case	2019 case
Market average price (€/MWh)	167.29	47.71
CSP average price (€/MWh)	185.42	93
Discharge average price (€/MWh)	202	51
Charge average price (€/MWh)	144	46
Incremental incomes (M€)	0.682	0.063
PTES number of working hours	1646	1449

3.6.4 Comparison of the proposed PTES to other works

Although the same electricity market prices and economic framework as in [8] were applied to the proposed CSP-PTES, the profit-income ratio and cost-income ratio would not be appropriate metrics for assessing the feasibility of the proposed PTES compared to those presented in [8]. This is because the PTES is integrated into the CSP, meaning that the profitability obtained is derived from the incremental revenues generated by the synergistic integration of the two systems, not only from the PTES itself. To make a valid comparison, the LCOS is used. The input energy is calculated hourly as the difference between the total energy produced by the CSP reference minus the total energy produced by the CSP-PTES while it is charging. In a similar way, the output energy is calculated as the total energy produced by the CSP-PTES when it is discharging minus the total energy produced by the CSP reference. To calculate these values

correctly, charging and discharging must occur within the same time intervals as the production of the reference CSP. Therefore, the code used to establish the scheduling of the CSP-PTES production must take this into account. This code was shown in Section 3.4.2. The charging price regarded is 30 €/MWh, that corresponds with one of the standardized values considered in [8]. Since the electricity market prices of the reference do not coincide with those considered in this work, the LCOS is calculated for the Spanish market prices of 2022 and 2019, also considering that the component costs are adjusted to those years using the CEPCI index. For these two years, similar LCOS values must be obtained in order to make the valid the comparison with the LCOS obtained in [8].

Table 3.20 shows the main results obtained for the two years considered. The CSP-PTES net energy values and their respective incremental incomes over the reference CSP are slightly lower than in Table 3.17. This is due to the constraint applied to schedule the charging and discharging processes. LCOS value for 2022 is slightly higher than that for 2019. The main reason is the higher cost of the investment. Considering that the LCOS value obtained by [8] for pumped hydro storage is the lowest (around 175 €/MWh for 4 hours of storage), even the LCOS obtained for the proposed PTES 2022 is lower. Rankine and Brayton PTES LCOS obtained by [8] are near 350 €/MWh. This is more than double the LCOS value for 2022.

Table 3.20 CSP-PTES and PTES summary data

	2022 Case	2019 Case
CSP-PTES net energy (GWh)	334.56	340.37
CSP-PTES incremental incomes (M€)	0.63	0.09
Input PTES gross power (GWh)	13.51	11.30
Output PTES gross power (GWh)	13.1	11.18
Input PTES net power (GWh)	12.34	10.33
Output PTES net power (GWh)	11.71	10.01
LCOS (€/MWh)	165.5	150.4

3.7 Conclusions

In this section, a PTES system integrated into the power block of a CSP has been proposed and analysed to improve its economic results. Considering the previous works studied and showed in the introduction, this is the first one to achieve positive profitability, even if it is small. The reference CSP has a power block based on the HRB-propane cycle, whose description, simulation, and economic evaluation were conducted in the previous section. The synergistic integration of the PTES allows for cost reductions compared to a conventional PTES, as it shares some components with the power block (turbine, condenser). It should be noted that the reference CSP-PTES components have the same size as the CSP-reference, being the added components the only difference between them. This assures a more effective comparison. Operating and economic results for the CSP-PTES have been shown, comparing them with the reference CSP results and with the conventional PTES results from [8].

Regarding operating results, the variation of the power produced due to the PTES operation does not affect significantly the turbine efficiency compared to the efficiency achieved when the PTES is off, since the mass flow rate value remains similar. Additionally, the annual net energy produced in the CSP-PTES is slightly higher than in the reference CSP as a result of the improved efficiency achieved during the charging and discharging.

Regarding the economic results, the CSP-PTES is profitable for the case of 4 hours of storage when using the hourly electricity market prices in Spain for the year 2022 as a reference. However, considering the results of the sensitivity analysis, the profitability of the plant varies significantly depending on the financial framework, the uncertainty in cost estimations, and the reference year used for the market hourly prices. The reference year considered for the hourly electricity market prices is the factor that most impacts the profitability of the system. The revenues obtained for the year 2022 around 11 times higher than those for 2019 (Table 3.19), which means that the profit/income ratio, derived from the levelized costs and revenues over the lifetime of the plant, could be up to 50 times lower if the year 2019 is used as the reference. Considering that the volatility of prices from one year to another largely depends on factors that cannot be easily predicted (for the two years considered, the price difference is due to the gas price difference), the uncertainty regarding the profitability of the system is very high, given the long lifespan of the plant (35 years). However, considering the growing integration of renewable energy production technologies without storage capacity into the electricity mix, combined with the closure of fossil fuel power plants with storage capacity, energy storage systems will be required to meet demand when the renewable energy source is not available.

The LCOS is calculated to compare the feasibility of the proposed PTES with that obtained from the energy storage systems shown in [8]. The LCOS obtained is half of the LCOS of Rankine and Brayton PTES. It is even lower than the LCOS of a hydro pumped energy storage with the same number of hours of storage. However, since the proposed PTES is integrated in a CSP and the energy storage systems shown in [8] are standalone plants, the comparison should be regarded as indicative only.

In conclusion, the proposed PTES not only improves the operational performance of the reference CSP but also enhances its economic results. The incremental benefits obtained are small and highly sensitive to the uncertainty in the estimation of costs and prices considered for the reference year. However, it is expected that in the coming years, the difference between the maximum and minimum daily prices will increase, which means that profitability could improve, and that bids for such systems might also be implemented. On the other hand, most of the unconventional PTES systems found in the scientific literature are integrated into fossil fuel power plants, either to reduce their emissions or to repurpose the plant as a storage system. Since the construction of new fossil fuel power plants is not expected, the PTES of that works can only be applied to existing plants. In contrast, the PTES proposed in this work is integrated into a CSP, whose presence in the grid is expected to increase in the coming years. Finally, another advantage of the proposed PTES is that it can be integrated with other recompression cycles, which enables the study of its introduction into high temperatures CSP with supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton power blocks.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
HRB	Hybrid Rankine Brayton
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HX	Heat Exchanger
NZE	Net Zero Emissions
RT-ORC	Transcritical Organic Rankine Cycle
PB	Power block
sCO ₂ -RB	supercritical CO ₂ recompression Brayton cycle
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

Symbols

amb	Ambient
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AMTD	Arithmetic Mean Temperature Difference (K)
B	Constant for installation costs
cel	Electricity purchase cost ($\text{€}\cdot\text{MWh}^{-1}$)
c_p	Specific heat ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)
C	Constant for equipment costs
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index
D	Diameter (m)
E	Energy (MWh)
F	Factor
h	Enthalpy ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
hr	Hour
I	Incomes (M€)
j	Temporal horizon index
L	Length (m)
LC	Levelized Cost (M€)
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy ($\text{€}\cdot\text{MWh}^{-1}$)
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage ($\text{€}\cdot\text{MWh}^{-1}$)
LI	Levelized Incomes (M€)
LMTD	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
N.R	Newton Raphson method
p	Pitch (mm)
P	Pressure (kPa)
\dot{P}	Power (MW)
\dot{Q}	Thermal power (MW)
r	Ratio
s	Entropy ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)
S	Stress (kPa)
t	Thickness (m)
T	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
UA	Global heat transfer coefficient x Area

Subscripts

BM	Bare module
c	PTES charging operation
cc	Charging compressor
ci	Cost over incomes
comp	Compressor
d	PTES discharging operation
des	Design
df	Defocus
I	Incomes
INV	Investment
max	Maximum
mh	Main heater
min	Minimum
mv	Maximum characteristic factor value
off	Off-design
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
otb	Outlet tube diameter
pf	Power fluid
pi	Profits over incomes
PB	Power block
Pr	Production
ref	Reference
rc	Recompressor
sec	Secondary
sto	Stodola

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stPB	Power Block start up
t	Turbine
Ub	Upper bound
wPr	Without Production
<hr/>	
<i>Greek letters</i>	
Δ	Increment
δ	Binary auxiliary variable
$\hat{\alpha}$	Binary variable (PB producing)
$\hat{\beta}$	Binary variable (PB startup)
$\hat{\gamma}$	Binary variable (Storing energy in TES)
$\hat{\eta}$	Binary variable (Shutting down PB)
$\hat{\tau}$	Binary input data (SF startup process)
$\hat{\theta}$	Binary auxiliary variable
<hr/>	

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4 PROPOSAL OF A PUMPED THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE FOR A HIGH-TEMPERATURE CSP WITH sCO₂-RB POWER BLOCK.

4.1 Introduction

As stated in the introduction section, although the dispatchability of Concentrated Solar Power plants (CSP) is a distinguishing feature compared to other renewable technologies, the still high levelized cost of energy is the main drawback that explains their relatively low installed capacity compared to other energy sources, such as photovoltaic or wind power. According to [1], the total CSP installed accumulated capacity until 2023 was 8.1 GW while photovoltaic was 1552 GW.

To reduce the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), main efforts focus on improving the thermal-electric efficiency of the plants. In this way, improving the plant's efficiency allows for a reduction in the relative size of the solar field, which is one of the highest-cost system in CSP, accounting for up to 60 % of the total cost in central receiver systems when including the receiver [2]. For that, CSP central-receiver systems allow for higher temperatures at the turbine inlet compared to CSP systems with parabolic trough solar fields (around 150 °C higher). Additionally, the heat transfer fluid is the same fluid that is stored in the tanks, avoiding the use of a heat exchanger. In this way, a more constant production value can be achieved during the night since the turbine inlet temperature value is closer to the nominal one. New CSP projects take mostly the central-receiver configuration. This is reflected in the proportions of installed capacity by CSP technologies in countries like China, where the introduction of solar thermal energy into the grid has been later compared to others like Spain and USA [3].

According to [4], the current state of the art for central receivers involves temperature levels of 565 °C and 290 °C at the outlet and inlet of the receiver, around 540 °C for the turbine inlet temperature, and a thermal-electric efficiency of 41.2 %. Wet cooling is considered to avoid high cooling temperatures that could reduce the efficiency. Regarding molten salts storage capacities, they are usually greater than 10 hours [5-7].

Reference [8] establishes different scenarios (advanced, moderate and conservative) for the next generation CSP depending on the level of innovation and research. All of them consider central receiver configuration instead of a parabolic trough solar field. The conservative scenario assumes no innovation. The moderate scenario considers the use of a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton (sCO₂-RB) power block instead of the conventional steam Rankine power cycle. The advanced scenario also uses the sCO₂-RB power block, but with an inlet turbine temperature around 700 °C. Indeed, research is done in both fields: In USA, the Gen3 CSP funding program considers three pathways to achieve the proposed temperature increase in the receiver: Using gas, particles or liquid fluids [9]. Because of this funding program, a Gen3 Particle Pilot Plant is being built [8]. This research is also being studied in other countries, such as Saudi Arabia, where another particle pilot plant is under construction [10], and in Australia, where a pilot plant will use liquid sodium [11].

Regarding the sCO₂-RB, it has been extensively studied not only for CSP but also for nuclear power plants. As it was stated in the introduction section, several studies have concluded that this power cycle has better efficiency than superheated and supercritical steam Rankine cycles for temperatures around 700 °C [12,13]. The most favourable studies have established that the sCO₂-RB has a higher efficiency than superheated steam Rankine and supercritical steam Rankine cycles for higher inlet turbine temperatures than 450 °C and 500 °C, respectively, considering a main compressor inlet temperature of 32 °C. However, it should be considered that this

temperature is usually higher, especially if dry cooling is considered. In those cases, the low temperature of the cycle can be even higher than 50 °C, so the inlet turbine temperature should be increased until 700 °C to achieve a higher efficiency than steam cycles. Ref. [12] sets that the efficiency losses depending on the main inlet compressor temperature follow a linear progression. In that study (550 °C at the turbine inlet and 20 MPa at the compressor outlet), the efficiency is reduced 1.5 % each time that main compressor inlet temperature is increased 5 °C. That study considers the optimization of the pressure at the compressor inlet for each temperature.

In this section, a pumped thermal energy storage system (PTES) is integrated into the power block of a high-temperature CSP with a central receiver configuration. The power cycle considered is a sCO₂-RB and the PTES is integrated similarly to in the HRB-propane case since both cycles have a recompressor. However, in this case, some additional modifications should be considered: The main compressor is placed in an independent shaft, and it is driven by an electric motor to ensure nominal efficiency under all operating conditions. In this way, losses during PTES charging are avoided, since the CO₂ mass flow rate entering the cooler can vary significantly. An additional compressor is placed in parallel to the main one to send the bypass fraction to the PTES heat exchanger during discharging. Finally, an extra compressor is placed in parallel to the recompression one to bypass an additional fraction of CO₂ through the PTES heat exchanger during the charging. In [Section 4.2](#) the layout diagrams are shown and explained.

The HTF considered are molten salts that are heated up to 565 °C in a central receiver. Although sCO₂-RB power cycle achieves higher efficiency at high temperatures, a conventional fluid and common temperatures values are selected to use commercial receivers and storage systems. In this way the uncertainty in the design, simulation and cost estimation are reduced. The sizing models considered to calculate the different subsystems of the CSP are shown in [Section 4.3](#).

In [Section 4.4](#), off-design models of each subsystem are shown along with the methodology used to couple them, the startup models for the receiver and the power block.

In [Section 4.5](#), equations used to estimate the costs of the equipment, and the figures of merit used to assess the profitability of the CSP and the PTES-CSP are shown.

Finally, in [Section 4.6](#) and [Section 4.7](#) the results and conclusions are shown.

4.2 Power cycle description

4.2.1 sCO₂-RB

The sCO₂-RB layout considered corresponds with the one used in high temperature applications as it has two recuperators ([Figure 4.1](#)). The recompressor is in the same shaft as the turbine, so it rotates always at the same speed. That means that at high ambient temperatures, the bypass fraction would be lower than in nominal conditions. On the other hand, the main compressor is placed in a different shaft, and it is driven by an electric motor. At off-design conditions the main compressor rotates at different speeds to maintain a similar efficiency to the nominal value. The reason to do that is to have a more effectively comparison with the sCO₂-RB that has the PTES integrated, since in this last case the main compressor needs to rotate at different speeds during charging and discharging to avoid too low efficiencies. The T-s diagram of the reference configuration is shown in [Figure 4.2](#).

Section 4: Proposal of a PTES for a high-temperature CSP with sCO₂-RB power block

Figure 4.1 Reference of sCO₂-RB layout

Figure 4.2 Reference sCO₂-RB T-s diagram

4.2.2 PTES-sCO₂-RB

In this configuration, a PTES is integrated in the power block in a similar way to its integration in the HRB-propane one. The number and typology of components is similar although a parallel compressor to the main one is needed in the sCO₂-RB instead of the parallel pump needed in the HRB-propane. During charging (Figure 4.3), an additional fluid fraction is extracted from the main flow before it enters the cooler and is bypassed through an added compressor. This compressor (PTES charging compressor) has the same size as the recompressor, so the mass flow rate that it drives at nominal conditions matches that of the recompressor. The heat absorbed by this fluid fraction is then delivered to the PTES storage system through a water/CO₂ heat exchanger. The storage system consists of pressurized water tanks. After being cooled, the flow fraction joins the main flow just after the main compressor. The additional charging compressor is driven by an electric motor and always delivers the nominal mass flow rate value. This is due to two reasons: First, to maintain a high-water temperature even when ambient temperatures are high, since the water pump always drives the same mass flow rate value. The second reason is to maintain a more balanced water/CO₂ heat exchanger, by keeping the mass flow rate values of the fluids that go through it at their nominal values. In Figure 4.4 the T-s diagram is shown. The thermodynamic properties of each point coincide with that of the reference configuration at nominal conditions. In summary, power production during the charging process decreases below the nominal value of the reference configuration due to the addition of the charging compressor. The electrical consumption of this compressor is converted into thermal energy that is stored in the water.

Section 4: Proposal of a PTES for a high-temperature CSP with sCO₂-RB power block

Figure 4.3 PTES sCO₂-RB charging layout

Figure 4.4 Charging sCO₂-RB T-s diagram

During discharging (Figure 4.5) a parallel compressor to the main one drives the same mass flow rate as the charging PTES-compressor. The discharging compressor is placed in an independent shaft and driven by an electric motor to always propel the nominal mass flow rate. This fraction is heated by the PTES storage and joins the main flow after the low temperature recuperator. In this way, this recuperator is more balanced than in the original configuration. So, the previously stored thermal energy is restored and, since the recompressor is off, an increase on electricity production is achieved. However, an aspect should be considered: the electricity production over the reference configuration is due the consumption difference between the recompressor and the parallel to the main one. So, if the minimum temperature of the cycle increases, the consumption of the main compressor and the parallel one increases as they are further away the supercritical point.

When the PTES is off, the original configuration is used, and the components maintain the same size, so the same power is achieved. It should be noted that the main compressor is placed also in an independent shaft. Thus, during charging, the flow that it drives is lower than if the PTES is off, so low efficiency could be expected if it always rotates at the same speed. However, an efficiency similar to the nominal value can be achieved adjusting the rotational speed.

Figure 4.5 Discharging sCO₂-RB T-s diagram

4.3 CSP sizing model

In this section the sizing methodology of the power block, the TES, the solar field and the receiver are shown for the two cases: the reference CSP and the CSP with the PTES integrated. It should be noted that, except for the components added by the PTES into the power block, the remaining components of the PTES-CSP are identical to those in the reference CSP. Therefore, both the methodology and the sizing of the thermal energy storage, the solar field and the receiver coincide for the two cases.

4.3.1 Reference CSP power block

The gross output power considered is 100 MW. The main compressor inlet temperature is 35 °C, ten degrees higher than the selected ambient temperature at nominal conditions. The maximum pressure of the cycle is limited to 260 bar, to avoid excessive stress on the components. Two pairs of pressure and bypass fraction values have been selected that maximize the power cycle efficiency for a main compressor inlet temperature of 35 °C and 40 °C, respectively. The pair of values considered are shown in Table 4.1. It should be noted, however, that to make a more effective comparison, the chosen nominal temperature at the inlet of the main compressor is 35 °C in both cases.

The temperature at the turbine inlet is 560 °C. Main heater and recuperators pinch point values are 5 °C. It is considered that in both sides of the high temperature recuperator (low and high pressure) there is a pressure drop while in the low temperature recuperator there is only pressure drop in the low-pressure side. The outlet pressure value of the fluid that is cooled in each recuperator is 2 % lower than the inlet value. In the high temperature recuperator, the outlet pressure of the fluid that is heated up is a 3 % lower than the inlet value. The pressure outlet of the CO₂ in the main heater is a 2 % lower than the inlet value. In all cases the pressure is considered that decrease linearly. These data are shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4.1 Main compressor inlet pressure and bypass fraction values for two optimization cases

Case	1	2
Main compressor inlet pressure (bar)	83	92
Bypass fraction	0.35	0.33

Table 4.2 Main compressor and bypass fraction values

Gross power (MW)	100
Main compressor inlet temperature (°C)	35
Main compressor outlet pressure (bar)	260
Main heater salts inlet temperature (°C)	565
Turbine inlet temperature (°C)	560
Main heater pressure drop in the CO ₂ side (%)	2
Recuperators pressure drop in the low pressure side (%)	2
HTR pressure drop in the high pressure side (%)	3
Turbomachinery polytropic efficiency (%)	90

The polytropic efficiency is used to calculate the outlet states in the turbomachinery. The total pressure change has been divided into 25 parts. As in the previous sections, this number is enough to apply the polytropic efficiency definition in each part without introducing significant errors. Equation 4.1 is used to calculate the exit enthalpy of each part of the turbine from the inlet one and the polytropic efficiency. Equation 4.2 is used for the compressor. These corresponds with the equations used in Section 2.3.

$$h_{i+1} = h_i - (h_i - h_{is,i+1}) \cdot \eta_t \quad (4.1)$$

$$h_{i+1} = h_i + (h_{is,i+1} - h_i) / \eta_{comp} \quad (4.2)$$

Since the CO₂ is at supercritical conditions, the specific heat can significantly vary inside the heat exchangers. So, to calculate the inlet and outlet temperatures of these components, the total enthalpy change has been also divided into 25 parts and energy balances have been established to calculate the unknown thermodynamic properties in each side of these segments. In the recuperators, one inlet and outlet temperature are known along with the pinch point value, so to calculate the unknown temperatures, the Newton-Raphson method is used. This method was explained in Section 2.3 and in this case is similarly applied. For the main heater and the cooler, the inlet and outlet temperatures of each fluid are known once the thermodynamic properties in each side of the recuperators are calculated.

Once all the thermodynamic properties of the cycle are determined, the efficiency, the specific power, the total thermal power, and the mass flow rates of the salts and the CO₂ can be calculated. The total UA factor of each heat exchanger is calculated as the sum of the UA of each one of the 25 parts in which it has been divided. As in the HRB-propane, the number of parts is enough to use the arithmetic mean temperature difference instead off the logarithmic one in each of them without making significant errors. Equation 4.3 is used to calculate the UA factors. It should be noted that, unlike the HRB-propane, in the sCO₂-RB the cooler has been also divided in 25 parts since in this component the fluid is very close to the critical point.

$$UA_{rec/mh/cooler} = \sum_{i=1}^{25} UA_i = \sum_{i=1}^{25} \frac{\dot{Q}_i}{AMTD_i} \quad (4.3)$$

The cooling system uses air. Same equations, fan efficiencies and air temperatures as in the HRB-propane case are considered. Table 4.3 reminds the input cooler data and Equation 4.4, Equation 4.5 and Equation 4.6 allows to calculation of the air mass flow rate, isentropic outlet fan temperature, and total power consumption.

$$\dot{m}_{air} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{cp_{air} \cdot (\Delta T_{ITD} - AP_{cooler})} \quad (4.4)$$

$$T_{outlet,fan,is} = T_{inlet,fan} \cdot pr_{fan}^{\frac{R}{cp_{air}}} \quad (4.5)$$

Section 4: Proposal of a PTES for a high-temperature CSP with sCO₂-RB power block

$$\dot{P}_{cooler} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} \cdot (h_{fan,out,is} - h_{fan,in})}{\eta_{fan}} \quad (4.6)$$

Table 4.3 Cooler input data

Fan total efficiency (%)	60
Cooler initial temperature difference* (%)	10
Cooler approach temperature** (°C)	3
Fan pressure ratio	1.0012
*It is the difference between the outlet temperature of the cycle and the air inlet temperature	
**It is the difference between the outlet temperature of the cycle and the air outlet temperature	

The process diagram shown in Figure 4.6 summarises each of the steps taken to calculate the output data at nominal condition. First, the pressure in each point of the cycle is calculated considering the pressure drops and the maximum and minimum pressures of the cycle. Then, the outlet temperatures of the main compressor and turbine are calculated. An estimated value for the inlet temperature of the CO₂ that is heated in the high-temperature recuperator (T_{2pp}) is set and the Newton-Raphson method is used to calculate the inlet and outlet temperatures of the recuperators. After that, the outlet temperature of the recompressor is calculated. Then, T_{2pp} is recalculated considering the mass and energy balance between the bypass fraction flow and the main one. When T_{2pp} converges, air, CO₂ and salts mass flow rate can be calculated along with the power consumed by the air cooler and the UA factors of the heat exchangers.

Figure 4.6 Reference power block sizing model diagram process

4.3.2 PTES-CSP power block

The bypass fraction for the PTES both at the charging and discharging is set equal to that of the reference configuration at nominal condition. The two cases of Table 4.1 with different bypass fraction and compressor inlet pressures are considered. The water/CO₂ heat exchanger temperature difference in the hot side is 10 °C and the pinch point is set to 5 °C. In this way, the pinch point is achieved around the middle of the heat exchanger and the temperature difference in the cold end is similar to that at the hot end. It should be considered that if the pinch point were set at the hot end, the temperature difference in the cold end would be too high. This behavior is explained by the variation of specific heats: the specific heat of water increases with temperature, while that of CO₂ decreases as the fluid moves away from the critical point. To support the selected values, temperature profile diagrams of the water/CO₂ heat exchanger are shown in Section 4.6.2.

The data values are shown in Table 4.4. Storage capacities considered are 3, 4 and 5 hours. The PTES-HX outlet temperature of the CO₂ (T_{2c}), matches the nominal outlet temperature of the main compressor of the reference configuration. In that way, the thermodynamic properties of the different power cycle points take the same values as in the reference power block.

The nominal water mass flow rate and the inlet water temperature to the water/CO₂ HX are calculated using the Newton-Raphson method considering the pinch point, the CO₂ inlet and outlet temperatures and the CO₂ mass flow rates as the input data.

Table 4.4 PTES-sCO₂-RB summarized input data

CO ₂ outlet temperature at the PTES-HX (°C)	$T_{2,des}$
PTES compressor bypass fraction values	0.35, 0.33
Main charging compressor inlet pressure (bar)	83, 92
Water/CO ₂ HX Pinch Point (°C)	5
Hot side temperature difference in water/CO ₂ HX (°C)	10
Storage capacity (hr)	3,4,5

4.3.3 Receiver and solar field models

An external receiver has been chosen due to the high thermal power required. The heat transfer fluid is molten salts. The external surface of the receiver is modelled as a cylinder divided into a series of rectangular panels. The area of the cylinder coincides with the sum of the area of the panels. Each panel is in series with the next one and is divided into a determined number of parallel tubes arranged vertically and separated by a minimum distance to allow free expansion of the tubes [14]. The main parameters of the receiver are shown in Table 4.5. In the same table, the parameters of a receiver from a real commercial plant are shown (Crescent Dunes [15,16]). Same outlet receiver temperatures are considered, although inlet temperatures are different. The use of two recuperators in the sCO₂-RB significantly increases the temperature reached before entering the main heater compared to the steam Rankine cycle, so a higher molten salts inlet temperature must be selected. On the other hand, although the nominal thermal power required is lower than the thermal power absorbed by the receiver of Crescent Dunes, the same diameter and height have been considered. This ensures that the maximum recommended peak flow is not exceeded. Noted that to achieve a similar internal tube velocity, the number of panels selected is lower than in Crescent Dunes even though the design thermal power is also lower. This is due to the significantly higher molten salt mass flow rate required because of the higher inlet HTF temperature.

Table 4.5 Receiver main parameters

Parameters	Model	Crescent Dunes
Design thermal power absorbed by HTF (MW)	440	565
Inlet HTF Temperature (°C)	400	290
Outlet HTF Temperature (°C)	565	565
Receiver Diameter (m)	20	20
Receiver height (m)	17.6	17.6
Number of panels	12	16
Number of tubes per panel	107	76
Internal tube diameter (mm)	42	42
Tower optical height (m)	180	180

The heliostats field has been sized using the SolarPilot software [17]. In Table 4.6 the main input data for the programme is shown. The heliostat geometry and focusing and mirror performance parameters chosen match those of [18].

Table 4.6 Main data of the heliostats field and design point

Design point conditions	
Location (latitude,longitude)	Seville, (37.41N, -5.9W)
Day and hour	June 21 at solar noon
Dry bulb Temperature (°C)	25
Direct Normal Irradiation, DNI (Wm ⁻²)	850
Wind velocity (ms ⁻¹)	5
Thermal power required by PB (MW)	220
Heliostat geometry and focusing	
Structure width(m) x height (m)	12.2x12.2
No. horizontal panels	2
No. vertical panels	8
Elevation/ Azimuth pointing error (mrad)	0
Surface slope error in x/y (mrad)	1.53
Reflected beam error in x/y (mrad)	0.2
Mirror performance parameters	
Reflective surface ratio	0.97
Mirror reflectivity	0.95
Soiling factor	0.95

SolarPilot also allows obtaining the map of optical flux per unit area applied to the external receiver surface. However, the heat losses (convection and radiation) are an input parameter for the program, so they must be initially estimated. So, the optical flux map obtained is used as an input for the receiver model programmed in Matlab, which calculates the heat losses. Once the heat losses are calculated, they are introduced again into SolarPilot in an iterative process until the convergence is achieved.

The optical flux map has been discretized into a 20x12 matrix, with each panel assigned a single optical flux value in the circumferential direction and for each meter of receiver height. The optical flux map obtained under design conditions is shown in Figure 4.7. The peak flux value is below 1 MW/m², which is the limit for molten salts receivers with high nickel-alloy tubes according to different references [16,19-22].

Figure 4.7 Incident optical flux in the receiver at the design-point

For the calculation of heat losses, the path flow of the molten salts must be defined: The salt flow enters from the north of the receiver, dividing into two parallel streams. One flows through the panels located to the east, while the other flows to the west. In each panel, the flow is divided into a series of parallel tubes. The tubes are arranged vertically, with a height equal to that of the receiver. The connection between panels is done in series, so the flow is alternatively going up and down in each panel. Midway along each path (after panel number 3), the streams cross over so that the stream passing through the panels on the east side shifts to the west side, and vice-versa. Finally, both flows exit the receiver from the south mixing in the downcomer header that leads to the hot salt tank. A diagram of the receiver is shown in [Figure 4.8](#).

The control of the salt outlet temperature is independently managed in each of the pathways. This layout is used in Solar Two, a pilot concentrated CSP that served as a model for current commercial CSP plants based on molten salts receivers [16]. This layout has been also discussed in the scientific literature [14,23]. On one hand, splitting the salt stream into two parallel paths significantly reduces pressure losses. On the other hand, although heat losses are greater than if the flow direction were reversed (entry from the south, exit from the north), the tubes on the north face (which receive the highest amount of radiation) are better cooled. Finally, the flow path crossover allows for a more balanced distribution of the incident power in each stream when the flow is not fully symmetric with respect to the north side. This allows, according to [23], an increase in the number of operating hours during sunrise and sunset, as a minimum flow rate must be ensured in each path.

Figure 4.8 Receiver layout. Upper view (left) and flow between two consecutive panels (right)

The heat loss calculation model for the receiver is discretized into the same number of parts as the optical flux matrix. Circumferential variations in the temperature of the tubes are not considered, so all the tubes in the same panel have the same temperature for each meter of receiver height. This consideration is used by models from other authors such as [24,25]. On the other hand, [26] considers circumferential variations in the temperature of the tubes, since not all surfaces of the tubes are equally exposed to the optical flux from the heliostats or to the radiation emitted by the tubes themselves. Despite this, [26] demonstrated that for the purpose of calculating heat losses, both models predict similar values. Conversely, the simplified model that does not consider circumferential temperature variations in the tubes significantly underestimates the temperature of the internal and external surfaces of the tubes. To mitigate this, the studied model considers only the most exposed half of each tube for the heat transfer processes, thereby increasing convection and conduction resistances and, consequently, surface temperatures. This is also considered in the model made by [14]. However, for the sizing of the receiver, CFD models or models that consider circumferential temperature variations should be used, as in [27,28], also performing thermal fatigue analyses. This is beyond the scope of the study, as the purpose of the presented model is to predict thermal losses values for an annual energy production simulation.

Receiver thermal model description

The procedure described applies to each of the two parallel streams that pass through the receiver. Table 4.7 shows additional parameters required for the model, along with the data presented in Table 4.5 and Table 4.6. The tube material is Incoloy 800H, a high nickel alloy used in Solar One receiver and in some Sandia receiver tests [29]. Properties can be obtained from [30]. The tube thickness has been chosen considering the maximum pressure and temperature in the receiver. Absorptivity and emissivity values correspond to standard values given for receiver panels coated with Pyromark 2500 Series [22].

Table 4.7 Additional input data for receiver model

Tube material	Inconel 800H
Tube thickness (mm)	1.65
Absorptivity	0.93
Emissivity	0.83
Height of each node (m)	1

Equation 4.7 allows calculating the heat flux absorbed per surface area by the receiver (W/m^2) in each of the nodes into which the external surface of the receiver has been divided. It is assessed considering the incident optical flux map and the tube coating absorptivity. Equation 4.8 allows calculating the thermal flux absorbed per surface area by the molten salts after accounting for thermal losses in each node. Equation 4.9 determines the mass flow passing through a panel. The area of a node is assessed with Equation 4.10 and corresponds to a panel section of height ΔH . Equation 4.11 computes the outlet salts enthalpy of node (i,j) . Equation 4.12 calculates the internal tube surface temperature using the average temperature of the salts, the thermal power absorbed by a single tube at node (i,j) , and the internal convection resistance term. In Equation 4.13, the internal convection film coefficient is obtained using the Gnielinski correlation [31]. The external surface temperature is computed using Equation 4.14 which considers conduction heat transfer through the tube. Equation 4.15 determines the conduction thermal resistance considering that the tube thermal conductivity depends on its temperature. Equation 4.16 and Equation 4.17 allow evaluating the heat flux losses due to radiation and convection for each node, referenced to the external surface of the receiver. The convection film

coefficient of Equation 4.18 is obtained using the Siebers & Kraabel correlation [32] that was specifically designed for receivers. It is more detailed in Appendix A.8.

$$\dot{q}_{rec,abs(i,j)} = \dot{q}_{opt(i,j)} \cdot \alpha \quad (4.7)$$

$$\dot{q}_{HTF(i,j)} = \dot{q}_{rec,abs(i,j)} - \dot{q}_{th,loss(i,j)} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\dot{m}_{panel} = \frac{A_{node} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{j=q} \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \dot{q}_{HTF(i,j)}}{h_{HTF,out(n,q)} - h_{HTF,in(1,1)}} \text{ where } q = N_{panels}/2 \text{ and } n = H_{rec}/\Delta H \quad (4.9)$$

$$A_{node} = \frac{\pi \cdot D_{rec} \cdot \Delta H}{N_{panels}} \quad (4.10)$$

$$h_{salt,out(i,j)} = h_{salt,in(i,j)} + \frac{\dot{q}_{HTF(i,j)} \cdot A_{node}}{\dot{m}_{panel}} \quad (4.11)$$

$$T_{surf,int(i,j)} = \frac{\dot{q}_{HTF(i,j)} \cdot A_{node}}{N_{tb \text{ per panel}}} \cdot R_{conv(i,j)} + T_{mean,HTF(i,j)} \quad (4.12)$$

$$R_{conv,int(i,j)} = \frac{1}{\check{h}_{int(i,j)} \cdot D_{tb,int}/2 \cdot \pi \cdot \Delta H} \quad (4.13)$$

$$T_{surf,ext(i,j)} = \frac{\dot{q}_{HTF(i,j)} \cdot A_{node}}{N_{tb \text{ per panel}}} \cdot R_{cond(i,j)} + T_{surf,int(i,j)} \quad (4.14)$$

$$R_{cond(i,j)} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{D_{tb,ext}}{D_{tb,int}}\right)}{\pi \cdot k_{tb(i,j)} \cdot \Delta H} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\dot{q}_{loss,rad(i,j)} = \sigma \cdot \epsilon \cdot \left[\left(T_{surf,ext(i,j)} \right)^4 - (T_{amb})^4 \right] \quad (4.16)$$

$$\dot{q}_{loss,conv(i,j)} = \check{h}_{ext(i,j)} \cdot \left(T_{surf,ext(i,j)} - T_{amb} \right) \quad (4.17)$$

$$\dot{q}_{th,loss(i,j)} = \dot{q}_{loss,rad(i,j)} + \dot{q}_{loss,conv(i,j)} \quad (4.18)$$

The structure of the model and the implementation order of the equations are represented in the process diagram in Figure 4.9. The process has several nested iterative processes. For each node, an internal surface temperature is estimated, which allows for the calculation of the internal convection coefficient, which in turn allows for recalculating this temperature by applying the convection heat transfer equation. Subsequently, after calculating the heat losses of the node, it must be verified if there is convergence with respect to the initially estimated heat losses. If not, the heat absorbed by the molten salts must be recalculated from the rest of the indicated equations. Once the convergence of the heat losses for a particular node has been achieved, the next node is calculated. After calculating the last node, it is observed whether the overall heat losses converge with the initially estimated value and if the outlet salt temperature of the receiver converges with the desired value. If not, the matrix of heat absorbed by the molten salts is recalculated, the flow rate circulating through each path is adjusted, and all nodes are recalculated. Finally, it is important to note that if the salts do not absorb the desired solar thermal power, the heat losses must be reintroduced into the SolarPilot to generate a new field of heliostats and a new matrix of incident optical flux at the receiver.

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Figure 4.9 Receiver model process diagram

Pressure drop and pump consumption:

The pressure increase that the pump must provide (total head) in steady-state conditions is the sum of the pressure drop in the receiver, the frictional pressure drop in the headers, and the pressure difference due to the density difference corresponding to the column of molten salts ascending and descending the tower.

The pressure drop in the receiver is the sum of the frictional pressure drop in the tubes and the pressure drop due the connections between panels (Equation 4.20). For the frictional pressure drop, the average properties in each panel are considered. Regarding the connections between panels, a factor of K=2 is considered, which is equal to twice the loss factor of a 90° elbow. The pressure drop in the headers due headers is considered 5 % of the pressure drop in the receiver Equation 4.21. The pressure difference due to the tower height and due to the density difference between the ascending and descending fluid in the tower is calculated using Equation 4.22. The height corresponds to the total height of the tower, considering the pump position as the reference point ($H_{tower}=180$ m). The density of each molten salt column corresponds to those at the inlet and outlet of the receiver. Finally, the consumption pump is assessed with Equation 4.23. The pump efficiency value is 85 %.

$$\Delta P_{pump} = \Delta P_{rec} + \Delta P_{fr,headers} + \Delta P_{height} \quad (4.19)$$

$$\Delta P_{rec} = \sum_{j=1}^{j=N_{panels}} f_j \frac{H_{rec}}{d_{int}} \cdot \frac{\rho_j \cdot v_j^2}{2} + \sum_{j=1}^{j=N_{panels}} K \cdot \frac{\rho_{1,j} \cdot v_{1,j}^2}{2} \quad (4.20)$$

$$\Delta P_{fr,headers} = 0.05 \cdot \Delta P_{rec} \quad (4.21)$$

$$\Delta P_{height} = H_{tower} \cdot g \cdot (\rho_{HTF,out} - \rho_{HT,in}) \quad (4.22)$$

$$\dot{P}_{pump} = \frac{\Delta P_{pump} \cdot \dot{m}_{HTF}}{\eta_{pump} \cdot \rho_{HTF,inlet}} \quad (4.23)$$

4.3.4 TES

Two-tanks system with a storage capacity for 12 hours of nominal power block thermal power requirement have been considered. The storage fluid is molten salts [33]. The nominal temperatures of the hot and cold molten salts tanks are respectively 565 °C and 400 °C that coincide with the inlet and outlet receiver and main heater temperatures.

4.4 Annual simulations methodology

4.4.1 General considerations. Operation criteria

The considerations for the annual simulations are similar to those of Section 2.6.1: A typical meteorological year for Sevilla has been considered as hourly data [34], including the dry bulb ambient temperature and the DNI. Each simulation time-step considered is half an hour. In this case, that time is required not only for the power block startup but also for the receiver startup. A single operation per time step is considered. These operations can be:

- 1) Electricity production and charging/discharging TES. Night production is considered.
- 2) TES charging without production.
- 3) Solar field and power block startup.

Each of these operations (except the solar field startup) are scheduled based on a mixed-integer linear optimization model to maximize revenue. The market hourly price data corresponds to the year 2022, and it has been obtained from [35].

The following criteria is considered in all cases:

- 1) The HTF mass flow rate through the main heater and the outlet temperature of the solar field take always the design value.

2) The maximum salts mass flow rate through the receiver is 20 % higher than the design mass flow rate (recommendation of [36]). Same limit is considered for the discharge/store in the TES.

4) For ambient temperatures lower than 22 °C, the low temperature of the cycle is 32 °C to ensure supercritical conditions. For ambient temperatures between 22 °C and 25 °C, the low temperature of the cycle is ten degrees higher. For ambient temperatures higher than 25 °C, the low temperature of the cycle is calculated considering that cooler fans drive the same mass flow rate as at the design condition. For each operation (reference, charging, and discharging), a specific design mass flow rate is considered, corresponding to the nominal value for each operational condition. Since the thermal power absorbed by the power block decreases when the ambient temperature increases, the minimum cycle temperature can be lower, and the decrease in efficiency is reduced. This is important in supercritical CO₂ cycles, as efficiency decreases considerably when the temperature moves away from the critical temperature, especially since the main compressor pressure at the inlet is optimized only for the nominal low cycle temperature.

5) The maximum salt mass flow rate through the TES corresponds to the maximum salt mass flow rate through the receiver. This is an important difference compared to the PTC-CSP considered for the HRB-propane. The key difference lies in the fact that, in the case of the PTC-CSP, the HTF mass flow rate through the TES is limited by the size of the HTF/molten salts heat exchanger, while in the central receiver CSP, there is no limitation since the same fluid contained in the TES is driven through the receiver.

4.4.2 Off-design models

sCO₂-RB Power block and cooling system

The following criteria are assumed:

1) The Stodola-Frügel Law is used to describe the behaviour of the turbine at part load [37] (Equation 4.24).

2) Constant volumetric flow in the recompressor is considered (Equation 4.25).

3) It is assumed that the main compressor always operates at its efficiency design value since it can change its rotation speed.

4) The turbine and recompressor efficiency at off-design conditions is reduced from the nominal value as the capacity moves away from the design value. Equation 4.26 relates the turbomachinery efficiency to its capacity. Equation 4.27 describes the turbomachinery capacity from the mass flow rate, the pressure, and the inlet temperature.

5) The UA factor values at off-design conditions decrease as the mass flow rate of the fluid with the highest thermal resistance also does (Equation 4.28). For the main heater, the mass flow rate corresponds to the HTF while for the condenser it corresponds to the air. The q exponent value is 0.8 for the main heater and the recuperators while for the cooler is 0.625. In the first case, the exponent coincides with the Reynolds number of the Dittus & Boelter correlation. In the second case, the exponent coincides with the Reynolds number of Weir correlation for the external heat transfer coefficient for finned tubes.

6) Pressure drop fraction values are the same as in the design condition.

7) The temperature difference between the turbine inlet and the HTF main heater inlet always takes the design value. That means that if the HTF temperature at the main heater inlet decrease 1 °C below the design value, the turbine inlet temperature also does.

$$\dot{m} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{T_{inlet}}{p_{inlet}^2 - p_{outlet}^2}} = K_{stod} \quad (4.24)$$

$$x_{rc} = x_{des} \cdot \frac{\dot{m}_{co2,des}}{\dot{m}_{co2}} \cdot \frac{\rho_{7,off}}{\rho_{7,des}} \quad (4.25)$$

$$\eta_{tbm} = \eta_{tbm_{dis}} - \left| 1 - \frac{\phi_{tbm}}{\phi_{tbm_{dis}}} \right| / 3 \quad (4.26)$$

$$\phi = \dot{m} \frac{\sqrt{T}}{P} \quad (4.27)$$

$$UA_{off} = UA_{dis} \cdot \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\dot{m}_{dis}} \right)^q \quad (4.28)$$

The off-design power cycle algorithm follows an iterative process. The process diagram considered is shown in [Figure 4.10-4.11](#). The code has two nested iterative processes: First, the off-design power cycle is solved considering an initial low-cycle temperature 10 °C higher than the ambient temperature, except if the ambient temperature is lower than 22 °C in which case the low-cycle temperature is fixed to 32 °C. Additionally, four iterative variables are considered: the turbine inlet pressure, P_4 , the CO₂ inlet temperature at the main heater, T_3 , the CO₂ inlet temperature in the high-temperature recuperator at the high-pressure side, T_{2pp} , and the recompression bypass fraction, x_{rc} . These four variables are initially estimated based on the design values and are recalculated during the off-design power cycle solving process. The turbine inlet pressure is recalculated using the Stodola constant. The CO₂ inlet temperature at the main heater is recalculated using the Newton-Raphson method in the high-temperature recuperator, considering the UA factor instead of the pinch point as part of the minimizing function. The recompression bypass fraction is recalculated assuming constant volumetric flow in this component. The CO₂ inlet temperature in the high-temperature recuperator at the high-pressure side is recalculated establishing an energy/mass balance between the flow that comes from the recompressor and the one that comes from the low temperature recuperator. Once all the points of the power cycle are solved and the iterative variables converge, the cooler consumption is determined. Before this step, it is necessary to check whether the ambient temperature is higher than 25 °C or lower. If it is lower, the initially estimated low cycle temperature is correct, and the air mass flow rate and outlet air temperature can be calculated using the Newton-Raphson method, considering the corresponding UA factor. It should be noted that the UA factor depends on the air mass flow rate so an initial value should be estimated and iterated until the convergence is achieved. If the ambient temperature is higher than 25 °C, the air mass flow rate is fixed at its nominal value, and the low cycle temperature is recalculated. This recalculated value (which should be lower than the initial estimated) is then used to restart the entire power block calculation process.

Figure 4.11 Off design reference power block model process diagram

PTES-sCO₂-RB power block

The following operation criteria are considered:

1°) The charging and discharging compressors drive always the CO₂ mass flow rate nominal value so they might rotate at different speeds. In this way, the low temperature recuperator is better balanced in off design conditions.

2°) The water pump always drives the nominal mass flow rate value.

3°) The temperature of the hot water tank must not exceed 220 °C, so the charging compressor will be able to adjust the CO₂ bypass fraction to prevent it.

The code process diagram for the charging process at off-design conditions is shown in Figure 4.12. Two new variables are initially estimated and iterated in this case in comparison with the design case: The inlet temperature of the heated fluid in the low-temperature recuperator, T_{2b} , and the recompression bypass factor, x_{rc} . The code process diagram for the discharging process is shown in Figure 4.13. The code related to the cooler off-design operation is not shown, as it is the same as that presented in Figure 4.11. However, the air mass flow rate driven by the cooler fans for ambient temperatures higher than 25 °C corresponds to the nominal value for each operation (charge and discharge), with each having its own distinct nominal value.

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Figure 4.12 Charging off-design power block algorithm diagram

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Figure 4.13 Discharging off-design power block algorithm diagram

Solar field/receiver:

The off-design operating conditions for various input parameters are used to generate matrices for interpolation during each step of the annual simulation. The model for calculating the total thermal power absorbed by the HTF in the annual simulation is:

$$\dot{Q}_{HTF} = \alpha \cdot A_{sf} \cdot DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} - \dot{Q}_{th,loss} \quad (4.29)$$

where η_{opt} (elevation, azimuth) and $\dot{Q}_{th,loss}$ (elevation, azimuth, DNI, T_{amb} , $T_{HTF,in}$)

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The solar field heliostats area (A_{sf}) is a result given by SolarPilot after the design point sizing. The absorptivity (α) and the direct normal irradiance (DNI) are known parameters, and the optical efficiency and the thermal losses are the values that must be interpolated. The optical efficiency depends only in the elevation and azimuth angles. The thermal losses depend on the elevation and azimuth angles, the direct normal irradiance, the ambient temperature and on the inlet molten salts temperature of the receiver. The outer molten salts temperature of the receiver takes a constant value (565 °C).

The off-design pump consumption is also obtained through the interpolation of matrices. The same methodology used for the heat loss calculation has been considered. The interpolation model used in the annual simulation for both optical efficiency and thermal losses in the receiver is explained below.

Two matrices have been considered depending on the input elevation angle value. Both are 6x5 matrix in which each row represents a different elevation angle and each column a different azimuth angle. There have been obtained using SolarPilot.

The parameters range of the two matrices are:

First matrix: Elevation (°) → [5,30] in 5° steps. Azimuth (°) → [0,300] in 60° steps

Second matrix: Elevation (°) → [30,80] in 10° steps. Azimuth (°) → [0,300] in 60° steps

Polynomial interpolation has been used to determine the optical efficiency for a given elevation and azimuth angle. Initially, the optical efficiency is calculated for each azimuth value of the matrix using 6th-degree polynomials, where the independent variable is the input elevation angle. There exists only a single polynomial for each azimuth angle value of the matrix. From the obtained optical efficiency values, a 4th-degree polynomial is generated. The final optical efficiency value is determined by inputting the given azimuth angle into this polynomial.

To calculate the elevation and azimuth angle for each time step of the simulation, next equations are used. The Time Zone for Spain is GMT+1. The longitude and latitude correspond with that of the location and were shown in Table 4.3. n is the day number within the annual count, λ is the latitude, δ is the declination and ω the solar angle.

$$Solar\ time = UTC\ time + \frac{length}{15} + \frac{correc}{60} \quad (4.30)$$

$$UTC\ time = Local\ Time - Time\ Zone \quad (4.31)$$

$$correc = 229.2 \cdot (0.000075 + 0.001868 \cdot \cos(B) - 0.032077 \cdot \sin(B) - 0.014615 \cdot \cos(2B) - 0.04089 \cdot \sin(2B)) \quad (4.32)$$

$$B = (n - 1) \cdot \frac{360}{365} \quad (4.33)$$

$$\delta = 23.45 \cdot \sin\left(360 \cdot \frac{284 + n}{365}\right) \quad (4.34)$$

$$\omega = 15 \cdot (Solar\ time - 12) \quad (4.35)$$

$$elevation = \sin^{-1}[\sin(\delta) \cdot \sin(\lambda) + \cos(\delta) \cdot \cos(\lambda) \cdot \cos(\omega)] \quad (4.36)$$

$$azimut = \cos^{-1}\left[\frac{[\sin(\delta) \cdot \cos(\lambda) - \cos(\omega) \cdot \cos(\delta) \cdot \sin(\lambda)]}{\cos(elevation)}\right] \quad (4.37)$$

Receiver thermal losses

Different matrices have been obtained for various values of DNI. Each matrix depends on the elevation and azimuth angle like in the optical efficiency case. The matrix values have been obtained using the receiver model considering as input the incident optical flux maps given by SolarPilot.

Linear interpolation over the matrices has been used to obtain the thermal losses in the receiver, because the heat losses do not vary much (the greatest difference found in the matrix values is approximately 3.5 MW).

The variation in ambient temperature and inlet receiver temperature does not significantly affect the heat losses (under 1 MW), so to simplify the calculation, simple approximation models have been considered, with a maximum error below 0.2 MW. The models are shown respectively in Equation 4.38 and Equation 4.39. They are applied once the heat losses have been interpolated from the matrices that depend on the elevation angle, azimuth angle, and DNI.

$$\dot{Q}_{th,loss_new}\{kW\} = \dot{Q}_{th,loss} - (T_{amb}\{^{\circ}C\} - 25) \cdot 30.29 \quad (4.38)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{th,loss_new} = \dot{Q}_{th,loss} \cdot \frac{T_{mean,HTF}\{^{\circ}C\}}{482.5} \quad (4.39)$$

The minimum mass flow rate is 5 % of the nominal flow rate. This is a conservative value that avoids excessively low flow rates (Re < 4000) in the receiver streams. The maximum flow rate is 20 % higher than the design value.

TES

Thermal losses of the storage tanks are calculated at every time step using Equation 4.40. This equation is explained in [38] and is based on a dimensionless analysis performed on tanks that have the same diameter-to-height ratio as ANDASOL I tanks [39]. *TL* stands for the tank level, $\dot{Q}_{losses,full}$ and $\dot{Q}_{losses,empty}$ are respectively the thermal losses when the reference tank is full, and it is at its minimum level. The heat losses are scaled by considering the ratio between the tank diameter and that of the reference one.

$$\dot{Q}_{losses} = [TL \cdot \dot{Q}_{losses,full} + (1 - TL) \cdot \dot{Q}_{losses,empty}] \cdot \frac{D}{D_{ref}} \quad (4.40)$$

4.4.3 Startup models

Receiver startup

The objective is to create a model for the annual simulation that allows for calculating the duration and energy consumed once the receiver begins to absorb energy.

In commercial plants, molten salt receivers drain the salts into the headers and from there into the tanks. Ref. [40] found that in an experimental cavity receiver and in the absence of solar radiation, molten salts freeze in the receiver in less than 25 minutes if not drained. In an external receiver, this time can be much shorter. Additionally, despite the insulation of the headers, it was necessary to activate the heat trace in the experiments to prevent freezing in them. This means

that salt drainage is not only done during the night but also during transient periods with cloud cover.

At startup, the empty tubes of the receiver are preheated with a uniform heat flux to prevent the salts from freezing once they start circulating. Ref. [41] developed an algorithm considering different incident heat fluxes depending on the startup time and wind speed, so that the process can be completed in 15 minutes, reaching a tube temperature of 380 °C. Ref. [42] also established the electrical energy consumed by the heat trace in the Solar Two receiver headers for a rapid heat up to 288 °C: 550 kWh if the receiver shut down during 16 hours and 700 kWh if the receiver shut down during 300 hours. This energy is not a linear function of time but is asymptotic, with the required energy being the same after 30 hours of shutdown.

The developed model in this work considers that the startup lasts one time step of the simulation (half an hour) and consists of three procedures: Preheating the receiver, preheating the headers, and establishing the salt flow in the tower. For the receiver preheating, it has been assumed that the average optical flux is 20 kW/m². It has been verified that, with this value, the time to reach a tube temperature of 380 °C is less than 15 minutes for any ambient temperature reached during the typical year with a constant wind speed of 5 m/s. If the optical flux does not reach this value, the receiver will remain off. To determine the electrical energy consumed by the headers, a curve has been generated from the data in [42], which were explained earlier. The curve is shown in Figure 4.14. Finally, to establish the salt flow in the tower, it is assumed that the pump must provide enough pressure to overcome the pressure losses in the receiver and headers (Equation 4.20 and Equation 4.21) and to elevate the salts to the top of the tower. Thus, Equation 4.22 that belongs to a steady state is replaced by Equation 4.41. The pump consumption during startup will be considerably higher because there is no downward flow of salts through the tower to assist the upward flow from the pump. It is assumed that the pump consumes energy throughout the entire time step.

$$\Delta P_{height} = H_{tower} \cdot g \cdot \rho_{HTF,in} \quad (4.41)$$

Figure 4.14 Electrical energy consumed by the headers heat trace respect the number of shutdown hours

Power startup thermal energy

The time duration constraint is 30 minutes and the thermal energy that must be supplied from the solar field, or the TES, or by a combination of both, is a 20 % of the thermal energy

demanded by the PB during 1 h at nominal conditions. If the available energy is not sufficient to start the cycle within half an hour, the power cycle will remain off during that time-step.

4.4.4 Systems coupling

The methodology used to couple the power block with the other systems of the CSP plant is similar than used in the HRB-propane case: power block results are obtained interpolating between different off-design points contained in certain matrices, rather than solving the entire code for each particular point. In this way some time is saved during the simulation. Different power block matrices are obtained depending on the PTES is off or on. For the case that the PTES is off, there are only two different variables to define the off-design operation points: Ambient temperature and salts temperature at the inlet of the main heater. Because of that, only one matrix is needed to define all the possible off-design operation points of the power block. In the case that the PTES is on, the power block off-design operation is defined by three variables depending on the PTES is charging or discharging. In the case that the PTES is charging, in addition to the ambient temperature and the temperature of the salts at the main heater inlet, the temperature of the cold-water tank of the PTES must be also considered. In the case of discharge, the temperature of the hot water PTES tank is considered instead the cold one.

First, a preliminary value of the heat absorbed by the receiver is calculated for each time-step from the heat losses and optical efficiency matrices. To do that, inlet and outlet nominal receiver temperatures are considered. Once these values are calculated, solar field start-up processes can be set depending on the power heat absorbed. Then, a mixed-integer linear algorithm is performed to set the operation schedule that maximizes the incomes for each time step. First a simplified model with a 48-hour time horizon is considered assuming that the temperature of the tanks at any time-step is equal to the temperature value at the beginning of the time horizon. After that, a detailed model that considers the temperature variations for each time step is performed, considering the calculated schedule. This model runs only during the first 24 hours scheduled. Then, the algorithm is performed again scheduling the next 48 hours, and considering the value obtained from the detailed model as the initial value.

The mixed-integer linear algorithm considered is similar that was shown in previous sections, while the process diagrams related to the operations of the detailed model are shown below. The fact that the storage fluid of the TES is the same as the HTF avoids the need to incorporate a heat exchanger, simplifying the codes compared to the HRB-propane case.

Power production and charging TES (SF→PB+TES):

Only two loops are considered. The first one is used to determine the convergence of the inlet receiver temperature, since it depends on the solar power absorbed and, therefore, on the mass flow rate of the salts. The second one assures that the salts mass flow rate value does not exceed 20 % the nominal value.

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Figure 4.15 (SF→PB+TES)

Power production and discharging TES: (TES+SF→PB):

Only one loop is considered. It is used to determine the convergence of the temperature at the inlet of the main heater, since it depends on the outlet temperature of the TES and in the salts mass flow rate.

Figure 4.16 (TES+SF→PB)

Power production without solar radiation (TES →PB):

Figure 4.17 TES→PB

Charging without production (SF →TES):

In this case, the power block is off, and the solar energy is only used to heat the TES. Unlike the HRB-propane case, there is no limitation on the mass flow rate of salts that can be stored, matching the maximum mass flow rate of salts that can circulate through the receiver.

Figure 4.18 SF→TES

4.5 Cost correlations and figures of merit

4.5.1 Cost correlations

The references of the cost correlations used are summarized in Table 4.8. All costs are accounted in \$. Water pump and motor are not considered due the negligible pressure drop in the water/sCO₂ heat exchanger.

Table 4.8 Components cost correlation references

Component	Reference
Recuperators, dry cooler, turbine, compressors, gear box, generator	[43]
Main heater	[44]
Compressor motor	[45]
Water/sCO ₂ heat exchanger	[46]
Solar field (including receiver) and TES	[47]
Pressurized water tanks	[48]

The recuperator and dry cooler purchase cost correlations are shown in Equation 4.42 and Equations 4.43. Pressure, temperature and UA factor values are within the validity range of the correlation. A 5 % and 20 % increment costs are considered respectively due indirect costs.

$$Cost_{rec} = 49.45 \cdot UA^{0.7544} \quad (4.42)$$

$$1.6 \cdot 10^5 < UA(W/K) < 2.15 \cdot 10^8$$

$$Cost_{cooler} = 32.88 \cdot UA^{0.75} \quad (4.43)$$

$$8.6 \cdot 10^5 < UA(W/K) < 7.5 \cdot 10^7$$

Main heater heat exchanger purchase cost [44] correlation is shown in Equation 4.44.

$$Cost_{MH} = 14.7 \cdot UA^{0.8778} \quad (4.44)$$

A sizing of the water/CO₂ heat exchanger has been performed due to the absence of cost correlations referenced to the UA factor for these specific fluids heat exchange in the scientific literature. Given the high pressure, a PCHE (Printed Circuit Heat Exchanger) has been considered. The Gnielinsky correlation has been used to calculate the heat transfer coefficient inside the channels. The global heat transfer coefficient considers only convective heat transfer. This method has been employed in other works such as [12,49,50]. A standard channel with a 2 mm width has been considered. The pitch between the channels has been calculated based on the mechanical stress limitations of [51]. Carbon steel, with a stress limitation of 120 MPa, is considered. The heat exchanger consists of modules measuring 1.5 m in length, 0.6 m in width and 0.6 m in height. The modules can be welded either in parallel or series to meet the required area and pressure drop objectives. To calculate the total cost of the heat exchanger, including installation, a unit cost of 40 \$/kg and a material density of 8000 kg/m³ have been considered [46].

Turbine cost is estimated from Equation 4.45. A 20 % cost increment is also considered due indirect costs.

$$Cost_{turbine} = (1 + 1.106 \cdot 10^{-4}) \cdot (T_{max} - 550 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}) \cdot 182600 \cdot \dot{W}^{0.5561} \quad (4.45)$$

$$10 < \dot{W}(\text{MW}) < 750$$

Compressors cost is estimated from Equation 4.46. A 20 % cost increment is also considered due indirect costs.

$$Cost_{compressor} = 1230000 \cdot \dot{W}^{0.3992} \quad (4.46)$$

$$1.5 < \dot{W}(\text{MW}) < 200$$

Gearboxes and generators costs are estimated from Equation 4.47 and Equation 4.48 respectively. A 20 % cost increment is also considered due indirect costs.

$$Cost_{gearbox} = 177200 \cdot W^{0.2434} \quad (4.47)$$

$$Cost_{generator} = 108900 \cdot W^{0.5463} \quad (4.48)$$

The motors cost to drive the main, charging and discharging compressors are calculated using Equation 4.49 where the characteristic dimension (X) is the power consumption. Since the characteristic dimension of the equipment exceeds the maximum value of the validity range, the purchase cost is first calculated using the maximum value of the range and then the six-tenth rule is used (Equation 4.50). X_{mv} is the purchase cost considering the maximum characteristic factor value of the interval specified in the reference and X is the characteristic factor value calculated of the equipment. The total cost of the component includes indirect costs that are evaluated through the constants B_1 and B_2 using Equation 4.51. The constant values are shown in Table 4.9.

$$\log_{10} Cost_{Motor} = C_{11} + C_{12} \log_{10}(X) + C_{13} [\log_{10}(X)]^2 \quad (4.49)$$

$$Cost_{equip} = Cost_{equip.mv} \cdot \left(\frac{X}{X_{mv}} \right)^{0.6} \quad (4.50)$$

$$Cost_{BM} = Cost_{motor} \cdot (B_1 + B_2) \quad (4.51)$$

Table 4.9 Motor coefficients

	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{13}	C_{21}	C_{22}	C_{23}	B_1	B_2	F_M
Motor	2.9508	1.0688	-0.1315	0	0	0	0.75	0.75	1

The cost of the solar field is calculated using Equation 4.52 and depends on the total area of the heliostats. The cost of the tower is calculated using Equation 4.53 and depends on its height, the receiver, and the heliostat, The area of the receiver is calculated using Equation 4.54 and depends on the value of its surface area, considering it as a cylinder with height and diameter equal to those of the receiver. The cost of the TES system depends on the total energy (kWh), that can store. It is calculated using Equation 4.55. This energy value is twelve times the thermal power absorbed by the power block in nominal conditions during 1 hour, as the TES capacity is 12 hours and the solar multiple value is 2.

$$Cost_{sf} = 143 \cdot A_{hel} \quad (4.52)$$

$$Cost_{Tower} = 3 \cdot 10^6 \cdot e^{0.0113 \cdot (H_{tow} - H_{rec}/2 + H_{hel}/2)} \quad (4.53)$$

$$Cost_{Rec} = 103 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{A_{rec}}{1571} \right)^{0.7} \quad (4.54)$$

$$Cost_{TES} = 22 \cdot E_{alm} \quad (4.55)$$

Ref. [48] is used to calculate the tanks cost. The purchased cost is calculated using Equation 4.56 where w is the weight of the emptied tank considering a carbon steel density of 7840 kg/m³. The total cost is calculated using Equation 4.57.

$$Cost_{equip} = -2500 + 200 \cdot w^{0.6} \quad (4.56)$$

$$C_{BM} = Cost_{equip} \cdot 4 \quad (4.57)$$

All costs have been expressed in €, so a conversion rate of 1€=1.05 USD representative of the 2022–2023 period is used. However, first, the costs from each correlation are updated using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI). The CEPCI coefficients per reference are shown in Table 4.10.

$$Cost_{equip_{2022}} = Cost_{equip_{ref}} \cdot \frac{CEPCI_{2022}}{CEPCI_{ref}} \quad (4.58)$$

Table 4.10 CEPCI coefficients for each reference

Year 2022	[43]	[44]	[45]	[46]	[47]	[48]
798.7	567.5	798.7	398.7	708.8	798.7	478.6

4.5.2 Figures of merit and economic scenario

Same figures of merit and economic scenario as in previous sections are considered. The Levelized cost of energy (LCOE) is calculated using Equation 4.59, where LC_{INV} , $LC_{O\&M}$ and $E_{net,year}$ are respectively the levelized costs of investment, of operation and maintenance and the yearly net energy production.

$$LCOE = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M}}{E_{net,year}} \quad (4.59)$$

The cost-income ratio (r_{CI}) is the sum of the levelized cost of investment (LC_{INV}) and operation and maintenance ($LC_{O\&M}$) divided by the levelized incomes (LI). Equation 4.60

$$r_{CI} = \frac{LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M}}{LI} \quad (4.60)$$

The profits over incomes ratio (r_{PI}) is calculated using Equation 4.61.

$$r_{PI} = \frac{LI - (LC_{INV} + LC_{O\&M})}{LI} \quad (4.61)$$

These two figures of merit are also considered since CSP has been optimized to maximize the revenues and not the annual energy production.

In Table 4.11 the economic scenario used to perform the financial calculations is shown.

Table 4.11 Economic scenario

Solar field O&M cost [37]	9 €/year · m ²
Yearly O&M equipment costs percentage of Inv. [37]	1 % Inv
Interest rate	4 %
Inflation	3.6 %
Amortization years	35

4.6 Results

4.6.1 Reference CSP

Table 4.12 shows the main results in nominal conditions for the two cases proposed for the reference configuration: The first one corresponds to a compressor inlet pressure value of 83 bar with a bypass fraction of 0.35, and the second one to a pressure value of 92 bar with a bypass fraction of 0.33. In both cases, the same receiver, solar field and TES sizing is considered. The first one achieves a higher nominal efficiency since this pair of values (pressure and bypass fraction) have been optimized for a compressor temperature inlet of 35 °C whereas the second case has been optimized for 45 °C. In both cases, the TES and solar field have the same size.

Table 4.12 Results for the two cases of the reference CSP

	Case 1	Case 2
Nominal power (MW)	100	100
Efficiency (%)	45.5	44.5
Fan power (MW)	2.9	3
Receiver pump power (MW)	1	1
Net power (MW)	97.9	97.8
Nominal thermal power (PB+TES) (MW)	440	450
Receiver efficiency (%)	86.7	86.7
Optical efficiency (%)	65	65
Number of heliostats	6323	6323
Reflective area (m ²)	915334	915334

Table 4.13 shows the thermodynamic parameters of the points for each power block case and Figure 4.19 shows the T-s diagram for each case. On the other hand, Table 4.14 shows the main characteristics parameter values to estimate the PB components costs, and Table 4.15 shows the PB components costs for each case. The cost of the turbomachinery in Case 2 is lower due to the reduced compression ratio. However, the cost of the heat exchangers has increased, particularly in the main heater. In this last one, the cost increase is attributed to a reduction in the

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pinch point temperature difference—from 5 °C in *Case 1* to 2 °C in *Case 2*. Finally, the total cost of the PB in *Case 2* is higher than in *Case 1*.

Table 4.13 Thermodynamic parameters of the points for each power block case

Case 1					Case 2				
	T (°C)	P (bar)	h (kJ/kg)	s (J/kgK)	T (°C)	P (bar)	h (kJ/kg)	s (J/kgK)	
1	35	83	316.5	1376.5	35	92	296.5	1307.1	
2	74.9	260	346.1	1385.5	63.8	260	321.9	1314.9	
2p	190.1	260	565.3	1935	159.9	260	517	1827	
2pp	190.1	260	565.4	1935.2	161.4	260	519.6	1833.1	
3	394.7	252.2	837.6	2422.9	398	252.2	841.7	2429	
4	560	247.2	1044.5	2710.8	560	247.1	1044.5	2710.8	
5	432.8	86.4	904.7	2731.1	444.4	95.8	917.2	2729.2	
6	195.1	84.7	632.4	2265.0	166.4	93.9	594.9	2164.7	
7	80.7	83	489.9	1917.2	71.5	92	464.2	1830.0	
8	190.3	260	565.6	1935.7	164.7	260	525.0	1845.5	

Figure 4.19 T-s diagram for each case ("Case 1": black, 'Case 2': red)

Table 4.14 Characteristic parameter values of the components of the PB for each case

	Case 1	Case 2
High temperature recuperator UA (MW/K)	14.5	15
Low temperature recuperator UA (MW/K)	21.9	24.2
Condenser UA (MW/K)	7.9	7.3
Main heater UA (MW/K)	41.1	64
Main compressor consumption (MW)	20.4	18.9
Recompressor consumption (MW)	28.2	22.2
Turbine mechanical power (MW)	148.6	141

Table 4.15 PB cost estimation for each case

	Case 1	Case 2
High temperature recuperator (M€)	17.6	18
Low temperature recuperator (M€)	24	25.9
Cooler (M€)	7.9	7.8
Main heater (M€)	67.5	99.6
Main compressor (M€)	6.6	6.4
Recompressor (M€)	7.5	6.8
Turbine (M€)	4.8	4.7
Main compressor motor (M€)	1.1	1
Generator+gearbox (M€)	3	3
Total (M€)	139	171.8

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Figure 4.20 shows the distribution of the operating points during the simulation, considering the compressor inlet temperature and the power block efficiency achieved for the two cases proposed for the reference configuration. It can be observed that the efficiency for the first case drops faster for high temperatures than the one it was optimized for 35 °C. For temperatures higher than 36.5 °C, the second case shows a higher efficiency than the first case.

Figure 4.20 Off design efficiency points for different main compressor inlet temperatures for case 1 and case 2

For the second case, the efficiency drops for temperatures above 40 °C, since it was optimized for that value. However, the rate of temperature decrease is lower than in the first case. This agrees with the lower variation in the thermophysical properties of sCO₂ at different pseudocritical points, as stated in various studies [52,53].

The highest efficiency decrement considering a 1 °C increment is 2.2 % for the first case and 0.75 % for the second one. Both are higher than those obtained in [12], since, as indicated in the introduction, that study assumes that the minimum cycle temperature increases with the ambient temperature.. This indicate that there is some room for improving the performance by adjusting this pressure.

Table 4.16 shows the main simulation results for both cases. The thermal energy supplied to the PB is calculated as the solar energy absorbed minus the solar field startup thermal energy, thermal storage losses, and PB startup thermal energy. In both cases, the same value is reached, as the receiver and solar field have the same size.

A slightly higher gross and net energy production is achieved in the first case since the yearly efficiency is also higher. The same happens with the total revenues. This is supported by Figure 4.20, which shows that there are more operating points where the efficiency is higher in the first case compared to the second case (approximately 70 %). This can be explained by the fact that a considerable number of points have an ambient temperature below 22 °C, at which the compressor low cycle temperature is fixed at 32 °C. This coincides with the maximum efficiency difference between the two cases.

On the other hand, the average power produced in the second case is higher than in the first one. This is due to at higher ambient temperatures, the efficiency is less reduced for the second case, that means that higher power production values are achieved. This can be observed in the net power range minimum value.

Regarding the cooler operation, the minimum consumption occurs at the lowest ambient temperature, 1.4 °C, as for ambient temperatures below 22 °C, the low cycle temperature is fixed

at 32 °C. On the other hand, the maximum consumption occurs at the highest ambient temperature, 43.2 °C, as the air mass flow rate is maintained at the design value. It should be considered that, with this operation pattern, the minimum temperature of the cycle achieved is very similar to the ambient one, that avoids a high decrease in the efficiency.

Regarding the receiver pump operation, it can be observed that there is a considerable variation between minimum and maximum consumption value. This is due the minimum value is obtained during normal operation and the maximum one during a receiver startup operation. In this last case, since the circulation of the salts is not established along the ascending and descending collectors of the tower, the pump must overcome by itself the pressure required to raise the salt flow to the top of the tower.

Table 4.16 Annual simulation results for the two cases of the reference CSP

	Case 1	Case 2
Revenues (M€)	71.96	71.25
Solar energy absorbed (GWh)	935.2	935.2
Solar field startup thermal energy (GWh)	19.4	19.4
Thermal Storage losses (GWh)	7.4	6.8
PB startup thermal energy (GWh)	20.3	21.2
Thermal energy delivered to the PB (GWh)	888.1	887.8
Gross energy production (GWh)	395.7	391.5
Yearly efficiency (%)	44.56	44.1
Cooling consumption (GWh)	9.8	9.9
HTF pump consumption (GWh)	3.1	3
Heat trace consumption (GWh)	0.2	0.2
Net energy production (GWh)	382.6	378.4
N° hours PB	4086	3990
Average power produced (MW)	96.9	98.1
Average net power produced (MW)	93.7	94.8
Net power range (MW)	68.3/100.8	71.3/99.7
Cooling system power range (MW)	0.9/3.1	0.9/3.2
Pump system range (MW)	0.05/13.8	0.04/11
PB efficiency range (%)	36.7/45.6	38.6/44.6
Lower PB temperature range (°C)	32/45.2	32/47.7
Ambient temperature range (°C)	1.4/43.2	1.4/43.2

Finally, [Table 4.17](#) shows the economic results. Both cases have a similar LCOE, profits over incomes and cost over incomes ratio although for case one is slightly higher favourable. The solar field system accounts for more than 50 % of the total investment, which aligns with the value provided by [2] This system includes the heliostats field, the receiver and the tower.

Table 4.17 Economic results for the two reference CSP cases

	Case 1	Case 2
INV _{SF-TOT} (M€)	236	
INV _{PB} (M€)	139	171.8
INV _{TES} (M€)	58	
LC _{INV} (M€)	23.2	25
LI (M€)	126.1	124.7
LC _{OM} (M€)	22	22.6
LCOE (€/MWh)	118	130.6
r_{CI}	0.36	0.38
r_{PI}	0.64	0.62

4.6.2 PTES-HX pinch point selection

The case with a main compressor pressure inlet of 83 bar is considered for the analysis. The water/CO₂ heat exchanger temperature difference in the hot side (10 °C) and the pinch point value at nominal condition (5 °C) have been selected to achieve an off-design temperature difference at each terminal that is not excessively large. In this way, the temperature difference in the hot side during charging is not too high. This is shown in Figure 4.21. The first one represents the T-Q diagram of the water/CO₂ heat exchanger for the design condition during charging. The pinch point is achieved around the middle of the heat exchanger while the temperature difference at both ends is similar.

For comparative purposes, a second alternative has been considered in which the selected pinch point value (5 °C) is achieved in the hot side of the heat exchanger during the charging. Figure 4.22 represents that in that case the temperature profiles diverge and the temperature difference in the cold side is too large. In consequence, during the discharging, the temperature difference in the hot side is also high, and the temperature achieved by the CO₂ during discharging is considerably lower than in the first case. The results for both alternatives are presented in Table 4.18. While the gross power values obtained in both alternatives are similar, this is not true for the thermal power absorbed during the discharge operation, which is higher in *Alternative 2*. This happens because the temperature reached by the CO₂ flow passing through the PTES heat exchanger is considerably lower than in the first case (155 °C vs 168 °C). As a result, the efficiency of the charge and discharge cycle is higher in the first alternative than in the second one. On the other hand, it can be observed that both the UA factor and the mass flow rate of water need to be higher in first alternative.

It should be noted, however, that the temperature of the cold reservoir during charging does not match that of the discharge, since for the charging process the nominal condition has been considered. To make a more effective comparison, the temperature of the cold reservoir during charging should match that of the discharge. This ensures that the same amount of heat is exchanged in both operations. Table 4.19 shows the results for both alternatives, taking this consideration into account. It can be observed that, although the temperature of the hot reservoir in the second alternative is higher than in the first alternative, the CO₂ temperature achieved is lower due to the high temperature difference at the hot terminal (close to 30 °C). Consequently, the efficiency for the first alternative remains higher than for the second one.

Figure 4.21 Temperature profiles for charging (left) and discharging (right). First alternative

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Figure 4.22 Temperature profiles for charging (left) and discharging (right). Second alternative

Table 4.18 Main results for charging/discharging operation at nominal conditions for two cases with different temperature values in the PTES-HX

	First alternative		Second alternative	
	Charging	Discharging	Charging	Discharging
ΔT at the cold end (°C)	15	1	40	0
ΔT at the hot end (°C)	10	9	5	30
Pinch point (°C)	5	1	5	0
Gross power (MW)	82.8	116.6	82.8	116
Cooler power (MW)	0.9	5.5	0.9	5.5
PB thermal power (MW)	219.9	227.9	219.9	235.5
Cold water temperature (°C)	59.5	76.1	37	75.2
Hot water temperature (°C)	180.3	180.3	185.3	185.3
CO ₂ bypass high temperature (°C)	190.3	168.9	190.3	155.8
PTES HX UA (MW/K)	11.3	11.3	7.4	7.4
Water mass flow rate (kg/s)	159.2	159.2	129.8	129.8
Efficiency (%)	44.53		43.65	

Table 4.19 Main results for charging/discharging operation considering the same water tank temperatures for two cases with different temperature values in the PTES-HX

	First alternative		Second alternative	
	Charging	Discharging	Charging	Discharging
Gross Power (MW)	81	116.9	79.4	116.7
Cooler Power (MW)	0.9	5.5	0.9	5.5
PB Thermal power (MW)	217.2	224.4	214.9	229
Cold water temperature (°C)	76.3	76.3	75.1	75.1
Hot water temperature (°C)	187.2	187.2	199.7	199.7
CO ₂ bypass high temperature (°C)	198.5	179.2	206	168.9
PTES HX UA (MW/K)	11.27	11.27	7.46	7.46
Water mass flow rate (kg/s)	159.16	159.16	129.8	129.8
Efficiency (%)	44.81		44.18	

4.6.3 Operation of sCO₂-RB-PTES

Table 4.20 compares the main results of the reference configuration with those of the charging and discharging PTES processes for *Case 1* (83 bar and 0.35 bypass fraction) and *Case 2* (92 bar and 0.33 bypass fraction). An inlet temperature of 35 °C is considered for the main compressor. Additionally, in both scenarios, a temperature difference of 10 °C on the hot side of the water/CO₂ heat exchanger and a pinch point value of 5 °C under nominal conditions are considered. The main advantage of *Case 2* over *Case 1* is the lower temperature required in the hot water storage tank, which allows for a reduction in tank pressure and, consequently, in the

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required wall thickness. On the other hand, the amount of water that needs to be stored for one hour of operation is higher, so a more detailed analysis would be necessary to determine whether an overall cost reduction could be achieved.

Table 4.20. Main sCO₂-RB operation results at main compressor inlet temperature of 25 °C for *Case 1* and *Case 2* (including reference and charging/discharging cycle)

	Case 1			Case 2		
	Reference	Charging	Discharging	Reference	Charging	Discharging
Gross Power (MW)	100	81	116.9	100	85.3	112.8
Cooler Power (MW)	2.9	0.9	5.5	3	1.12	5.5
PB Thermal power (MW)	220	217.2	224.4	224.7	222	228
Cold water temperature (°C)	-	76.3	76.3	-	67.7	67.7
Hot water temperature (°C)	-	187.2	187.2	-	160.6	160.6
CO ₂ bypass high temperature (°C)	190.3	198.5	179.2	167.4	171.8	156.8
PTES HX UA (MW/K)	-	11.27	11.27	-	11.7	11.7
Water mass flow rate (kg/s)	-	159.16	159.16	-	176.3	176.3
Efficiency (%)	45.5		44.81	44.5		44.02

Since the revenues of the original configuration are higher in *Case 1* than in *Case 2*, and it is not clear that the PTES profitability for *Case 2* would exceed that of *Case 1*, only *Case 1* is considered from this point onward, while *Case 2* will be study in future works.

Table 4.21 shows the main results of the sCO₂-RB for the reference case (PTES off) and the case where the PTES performs a charge/discharge cycle, with the main compressor inlet temperature set to 40 °C. Table 4.22 shows the CO₂ mass flow rate fraction values through each component. There is 4 % efficiency drop in the reference case compared to the nominal condition, even though the difference in compressor inlet temperature is only 5 °C. This is mainly due to the increased consumption of the main compressor, as the inlet temperature is higher than the pseudocritical point selected for the nominal conditions. The gross power produced in the reference case is reduced around 25 % respect the nominal condition. This is due both to the loss of efficiency and to the reduction in thermal power absorbed by the main heater. The latter is a consequence of the increase in the CO₂ temperature at the inlet of the main heater compared to the nominal condition.

As it is shown in Table 4.21, there is an efficiency loss of about 0.9 % between the charging/discharging cycle and the reference case. This is slightly higher than for the nominal temperature. The main reason is due the maximum temperature of the hot water tank is limited to 220 °C so the temperature reached by the CO₂ fraction during discharge is considerably lower than in the reference case.

Additionally, the consumption of the charging compressor is higher than that of the recompressor, as the latter handles a lower mass flow rate due to the reduced density at the inlet when the temperature rises. In contrast, when compared to the results obtained for the HRB-propane case, an opposite behaviour is observed: In the HRB-propane, an increase in condensation temperature leads to an increase in pressure at the inlet of the recompressor. This significantly increases the mass flow rate through it and its consumption, which also causes an imbalance in the recuperator and results in the efficiency of the charging/discharging cycle being higher than that of the reference case. As in the HRB-propane case, RTE and COP are reported in the tables for completeness but are not further analyzed, since their interpretation was already discussed in Section 3.3.

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Table 4.21 Main sCO₂-RB operation results at main compressor inlet temperature of 40 °C (reference and charging/discharging cycle)

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main compressor inlet temperature (°C)	40	40	40
Cold storage temperature (°C)	-	128.3	128.3
Hot storage temperature (°C)	-	220	220
CO ₂ bypass high temperature (°C)	246	250.6	220
Outlet LTR low pressure side temperature (°C)	120	126.6	125.8
Inlet LTR high pressure side temperature (°C)	116	121.8	115.7
Recuperator heat capacity ratio (low pressure/high pressure)	1	1	1.09
PB thermal power inlet (MW)	204.5	202.4	209
CO ₂ main heater inlet temperature (°C)	407.1	408	403.4
Thermal power absorbed by PTES storage (MW)	-	64	-64
Gross power produced (MW)	85.5	66.5	101.8
Total CO ₂ mass flow (kg/s)	1067.6	1068.2	1066.1
Recompressor consumption (MW)	29.8	30.2	-
PTES charging compressor consumption (MW)	-	30	-
Main compressor consumption (MW)	34.6	24.3	30.9
PTES discharging compressor consumption (MW)	-	-	17.6
Coefficient of Performance (COP)		2.13	
Roundtrip efficiency (RTE) (%)			85.7
Power gross efficiency (%)	41.8		40.91
Efficiency difference (%)	-0.89		

Table 4.22 CO₂ mass flow fraction through each component (reference and charging/discharging cycle)

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main compressor	0.73	0.47	0.65
PTES discharging compressor	-	-	0.35
Low temperature recuperator high-pressure path	0.73	0.74	0.65
Recuperator high-pressure path		1	1
Main heater	1	1	1
Turbine	1	1	1
Recuperator low pressure path	1	1	1
Recompressor	0.27	0.26	-
PTES charging compressor	-	0.27	-
Cooler	0.73	0.47	1

Table 4.23 shows the results of the reference sCO₂-RB compared to a charge/discharge cycle of the PTES-sCO₂-RB for a main compressor inlet temperature of 32 °C, the minimum possible. Table 4.24 shows the mass flow rate fraction through each component. The performance difference between the two cases is 0.6 %, which is lower than the performance difference observed for the 40 °C main compressor inlet case. This is partly due to the smaller temperature difference between the hot tank and the temperature reached by the bypass CO₂ fraction during discharge compared to the 40 °C case. Additionally, the recompressor consumption increases, surpassing that of the charging compressor. This is because the higher density at the recompressor inlet leads to a greater mass flow rate, which also causes an imbalance in the recuperator.

In the annual simulation, charging typically occurs at higher ambient temperatures than discharging. Similar to the HRB-propane case, the charging phase usually takes place during the central hours of the day, which often correspond to the lowest energy prices (peak PV production), while discharging occurs in the evening, when energy prices tend to be at their highest. In these conditions the PTES-CSP operational cycle achieves a higher efficiency than the reference configuration, as shown in Table 4.25.

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Additionally, during the months with higher solar radiation, an additional daily cycle of charging and discharging occurs. In this case, charging occurs around midnight, and discharging takes place during the hours just before sunrise. This behaviour is not observed in the HRB-propane case. It occurs only in the sCO₂-RB case due to the greater operational flexibility of the TES in the central receiver configuration, which has no limitation on the amount of molten salt directed to storage. This allows for extended operation during nighttime hours in the summer. In [Appendix A.9](#) the number of operating hours of the PTES distributed by month and hour are shown. They correspond with the PTES case with 6 hours.

Table 4.23 Main sCO₂-RB operation results at main compressor inlet of 32 (reference and charging/discharging cycle)

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main compressor inlet temperature (°C)	32	32	32
Cold storage temperature (°C)	-	63	63
Hot storage temperature (°C)	-	177.2	177.2
CO ₂ bypass high temperature (°C)	178.8	186	165
Outlet recuperator high pressure side temperature (°C)	71.5	77.6	68.6
Inlet recuperator high pressure side temperature (°C)	61.9	70.7	61.9
Recuperator heat capacity ratio (low pressure/high pressure)	1.05	1.02	1
PB thermal power inlet (MW)	223	220.9	232
CO ₂ main heater inlet temperature (°C)	392.2	393.9	385
Thermal power absorbed by PTES storage (MW)	-	76.8	-76.8
Gross power produced (MW)	101.7	84.3	119.8
Total CO ₂ mass flow (kg/s)	1061.8	1062.5	1059.3
Recompressor consumption (MW)	29.2	28.5	-
PTES charging compressor consumption (MW)	-	27.6	-
Main compressor consumption (MW)	17.5	8.2	18.2
PTES discharging compressor consumption (MW)	-	-	9.8
COP (Coefficient of Performance)	-	2.78	-
Roundtrip efficiency (RTE) (%)	-	-	104
Power gross efficiency (%)	45.6	-	45.1
Efficiency difference (%)	-0.5		

Table 4.24 CO₂ mass flow fraction through each component (reference and charging)

	Reference	Charge	Discharge
Main compressor	0.62	0.29	0.65
PTES discharging compressor	-	-	0.35
Low temperature recuperator high-pressure path	0.62	0.65	0.65
High Recuperator high-pressure path	1	1	1
Main heater	1	1	1
Turbine	1	1	1
Low/High temperature recuperator low pressure path	1	1	1
Recompressor	0.38	0.36	-
PTES charging compressor	-	0.35	-
Cooler	0.62	0.29	1

Table 4.25 Operation results for different low-cycle temperatures

Configuration	Reference		Charge	Discharge
Low-cycle temperature (°C)	40	32	40	32
Gross power output (MW)	85.51	101.7	72.37	120.53
Hot storage temperature (°C)	-	-	203.9	203.9
PTES thermal power storage (MW)	-	-	40.7	-40.7
CO ₂ bypass temperature (°C)	245.6	178.77	-	196.1
Gross efficiency (%)	43.78		44.78	

4.6.4 Sizing and cost results of the components

It was only necessary to size the water/CO₂ heat exchanger and the water tanks in order to estimate the costs; the cost of the remaining components was calculated directly based on cost correlations, using power consumption values (for compressors and motors) and the UA factor for the cooler.

The water/CO₂ heat exchanger has been designed as a PCHE. Table 4.26 shows the main results. The highest pressure drop take place in the CO₂ side since the mass flow rate is higher than the water one (about 3 times more) and the density is lower.

Table 4.26 water/CO₂ heat exchanger main results

Total HX weight (ton)	101.2
Module dimension (m)	0.6x0.6x1.5 (length)
Number modules in parallel	5
Number modules in series	7
Summary results per module	
Channel diameter (mm)	2
Pitch between channels (both directions) (mm)	0.7
Wall thickness (vertical direction) (mm)	10
Edge width (horizontal direction) (mm)	0.7
Number of channels per module	75728
Water heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	2277
CO ₂ heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	2489
Global heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	1165
Water pressure drop (bar)	0.07
CO ₂ pressure drop (bar)	0.38

The main results of the pressurized water tanks are shown in Table 4.27.

Table 4.27 Pressurized water tanks main results

	3 hr case	4 hr case	5 hr case
Total weight (ton)	836	1045	1254
Number of tanks	4	5	6
Summary results per tank			
Mass (ton)	209		
Length (m)	25		
Diameter (m)	6.1		
Thickness (mm)	50.8		
Insulating thickness (mm)	217		
Pressure (bar)	24.2		
Hot tank nominal temperature (°C)	180.3		
Nominal temperature drop per hour (°C)	0.036		
Nominal thermal losses (kW)	12.7		

The total incremental costs for 3, 4 and 5 hours of storage are shown in Table 4.28. The investment is considerable higher than in the HRB-propane case (near the double).

Table 4.28 Incremental investment for 3,4 and 5 hours of PTES storage

	Cost per unit		Units	Total cost (M€)
	(M€/unit)			
Cooler	4.598		1	4.598
Charging compressor motor	1.396		1	1.396
Discharging compressor motor	0.794		1	0.794
Charging compressor	6.251		1	6.251
Discharging compressor	4.295		1	4.295
Heat exchanger	4.347		1	4.347
Tank	1.793	4 5 6	7.17	8.963 10.755
			28.851	30.644 32.436

4.6.5 Annual results

Table 4.29 shows the economic results of the annual simulation for the reference case and the 3, 4 and 5 hr CSP-PTES cases. The net energy production is higher in the three PTES cases than in the reference case. This is due to the increased efficiency resulting from charging at a higher ambient temperature than during discharging, especially in summer. In particular, during discharge, the temperature of the hot tank is higher than the temperature that propane would reach at the outlet of the recompressor in the reference case (without PTES), which contributes to improve the efficiency.

The 5 hours case is the most profitable, however the solution is not feasible due it high costs. The incomes increment is around a 1.6 %, that is higher than in the HRB-propane.

On the other hand, even if a maximum tank temperature limit equal to the design value were set, and assuming the same revenues, the cost reduction would not be sufficient for the system to be profitable. However, if costs were 30 % lower (a value within the uncertainty range of cost correlations), the system would become profitable, with a profits-incomes ratio of 22 %.

Table 4.29 Annual economic results for the reference case and the 3,4 and 5 hr CSP-PTES cases

	Reference case	CSP-PTES		
		3 hr	4 hr	5 hr
Net energy (GWh)	382.6	383.4	383.4	383.4
CSP utilization factor (%)	46.6	46.1	46.4	46.1
PTES utilization factor (%)	-	35.2	37.6	38.9
Incomes (M€)	71.956	72.854	72.983	73.073
Incremental incomes (M€)	-	0.898	0.915	1.117
Incremental investment (M€)	-	28.851	30.644	32.436
Cost-income ratio	-	1.3	1.21	1.18
Profits-income ratio (%)	-	-30.4	-21.1	-17.9
Charging price (€/MWh)	-	172.22	170.57	170.97
Discharging price (€/MWh)	-	201.96	203.5	203.91

Figure 4.23 shows the average monthly prices for the market, the CSP plant, and PTES charging and discharging throughout 2022. Figure 4.24 presents the monthly income and PTES operating hours during the same year. Months with high solar radiation (summer, particularly July

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and August) achieve the highest revenues and number of operating hours, despite having one of the lowest price differences between charging and discharging. This is not the case for September, which generates higher income than June due to a more favourable price difference.

As previously explained, the significant revenue increase during high-radiation months is driven by two main factors. First, since the price difference between charging and discharging is small (Figure 4.23), the increment is mainly explained by the improved efficiency of PTES operation: during discharging, the cycle low temperature is significantly lower than during charging (Figure 4.25), which enhances efficiency compared to the reference case. The second reason is that the greater heat stored in the TES enables nighttime operation, adding an extra charging and discharging cycle in most days.

The incomes during months with low ambient temperatures (particularly January, February, and December) are negligible. This is because when the ambient temperature falls below 22 °C, the temperature at the inlet of the main compressor remains constant at 32 °C. As a result, there is no significant temperature variation between the charging and discharging phases, leading to reduced efficiency.

Finally, Figure 4.26 compares the monthly incomes and PTES operating hours between the HRB-propane and sCO₂-RB cases. For most months the revenues are similar, but in July, August, and September the sCO₂-RB configuration shows significantly higher incomes for the reasons previously justified.

Figure 4.23 Average monthly prices in 2022

Figure 4.24 Monthly incomes and PTES working hours in 2022

Figure 4.25 Average monthly low-cycle temperatures for charging/discharging and reference case

Figure 4.26 Comparison between sCO₂-RB and HRB-propane in the incremental incomes/PTES number of hours comparison for the year 2022

4.7 Conclusions

In this section, the PTES system is integrated into the power block of a high-temperature CSP plant. The reference power block is based on an sCO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB), and the solar field consists of a heliostat field and a central receiver. The heat transfer fluid (HTF) used is molten salts, which are heated up to 565 °C in the central receiver. Although the sCO₂-RB power cycle achieves higher efficiency at elevated temperatures, conventional fluids and typical temperature values are selected to allow the use of commercially available receivers and storage systems. This approach reduces uncertainties in the design, simulation, and cost estimation.

The PTES system is integrated into the power block in a similar manner to its integration in the HRB-propane configuration. The number and type of additional components required are similar, although the discharge pump used in the HRB case is replaced by a compressor operating in parallel with the main compressor in the sCO₂-RB. During charging, a fraction of the main flow is diverted through the charging compressor just before entering the cooler. The heat gained by this bypass flow is transferred to a pressurized heat storage system through a water/CO₂ heat exchanger. After being cooled, this flow rejoins the main stream downstream of the main compressor. During discharging, an additional compressor operating in parallel with the main one bypasses a fraction of the flow that absorbs the thermal energy previously stored in the PTES during charging. In this way, the power output that was reduced during the charging phase is recovered during discharging, resulting in a net increase in power output compared to the reference case without PTES. Charging, discharging, and the main compressor are all driven by electric motors. In the first two cases, the compressors always operate at the nominal mass flow rate to maintain heat capacity balance between the water and CO₂ streams in the PTES heat exchanger. For the main compressor, the motor is used to adjust the rotational speed to maintain efficiency close to the nominal value. This is particularly important because the mass flow rate through the main compressor is significantly reduced during the charging operation compared to the reference operation without PTES.

The reference power block has been optimized by considering two nominal low-pressure values: 85 bar and 92 bar, while keeping the same solar field and TES size. Annual simulation results indicate that revenues are higher for the 85 bar case compared to the 92 bar case, due to a greater number of operating hours with ambient temperatures below 32 °C. From a cost perspective, it is not evident that the 92 bar power block is cheaper: although the turbomachinery may be less expensive, the heat exchangers are more costly. Similarly, it is unclear whether the PTES system would be more cost-effective at 92 bar. While the turbomachinery and the required pressure for the storage tanks would be lower, the increased water flow required compared to the 85 bar case would raise the cost of the storage tanks. As a result, the PTES is implemented for the 85 bar case, leaving the analysis of other compressor inlet pressures for future studies.

A study was conducted to select an appropriate terminal temperature difference in the water/CO₂ heat exchanger that aligns with the desired pinch point, in order to maintain a similar temperature difference on the hot side during both charging and discharging. The complexity in this case arises from the divergent temperature profiles of the two fluids: the heat capacity of water increases with temperature, while that of CO₂ decreases as it moves away from its critical point.

A comparative study was carried out to evaluate the efficiency of the reference cycle (without PTES) at different ambient temperatures and compare it with the efficiency obtained during the charging/discharging cycles of the PTES. Unlike the HRB-propane case, in the sCO₂-RB configuration, the PTES charging/discharging cycle does not achieve higher efficiency than

the reference cycle. However, higher incremental revenues are obtained in the annual simulation of the CSP-PTES system compared to the reference case without PTES, proportionally to those observed in the HRB case (1.6 % for the sCO₂-RB compared to 1.1 % for the HRB case).

In the CO₂-RB case, the highest incremental revenues occur during high-radiation months, driven by two main factors. First, the larger ambient temperature difference between the charging and discharging operations of the PTES improves efficiency relative to the reference configuration. Second, the greater amount of heat stored in the TES enables nighttime operation, allowing for an additional charging and discharging cycle. This increase is more pronounced in the sCO₂-RB case than in the HRB-propane case, due to the greater flexibility of the TES when integrated with a central receiver CSP system, as compared to one based on parabolic trough collectors. As previously explained, the significant revenue increase during high-radiation months is driven by two key factors: the larger ambient temperature difference between charging and discharging, and the increased amount of heat stored in the TES, which allows for extended nighttime operation with an additional charge/discharge cycle.

Despite the high incremental revenues of the CSP-PTES system over the reference case without PTES, the high incremental costs mean that none of the evaluated configurations (3, 4, or 5 hours of PTES storage) are profitable under the financial and electricity price assumptions considered. Because of that, no LCOS analysis is considered. However, if a 30 % reduction in capital costs is assumed—that could be a reasonable estimate given the uncertainties in the cost correlations—the CSP-PTES configuration with 5 hours of storage becomes profitable, achieving a profit-income ratio of 22 %.

For future studies, the main objective will focus on reducing incremental costs. An operational strategy that optimizes the low-pressure level based on ambient temperature will be considered, with the aim of increasing efficiency under off-design conditions and lowering the temperature in the hot storage tanks. Different main compressor inlet pressure values will be studied in order to achieve an efficiency comparable to that of the 85 bar case, but with a lower pressure ratio to reduce turbomachinery and water tank costs. In this scenario, heat exchanger costs could also be reduced, as more similar pressure levels between the two streams may result in more balanced pressure drops on both sides. To assess this, detailed heat exchanger designs will be performed, and cost correlations based on surface area or weight will be used instead of those based on the UA factor. In addition, higher receiver temperatures will be considered to assess the performance of the PTES integration.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
HRB	Hybrid Rankine Brayton
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HX	Heat Exchanger
NZE	Net Zero Emissions
PB	Power block
RT – ORC	Transcritical Organic Rankine Cycle
sCO ₂ – RB	Supercritical CO ₂ recompression Brayton cycle
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

Symbols

A_{node}	Area of the node (m ²)
AMTD	Arithmetic Mean Temperature Difference (K)
B	Constant for installation costs
cel	Electricity purchase cost (€ · MWh ⁻¹)
c_p	Specific heat (kJ · kg ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹)

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C	Constant for equipment costs
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index
D	Diameter (m)
E	Energy (MWh)
F	Factor
g	Gravity acceleration ($m \cdot s^{-2}$)
h	Specific enthalpy ($kJ \cdot kg^{-1}$)
hr	Hour
H	Height (m)
HTR	High temperature recuperator
I	Incomes (M€)
j	Temporal horizon index
k	Thermal conductivity ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
K	Pressure drop constant
L	Length (m)
LC	Levelized Cost (M€)
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy ($€ \cdot MWh^{-1}$)
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage ($€ \cdot MWh^{-1}$)
LI	Levelized Incomes (M€)
LMTD	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
LTR	Low temperature recuperator
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate ($kg \cdot s^{-1}$)
N. R	Newton Raphson method
p	Pitch (mm)
P	Pressure (kPa)
\dot{P}	Power (MW)
\dot{q}	Heat flux per surface area ($W \cdot m^{-2}$)
\dot{Q}	Thermal power (MW)
r	Ratio
R	Thermal resistance ($K \cdot m^2 \cdot W^{-1}$)
s	Specific entropy ($kJ \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
S	Stress (kPa)
t	Thickness (m)
T	Temperature (°C)
UA	Global heat transfer coefficientx Area ($W \cdot K^{-1}$)
v	Velocity ($m \cdot s^{-1}$)
<hr/>	
<i>Subscripts</i>	
amb	Ambient
BM	Bare module
C	PTES charging operation
cc	Charging compressor
ci	Cost over incomes
cond	Conduction
conv	Convection
comp	Compressor
dc	Discharging compressor
des	Design
ext	External
df	Defocus
fr	Friction
int	Internal
I	Incomes (M€)
INV	Investment
max	Maximum
mh	Main heater
min	Minimum
mv	Maximum characteristic factor value
off	Off – design
opt	Optical

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otb	Outlet tube diameter
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
pf	Power fluid
pi	Profits over incomes
PB	Power block
Pr	Production
rad	Radiation
rc	Recompressor
rec, abs	Absorbed by the receiver
ref	Reference
sec	Secondary
sf	Solar field
sto	Stodola
stPB	Power Block start up
t	Turbine
tb	Tube
th_loss	Thermal losses
Ub	Upper bound
wPr	Without Production

<i>Greek letters</i>	
Δ	Increment
ρ	Density ($\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)
ϵ	Emissivity
σ	Stefan – Boltzmann constant
α	Absorptivity
\tilde{h}	Convection heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$)

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5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusions

The purpose of this work has been to introduce a PTES (Pumped Thermal Energy Storage) that can be integrated into the power blocks of medium- and high-temperature solar CSP (Concentrated Solar Powerplants) as well as to carry out an economic analysis of the system to assess its feasibility. The proposed PTES is integrated synergistically into recompression power cycles, which allows for a reduction in the number of components compared to traditional PTES systems based on Brayton or Rankine cycles. For the medium temperature CSP the PTES is integrated into a Hybrid Rankine Brayton cycle (HRB) that works with propane while for the high temperature CSP the PTES is integrated into a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton power cycle (sCO₂-RB). The viability of the PTES system is evaluated by comparing the economic outcomes from the annual operation simulation of the CSP plant with integrated PTES to those of the reference CSP configuration. Accordingly, this work also defines the methodology for component sizing and for simulating system performance under off-design conditions. Additionally, an optimization algorithm is developed to determine the operating schedule of both the CSP plant and the PTES system. The objective of the algorithm is to maximize revenue over the course of a representative solar year, using as input data the hourly electricity market prices for Spain in 2022 and hourly solar data of a typical meteorological year in Sevilla.

The [introduction section](#) analyzes the current energy context, highlighting the growing need for energy storage systems due to the increasing share of non-dispatchable renewable electricity generation technologies. In addition, the current state of the art of CSP is examined, covering both medium-temperature systems—based on parabolic trough collector fields using a HTF (Heat transfer fluid) that reaches around 400 °C—and high-temperature systems—which rely on central tower receivers and heliostat fields capable of achieving temperatures of up to 565 °C. Next conclusions are obtained:

- Pumped Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) stands out as a promising solution. However, a review of existing studies in the scientific literature suggests that PTES systems are not yet economically viable when operating in open electricity markets without the support of subsidies.
- Although the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) of CSP plants is decreasing, it remains relatively high compared to other renewable energy production systems like the photovoltaic ones.
- Very few studies have explored alternative power cycles for medium-temperature CSP. In most of the existing literature, the proposed cycles do not reach performance levels comparable to those of the superheated and reheated steam Rankine cycles currently used in commercial plants. One promising alternative proposed in this context is the HRB (Hybrid Rankine Brayton cycle) using propane. This is a recompression-based cycle that shares similarities with both T-ORC (transcritical organic Rankine cycles) and sCO₂-RB, achieving thermal efficiencies comparable to those of steam Rankine cycles with superheating and reheating. However, in these studied no annual performance simulations or economic analyses of this cycle have yet been carried out.
- sCO₂-RB (supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle) is the most promising alternative to the conventional Rankine cycle for high-temperature CSP, particularly when even higher operating temperatures than 565 °C are considered.

Section 5: Conclusions and future work

Section 2 analyzes and simulates a medium-temperature CSP with a HRB-propane power block for a yearly operation, estimating also the costs and the feasibility of the plant. CSP with other power cycles are also simulated (steam Rankine with reheat and superheat, sCO₂-RB, HRB-isobutane, ORC-Toluene) to validate the HRB-propane as a possible alternative to the steam Rankine cycle. The methodology followed can be resumed in the following steps:

- A 100 MW CSP with a HRB-propane power block based, 12 hours of molten salts storage, solar multiple of 2, parabolic trough solar field based, and dry cooling system is sized. The HRB-propane nominal point is selected considering a sensitivity analysis in order to maximize the efficiency.
- The CSP and its respective power blocks share the same solar field size, thermal energy storage capacity, and thermal power delivered to the power block. The thermodynamic design for the steam Rankine power cycle is fixed. The other cycles are sized considering the same total UA factor value from the heat exchangers of the HRB-propane. A genetic algorithm is used to maximize the nominal net power for each cycle by optimizing the UA factors of each heat exchanger.
- A yearly simulation of the CSP operation is performed. Solar and price hourly data is considered although half-and hour steps are considered for the schedule of the operations. Operations considered are: 1°) Power production with charging or discharging the TES. 2°) Charging the TES with the power block off. 3°) Solar field startup. 4°) Power block startup. The operation schedule is defined using a mixed-integer linear algorithm that maximizes the incomes for each time step. The algorithm models cover a 48-hour time horizon that is performed every 24 hours.
- Steam Rankine and HRB-propane are also compared in terms of feasibility. To calculate the costs associated with the PB, same cost correlations are considered, and several components are sized using genetic algorithms.

The main conclusions obtained from this section are:

- Although ORC-toluene achieves a 3 % higher net power in nominal conditions than HRB-propane, the revenue increment during the annual simulation is negligible (around 0.3 %). The marginal revenue does not justify the use of toluene in this application due to its inherent risks: The ORC-toluene cycle operates under vacuum on the low-pressure side, allowing air entering in it, which is critical since toluene is flammable. Besides, air must be removed from the system, which causes small toluene leaks, representing a toxic and safety hazard. In contrast, the HRB-propane operates above ambient pressure, avoiding these risks.
- The HRB-propane achieves a similar annual energy production to the Steam Rankine cycle. However, in terms of revenue, the HRB-propane yields approximately 1.5 % higher incomes.
- The estimated cost of the HRB-propane power block ranges between 67.49-89.76 M€, whereas the Steam Rankine cycle ranges from 74.11-115.4 M€.
- The HRB-propane achieves a reduction in LCOE of approximately 1.2-4.1 %. The improvement in the profits over incomes ratio is between 0.9-2.3 %. This latter metric is

Section 5: Conclusions and future work

more appropriate for assessing feasibility, as the annual simulation is performed maximizing the total revenues rather than net energy output.

Section 3 analyzes and simulates the PTES integrated into the power block of the CSP-HRB propane, which was sized in the previous section. The integration of the PTES introduces some components to the HRB-propane: a water/propane heat exchanger, storage tanks with pressurized water, incremental cooler area, and an additional pump and an additional compressor each with their respective electric motors. The charging process requires additional compression work compared to the reference configuration, which is stored as thermal energy. During discharging, the compressors are off, and the added pump drives the propane bypass fraction, which is heated using the previously stored energy and resulting in an increased power output. The methodology followed can be resumed in the following steps:

- The feasibility of the PTES is assessed from the annual incremental incomes and costs between the PTES-CSP and the reference one.
- PTES charging and discharging operations are scheduled during periods when the reference CSP system is generating power.
- The LCOS (Levelized Cost of the Storage) is estimated using a secondary optimization model that allows calculate of the energy produced/consumed solely by the PTES. For that, the production time intervals of the CSP-PTES are constrained to the dispatch schedule of the reference CSP. This approach enables a fairer comparison of the calculated LCOS with those reported in other studies, where standardized purchase costs are considered.

The main conclusions obtained from this section are:

- The variation of the power produced due the PTES operation does not affect significantly the turbine efficiency compared to the efficiency achieved when the PTES is off, since the mass flow rate value remains similar.
- The efficiency of the HRB-propane with the PTES integrated is higher than that of the reference case considering a PTES cycle (charging plus discharging) at high condensing temperatures (e.g., 45 °C). This improvement is mainly due to the use of a pump instead of a compressor to propel the bypass fraction during the discharging. This configuration enables better thermal balance in the recuperator particularly at high temperatures, where the recompressor in the reference case would bypass an excessive fraction. The efficiency is enhanced also during the yearly operation since charging usually occurs at high ambient temperatures and discharging during cooler periods.
- The CSP-PTES is profitable for the 4 hour storage case when using the hourly electricity market prices in Spain for the year 2022 as a reference achieving a 0.92 % profits-incomes ratio.
- From the sensitivity analysis, the reference year considered for the hourly electricity market prices is the factor that most impacts the profitability of the system. Considering 2019 prices, the profits/incomes ratio can be 50 times lower than in year 2022. However, considering the growing integration of renewable energy production technologies without storage capacity into the electricity mix, combined with the closure of fossil fuel power plants with storage capacity, energy storage systems will be required to meet demand when the renewable energy source is not available.

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- The LCOS obtained is a half of the LCOS of Rankine and Brayton PTES and in the same price level that pumped hydro energy storage (the cheapest one) considering the same year costs, purchase electricity and capacity.

Section 4 analyzes and simulates the integration of the PTES system into the power block of a high temperature CSP plant based on a supercritical CO₂ recompression Brayton cycle (sCO₂-RB). The feasibility of the PTES is evaluated by comparing the annual incremental revenues and costs of the CSP-PTES system against those of the reference configuration, as in the previous section. The methodology followed can be resumed in the following steps:

- A 100 MW CSP, with a 12 hours of molten salts storage, solar multiple of 2, solar field composed of a heliostat array and a central receiver is considered. The heat transfer fluid (HTF) used is molten salt, which is heated up to 565 °C in the central receiver.
- Like in the HRB-propane case the feasibility of the PTES is assessed from the annual incremental incomes and costs between the PTES-CSP and the reference one.
- The optimized main compressor inlet pressure value is 85 bar considering that the corresponding temperature is 35 °C. A 92 bar pressure value (corresponding to a higher temperature) is also considered.

A study was conducted to select an appropriate terminal temperature difference in the water/CO₂ heat exchanger that aligns with the desired pinch point, in order to maintain a similar temperature difference on the hot side during both charging and discharging.

The main conclusions obtained from this section are:

- The case with a low-side cycle pressure of 85 bar is the most cost-effective. It yields the highest revenues and the lowest costs for the power cycle components.
- Unlike the HRB-propane case, in the sCO₂-RB configuration, a PTES charging/discharging cycle does not achieve higher efficiency than the reference cycle at any of the ambient temperatures considered.
- The CSP-PTES system with the sCO₂-RB configuration yields higher incremental revenues than the reference case without PTES considering an annual simulation operation, with a 1.6 % increase compared to 1.1 % in the HRB case. These gains are concentrated in high-radiation months, primarily due to two factors: the larger ambient temperature differential between PTES charging and discharging phases, which enhances efficiency, and the greater thermal energy storage capacity, which enables an additional charge/discharge cycle through nighttime operation. These effects are more significant in the sCO₂-RB system, owing to the increased flexibility of TES integration with central receiver CSP plants relative to parabolic trough systems, as there is no limitation on the thermal power to be stored in the TES in central receiver configurations.
- Although the CSP-PTES generates higher incremental revenues than the reference case, none of the configurations with 3, 4, or 5 hours of storage are economically viable due to high capital costs. However, if a 30 % reduction in capital costs is assumed—that could be a reasonable estimate given the uncertainties in the cost correlations—the 5-hour storage configuration becomes profitable, achieving a 22 % profit-income ratio.

5.2 Future works

The positive economic results from the HRB–propane system suggest that further research is needed to explore this novel cycle as a potential alternative to existing technologies. This encourages also further studies on the design of propane turbomachinery, which represents a potential area of investigation. In addition, studies should focus on propane's flammability and thermal stability to assess the safety-related costs of the system. It is also crucial to determine if propane can reach temperatures of up to 400 °C within the thermal cycle, as achieving this would enable the development of new correlations and could substantially enhance cycle efficiency. Furthermore, a configuration with a compressor on an independent shaft will be explored to optimize the bypass fraction that maximizes efficiency under off-design conditions. This is expected to improve performance, particularly during high ambient temperature periods, when power block efficiency typically decreases.

Regarding the integration of PTES in the CSP-HRB–propane, economic results could be improved if the TES flexibility were similar to that of the CSP-central receiver system. This could be achieved by installing multiple HTF/molten salt heat exchangers in parallel, thus eliminating the power limitation in the TES storage.

Regarding the integration of PTES in the CSP-sCO₂-RB, future research would primarily aim at reducing incremental costs. A strategy would be developed to optimize the low-pressure level according to ambient temperature, with the goal of enhancing efficiency under off-design conditions and reducing the temperature in the hot storage tanks. Various inlet pressures for the main compressor would be tested to achieve an efficiency similar to that of the 85 bar case, but with a lower pressure ratio to reduce turbomachinery and water tank costs. In this context, heat exchanger costs could also decrease, as similar pressure levels between the fluid streams might lead to more uniform pressure drops on both sides. To evaluate this, detailed designs for heat exchangers would be carried out, using cost correlations based on surface area or weight instead of those based on the UA factor. Furthermore, higher receiver temperatures would be explored to analyze the performance of PTES integration.

CONCLUSIONES Y TRABAJO FUTURO

Conclusiones

El objetivo de este trabajo ha sido presentar un sistema de almacenamiento de energía térmica bombeada (PTES, por sus siglas en inglés) que pueda integrarse en los bloques de potencia de centrales termosolares de concentración (CSP) de media y alta temperatura, así como realizar un análisis económico del sistema para evaluar su viabilidad. El sistema PTES propuesto se integra de forma sinérgica en ciclos de potencia de recompresión, lo que permite reducir el número de componentes en comparación con los sistemas PTES tradicionales basados en ciclos Brayton o Rankine. Para CSP de media temperatura, el PTES se integra en un ciclo Rankine-Brayton híbrido (HRB) que opera con propano; para CSP de alta temperatura, el PTES se integra en un ciclo Brayton de recompresión con CO₂ supercrítico (sCO₂-RB). La viabilidad del sistema PTES se evalúa comparando los resultados económicos derivados de la simulación anual de operación de la planta CSP con PTES integrado frente a los de una configuración de referencia sin PTES. En consecuencia, este trabajo también define la metodología para el dimensionamiento de componentes y la simulación del comportamiento del sistema en condiciones fuera de diseño. Además, se desarrolla un algoritmo de optimización para determinar el calendario de operación tanto de la planta CSP como del sistema PTES. El objetivo del algoritmo es maximizar los ingresos durante un año solar representativo, utilizando como datos de entrada los precios horarios del mercado eléctrico de España en 2022 y datos solares horarios de un año meteorológico típico en Sevilla.

La introducción analiza el contexto energético actual, destacando la creciente necesidad de sistemas de almacenamiento de energía debido al aumento de generación eléctrica renovable no gestionable. Además, se examina el estado del arte de las CSP, abarcando tanto los sistemas de media temperatura—basados en campos de colectores cilindro-parabólicos con fluidos caloportadores (HTF) que alcanzan temperaturas cercanas a los 400 °C—como los de alta temperatura, que emplean receptores centrales y campos de heliostatos capaces de llegar hasta los 565 °C. Las conclusiones iniciales son:

- El almacenamiento térmico bombeado (PTES) se perfila como una solución prometedora. Sin embargo, una revisión de la literatura científica existente indica que estos sistemas aún no son viables económicamente sin subsidios en mercados eléctricos abiertos.
- Aunque el LCOE (coste nivelado de la electricidad) de las plantas CSP está disminuyendo, sigue siendo relativamente alto en comparación con otras fuentes renovables como la fotovoltaica.
- Existen pocos estudios que exploren ciclos alternativos para CSP de media temperatura. En la mayoría, los ciclos propuestos no alcanzan rendimientos comparables a los Rankine de vapor sobrecalentado y recalentado usados en plantas comerciales. Una alternativa prometedora es el ciclo HRB con propano, basado en recompresión, con similitudes con los ciclos ORC transcíticos (RT-ORC) y sCO₂-RB, logrando eficiencias térmicas similares a los Rankine de vapor. No obstante, no se han realizado simulaciones anuales ni análisis económicos de dicho ciclo en estudios previos.
- El ciclo sCO₂-RB se perfila como la mejor alternativa al Rankine convencional para CSP de alta temperatura, especialmente si se consideran temperaturas operativas superiores a 565 °C.

En la **Sección 2** se analiza y simula una CSP de media temperatura con un ciclo HRB-propano durante un año de operación, estimando también costes y viabilidad. Se simulan distintas CSP con otros ciclos (Rankine con recalentamiento y sobrecalentamiento, sCO₂-RB, HRB-

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isobutano y ORC-tolueno) para validar el HRB-propano como alternativa viable. La metodología incluye:

- Dimensionamiento de una CSP de 100 MW con ciclo HRB-propano, 12 h de almacenamiento en sales fundidas, múltiplo solar de 2, campo solar cilindro-parabólico y refrigeración de aire. Se selecciona el punto de diseño del HRB-propano mediante un análisis de sensibilidad que maximiza la eficiencia.
- Las CSP y sus respectivos bloques de potencia comparten el mismo campo solar, capacidad de almacenamiento y cantidad de energía térmica entregada al ciclo de potencia en el punto de diseño. El diseño termodinámico del ciclo Rankine de vapor está fijado de antemano. Los otros ciclos son dimensionados considerando el mismo valor de la suma total de los factores UA de los intercambiadores de calor del HRB-propano. Se utiliza un algoritmo genético para maximizar la potencia neta nominal producida de cada ciclo optimizando los factores UA de cada intercambiador de calor.
- Se realiza una simulación anual de la operación de la CSP. Se consideran datos horarios de radiación solar y precios de la electricidad, aunque para la programación de las operaciones se utilizan intervalos de media hora. Las operaciones consideradas son: 1º) Producción eléctrica con carga o descarga del sistema de almacenamiento térmico de sales fundidas (TES). 2º) Carga del TES con el bloque de potencia apagado. 3º) Puesta en marcha del campo solar. 4º) Puesta en marcha del bloque de potencia. El calendario de operación se define mediante un algoritmo lineal mixto-entero que maximiza los ingresos en cada intervalo de tiempo. Los modelos del algoritmo cubren un horizonte temporal de 48 horas, que se actualiza cada 24 horas.
- También se comparan los ciclos Rankine de vapor y HRB-propano en términos de viabilidad. Para calcular los costes asociados a cada bloque de potencia, se utilizan las mismas correlaciones de costes, así como varios de los componentes se dimensionan utilizando algoritmos genéticos.

Las principales conclusiones obtenidas en esta sección son:

- Aunque el ciclo ORC- tolueno alcanza un incremento del 3 % de la potencia nominal neta producida con respecto al HRB-propano, el incremento de ingresos anual obtenido a partir de la simulación de la operación anual de la CSP es insignificante (alrededor del 0.3 %). Este ingreso marginal no justifica el uso de tolueno en esta aplicación debido a sus riesgos inherentes: el ciclo ORC-tolueno opera bajo vacío en el lado de baja presión, lo que permite la entrada de aire, algo crítico ya que el tolueno es inflamable. Además, el aire debe ser eliminado del sistema, lo que provoca pequeñas fugas de tolueno, representando un riesgo tóxico y de seguridad. En contraste, el HRB-propano opera por encima de la presión atmosférica, evitando estos riesgos.
- El ciclo HRB-propano logra una producción de energía anual similar al ciclo Rankine de vapor. Sin embargo, en términos de ingresos, el HRB-propano genera aproximadamente un 1.5 % más.
- El coste estimado del bloque de potencia del HRB-propano se sitúa entre 67.49 y 89.76 millones de euros, mientras que el del ciclo Rankine de vapor varía entre 74.11 y 115.4 millones de euros.
- El HRB-propano consigue una reducción del LCOE en el rango del 1.2-4.1 %. La mejora del ratio beneficio/ingresos está entre el 0.9-2.3 %. Esta última métrica resulta más

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adecuada para evaluar la viabilidad, ya que la simulación anual se ha realizado maximizando los ingresos totales en lugar de la energía neta generada.

En la **Sección 3** se analiza y simula el sistema PTES integrado en el bloque de potencia de la CSP con ciclo HRB-propano, la cual fue dimensionada en la sección anterior. La integración del PTES introduce algunos componentes adicionales al ciclo HRB-propano: un intercambiador de calor agua/propano, tanques de almacenamiento con agua a presión, una superficie de refrigeración adicional, así como una bomba y un compresor extra, cada uno accionado por su respectivo motor eléctrico. El proceso de carga requiere un trabajo de compresión adicional en comparación con la configuración de referencia, el cual se almacena en forma de energía térmica. Durante la descarga, los compresores permanecen apagados y la bomba añadida impulsa la fracción de propano del bypass, que se calienta utilizando la energía previamente almacenada, lo que da lugar a un aumento de la potencia generada. La metodología seguida puede resumirse en los siguientes pasos:

- La viabilidad del sistema PTES se evalúa a partir de los ingresos y costes incrementales anuales entre la planta CSP con PTES integrado y la configuración de referencia.
- Las operaciones de carga y descarga del PTES se programan durante los periodos en los que la CSP de referencia está generando electricidad.
- El LCOS (Levelized Cost of Storage, coste nivelado del almacenamiento) se estima utilizando un modelo de optimización secundario que permite calcular la energía producida/consumida exclusivamente por el sistema PTES. Para ello, los intervalos de producción del sistema CSP-PTES se restringen al calendario de operación de la CSP de referencia. Este enfoque permite una comparación más justa del LCOS entre el calculado en este trabajo y los reportados por otros estudios, en los que se consideran costes de compra de la electricidad estandarizados.

Las principales conclusiones obtenidas de esta sección son:

- La variación de potencia producida debido al funcionamiento del PTES no afecta significativamente a la eficiencia de la turbina en comparación con la eficiencia obtenida cuando el PTES está apagado, ya que el caudal másico se mantiene similar.
- La eficiencia del sistema HRB-propano con el PTES integrado es superior a la del caso de referencia si se considera un ciclo completo de carga y descarga del PTES a altas temperaturas de condensación (por ejemplo, 45 °C). Esta mejora se debe principalmente al uso de una bomba en lugar de un compresor para impulsar la fracción de bypass durante la descarga. Esta configuración permite un mejor equilibrio térmico en el recuperador, especialmente a altas temperaturas, donde en el caso de referencia el recompresor deriva una fracción excesiva. La eficiencia también se ve incrementada durante el funcionamiento anual, ya que la carga suele ocurrir con temperaturas ambiente elevadas y la descarga durante periodos más fríos.
- El sistema CSP-PTES resulta rentable en el caso de 4 horas de almacenamiento de agua a presión, utilizando como referencia los precios horarios del mercado eléctrico español del año 2022, alcanzando un ratio beneficio/ingresos de 0.92 %.
- A partir del análisis de sensibilidad, se concluye que el año de referencia considerado para los precios del mercado eléctrico es el factor que más influye en la rentabilidad del sistema. Por ejemplo, si se utilizan los precios de 2019, el ratio beneficio/ingresos puede ser hasta 50 veces menor que en 2022. Sin embargo, dada la creciente penetración de tecnologías renovables sin capacidad de almacenamiento en la red eléctrica, junto con el

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cierre de plantas fósiles con almacenamiento, los sistemas de almacenamiento serán esenciales para cubrir la demanda cuando no haya generación renovable disponible.

- El LCOS obtenido es la mitad del correspondiente a sistemas PTES basados en ciclos Rankine o Brayton, y se encuentra en el mismo nivel de coste que el almacenamiento hidroeléctrico por bombeo (la tecnología más económica), considerando los mismos costes anuales, electricidad de compra y capacidad instalada.

En la **Sección 4** se analiza y simula la integración del sistema PTES en el bloque de potencia de una planta CSP de alta temperatura, basada en un ciclo Brayton de recompresión con CO₂ supercrítico (sCO₂-RB). La viabilidad del sistema PTES se evalúa comparando los ingresos y costes incrementales anuales del sistema CSP-PTES con los de la configuración de referencia, como se hizo en la sección anterior. La metodología seguida se resume en los siguientes pasos:

- Se considera una planta CSP de 100 MW, con 12 horas de almacenamiento en sales fundidas, un múltiplo solar de 2, y un campo solar compuesto por un campo de heliostatos situados alrededor de un receptor central. El fluido caloportador (HTF) utilizado es sales fundidas, que se calienta hasta 565 °C en el receptor central.
- Al igual que en el caso del HRB-propano, la viabilidad del PTES se evalúa comparando los ingresos y costes incrementales anuales entre el sistema CSP-PTES y la configuración de referencia.
- Se optimiza la presión de entrada al compresor principal, tomando un valor de 85 bar, correspondiente a una temperatura de 35 °C. También se considera una opción alternativa con una presión de 92 bar, asociada a una temperatura más elevada.
- Se realiza un estudio para seleccionar una diferencia de temperatura terminal adecuada en el intercambiador agua/CO₂, alineada con el pinch point deseado, con el fin de mantener una diferencia térmica similar en el lado caliente tanto en la carga como en la descarga.

Las principales conclusiones obtenidas de esta sección son:

- La opción con una presión baja de ciclo de 85 bar resulta la más rentable: genera mayores ingresos y menores costes en los componentes del ciclo de potencia.
- A diferencia del caso HRB-propano, en la configuración sCO₂-RB, un ciclo de carga/descarga del PTES no logra una eficiencia superior a la del ciclo de referencia en ninguna de las temperaturas ambiente consideradas.
- El sistema CSP-PTES con sCO₂-RB genera ingresos incrementales más altos que el caso de referencia sin PTES en una simulación anual, con un incremento del 1,6 % frente al 1,1 % en el caso HRB. Estas ganancias se concentran en los meses de alta radiación, principalmente por dos factores: el mayor diferencial de temperatura ambiente entre las fases de carga y descarga del PTES, lo que mejora la eficiencia, y la mayor capacidad de almacenamiento térmico de las sales fundidas (TES), lo que permite realizar un ciclo adicional de carga/descarga durante la noche. Estos efectos son más pronunciados en el sistema sCO₂-RB, debido a la mayor flexibilidad en la integración del TES en plantas CSP de torre central frente a las de colectores cilindro-parabólicos, ya que no existe una limitación de potencia térmica para almacenar en configuraciones de receptor central.
- Aunque el sistema CSP-PTES genera mayores ingresos incrementales que el caso de referencia, ninguna de las configuraciones con 3, 4 o 5 horas de almacenamiento de agua

a presión resulta viable económicamente debido a los altos costes de capital. Sin embargo, si se asume una reducción del 30 % en los costes de capital —una estimación razonable dadas las incertidumbres en las correlaciones de coste— la configuración con 5 horas de almacenamiento de agua a presión se vuelve rentable, alcanzando una relación beneficio/ingresos del 22 %.

Trabajo futuro

Los resultados económicos positivos del sistema HRB–propano sugieren que se requiere más investigación para explorar este ciclo novedoso como una posible alternativa a las tecnologías existentes. Esto también motiva nuevos estudios sobre el diseño de turbomáquinas para propano, lo cual representa un área potencial de investigación. Además, se deberían realizar estudios centrados en la inflamabilidad y la estabilidad térmica del propano, con el fin de evaluar los costes asociados a la seguridad del sistema. También es crucial determinar si el propano puede alcanzar temperaturas de hasta 400 °C dentro del ciclo térmico, ya que lograrlo permitiría desarrollar nuevas correlaciones y podría mejorarse sustancialmente la eficiencia del ciclo. Asimismo, se explorará una configuración en la que el compresor esté montado en un eje independiente, con el objetivo de optimizar la fracción de bypass que maximice la eficiencia en condiciones fuera de diseño. Se espera que esta mejora en la configuración incremente el rendimiento, especialmente durante periodos de altas temperaturas ambiente, cuando la eficiencia del bloque de potencia tiende a disminuir.

En cuanto a la integración del PTES en la CSP con HRB–propano, los resultados económicos podrían mejorarse si la flexibilidad del TES fuera similar a la que tiene en una planta CSP con receptor central. Esto podría lograrse mediante la instalación de múltiples intercambiadores de calor HTF/sales fundidas en paralelo, lo que permitiría eliminar la limitación de potencia a almacenar en el TES.

Respecto a la integración del PTES en la CSP con sCO₂–RB, la investigación futura debería centrarse en reducir los costes incrementales. Podría desarrollarse una estrategia para optimizar en cada momento el valor de la presión de baja en función de la temperatura ambiente, con el objetivo de mejorar la eficiencia en condiciones fuera de diseño y reducir la temperatura en los tanques de agua presurizada. Además, se probarán diferentes presiones de entrada al compresor principal para lograr una eficiencia similar a la del caso de 85 bar, pero con una relación de compresión menor, lo cual permitiría reducir los costes de las turbomáquinas y los tanques de agua. En este contexto, también podrían disminuir los costes de los intercambiadores de calor, ya que niveles de presión similares entre las corrientes de fluido podrían provocar caídas de presión más uniformes en ambos lados. Para evaluar esto, se realizarán diseños detallados de intercambiadores de calor, utilizando correlaciones de coste basadas en superficie o peso, en lugar de aquellas basadas en el factor UA. Finalmente, se explorarán temperaturas más altas en el receptor solar para analizar el comportamiento de la CSP-PTES frente a estas condiciones.

APPENDIX**A.0 Piping model****Nomenclature***Acronyms*

HTF

heat Transfer Fluid

Symbols f

friction factor

 D

diameter (m)

 \dot{m} mass flow rate ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) v velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) N

number

 L

Length (m)

 k

pressure drop constants

Subscripts $run, 1$

primary runners (inside PB)

 $run, 2$

secondary runners (connection with headers)

 p, ext

header HTF extraction points

 L

length

 SCA

Solar Collector Assembly

 ex

expansion

 PB

power block

Greek letters ΔP

pressure drop (Pa)

 ρ density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)

The first step is to calculate the diameter of the pipes. Three main types of pipes are considered. The first type are the main runner pipes, which are located inside the power block. They extend the main flow to the north and the south, so there are four main pipes (two of them contain hot HTF and the other two contain cold HTF). The second type is the secondary runner pipes and extend the HTF from the main runner pipes to the headers of subfield 1, 2, 5 and 6. These pipes are coloured orange in [Figure A0.1](#). Finally, the headers distribute the HTF mass flow through each loop of each subfield. These pipes are coloured blue. [Figure A0.1](#) shows the distribution of the subfields and the power block.

Figure A0.1 Power block and solar field distribution

Appendix

To calculate the diameter of each pipe, minimum and maximum velocity values are considered (2 and 3 m/s). The standardized diameter values are shown in [Table A0.1](#). So, diameter values must meet [Equation A0.1](#). The mass flow rate in main and secondary pipes is calculated through [Equation A0.2](#) and [Equation A0.3](#). Regarding the headers, the mass flow rate circulating through each of them varies each time that there is a connection point with the loops. In cold headers, the mass flow rate decreases while in hot headers, the mass flow rate increases. The diameter of the headers changes when the velocity falls outside the defined range between the maximum and minimum velocities. The total number of connection points is calculated considering that two loops are connected in each of them ([Equation A0.4](#)). The header mass flow rate variation in each connection point is calculated from [Equation A0.5](#).

Table A0.57 Standardized HTF pipes diameter

Diameters (m)
0.0688, 0.0847, 0.1082, 0.1615, 0.2064, 0.2604, 0.3112, 0.3398, 0.3906, 0.4382, 0.4890, 0.5334, 0.5842, 0.6350, 0.6795, 0.7303, 0.7811, 0.8286, 0.8763, 1.0287, 1.1684, 1.3208, 1.4732, 1.6256, 1.7780

$$\sqrt{\frac{4 \cdot \dot{m}}{\pi \cdot v_{min} \cdot \rho}} < D < \sqrt{\frac{4 \cdot \dot{m}}{\pi \cdot v_{max} \cdot \rho}} \quad (\text{A0.1})$$

$$\dot{m}_{run,1} = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTF}}{2} \quad (\text{A0.2})$$

$$\dot{m}_{run,2} = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTF}}{3} \quad (\text{A0.3})$$

$$N_{p,ext} = \frac{N_{loops}}{N_{subfields} \cdot 2} \quad (\text{A0.4})$$

$$\dot{m}_{header,i} = \dot{m}_{header,(i-1)} \pm 2 \cdot \dot{m}_{loop} \quad (\text{A0.5})$$

The length of each pipe is calculated using [Equation A0.6-A0.11](#). L_{I0cop} is the length of the cross-over piping.

$$L_{row} = 17.5 \quad (\text{A0.6})$$

$$L_{I0cop} = 40 + L_{row} \quad (\text{A0.7})$$

$$L_{loop} = NSCA \cdot L_{col,SCA} \quad (\text{A0.8})$$

$$L_{run,1} = 50 \quad (\text{A0.9})$$

$$L_{run,2} = 4 \cdot L_{row} + L_{loop} \quad (\text{A0.10})$$

$$L_{hdr} = L_{row} \cdot 2 + 4.275 \quad (\text{A0.11})$$

The pressure drop due friction losses is assessed through [Equation A0.12](#). The friction factor is assessed considering the Colebrook-White equation.

$$\Delta P_L = f \cdot \frac{v^2}{2} \cdot D \cdot \rho \cdot L \quad (\text{A0.12})$$

The pressure drop due expansion and contractions for runner pipes is calculated using [Equation A0.13](#). Regarding the headers, the pressure drop is calculated for each segment where the diameter changes.

$$\Delta P_{ex} = 0.5 \cdot \frac{v^2}{2} \cdot \rho \quad (\text{A0.13})$$

Appendix

The pressure drop due valves and elbows is calculated with Equation A0.14. The coefficient for each type of pipe appears in Table A0.2

$$\Delta P_v = k_{\Delta P} \cdot \frac{v^2}{2} \cdot \rho \quad (\text{A1.14})$$

Table A0.58 Power block and solar field

$k_{\Delta P}$	IOCop	Loop	Runners	Headers
15.78	9+8.69·(3+N _{SCA})	0.6·N _{elbow,L} +1·0.19	0.6	0.6

$$N_{elbow,L} = \max \left(\left\lfloor \frac{L_{run}}{70} + .5 \right\rfloor \cdot 4.8 \right) \quad (\text{A1.15})$$

Additionally, the pipes that connect the power block with the main heater, thermal energy storage and pumping system are calculated considering a design velocity of 1.85 m/s. The length of each pipe is shown in Table A0.3. Piping lines 1-2 carry a mass flow of $\frac{1}{2} \cdot \dot{m}_{sf}$, piping lines 3-4 carry the \dot{m}_{sf} , and 5-7 carry \dot{m}_{PB} . The pressure drop associated with these pipes is only due friction losses and can be assessed with Equation A1.12.

Table A0.106 TES and pumping system connection to power block

Line	Description	Length (m)
1	Pump suction header to pump inlet	45
2	Pump discharge to discharge header	45
3	Pump discharge header	100
4	Collector field to expansion vessel/TES	120
5	Steam generator supply header	80
6	Inter-steam-generator piping	120
7	Steam generator exit to exp. Vessel/TES	80

The pump consumption when the solar field is on is calculated with Equation A0.16. $\Delta P_{heat\ exchanger}$ is the pressure drop of the main heater. The pressure drop of the HTF/molten salts heat exchanger is assumed to be the same than the pressure drop of the main heater.

$$\dot{P}_{HTF,pump} = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTF} \cdot (\Delta P_{ex} + \Delta P_v + \Delta P_L) + \dot{m}_{PB} \cdot \Delta P_{heat\ exchanger}}{0.85 \cdot \rho} \quad (\text{A0.16})$$

The pump consumption when the solar field is off and the TES is supplying energy to the power block is calculated with Equation A0.17. The considered pressure drops include those from lines 1-7, the main runner pipes, the molten salts heat exchanger, and the main heater.

$$\dot{P}_{HTF,pump} = \frac{\dot{m}_{PB} \cdot (\Delta P_{L,1-7} + \Delta P_{L,run,1} + \Delta P_{v,run,1} + \Delta P_{ex,run,1} + 2 \cdot \Delta P_{heat\ exchanger})}{0.85 \cdot \rho} \quad (\text{A0.17})$$

A.1 Heat transfer correlations inside tubes

Nomenclature

Acronyms

HTF

Heat Transfer Fluid

Symbols

 cp specific heat capacity ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$) \overline{cp}

average specific heat capacity

 D

diameter (m)

 f

Darcy friction factor

 h enthalpy ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$) \tilde{h} heat transfer coefficient ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$) k thermal conductivity ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)

Nu

Nusselt number

 Pr

Prandtl number

 Re

Reynolds number

T

temperature (K)

Subscripts

 b

bulk fluid

 i

internal

 l

liquid

 pc

pseudo-critical

sat

saturation

 v

vapor

 w

wall

Greek letters

 λ latent heat ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$) λ' modified latent heat ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)

In all cases an inlet wall temperature should be estimated and recalculated when the overall heat transfer coefficient is assessed.

A.1.1 Jackson correlation

The Nusselt number is calculated using Equation A1.1 where b refers to the properties calculated at the bulk fluid temperature and w to wall temperature. The average specific heat capacity of the medium is calculated using Equation A1.2. The exponent n of Equation A1.1 is calculated using the expressions of Equation A1.3 depending on the relation between the pseudo-critical temperature, the bulk temperature and the wall temperature.

$$Nu = 0.0183 \cdot Re_b^{0.82} \cdot Pr_b^{0.5} \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_w}{\rho_b}\right)^{0.3} \cdot \left(\frac{\overline{cp}}{cp_b}\right)^n \quad (A1.1)$$

$$\overline{cp} = \frac{h_w - h_b}{T_w - T_b} \quad (A1.2)$$

$$n = 0.4 \text{ for } T_b < T_w < T_{pc} \text{ and } 1.2 \cdot T_{pc} < T_b < T_w$$

$$n = 0.4 + 0.2 \left(\frac{T_w}{T_{pc}} - 1\right) \text{ for } T_b < T_{pc} < T_w \quad (A1.3)$$

$$n = 0.4 + 0.2 \left(\frac{T_w}{T_{pc}} - 1\right) \cdot \left(1 - 5 \cdot \left(\frac{T_b}{T_{pc}} - 1\right)\right)$$

$$\text{for } T_{pc} < T_b < 1.2 \cdot T_{pc}$$

A.1.2 Gnielinsky correlation

The Nusselt number is calculated using Equation A1.4-A1.6 where all the properties except Pr_w are calculated at the bulk temperature of the fluid. w refers to the properties calculated at the wall temperature.

If $Re < 2300$

$$Nu = 4.089 \quad (A1.4)$$

If $2300 < Re < 5 \cdot 10^6$

$$Nu = 4.089 + \frac{Nu_{5000} - 4.089}{5000 - 2300} \quad (A1.5)$$

If $2300 < Re < 5 \cdot 10^6$

$$Nu = \frac{\left(\frac{f}{8}\right) \cdot (Re - 1000) \cdot Pr}{1 + 12.7 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{f}{8}}\right) \cdot (Pr^{2/3} - 1)} \cdot \left(\frac{Pr}{Pr_w}\right)^{0.11} \quad (A1.6)$$

A.1.3 Condensation of superheated vapor inside tubes

Equation A1.7 allows to calculate the condensation latent heat for superheated vapor. It is valid if the wall temperature is below the saturation temperature.

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \left(1 + cp_v \cdot \frac{(T_v - T_{sat})}{\lambda}\right) \quad (A1.7)$$

The average heat-transfer coefficient for condensation inside tubes in stratifying flow conditions is calculated considering Equation A1.8. l refers to the properties calculated of the saturated liquid at the bulk temperature while v to the saturated vapor.

$$\tilde{h} = 0.56 \cdot \left[\frac{k_l^3 \cdot \rho_l \cdot (\rho_l - \rho_v) \cdot 9.81 \cdot \lambda'}{\mu_l \cdot (T_{sat} - T_w) \cdot D_i} \right]^{0.25} \quad (A1.8)$$

A.2 Shell and tube heat transfer correlations outside tubes

Nomenclature

Symbols

BC	Baffle cut (%)
$cl_{s,b}$	Diametral clearance between the shell and the tube bundle (m)
$cl_{t,bf}$	Diametral clearance between a tube and a baffle (m)
c_p	Specific heat capacity ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
C_{bf}	Distance between baffles (m)
D_{CTL}	Central tube diameter (m)
D_h	Hydraulic diameter of the shell (m)
D_{OTL}	Outer tube limit diameter (m)
D_s	Shell diameter (m)
D_o	External tube diameter (m)
f	Friction factor
F_b	Factor that accounts for convective effects in boiling on tube bundles
F_c	Fraction of tube between baffle tips
F_p	Pressure correction factor
F_w	Fractional area of the window
G_s	Shell side mass velocity ($kg \cdot m^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$)
G_w	Window mass velocity ($kg \cdot m^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$)
h	Shell-side heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)
h_{id}	Ideal tube bank heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)
h_L	Shell-side heat transfer coefficient for the liquid fraction (condenser) (W/m^2K)
h_{nb}	Nucleate boiling heat-transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)
J_B	Heat-transfer correction factor for bundle bypass effects
J_c	Heat-transfer correction factor for effect of baffle window flow
J_L	Heat-transfer correction factor for baffle leakage effects
L_c	length of the baffle cut (m)
\dot{m}_s	Shell side mass flow rate ($kg \cdot s^{-1}$)
N_{cc}	Number of tube rows crossed in flow between two baffle tips
N_{cw}	Effective number of tube rows crossed in flow through one baffle window
N_{ss}	Number of pairs of sealing strips
N_t	Number of tubes in bundle
P_c	Critical pressure of the fluid (kPa)
Pr	Prandtl number
q	Heat flux per unit area ($W \cdot m^{-2}$)
R_B	Pressure drop correction factor for bundle bypass effects
R_L	Pressure drop correction factor for baffle leakage effects
Re	Reynolds number (Referred to D_o)
S_b	Bundle bypass flow area (m^2)
S_m	Cross flow area (m^2)
$S_{s,bf}$	Shell to baffle leakage area (m^2)
$S_{t,bf}$	Tube to baffle leakage area (m^2)
S_w	Window flow area (m^2)
S_{wg}	Gross window area (m^2)
x	Vapor weight fraction
X_{tt}	Lockhart-Marfinelli parameter for turbulent flow in both phases
Greek letters	
ΔP_c	Total pressure drop in all central baffle spaces (Pa)
ΔP_e	Sum of pressure drops in the entrance and exit baffle spaces (Pa)
ΔP_{ic}	Ideal tube bank pressure drop (Pa)
ΔP_{iw}	Ideal pressure drop in one baffle window (Pa)
ΔP_s	Total pressure drop in the shell (Pa)

Appendix

$(\Delta P_s)_V$	Pressure drop of the vapor fraction (condenser) (Pa)
ΔP_w	Total pressure drop in all baffle windows (Pa)
μ	Dinamic viscosity calculated at the bulk temperature of the fluid (Pa·s)
μ_l	Dinamic viscosity of the liquid fraction (Pa·s)
μ_v	Dinamic viscosity of the vapor fraction (Pa·s)
μ_w	Dinamic viscosity calculated at the wall temperature (Pa)
ρ_l	Density of the liquid fraction ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
ρ_v	Density of the vapor fraction ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
ρ	Density calculated at the bulk temperature of the fluid ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
θ_{CTL}	Angle defined by Equation A2.13
θ_{DS}	Baffle window angle

A.2.1 Shell diameter calculation

[Equation A2.1](#) is used to calculate the outer tube limit diameter. This diameter encircles the outermost tube in the tube bundle layout. The equation depends on the number of passes, the tube pattern, the Pitch, the number of tubes and their external diameter. [Table A2.1](#) and [Table A2.2](#) shows the value of the different parameters considered.

$$D_{OTL} = \frac{\sqrt{f_1 \cdot N_t \cdot (1000 \cdot P_T)^2 + f_2 \cdot \sqrt{N_t} \cdot (1000 \cdot P_T) + D_o \cdot 1000}}{1000} \quad (\text{A2.1})$$

Table A2.98 Number of tube

No. of passes	1	2	4	8
f₂ in mm	0	22	70	105

Table A2.146 Tube pattern

Tube pattern	Triangular	Square
f₁	1.1	1.3

The shell diameter is calculated from the OTL diameter and the diametral clearance between the shell and the bundle. [Equation A2.2](#)

$$D_s = D_{OTL} + cl_{sl,b} \quad (\text{A2.2})$$

The central tube diameter is the diameter of the circle that passes through the centers of the outermost tubes in the bundle. It is defined through [Equation A2.3](#)

$$D_{CTL} = D_{OTL} - D_o \quad (\text{A2.3})$$

The diametral clearance between the shell and the tube bundle is calculated using [Equation A2.4](#)

$$cl_{s,b} = D_s \cdot 0.005 + 0.0125 \quad (\text{A2.4})$$

The diametral clearance between the shell and a baffle is calculated using [Equation A2.5](#)

$$cl_{s,bf} = 0.004 \cdot D_s + 0.0031 \quad (\text{A2.5})$$

The diametral clearance between a tube and a baffle is calculated from [Equation A2.6](#). C_{bf} is the distance between baffles.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } 2 \cdot C_{bf} > 1 \\ & \quad cl_{t,bf} = 0.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \\ & \text{else} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2.6})$$

$$cl_{t,bf} = 0.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

A.2.2 Delaware method

Geometric calculations.

The maximum space between baffles is calculated from [Equation A2.7](#)

$$C_{bf} = \frac{(68 \cdot D_o \cdot 1000 + 228)}{2 \cdot 1000} \quad (\text{A2.7})$$

The length of the baffle cut is calculated from [Equation A2.8](#). The baffle cut (BC) is represented in percentage.

$$L_c = D_s \cdot \frac{BC}{100} \quad (\text{A2.8})$$

The external hydraulic diameter is calculated using [Equation A2.9](#)

$$D_h = \frac{4 \cdot P_T^2}{\pi \cdot D_o} - D_o \quad (\text{A2.9})$$

The crossflow area (minimum flow area in one central baffle space at the centre of the tube bundle) is calculated using [Equation A2.10](#).

$$S_m = C_{bf} \cdot \left(D_s - D_{OTL} + \frac{D_{OTL} - D_o}{P_T} \cdot (P_T - D_o) \right) \quad (\text{A2.10})$$

The number of tube rows crossed by the fluid between baffle tips is calculated through [Equation A2.11](#)

$$N_{cc} = \frac{D_s - 2 \cdot L_c}{P_{T,p}} \quad (\text{A2.11})$$

where $P_{T,p} = P_T$ for square tube layout and $P_{T,p} = P_T \cdot \cos 30^\circ$ for triangular layout

The effective number of tube rows crossed in the window is calculated through [Equation A2.12](#).

$$N_{cw} = \frac{0.8 \cdot L_c}{P_T} \quad (\text{A2.12})$$

The center tube limit angle (θ_{CTL}) defines a circular sector that contains the baffle cut and it is limited by the center tube limit diameter. [Equation A2.13](#)

$$\theta_{CTL} = 2 \cdot \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{D_s}{D_{CTL}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot BC}{100} \right) \right) \quad (\text{A2.13})$$

The shell diameter angle (θ_{DS}) is calculated directly through the baffle cut percentage. [Equation A2.14](#)

$$\theta_{DS} = 2 \cdot \cos^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot BC}{100} \right) \quad (\text{A2.14})$$

The gross window area is the open area between the shell and the baffle edge formed by the baffle cuts. [Equation A2.15](#)

$$S_{wg} = (\theta_{DS} - \sin(\theta_{DS})) \cdot D_s^2 / 8 \quad (\text{A2.15})$$

The fractional area of the window is calculated through [Equation A2.16](#)

$$F_w = \frac{\theta_{CTL} - \sin(\theta_{CTL})}{2 \cdot \pi} \quad (\text{A2.16})$$

The area occupied by the tubes in the window is assessed through [Equation A2.17](#). If there are no tubes in windows, the value of this area is 0.

Appendix

$$S_{tw} = N_t \cdot F_w \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{D_o^2}{4} \quad (\text{A2.17})$$

The flow area in one baffle window is the gross window area minus the tube window area. [Equation A2.18](#)

$$S_w = S_{wg} - S_{tw} \quad (\text{A2.18})$$

The bundle bypass flow area is the area between the outermost tubes and the shell at the shell centerline in one central baffle space. [Equation A2.19](#)

$$S_b = C_{bf} \cdot (D_s - D_{OTL}) \quad (\text{A2.19})$$

The fraction of tubes between baffle tips. [Equation A2.20](#)

$$F_c = 1 - 2 \cdot F_w \quad (\text{A2.20})$$

The shell to baffle leakage area is calculated through [Equation A2.21](#)

$$S_{s,bf} = \pi/2 \cdot D_s \cdot cl_{s,bf} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot \pi - \theta_{DS}}{2 \cdot \pi} \quad (\text{A2.21})$$

The tube to baffle leakage area is calculated through [Equation A2.22](#)

$$S_{t,bf} = N_t \cdot \pi \cdot \left((D_o + 2 \cdot cl_{t,bf})^2 - D_o^2 \right) \cdot \frac{(1 - F_w)}{4} \quad (\text{A2.22})$$

Correlations for correction factors

The correction factor for baffle window flow, J_c , expresses the effect on heat transfer of flow in baffle windows. In heat exchangers with no tubes in windows the value of $J_c = 1$. [Equation A2.23](#)

$$J_c = 0.55 + 0.72 \cdot F_c \quad (\text{A2.23})$$

The correction factor for baffle leakage is assessed through [Equation A2.24](#). The factors involved are assessed through [Equation A2.25](#) and [Equation A2.26](#)

$$J_L = 0.44 \cdot (1 - r_s) + [1 - 0.44 \cdot (1 - r_s)] \cdot \exp(-2.2 \cdot r_l) \quad (\text{A2.24})$$

$$r_s = \frac{S_{s,bf}}{S_{s,bf} + S_{t,bf}} \quad (\text{A2.25})$$

$$r_l = \frac{S_{s,bf} + S_{t,bf}}{S_m} \quad (\text{A2.26})$$

Correction factor J_B express the effect of the bundle bypass flow on the heat transfer ([Equation 2.27](#)). Since no sealing strip is used $r_{ss} = 0$ ([Equation 2.28](#)), and $C_j = 1.25$ since $Re > 100$

$$J_B = \exp\left[(-C_j \cdot S_b/S_m) \cdot \left(1 - \sqrt[3]{2 \cdot r_{ss}}\right)\right] \text{ for } r_{ss} < 0.5 \quad (\text{A2.27})$$

$$r_{ss} = N_{ss}/N_{cc} \quad (\text{A2.28})$$

Ideal tube bank correlations.

Appendix

The following equations (A2.29- A2.32) allow for the calculation of the constants that are later used in the pressure drop and heat transfer coefficient calculations. The Reynolds number is calculated considering D_o

$$j = a_1 \cdot \left(\frac{1.33}{P_T/D_o} \right)^a \cdot Re^{a_2} \quad (\text{A2.29})$$

$$f = b_1 \cdot \left(\frac{1.33}{P_T/D_o} \right)^b \cdot Re^{b_2} \quad (\text{A2.30})$$

where

$$a = \frac{a_3}{1 + 0.14 \cdot Re^{a_4}} \quad (\text{A2.31})$$

$$b = \frac{b_3}{1 + 0.14 \cdot Re^{b_4}} \quad (\text{A2.32})$$

Coefficients depends on the Reynolds number and tube pattern:

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4
$Re \geq 10^4$								
Triangular pattern	0.321	-0.388	1.45	0.519	0.372	-0.123	7	0.5
Square pattern	0.37	-0.395	1.187	0.37	0.391	-0.148	6.3	0.378
$10^4 > Re \geq 10^3$								
Triangular pattern	0.321	-0.388	1.45	0.519	0.486	-0.152	7	0.5
Square pattern	0.107	-0.266	1.187	0.37	0.0815	0.022	6.3	0.378
$10^3 > Re \geq 10^2$								
Triangular pattern	1.36	-0.657	1.45	0.519	45.1	-0.973	7	0.5
Square pattern	0.9	-0.631	1.187	0.37	32.1	-0.963	6.3	0.378
$10^2 > Re \geq 10$								
Triangular pattern	1.36	-0.657	1.45	0.519	45.1	-0.973	7	0.5
Square pattern	0.9	-0.631	1.187	0.37	32.1	-0.963	6.3	0.378

Heat-transfer coefficient

It is calculated considering the properties evaluated at the bulk temperature except μ_{wall} , that is the dynamic viscosity evaluated at the film temperature. Shell side mass velocity and window velocity are calculated using [Equation A2.33](#) and [Equation A2.34](#)

$$h_i = j \cdot c_p \cdot G_s \cdot Pr^{-2/3} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_{wall}} \right)^{0.14} \quad (\text{A2.33})$$

$$h = h_{is} \cdot J_c \cdot J_B \cdot J_L \quad (\text{A2.34})$$

$$G_s = \frac{\dot{m}_s}{S_m} \quad (\text{A2.35})$$

$$G_w = \frac{\dot{m}_s}{\sqrt{S_m \cdot S_w}} \quad (\text{A2.36})$$

Shell pressure drop

The ideal tube bank pressure drop is the pressure drop in one central baffle space and it is calculated through [Equation A2.37](#).

$$\Delta P_{ic} = 2 \cdot N_{cc} \cdot f \cdot \frac{G_s^2}{\rho} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14} \quad (\text{A2.37})$$

The ideal pressure drop in one baffle window is calculated through [Equation A2.38](#).

$$\Delta P_{iw} = G_w^2 \cdot \frac{(2 + 0.6 \cdot N_{cw})}{2 \cdot \rho} \quad (\text{A2.38})$$

Appendix

The pressure drop in the entrance and exit baffle spaces are obtained through [Equation A2.39](#), where R_B is the corrector factor for bundle bypass flow.

$$\Delta P_e = \Delta P_{ic} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{N_{cw}}{N_c}\right) \cdot R_B \quad (\text{A2.39})$$

$$R_B = \exp\left[(-3.7 \cdot S_b/S_m) \cdot (1 - \sqrt[3]{2 \cdot r_{ss}})\right] \quad (\text{A2.40})$$

$$p = 0.8 - 0.15 \cdot (1 + r_s) \quad (\text{A2.41})$$

The real tube bank pressure drop is the ideal tube bank pressure drop corrected with the bundle bypass flow and the factor for baffle leakage. [Equation A2.42](#) and [Equation A2.43](#)

$$\Delta P_c = \Delta P_{ic} \cdot R_B \cdot R_L \quad (\text{A2.42})$$

$$R_L = \exp\left[(-1.33 \cdot (1 + r_s) \cdot (r_L)^p)\right] \quad (\text{A2.43})$$

The real window pressure drop is the ideal window pressure drop corrected with the factor for baffle leakage [Equation A2.44](#).

$$\Delta P_w = \Delta P_{iw} \cdot R_L \quad (\text{A2.44})$$

Finally, the total shell pressure drop is calculated through [Equation A2.45](#)

$$\Delta P_s = 2 \cdot \Delta P_e + (N_{bf} - 1) \cdot \Delta P_c + N_{bf} \cdot \Delta P_w \quad (\text{A2.45})$$

A.2.3 Condensation in the shell-side

Shell side mass velocity and window velocity are calculated using ([Equation A2.46](#) and [Equation A2.47](#)) since only the liquid fraction is considered. The liquid heat transfer coefficient is calculated, (h_L), through [Equation A2.33- Equation A2.34](#) . Finally modified heat transfer coefficient is calculated through [Equation A2.48- Equation A2.49](#).

The pressure drop in the shell is calculated using [Equation A2.50](#). The pressure drop of the vapor fraction, $(\Delta P_s)_v$, is calculated using [Equations A2.37-A2.45](#) but considering vapor at inlet conditions. The shell side mass velocity and window velocity are calculated considering the vapor fraction only.

$$G_s = \frac{\dot{m}_s \cdot (1 - x)}{S_m} \quad (\text{A2.46})$$

$$G_w = \frac{\dot{m}_s \cdot (1 - x)}{\sqrt{S_m \cdot S_w}} \quad (\text{A2.47})$$

$$X_{tt} = \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l}\right)^{0.5} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_l}{\mu_v}\right)^{0.1} \cdot \left(\frac{1 - x}{x}\right)^{0.9} \quad (\text{A2.48})$$

$$h = 1.26 \cdot h_L \cdot X_{tt}^{-0.78} \quad (\text{A2.49})$$

$$\Delta P_s = (\Delta P_s)_v \cdot 0.5 \quad (\text{A2.50})$$

A.2.4 Kettle reboiler

The Mostinski correlation is used to calculate the nucleate boiling heat transfer coefficient (Equations A2.51-A2.53).

$$P_r = \frac{P_{sat}}{P_c} \quad (A2.51)$$

$$F_p = 1.8 \cdot P_r^{0.17} + 4 \cdot P_r^{1.2} + 10 \cdot P_r^{10} \quad (A2.52)$$

$$h_{nb} = 0.00417 \cdot P_c^{0.69} \cdot q^{0.7} \cdot F_p \quad (A2.53)$$

The shell heat-transfer coefficient for the tube bundle is calculated using Equation A2.54 and Equations A2.55. $C_1 = 1$ for a square layout distribution

$$F_b = 1 + 0.1 \cdot \frac{0.785 \cdot D_{OTL}^{0.75}}{C_1 \cdot \left(\frac{P_T}{D_o}\right)^2 \cdot D_o - 1} \quad (A2.54)$$

$$h = h_{nb} \cdot F_b \quad (A2.55)$$

It is assumed that the uppermost tube to the top of the shell is a 40 % of the shell diameter, so Equation A2.56 is used.

$$D_s = D_{OTL}/0.6 \quad (A2.56)$$

A.3 Air cooler design

Nomenclature

Symbols

A_b	Surface area of a unit tube bank (including fins) (m ²)
A_{fin}	Surface area of fins in a tube (m ²)
A_{minL}	Minimum flow area in a tube bank per tube length (m ²)
A_{pr}	Prime surface area in a tube (m ²)
A_{total}	Total surface area of all the tube banks of the air cooler (m ²)
D_{fan}	Fan diameter (m)
D_{fin}	Outer fin diameter (m)
D_i	Internal tube diameter (m)
D_o	External diameter of root tube (m)
f	Friction factor
f_{aux}	Pressure drop factor due including auxiliary components
G_e	Mass velocity (kg·m ⁻² ·s ⁻¹)
h_{in}	Inlet specific enthalpy of the condensing fluid (kJ·kg ⁻¹)
h_{out}	Outlet specific enthalpy of the condensing fluid (kJ·kg ⁻¹)
\tilde{h}_i	Internal heat transfer coefficient (W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹)
\tilde{h}_o	External heat transfer coefficient (W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹)
he_{fin}	Fin height (m)
k_{fin}	Fin thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)
k_o	External fluid thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)
k_t	Root tube thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)
L_t	Tube length (m)
L_u	Unit length (m)
\dot{m}_u	Mass flow rate through a unit (kg·s ⁻¹)
$N_{fin,L}$	Number of fins per meter length of tube
N_{fan}	Number of fans per unit
$N_{t,r}$	Number of tubes per row in a unit
$N_{t,u}$	Number of tubes in a unit
N_u	Number of units
q	Heat flow per surface area of tube (W·m ⁻²)
\dot{Q}	Total heat flow evacuated through the cooler (W)
P_T	Tube pitch (m)
\dot{P}_{fan}	Total consume of the fans (W)
Pr	Prandtl number
Re	Reynolds number referred to the maximum velocity
Re_{eff}	Effective Reynolds (used in the pressure drop calculation)
T_{sat}	Saturation temperature of the fluid inside tubes (K)
T_{wi}	Internal wall temperature of the tubes (K)
th_{fin}	Fine thickness (m)
u_f	Face velocity (m/s)
u_{fan}	Flow velocity in the outlet of a fan (m/s)
u_{max}	Maximum flow velocity across the tube bank. (m·s ⁻¹)
U	Global heat transfer coefficient (W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹)
\dot{V}_{fan}	Volumetric flow through a fan (m ³ ·s ⁻¹)
W_u	Width of the projection of the A-frame projection to a horizontal plane (m)
Greek letters	
ΔP	Total pressure drop (Pa)
ΔP_b	Pressure drop of the air across the tube bank (Pa)
ΔP_{fan}	Pressure drop due to the air velocity increment across the fan (Pa)
ρ	Density of the air (kg·m ⁻³)
μ	Dinamic viscosity of the air (Pa·s)
η_{fan}	Total fan efficiency

Appendix

η_{fin} Fin efficiency

The heat transferred per tube length is calculated considering the inside heat transfer coefficient. (Equation A3.1)

$$q = \pi \cdot D_i \cdot h_i \cdot (T_{sat} - T_{wi}) \quad (A3.1)$$

The total condensing flow is divided in different units in parallel. Each unit includes a contains a complete A-frame tube bundle with their respective fans and enclosures. The total length of the tubes is calculated through Equation A3.2..

$$L_t = \frac{\dot{Q}}{N_{t,u} \cdot q \cdot N_u} \quad (A3.2)$$

The air mass flow rate per unit is calculated through Equation A3.3.

$$\dot{m}_u = \frac{\dot{Q}}{(h_{out} - h_{in}) \cdot N_u} \quad (A3.3)$$

The face velocity is the air velocity when it crosses the first tube row bundle. Equation A3.4 .

$$u_f = \frac{\dot{m}_u}{P_T \cdot (N_{t,r} - 1) \cdot \rho \cdot L_t} \quad (A3.4)$$

Since an equilateral triangular pitch is considered, the minimum flow area per tube length is the tube pitch minus the root diameter minus the area occupied by the fins. (Equation A3.5)

$$A_{minL} = (P_T - D_o) - 2 \cdot N_{fin,L} \cdot th_{fin} \cdot he_{fin} \quad (A3.5)$$

The maximum velocity is calculated using Equation A3.6

$$u_{max} = \frac{P_T \cdot u_f}{A_{minL}} \quad (A3.6)$$

The Reynolds number is calculated considering the maximum velocity. Equation A3.7

$$Re = \frac{D_o \cdot u_{max} \cdot \rho}{\mu} \quad (A3.7)$$

The prime area is the external area of a tube minus the area occupied by the base of the fin. It is calculated using Equation A3.8.

$$A_{pr} = \pi \cdot D_o \cdot L_t \cdot (1 - N_{fin,L} \cdot th_{fin}) \quad (A3.8)$$

The fins area is calculated through Equation A3.9

$$A_{fin} = 2 \cdot N_{fin,L} \cdot L_t \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{(D_{fin}^2 - D_o^2)}{4} \quad (A3.9)$$

The external heat transfer coefficient is calculated through Equation A3.10.

$$h_o = \frac{k_o}{D_o} \cdot 0.38 \cdot (Re^{0.6}) \cdot (Pr^{1/3}) \cdot \left(\frac{A_{pr} + A_{fin}}{\pi \cdot D_o \cdot L_t} \right)^{-0.15} \quad (A3.10)$$

The global heat transfer coefficient is assessed through Equation A3.11. Equation A3.12 ,Equation A3.13 , Equation A3.14 and Equation A3.15. allows to assess the different factors involved.

Appendix

$$U = \frac{1}{\frac{A_{pr} + A_{fins}}{\pi \cdot D_i \cdot h_i} + \frac{(A_{pr} + A_{fin}) \cdot \log \frac{D_o}{D_i}}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot k_t} + \frac{1}{h_o \cdot \eta_{fin}}} \quad (A3.11)$$

$$f_1 = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot h_o}{k_{fin} \cdot t h_{fin}}} \quad (A3.12)$$

$$D_{fin,c} = D_{fin} + t h_{fin} \quad (A3.13)$$

$$f_2 = \left(\frac{D_{fin,c} - D_o}{2} \right) \cdot \left(1 + 0.35 \cdot \log \frac{D_{fin,c}}{D_o} \right) \quad (A3.14)$$

$$\eta_{fin} = \frac{\tanh(f_1 \cdot f_2)}{(f_1 \cdot f_2)} \quad (A3.15)$$

The projection of the A-frame tube bundle to the horizontal plane is calculated through [Equation A3.16](#). It is supposed that the angle of the A-frame is 60°.

$$W_u = 2 \cdot L_t \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \quad (A3.16)$$

The length of one air cooler unit is calculated through [Equation A3.17](#)

$$L_u = \frac{P_T \cdot (N_{t,r} - 1)}{2} \quad (A3.17)$$

The number of fans contained in one unit is assessed dividing the length of the unit between the width [Equation A3.18](#)

$$N_{fans} = \frac{L_u}{W_u} \quad (A3.18)$$

It is considered that the fan diameter is 0.75 the width of the A frame. The 25 % is occupied by support structures, enclosures...([Equation A3.20](#))

$$D_{fan} = W_u \cdot 0.75 \quad (A3.19)$$

The fan velocity is calculated through [Equation A3.20](#)

$$u_{fan} = \frac{4 \cdot \dot{m}_u}{N_{fan} \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot D_{fan}^2} \quad (A3.20)$$

The external area of the tube bundle of one unit is calculated using [Equation A3.22](#)

$$A_b = N_{t,u} \cdot (A_{fin} + A_{pr}) \quad (A3.22)$$

The total area of the air cooler heat exchanger is calculated through [Equation A3.23](#)

$$A_{total} = A_b \cdot N_u \quad (A3.23)$$

The external friction factor is calculated through [Equation A3.24](#). [Equation A3.25](#), [Equation A3.26](#) and [Equation A3.27](#) are used to assess the other factors involved.

$$f = \frac{1 + (2 \cdot \exp(-a/4))}{1 + a} \cdot \left(0.021 + 27.2/Re_{eff} + 0.29/Re_{eff}^{0.2} \right) \quad (A3.24)$$

$$D_{fin} = D_o + 2 \cdot h e_{fin} \quad (A3.25)$$

$$a = \frac{(Pitch - D_o)}{D_{fin}} \quad (A3.26)$$

Appendix

$$Re_{eff} = Re_e \cdot \frac{1}{L_{fin} \cdot h_{e_{fin}}} \quad (A3.27)$$

The total pressure drop is the pressure drop across the bundle plus a term that considers the outlet air velocity since the air inlet velocity is assumed to be zero. (Equation A3.28)

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_b + \Delta P_{fan} \quad (A3.28)$$

The pressure drop of the air across the tube bundle increases as the number of rows, mass velocity, and friction factor increase. It has been assumed that auxiliary components increase pressure losses by 25 % (Equation A3.29, Equation A3.30, Equation A3.31)

$$\Delta P_b = f_{aux} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot f \cdot N_r \cdot G_e^2}{\rho} \quad (A3.29)$$

$$G_e = u_{max} \cdot \rho \quad (A3.30)$$

$$f_{aux} = 1.25 \quad (A3.31)$$

The pressure drop due to the fluid velocity increment across the fan is calculated through (Equation A3.32)

$$\Delta P_{fan} = \rho \cdot \frac{u_{fan}^2}{2} \quad (A3.32)$$

The total fan power consume depends on the total pressure drop, the fan volumetric flow, the number of fans per unit, the number of units and it is divided by the fan efficiency (Equation A3.33 and Equation A3.34). A fan efficiency value of 60 % has been considered.

$$\dot{P}_{fan} = N_{fan} \cdot N_u \cdot \frac{(\Delta P \cdot \dot{V}_{fan})}{\eta_{fan}} \quad (A3.33)$$

$$\dot{V}_{fan} = \frac{\pi \cdot D_{fan}^2}{4} \cdot u_{fan} \quad (A3.34)$$

A.4 Axial compressor correlations

Nomenclature

Symbols

c	Absolute velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
C_{an}	Coefficient of annular losses
C_p	Coefficient of profile losses
C_s	Coefficient of secondary losses
DR_E	Lieblein diffusion ratio
h	Enthalpy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
H	Mean height of a blade (m)
n_{bl}	Number of blades of one stage
R	Reaction degree
s	Pitch (m)
u	Peripheral velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
v_a	Axial velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
w	Relative velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
W_{comp}	Total specific work developed by the compressor ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
W_{stage}	Specific work developed by a compressor stage ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
Y_{st}	Sum of the coefficient losses in one stator stage
Y_{rot}	Sum of the coefficient losses in one rotor stage
D_m/H	Mean diameter-blade height ratio of the first stage
H/ch	Mean blade height-axial chord ratio of a stage (aspect ratio)

Subscripts

01	It refers to a thermal property at the rotor inlet under stagnation conditions
03	It refers to a thermal property at the stator outlet under stagnation conditions
0in	It refers to a thermal property at the compressor inlet under stagnation conditions
0end, ss	It refers to a thermodynamic property at the compressor outlet, assuming the flow has expanded isentropically from the compressor inlet
1	It refers to the rotor inlet/stage inlet
2	It refers to the stator inlet/rotor outlet
3	It refers to the stator outlet/stage outlet
i	It refers to each stage

Greek letters

ϕ	Flow coefficient
ψ	Load coefficient
β_1	Relative flow angle at the rotor inlet
β_2	Relative flow angle at the rotor outlet
α_1	Absolute flow angle at the rotor inlet
α_2	Absolute flow angle at the rotor outlet
β_m	Angle calculated using Equation A3.1
σ	Solidity (axial chord-Pitch ratio)
η_{comp}	Compressor efficiency
η_{stage}	Stage efficiency
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
ρ	Density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)

The inlet and outlet relative flow angles (β_1 and β_2) are obtained from [Equation A4.1-A4.2](#) (Lieblein correlation for the equivalent diffusion ratio calculation).

$$\tan \beta_m = \frac{\tan \beta_1 + \tan \beta_2}{2} \quad (\text{A4.1})$$

$$DR_E = \frac{\cos \beta_2}{\cos \beta_1} \cdot \left(1.12 + \frac{0.61}{\sigma} \cdot \cos^2 \beta_1 \cdot (\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2) \right) \quad (\text{A4.2})$$

Appendix

The flow coefficient (ϕ) and the load coefficient (ψ) are calculated using [Equations A4.3-A4.4](#). The inlet and outlet absolute flow angles (α_1 and α_2), are calculated using [Equations A3.5-A3.6](#).

$$\phi = \frac{R}{\tan \beta_m} \quad (\text{A4.3})$$

$$\psi = \phi \cdot (\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2) \quad (\text{A4.4})$$

$$\psi = 1 - \phi \cdot (\tan \beta_2 + \tan \alpha_1) \quad (\text{A4.5})$$

$$\psi = \phi \cdot (\tan \alpha_2 - \tan \alpha_1) \quad (\text{A4.6})$$

Profile losses are calculated using the Lieblein correlation from [Equation A4.7](#), while annual and secondary losses are calculated using Howell correlations from [Equation A4.8- A4.9](#). Should be considered that the annular losses are different for each stage since it depends on $\frac{ch}{H}$ (the inverse of the aspect ratio). The total coefficient losses are calculated for stator and rotor ([Equation A4.10-A4.11](#)). The efficiency of each stage is calculated using [Equation A4.12](#)

$$C_p = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{0.004}{1 - 1.17 \cdot \ln DR_E} \right) \cdot \sigma \cdot \frac{\cos^2 \beta_1}{\cos^3 \beta_2} \quad (\text{A4.7})$$

$$C_{an,i} = 0.02 \cdot \left(\frac{ch}{H} \right)_i \cdot \frac{\cos^2 \beta_1}{\cos^3 \beta_m} \quad (\text{A4.8})$$

$$C_s = 0.072 \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma} \cdot (\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2)^2 \cdot \frac{\cos^2 \beta_1}{\cos \beta_m} \quad (\text{A4.9})$$

$$Y_{st,i} = C_{p,st} + C_{an,st,i} + C_{s,st} \quad (\text{A4.10})$$

$$Y_{rot,i} = C_{p,rot} + C_{an,rot} + C_{s,rot} \quad (\text{A4.11})$$

$$\eta_{stage,i} = 1 - \frac{1}{2\psi} \left(Y_{est,i} \cdot \left(\phi^2 + \left(1 - R + \frac{\psi}{2} \right)^2 \right) + Y_{rot,i} \cdot \left(\phi^2 + \left(R + \frac{\psi}{2} \right)^2 \right) \right) \quad (\text{A4.12})$$

The outlet pressure of each stage is calculated using an optimization algorithm, considering that the specific work developed in each stage has the same value. The input data includes the efficiency of each stage, calculated using [Equation A4.12](#), as well as the stagnation thermal properties at the inlet and outlet of the turbomachine.

Once the stagnation thermodynamic properties at the inlet and outlet of each stage are obtained, the flow and load coefficients and characteristic velocities are calculated using [Equation A4.13-A4.18](#).

$$\phi = \frac{v_a}{u} \quad (\text{A4.13})$$

$$\psi = \frac{W_{stage}}{u^2} \quad (\text{A4.14})$$

$$c_1 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \alpha_1} \quad (\text{A4.15})$$

$$w_1 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \beta_1} \quad (\text{A4.16})$$

$$c_2 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \alpha_2} \quad (\text{A4.17})$$

$$w_2 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \beta_2} \quad (\text{A4.18})$$

Appendix

The overall compressor efficiency is calculated using Equation 4.19.

$$\eta_{comp} = \frac{h_{0end,ss} - h_{0in}}{W_{comp}} \quad (A4.19)$$

The inlet and outlet properties of each stage are calculated using Equation A4.20- A4.25. Equation A4.20 relates the inlet enthalpy with the stagnation one. Equation A4.21 allows to calculate the rotor outlet enthalpy from the degree reaction. Equation A4.22 is used to calculate the rotor outlet isentropic enthalpy. Equation A4.23 relates the stagnation inlet and outlet enthalpies of each stage to the specific work developed by each one. Equation A4.24 is used to assess the stagnation outlet enthalpy of the stage from the stage efficiency definition. Finally, Equation A4.25 allows to calculate the outlet enthalpy of the stage from the stagnation one.

$$h_1 = h_{01} - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \quad (A4.20)$$

$$h_2 = R \cdot W_{stage} + h_1 \quad (A4.21)$$

$$h_{2s} = h_2 - Y_{rot} \cdot \frac{w_1^2}{2} \quad (A4.22)$$

$$h_{03} - h_{01} = W_{stage} \quad (A4.23)$$

$$h_{03s} = h_{01} + \eta_{stage,i} \cdot W_{stage} \quad (A4.24)$$

$$h_3 = h_{03} - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \quad (A4.25)$$

From Equation A4.26 and the $\frac{D_m}{H}$ value at the inlet of the turbomachine, the mean diameter and the height of the first stage are calculated. Since the mean diameter is constant for all the machine, the height of each stage varies depending only on the density.

$$H = \frac{\dot{m}}{\pi \cdot D_m \cdot v_a \cdot \rho} \quad (A4.26)$$

The axial chord at each stage is calculated from the aspect ratio and the calculated mean height. The pitch of each stage is obtained from the axial chord and the solidity. Finally the number of blades of each stage is calculated is using Equation A4.28

$$n_{bl,i} = \frac{D_m \cdot \pi}{s_i} \quad (A4.28)$$

A.5 Axial turbine correlations

Nomenclature

Symbols

B	Constant calculated in Equation A5.37
c	Absolute velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
ch	Axial chord (m)
ch_r	Real chord (m)
C_{in}	Coefficient of interstitial losses
C_p	Coefficient of profile losses
C_s	Coefficient of secondary losses
D_r	Diameter at the root of a blade
D_t	Diameter at a tip of a blade
h	Enthalpy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
ig	Interstitial gap (m)
H	Mean height of a blade (m)
K	Coefficient reduction for centrifugal stress.
n	Constant calculated in Equation A5.38
n_{bl}	Number of blades of one stage
r_r	Radius at the root of a blade (m)
r_t	Radius at the tip of a blade (m)
rpm	Revolutions per minute
R	Reaction degree
s	Pitch (m)
u	Peripheral velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
v_a	Axial velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
w	Relative velocity ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
W_{comp}	Total specific work developed by the turbine ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
W_{stage}	Specific work developed by a turbine stage ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
Y_{st}	Sum of the coefficient losses in one stator stage
Y_{rot}	Sum of the coefficient losses in one rotor stage
Z	Constant calculated in Equation A5.38
H/ch	Mean blade height-axial chord ratio of a stage (aspect ratio)
t/ch	Thickness-chord ratio

Subscripts

01	It refers to a thermal property at the stator inlet under stagnation conditions
03	It refers to a thermal property at the rotor outlet under stagnation conditions
0in	It refers to a thermal property at the turbine inlet under stagnation conditions
0end, ss	It refers to a thermodynamic property at the turbine outlet, assuming the flow has expanded isentropically from the turbine inlet
1	It refers to the stator inlet/stage inlet
2	It refers to the stator outlet/rotor inlet
3	It refers to the rotor outlet/stage outlet
i	It refers to each stage
<i>Greek letters</i>	External diameter of root tube (m)
ϕ	Flow coefficient
ψ	Load coefficient
β_1	Relative flow angle at the rotor inlet
β_2	Relative flow angle at the rotor outlet
α_1	Absolute flow angle at the rotor inlet
α_2	Absolute flow angle at the rotor outlet
σ	Solidity (axial chord-Pitch ratio)
σ_r	Real solidity (real chord-Pitch ratio)
η_{turb}	Compressor efficiency
η_{stage}	Stage efficiency
ρ	Density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
δ	Flow deviation angle calculated from Carter correlation

Appendix

τ_c	Centrifugal stress (Pa)
τ_t	Bending stress (Pa)

The main angles are calculated considering that $\phi < 1$ and $\psi < 1$. [Equation A5.1-5.4](#).

$$\alpha_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\frac{\psi}{2} - R + 1}{\phi} \right) \quad (\text{A5.1})$$

$$\alpha_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\frac{\psi}{2} + R - 1}{\phi} \right) \quad (\text{A5.2})$$

$$\beta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\frac{\psi}{2} - R}{\phi} \right) \quad (\text{A5.3})$$

$$\beta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\frac{\psi}{2} + R}{\phi} \right) \quad (\text{A5.4})$$

The profile, secondary and interstitial losses coefficients are calculated considering [Equation A4.5-A4.7](#). Secondary and interstitial coefficient losses for each stage should be estimated as ch/H is only known for the first stage. The total stator and rotor losses for each stage are calculated through [Equation 5.5](#) and [Equation A5.10](#).

$$C_p = 0.025 \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{\beta_2 - \beta_1}{90} \right)^2 \right) \quad (\text{A5.5})$$

$$C_{s,i} = 3.2 \cdot C_p \cdot \left(\frac{ch}{H} \right)_i \quad (\text{A5.6})$$

$$C_{in,i} = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{ig}{H} \right)_i \cdot \frac{(\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2)^2}{\cos \beta_m} \cdot \cos^2 \beta_2 \quad (\text{A5.7})$$

$$Y_{st,i} = C_{p,st} + C_{in,st,i} + C_{s,st,i} \quad (\text{A5.9})$$

$$Y_{rot,i} = C_{p,rot} + C_{in,rot,i} + C_{s,rot,i} \quad (\text{A5.10})$$

The efficiency of each stage is calculated through [Equation A4.11](#)

$$\eta_{stage,i} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \psi} \cdot \left(Y_{est,i} \cdot \left(\phi^2 + \left(1 - R + \frac{\psi}{2} \right)^2 \right) + Y_{rot,i} \cdot \left(\phi^2 + \left(R + \frac{\psi}{2} \right)^2 \right) \right)} \quad (\text{A5.11})$$

The outlet pressure of each stage is calculated using an optimization algorithm, considering that the specific work developed in each stage takes the same value. The input data includes the efficiency of each stage, calculated using [Equation A5.11](#), as well as the stagnation thermal properties at the inlet and outlet of the turbomachine.

The total efficiency is calculated through [Equation A5.12](#)

$$\eta_{turb} = \frac{W_{turb}}{h_{0in} - h_{0endss}} \quad (\text{A5.12})$$

Once the stagnation thermodynamic properties at the inlet and outlet of each stage are obtained, the characteristic velocities are calculated using [Equation A5.13-A5.18](#).

$$\phi = \frac{v_a}{u} \quad (\text{A5.13})$$

$$\psi = \frac{W}{u^2} \quad (\text{A5.14})$$

$$c_1 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \alpha_1} \quad (\text{A5.15})$$

$$w_1 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \beta_1} \quad (\text{A5.16})$$

Appendix

$$c_2 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \alpha_2} \quad (\text{A5.17})$$

$$w_2 = \frac{v_a}{\cos \beta_2} \quad (\text{A5.18})$$

The mean diameter is calculated from [Equation A5.19](#)

$$D_m = 60 \cdot \frac{u \cdot \pi}{rpm} \quad (\text{A5.19})$$

The inlet and outlet properties of one stage are calculated using [Equation A5.20-A5.24](#). [Equation A5.20](#) relates the inlet enthalpy in the stator with the stagnation one in the stator. [Equation A5.21](#) is used to calculate the outlet stagnation enthalpy of the stage. [Equation A5.22](#) allows to calculate the rotor inlet enthalpy from the reaction degree. [Equation A5.23](#) is used to calculate the rotor inlet isentropic enthalpy. [Equation A5.24](#) is used to assess the isentropic outlet enthalpy of the stage from the efficiency definition.

$$h_1 = h_{01} - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \quad (\text{A5.20})$$

$$h_{03} = h_{01} - W_{stage} \quad (\text{A5.21})$$

$$h_2 = h_3 + R \cdot W_{stage} \quad (\text{A5.22})$$

$$h_{s2} = h_2 - \frac{c_2^2}{2} \cdot Y_{est,i} \quad (\text{A5.23})$$

$$h_{03ss} = h_{01} - \frac{W_{stage}}{\eta_{stage,i}} \quad (\text{A5.24})$$

The flow area for each stage is calculated through [Equation A5.26](#). The root and tip blade diameters are calculated using [Equation A4.56-A5.27](#). The blade height is calculated using [Equation A5.28](#).

$$A_i = \frac{\dot{m}}{v_a \cdot \rho_i} \quad (\text{A5.25})$$

$$D_{r,i} = D_m - \frac{A_i}{\pi \cdot D_m} \quad (\text{A5.26})$$

$$D_{t,i} = D_m + \frac{A_i}{\pi \cdot D_m} \quad (\text{A5.27})$$

$$H_i = \frac{D_{t,i} - D_{r,i}}{2} \quad (\text{A5.28})$$

Once the height of each stage is calculated, the axial chord and aspect ratio of each stage are recalculated using the aspect ratio of the first stage and the chord variation between the first and last stages of the turbine, as these are input data. The interstitial losses are also recalculated since the interstitial gap (ig) is also a known parameter. [Equation A5.5-A5.28](#) are used again to recalculate all the parameters until the convergence is achieved.

The centrifugal stress at the root of the blades is calculated using [Equation A5.29](#). The density considered (ρ) is $7800 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ and the reduction factor (K) is 0.6.

$$\tau_{c,i} = \rho \cdot \frac{Ku^2}{2} \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_{t,i}}{r_{r,i}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (\text{A5.29})$$

The solidity (axial chord-pitch ratio) is calculated through the Zweifel correlation since the profile and secondary coefficient losses have been calculated through simplified Soderberg correlation:

$$\sigma = 2.5 \cdot (\cos \beta_2)^2 \cdot (\tan \beta_2 - \tan \beta_1) \quad (\text{A5.30})$$

Appendix

The number of blades is calculated through [Equation A5.31](#). Since the mean diameter is constant, the variation of the number of blades is inversely proportional to the pitch. The pitch is calculated through the solidity and the obtained chord for each blade stage.

$$n_{bl,i} = \frac{D_m \cdot \pi}{s_i} \quad (\text{A5.31})$$

[Equation A5.32- A5.34](#) are used to calculate the real chord of the blades. So, the deviation of the fluid with respect to the exit angle is calculated using the Carter correlation [Equation A5.32](#). For the first iteration, the real solidity value is estimated considering the same value than the solidity value obtained from the axial chord. Once the deviation is calculated, the draft angle is calculated through [Equation A4.33](#). This equation is obtained considering that the mean camber line of the profile is an arc of a circle. The real solidity value is then calculated using [Equation A5.34](#).

$$\delta = 0.19 \cdot (\beta_2 - \beta_1) \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_r} \quad (\text{A5.32})$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\beta_2 + \beta_1 + \delta}{\frac{2}{\sigma}} \quad (\text{A5.33})$$

$$\sigma_r = \frac{2}{\cos \gamma} \quad (\text{A5.34})$$

The bending stress is calculated using equations [Equation A5.35- A5.38](#)

$$\tau_{b,i} = \frac{\dot{m} \cdot W_{stage}}{u \cdot n_{bl,i}} \cdot \frac{H_i}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{z \cdot ch_{r,i}^3} \quad (\text{A5.35})$$

$$z = \frac{1}{B} \cdot \left(10 \cdot \frac{t}{ch}\right)^n \quad (\text{A5.36})$$

$$n = 2.08 - 0.009 \cdot (\beta_2 - \beta_1 + \delta) \quad (\text{A5.37})$$

$$B = 1560 - 11 \cdot (\beta_2 - \beta_1 + \delta) \quad (\text{A5.38})$$

A.6 Water tanks heat transfer correlations

The external heat transfer coefficient is calculated considering convection over a horizontal cylinder (Churchill-Chu correlation)

$$Nu = \left(0.6 + \frac{0.387 \cdot Ra^{1/6}}{[1 + (0.559/Pr)^{9/16}]^{8/27}} \right)^2 \quad (A6.1)$$

Where Ra is the Raleigh number and Pr the Prandtl number. All the properties are evaluated at the film temperature. The hydraulic diameter is the diameter of the tank.

The internal heat transfer coefficient of the closures are calculated considering free convection over vertical plates:

$$Nu = \left(0.825 + \frac{0.387 \cdot Ra^{1/6}}{[1 + (0.492/Pr)^{9/16}]^{8/27}} \right)^2 \quad (A6.2)$$

Where the hydraulic diameter is the height of the phase (water or air) that contacts the closure

The internal heat transfer coefficient of the curved surface of the lower half is calculated considering free convection over the upper surface of a cold horizontal plate (Mcaddams correlation):

$$\begin{aligned} Nu &= 0.54 \cdot Ra^{1/4} \text{ for } 10^4 < Ra < 10^7 \\ Nu &= 0.15 \cdot Ra^{1/3} \text{ for } 10^7 < Ra < 10^{11} \end{aligned} \quad (A6.3)$$

Where the hydraulic diameter is the surface are divided by the perimeter.

The internal heat transfer coefficient of the curved surface of the upper half is calculated considering free convection over the lower surface of a cold horizontal plate.

$$Nu = 0.27 \cdot Ra^{1/4} \text{ for } 10^5 < Ra < 10^{11} \quad (A6.4)$$

Appendix

A.7 PTES-CSP HRB propane hourly production distribution

Black: Number of total hours of production

Red: Number of hours of production when the PTES is discharging

Blue: Number of hours of production when the PTES is charging

	January	February	March	April	May	June
0	3.5 0 0	3 0 0	4.5 0 0	5 0 0	13 0 2	17 0 1
1	2 0 0	1.5 0 0	2.5 0 0	4 0 0	13 0 0.5	17 0 1.5
2	1 0 0	0.5 0 0	1 0 0	3.5 0 0	13.5 0 0	15 1 1
3	1 0 0	0 0 0	1 0 0	5 0 0	14 0 0	17 1 0.5
4	1 0 0	0 0 0	4 0 0	10 1 0	14 4.5 0	16 2.5 0
5	2 0 0	1 0 0	7 0.5 0	12 1.5 0	13.5 8 0	12 4.5 0
6	2 0 0	1 0 0	6 1.5 0	9 1 0	1 0 0	0 0 0
7	2 0 0	1 0 0	3 0 0	1 0 0	6.5 0 0.5	9.5 1 0.5
8	0 0 0	0 0 0	2.5 1 0	9.5 0 2	22.5 1 3	25 0.5 2
9	0 0 0	1 0 0	12 1.5 0	12.5 0 3	24.5 0 7	27 0 4
10	2 0 0	2 0 0	15 0 1	13 0 3.5	20.5 1 2	27 0 7
11	2.5 0 0	1 0 0	14 0 3.5	12 0 2	19 0 6	27 0 4
12	3 0 0	0 0 0	14 0 4.5	10.5 0 4.5	18 0.5 13.5	27 0 13
13	3 0 0	0 0 0	14.5 0 8.5	11 0 7	18 0 16	24.5 0 19
14	3 0 0	0.5 0 0	15 0 13.5	11.5 0 7.5	18.5 0 16.5	24 0 19
15	4 0 0	4 0 0	16.5 0 7	15 0 9	19 0 9	24.5 2 19.5
16	8 0 0	9 0 0	20.5 0 3	18 0 5.5	20 1.5 5	25 1 12
17	12 0 0	17 0 0	19.5 3 1.5	19 2 1	21 3 0	24.5 0 3.5
18	11 0 0	17.5 0 0	19 13.5 0	24.5 13.5 1	26 15 0	27 13 0.5
19	11 0 0	18 0 0	19 13 0	25 17 0	26 23.5 0	29 29 0
20	10 0 0	17 0 0	17 6 0	23.5 8 0	24.5 19.5 0	29 29 0
21	6.5 0 0	12.5 0 0	12.5 1 0	19.5 1 1	23 5 1	28 11.5 1
22	4 0 0	6.5 0 0	9 0.5 0	15 2 0	18.5 1 0	26.5 10.5 0
23	4 0 0	4 0 0	6.5 0 0	9.5 1 0	13.5 0 2	23.5 1 0

Time

Time

	July	August	September	October	November	December
0	30.5 0.5 10.5	16.5 1 0	7 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
1	30 0 11	13.5 0 0	3.5 0 1.5	0 0 0	0.5 0 0.5	0 0 0
2	28 0 5	11 0 0	5.5 0 1.5	1 0 0	1 0 0.5	0 0 0
3	24.5 0 2	10 0 1	6 0.5 0	1 0 0	1 0 0	0 0 0
4	21.5 3 0	10.5 1 0	8.5 2.5 0	2.5 0 0.5	1 0 0	0 0 0
5	16 3 0	9 2 0	12 6 0	10 0.5 0	1 0 0	0 0 0
6	0 0 0	3 1.5 0	11.5 5 0	10 3.5 0	1 0 0	0 0 0
7	12 0.5 3	0 0 0	0 0 0	3 0 0	1 1 0	0 0 0
8	31 0 14.5	21.5 0 9	7.5 0.5 1	0.5 0 0	0 0 0	0 0 0
9	31 0.5 12.5	30 0.5 22	20 0 6.5	7 0 4	0.5 0 0	0 0 0
10	31 6.5 7.5	31 1 20	18.5 0 8	7.5 0 4.5	1.5 0 0	1 0 0
11	31 12 3	31 4 8	17 0 4.5	4 0 4	1 0 0	1 0 0
12	31 9.5 4	31 3 10.5	15 0 10.5	4 0 4	1 0 0	1 0 0
13	31 7 7	31 0.5 19.5	14 0 12	5 0 4	0 0 0	1 0 0
14	31 2 16.5	31 0.5 22.5	16.5 0 13.5	7.5 0 6.5	1 0 1	1 0 0
15	31 1 17	30 2.5 15	20 0 13	16.5 0 11	10 0 7.5	2 0 0.5
16	31 3 16.5	31 2 7	24 1 10	18 0 6	17 0 2.5	7.5 0 1.5
17	31 1.5 11	30 0.5 0	22 8 4	21 9 1	18 1 0	14 0 0
18	30 15.5 1	30 28 0	25 19 0	24.5 17 0.5	17 4 0	16 0 0
19	30 30 0	31 31 0	25.5 25 0	23.5 14.5 0	18 6 0	15 0 0
20	30 26 0	31 29 0	21.5 11 0	19.5 4 1	16 0 0	10 0 0
21	30 14 3	29 14.5 1.5	16 3.5 2	5.5 0 1	10.5 0 0	3.5 0 0
22	30 11 1	27 11.5 0	13.5 5 0	5 1 0	3.5 0 0	0.5 0 0
23	30.5 3.5 2	24 1 0	9 1 1	2.5 0.5 0	2 0 0	0 0 0

A.8 Siebers & Kraabel correlation

Nomenclature

Symbols

d_{ext}	External tube diameter (m)
D_{rec}	Receiver diameter (m)
$Gr_H^{1/3}$	Grashof number
\check{h}_{ext}	External heat transfer coefficient ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$)
\check{h}_{fc}	Forced heat transfer coefficient due wind ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$)
\check{h}_{nc}	Natural convection heat transfer coefficient ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$)
Nu_{fc}	Nusselt number in the forced convection case
Re_D	Reynolds number based on the receiver diameter

The Siebers & Kraabel correlation considers that the heat transfer coefficient for convection in a receiver is a combination of the forced convection coefficient due to wind speed and the natural convection coefficient. It is assessed using [Equation A6.1](#).

$$\check{h}_{ext} = (\check{h}_{fc}^{3.2} + \check{h}_{nc}^{3.2})^{1/3.2} \quad (A6.1)$$

The Nusselt number in the forced convection case is based on the receiver diameter. All fluid properties are evaluated at the film temperature. Depending on the Reynolds number and surface roughness, different correlations are considered [Equation A6.2-A6.7](#). The surface roughness is calculated as the relative roughness of the tubes, that is equal to the external radius of a tube divided by the receiver diameter, $rug = \frac{d_{ext}/2}{D_{rec}}$

for $rug = 0$ (a smooth cylinder)

$$Nu_{fc} = 0.3 + 0.488 \cdot Re_D^{0.5} (1 + (Re_D/282000)^{0.625})^{0.8} \quad (A6.2)$$

for $rug = 75 \cdot 10^{-5}$

if $Re_D \leq 7 \cdot 10^5$ use [A6.2](#)

$$\text{if } 7 \cdot 10^5 < Re_D < 2.2 \cdot 10^7 \quad Nu_{fc} = 2.57 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot Re_D^{0.98} \quad (A6.3)$$

$$\text{if } Re_D \geq 2.2 \cdot 10^7 \quad Nu_{fc} = 0.0455 Re_D^{0.81} \quad (A6.4)$$

for $rug = 300 \cdot 10^{-5}$

if $Re_D \leq 1.8 \cdot 10^5$ [A6.2](#)

$$\text{if } 1.8 \cdot 10^5 < Re_D < 4 \cdot 10^6 \quad Nu_{fc} = 0.0135 Re_D^{0.89} \quad (A6.5)$$

if $Re_D \geq 4 \cdot 10^6$ use [A6.4](#)

for $rug = 900 \cdot 10^{-5}$

if $Re_D \leq 1 \cdot 10^5$ [A6.2](#)

if $Re_D > 1 \cdot 10^5$ use [A6.4](#)

Appendix

The Nusselt number in natural convection case is based on the height of the receiver. All fluid properties are evaluated at the ambient temperature. [Equation A6.6](#)

$$Nu_{nc} = 0.098 \cdot Gr_H^{1/3} \cdot \left(\frac{T_{surf}}{T_{amb}} \right)^{-0.14} \quad \text{A6.6}$$

Appendix

A.9 PTES-CSP sCO₂-RB hourly production distribution

Black: Number of total hours of production

Red: Number of hours of production when the PTES is discharging

Blue: Number of hours of production when the PTES is charging

	January			February			March			April			May			June		
0	2.6	1.5	1	2.5	1	1.5	6.2	0.5	4.5	5.9	2.5	2.5	16.0	0	12	23.5	2	12.5
1	2	1	1	1.3	0	1	2.8	0	1	3.2	1	1.5	12.0	0.5	10.5	21.5	0.5	9.5
2	1	0	1	0.0	0	0	1.0	0	1	2.5	1	1.5	14.0	1	10	21.0	2.5	9.5
3	0	0	0	0.0	0	0	1.5	0	2	6.0	0.5	2.5	15.0	7	2	21.9	10.5	5.5
4	1	0	1	0.5	0	0	7.5	4.5	0	16.0	7.5	7.5	20.0	18.5	0	24.6	19.5	2
5	4	1	3	6.0	0	5.5	10.0	9	0	19.0	14.5	2.5	22.2	21.5	0	25.7	23	1
6	5	2.5	2	7.5	5	2.5	12.0	10	0	18.0	13.5	2	20.0	14.5	0.5	21.0	10.5	2
7	6	4	2	10.0	8	1.5	15.0	11	1	19.0	5.5	5	21.1	3	4	21.5	0	7.5
8	5.5	3	0	9.5	5	0.5	16.0	4	3	16.5	1	9.5	20.0	0	12.5	20.0	0	8
9	5	0	1	9.0	1	5	15.0	0	4	9.5	0	7	17.0	1.5	9.5	18.0	0	12.5
10	5	0	2	8.0	0	4.5	14.5	0	6.5	6.0	0	2	13.5	2	5.5	14.0	0.5	10
11	4	0	4	5.0	1	3	15.0	0	9	5.0	0	2	8.5	0	6	12.0	2	8.5
12	4	0	4	5.0	0	5	13.0	0	10.5	5.0	0	2.5	6.0	1	4	7.5	0	6
13	5	0	5	5.0	0	5	11.0	0	10.5	5.5	0	4	4.5	0	5	6.0	0	3
14	8	0	8	5.0	0	4	12.0	0	9	6.0	0	5	3.0	0	3	6.0	0	4
15	10	0	9	6.0	0	2	14.0	0	6	9.5	0	8.5	5.0	0	3	8.0	0	6
16	21	1	16	14.0	0	9.5	17.4	0	7.5	14.0	0	9	11.0	0	11	8.0	3	3.5
17	26	16.5	8.5	19.0	5.5	10.5	19.0	2	5.5	20.0	0	10	20.0	2.5	14	14.0	0.5	12
18	26	22	3	18.6	17	1.5	20.0	15.5	3	26.0	15.5	6	23.0	11	7	18.5	5.5	11
19	25	21	4	18.0	19	1	19.5	18.5	1	26.0	22.5	1.5	23.5	24.5	0	29.0	27	2
20	22.7	14	7	18.0	14.5	4	18.1	15	1.5	24.0	19	2	25.0	21	1	30.0	27	2
21	15.8	5.5	9	15.8	3.5	7	16.0	5.5	8.5	21.1	7.5	10.5	24.5	7.5	7.5	30.0	10	13.5
22	7.5	1	6.5	6.8	0	8	12.3	3	6.5	15.0	6	8	21.5	8	8	29.0	14	4
23	4.5	4	0	5.3	3	2	10.1	4	3	8.5	2	4	18.0	2.5	12.5	26.5	6.5	11

	July			August			September			October			November			December		
0	25.5	2	15.5	24.5	4.5	15	8.5	1	5.5	2.1	0	0.5	4.1	1	2.5	0	0	0
1	22.5	5.5	15.5	21	4	14	6	0	2.5	2	0	2.5	2.1	0	1.5	0	0	0
2	20.5	5	10	22	2	11	7	0.5	5	3	1	3	1	0	1	0	0	0
3	21	10	1.5	23	6.5	7	9	3.5	3.5	3.1	0	2.5	1	0	0.5	0	0	0
4	23	19	0	30	19.5	2	12.5	7.5	3.5	8.5	1.5	6.5	2	0	1	0	0	0
5	27	20.5	0.5	29.1	22.5	1	20.5	14.5	3	16	11.5	3	3.5	1	1	1	0	1
6	27	13	0.5	24	15	3	22	15.5	2	17	16.5	0	5.5	4	1	1	0.5	0.5
7	28	2.5	4	24	4	5.5	19.7	8.5	3	17.5	11.5	3	7	5.5	1	4	2	1.5
8	28	4	11.5	22	0	16.5	18	0.5	7	15	0.5	6	7	2.5	3.5	4	3	0
9	28	3.5	15.5	18.5	0.5	16.5	12.5	0	6.5	8	0	3.5	4.5	0	1.5	5	0	1
10	28	11.5	11.5	17	1	11.5	11	0.5	6.5	5	0	2	4.5	0	3	6.5	0	4
11	28.5	7.5	18	11.5	1	8	12	1.5	8	4	0	3	6	0	4.5	8	0	7
12	28	5	17.5	8	0	4.5	10	1	7.5	3	0	4	5	0	5	8	0	5
13	23	3	16.5	6.5	0	5	7	0	7	4.5	0	4.5	5	0	5	9	0	7
14	16	0	14	8	0	7	7	0	7	6.5	0.5	6	7	0	6	11	0	9
15	14	0	13	8	0	7.5	9.5	1.5	6	10.5	0.5	9.5	12.5	0	10	14	0	9
16	17.5	3	12.5	15.5	2.5	11	16	0.5	12.5	21	2	14.5	19	1	12	19	3	12
17	23.5	5	15.5	20	1	18	23	10.5	10.5	25	10.5	10	26	17	8	25	14.5	8.5
18	23.5	12	9	21	16	6	28	22	4	26	24	0.5	26	20	4	25	22	1.5
19	29	23.5	5	27.5	22.5	3.5	27.5	26	0	25.5	21.5	2	25	21	3	23.3	20.5	0.5
20	30	27	2	31	30	0.5	26.5	18	5	23.3	7.5	7.5	24.5	17	6	16.8	8	3.5
21	29	18.5	7.5	30	16.5	10	23	3.5	12	17	1	13.5	16.1	2	8	7.8	1.5	1.5
22	29	20.5	6.5	30.5	23.5	5.5	18.7	5	9.5	10.8	6	4.5	12	1.5	7.5	2.5	0	1.5
23	26.5	10.5	8	30	9.5	12	12.5	2	7	6	1	3	9.7	4.5	1.5	1.1	0	1

Appendix